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**NEGOTIATING TRADITION AND
INNOVATION:
Medical Pluralism and Healthcare
Transformations in the 20th and 21st Centuries**

**Editors:
Anelia Kassabova
Denitsa Nencheva
Jakub Střelec**

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Medical Pluralism Revisited (Editorial)¹

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After the Second World War, the question of health, both individual and collective, became a central concern on both sides of the Iron Curtain. In liberal democracies as well as in state socialist regimes, efforts to combat and prevent disease, to improve healthcare and hygiene, and to regulate reproduction emerged as key pillars of post-war development. These initiatives were deeply tied to matters of political legitimacy, social stability, and economic modernization. Healthcare was not merely a technocratic domain. It became a contested arena where ideologies, institutions, and everyday experiences converged, while also

¹ The research is within the ERC Project "Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good". The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

emerging as a transnational space, shaped by Cold War geopolitics, international organizations, and the interaction between national systems and global health discourses.

This special issue approaches these dynamics through the conceptual lens of *medical pluralism* as both a thematic and methodological point of departure. Building on classic and contemporary scholarship (Leslie, 1976; Janzen, 1978; Kleinman, 1980; Cant & Sharma, 1999; Adams et al., 2009; Raffaetà et al., 2017), we understand medical pluralism not simply as the coexistence of multiple therapeutic traditions, but as an entangled and dynamic field in which different medical epistemologies, institutional authorities, and cultural practices interact. In particular, our aim is to move beyond a binary view of (bio)medicine versus tradition, and instead explore how people, institutions, and states negotiated health through hybrid practices, competing logics, and cross-system entanglement. Furthermore, our approach seeks to transcend disciplinary boundaries and examine the history of medicine from multiple vantage points – combining anthropological approaches with intellectual history, legal history and the history of medical heritage. This interdisciplinary dialogization, we think, is particularly valuable for understanding the relationship between health, the body, and state power in post-war Europe – the core focus of this special issue

This perspective encompasses three key dimensions: first, it involves the analysis of diverse medical approaches, treatments, institutions, and practices addressing health problems across different societies and political systems in post-war Europe. Hence, secondly, arises the call for methodological pluralism, encouraging the use of varied disciplinary perspectives. Third, it entails working with a wide range of source materials, including archival documents, oral histories, media representations, architectural legacies, and museum exhibitions. This special issue attempts to combine all three aspects by focusing on a variety of research topics.

Therefore, while the concept of medical pluralism traditionally refers to the coexistence of multiple healing systems, we also use it here in a broader sense – to signal the diversity of analytical approaches, disciplines, and narrative styles that shape this volume. The included articles range across medical anthropology, social history, legal studies, environmental and architectural history, and museum studies, reflecting the plurality not only of medical systems but also of the scholarly lenses through which they are interpreted. This conceptual openness resonates with broader efforts in anthropology and the social sciences to move

beyond disciplinary silos and examine medical systems through heterogeneous modes of knowing (Pickstone, 2000; Rabinow et al., 2008; Lock & Nguyen, 2010).

Rather than enforcing conceptual uniformity, we embrace this heterogeneity as part of the volume's core strength: a commitment to examining healthcare transformations through multiple, sometimes competing, disciplinary perspectives.

While the majority of contributions focus on countries in Eastern Europe, the special issue seeks to transcend Cold War divisions. It therefore also includes articles that explore East-West comparisons, such as between Hungary and the Netherlands, introducing multinational overviews or examining other national contexts, such as Italy. Importantly, the special issue does not treat the 'Eastern Bloc' as a monolithic entity, nor does it portray state socialism as a uniform system. Instead, it attends to the political, social, and cultural specificities of individual Central and Eastern European countries, each shaped by its own historical trajectory. This approach is reflected in the geographical scope of the volume, which includes analyses of Albania, Bulgaria, Poland, Hungary, and Yugoslavia. At the same time, the broader international context remains central.

Despite the thematic and methodological diversity represented in the contributions, a unifying research question runs throughout: the analysis of various regimes of care and control in modern European societies. We aim to offer a framework for the historical analysis and contextualization of institutions, health infrastructures, power relations, and state interventions across different countries in the post-war period. Special attention is paid to the ways in which the governance of health was legitimized, implemented, and embedded in everyday life, and how normative expectations and practices shaped access to care. At the same time, the conceptual lens of *tradition* and *innovation*, through which aspects of governance and care are negotiated, opens space to explore resistance, individual agency, and the adaptive strategies people employed in response to institutional constraints. This is especially relevant in the field of medicine, where the biopolitical entanglement of health, discipline, and state authority created a complex picture of regulation and self-control. From self-managed reproductive care to vernacular healing and selective use of institutional medicine, the articles in this issue demonstrate that medical landscapes were actively navigated and reconfigured from below. Instead of generalizing, the

volume aims to present various modes of governing and caring for population health as transnational phenomena in modern European societies. In doing so, the authors also open research avenues related to phenomena such as medicalization, responsabilization, de-institutionalization and self-governance.

The special issue is structured into four main thematic blocks, each addressing different dimensions of medical pluralism and transformation: *Negotiating Modernity: State Medicine and Local Knowledge*; *Medical Heritage and Memory: Institutions, Infrastructures, Artifacts*; *Biopolitics and Reproductive Governance*; *Margins of Care: Silence, Risk, and Contested Ethics*.

The first section, *Negotiating Modernity: State Medicine and Local Knowledge*, explores the intersection between state-led modernization in medicine and healthcare and the persistence of local healing practices and culturally embedded notions of the body and well-being. This section highlights the frictions that emerged when top-down interventions and scientific trends encountered longstanding traditions and everyday practices. The articles explore how state-driven reforms and therapeutic discourses – ranging from hygiene campaigns to psychiatric treatment – interacted with enduring moral orders, philosophical orthodoxy, and local worldviews. For instance, Klejd Këlliçi analyzes hygiene campaigns in 1960s socialist Albania, which were designed to improve living conditions in rural areas. His article reveals the tensions between socialist modernization efforts and enduring, traditional forms of social organization. Special attention is given to the gendered dimensions of these campaigns, particularly how women were targeted by state initiatives that sought to penetrate and reshape the intimate space of the home. Approaching the question from a different angle, Tiago Pires examines the work of Italian philosopher and anthropologist Ernesto de Martino, whose theories significantly influenced the development of Italian ethnopsychiatry. De Martino's writings laid the groundwork for what Pires refers to as a “decolonization of mental health” in post-war Italy. Rather than relying on standardized models derived from Anglo-Saxon clinical psychiatry, de Martino offered a culturally situated understanding of psychological suffering. His work emphasized the symbolic and ritual dimensions of mental health, deeply rooted in the traditions of Southern Italy. In another paper, Inxhi Brisku analyzes Albanian Marxist philosophy in the 1980s and its response to the rise of Neo-Freudianism. Brisku points out that the inflexible ideological structure of Albanian Marxism severely limited the possibility

of engaging critically with alternative psychotherapies and intellectual traditions, ultimately reinforcing the regime's ideological continuity. Together, the three papers highlight different facets of negotiating the practical and conceptual dimensions of 'welfare' – from the instilling of a modern (socialist) way of life through bodily transformation and new habits, to the culturally embedded sense-making and treatment of one's mental suffering, and the ideologically coded reception of revolutionary theories of the human psyche, such as those of Sigmund Freud.

The second section, *Medical Heritage and Memory: Institutions, Infrastructures, Artifacts*, engages with the material and symbolic aspects of medical history, from architectural transformations of public baths in Bulgaria to museum curation. How is medical knowledge and infrastructure preserved, transformed, displayed, and narrated? How are histories of health and healing remembered? What becomes the face of medical innovation? Examining case studies of public baths and regional museums, the articles reveal the ideological and affective work of 'using and curating the past' with a view to the present, showing how medical modernity is staged and remembered. Slava Savova explores the built environment in Bulgaria after its liberation from Ottoman rule, focusing on case studies of Ottoman public baths and their modernization. She demonstrates that the processes of Europeanization and de-Ottomanization were not abrupt breaks, but rather gradual transformations shaped by enduring cultural practices. Based on these case studies, Savova points out that the country's balneological modernization was an adaptation to preexisting cultural practices rather than a linear or uniform process. In her contribution, Katarzyna Jarosz analyzes case studies of smaller-scale medical museums and the ways in which they construct historical narratives about medical innovation. She focuses on curatorial strategies such as spatial arrangement and object selection, showing how these institutions, often of regional significance, played a crucial role in shaping the public history of medicine. Jarosz highlights how medical breakthroughs are frequently presented through the lens of individual figures. While at first glance the two papers reveal diametrically opposed tendencies – the deliberately 'silent' incorporation of previous material and cultural heritage versus the public display of medical advancement and innovation – both contributions explore the employment and framing of national resources with international significance, whether natural healing treasures or singular medical achievements.

In the third section, *Biopolitics and Reproductive Governance*, the contributions explore the biopolitical dimensions of modern healthcare, with particular attention to the interplay between state power and reproductive practices. This section highlights how reproductive health became a central domain of state intervention, shaped by broader political ideologies, public health priorities, and cultural norms. Contraception, genetic counseling, and prenatal care were often framed as tools for population planning, scientific progress, and civic responsibility. At the same time, individuals and communities navigated these pressures through selective adoption, hesitation, or refusal. These research topics offer insight into the gendered dimensions of health policy and the contested politics of reproductive agency in post-war Europe. For example, Ina Dimitrova, in her study, examines genetic counseling in socialist Bulgaria, with a particular focus on efforts to popularize prenatal diagnosis within the medical system. She situates these developments within the framework of the preventive model of public health promoted by the socialist state, while also drawing attention to its underlying eugenic implications. Dimitrova asks how these preventive measures were implemented and how they functioned as tools to promote the responsabilization of socialist citizens in matters of reproduction. Ivana Dobrivojević Tomić explores the topic of contraception in socialist Yugoslavia, focusing on how government initiatives and prevailing cultural norms shaped societal attitudes toward birth control. Her article investigates the factors that contributed to the population's hesitancy to adopt contraceptive methods, offering insights into the tension between state policy, expert knowledge and private decision-making. Finally, Alexandra Barmpouti examines the phenomenon of do-it-yourself (DIY) abortion, analyzing the factors that influence a pregnant person's decision to pursue self-managed medical abortion. Her provocative general overview considers a range of legal, social, and political contexts across different European countries, demonstrating how national frameworks and global events shape individual reproductive choices. These contributions partake in the longstanding debate over the boundaries between the common good and individual rights, addressing issues of reproductive and sexual freedom and personal agency, which intersect with historically rooted gender roles and social expectations.

The fourth section, titled *Margins of Care: Silence, Risk, and Contested Ethics*, turns to the outer boundaries of care, where medicine grapples with silence, stigma, and ethical ambiguity – particularly in

areas where issues of life, death, and illness became taboo or politically sensitive. This is exemplified in the article by Judit Sándor and Mária Éva Földes, which compares the medicalization of death and dying in two contrasting post-war societies: Hungary and the Netherlands. While physician-assisted dying has become legally available in the Netherlands, in Hungary it remains a medical taboo. The authors trace legal developments and ethical debates in both contexts, focusing on the evolution of doctor – patient relationships, patient rights to information, autonomy, and transparency. Their analysis reveals that, despite legal and cultural differences, end-of-life care continues to pose profound ethical and institutional challenges in both countries. In a different yet thematically related case, Sławomir Łotysz examines the AIDS panic in late 1980s Poland, focusing on how the media and state censorship shaped public responses. His article traces how fear of AIDS manifested across various spheres of life, how it was translated through popular media discourse, and how it was addressed by both the state and other significant actors such as medical personnel, law enforcement, and insurance companies. Łotysz illustrates how fear-mongering narratives – coupled with ineffective state policies on prevention and public information – profoundly influenced perceptions of health risks and of those most vulnerable to them. These final papers again address fundamental issues from a historical perspective, discussing how different societies confront the limits of medical intervention in its conventional sense, and posing questions of personal dignity, ethical responsibility, and the boundaries of care.

Alongside the four thematic sections, this volume also includes a contribution under the heading *Fieldwork Notes* that presents yet another perspective on the pluralities of healing. The text written by Emil Antonov offers an auto-ethnographic reflection on the ‘transplantation’ of Huichol (Wixárika) healing practices from Mexico to Bulgaria. Through first-hand observation of peyote rituals and interviews with both shamans and participants in the ceremonies, the author explores the negotiation of authenticity, spiritual meaning, and cultural transformation in contemporary ritual contexts. The text invites readers to consider how native medical and spiritual practices circulate globally, becoming embedded in new articulations and geographies of healing. It complements the volume’s broader inquiry into medical pluralism by foregrounding lived experience and the evolving entanglements between tradition, commodification, and cross-cultural exchange.

The volume concludes with three contributions under the rubric *Vita Academica* and a collection of thematically related book reviews. The former reflect on academic endeavors and events, dedicated to topics like the anxieties surrounding ageing and care in Southeastern Europe, the challenge of therapeutic approaches in psychotherapy emerging during the Cold War, and the matter of risk-thinking in relation to health and medicine in several socialist societies. The presented books enrich this line of inquiry by addressing anthropological questions and themes such as care and treatment, health education and socialization, disability and social stigmatization.

Taken together, the contributions to this special issue illuminate the multifaceted nature of healthcare in 20th- and 21st-century Europe. They show that, in the post-war period, health became a contested domain, far from neutral, shaped by the interaction of state power, cultural practices, technological advancements, institutional frameworks, and social norms. It emerged as both a tool of governance and a crucial site/field where questions of legitimacy, identity, and social order were negotiated and challenged. By tracing the entanglements between official policies, leading institutions and alternative practices, between ideological orthodoxy and heterodox gestures, this collection offers new insights into how plural medical systems have shaped and been shaped by European societies. We hope that it contributes to current academic debates in the history and anthropology of medicine by acknowledging the international dimensions of health and welfare systems, analyzing the effects of state policies on individual experiences, foregrounding the lived experiences of care, and the moral and epistemic boundaries of medicine while exploring the enduring legacies of the post-war period.

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***NEGOTIATING MODERNITY: STATE MEDICINE
AND LOCAL KNOWLEDGE***

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**Hygiene Campaigns and State Penetration in
the Sixties in Socialist Albania**

Abstract: *This paper discusses hygiene campaigns in socialist Albania from the early 1960s up to 1970. During this period, communist authorities undertook a series of hygiene campaigns aimed at improving the living conditions of the population, especially in rural areas. These campaigns were directed by state agencies and carried out in schools, factories, and public spaces. Their principal aim was education and the prevention to health hazards, particularly during a time marked by increased urbanization, industrialization, and collectivization. This paper employs the theoretical concept of state penetration, understood here as the state's capacity to brake and reform traditional or resilient forms of premodern organization. In the Albanian case, the authorities pursued a series of reforms aimed at breaking and reforming the family structure to align with broader efforts of industrialization and modernizations.*

In addition to state agencies, other organizations were tasked with implementing such campaigns – most notably the Union of Albanian Women (Bashkimi i Grave të Shqipërisë). This article focuses in particular on the methods used by U.A.W.'s local chapters and women activists to conduct hygiene campaigns. Focusing on the organization's role in these efforts reveals a wide range of instruments the state deployed to penetrate and shape women's lives, as well as the intimate space of the home.

Keywords: *hygiene; state penetration; women; emancipation.*

Introduction

As a young child attending elementary school in mid-1980s socialist Albania, I, like my peers, was subject to strict discipline enforced by our (mostly) female teachers. Every week, usually on Mondays, we were required to place our hands on the desk for inspection. The teacher

would calmly walk between the rows, checking each student to ensure their nails were clipped, their hands were clean, and that they had a clean handkerchief. Occasionally, she would also inspect our hair for lice. If lice were found, the student was sent home to undergo a rather unpleasant purification process. First, the hair was treated with kerosene, then meticulously combed with a fine-toothed comb. In the best-case scenario, when available, a locally produced anti-lice shampoo was used instead.

Personal hygiene came under public scrutiny, children became its focus, and schools served as the stage where this control was enacted. A clean child was seen as a reflection of the household's condition and the housewife's efficiency, particularly in the eyes of the broader public. At school, the child was monitored by the teacher – an authority figure who, often being a woman herself, was attuned to both public expectations and private norms of hygiene. In this dual role, she represented both state authority and maternal sensibility. Women, in general, were primary targets of state intervention, (Stark, 2007: 98) as the state relied on their traditional association with the household and child-rearing to implement its social and hygiene policies. Personal hygiene and cleanliness were not merely matters of individual or societal well-being; they constituted a political stance that shaped every aspect of an individual's life, both within the family and in public spaces. Through the promotion and enforcement of hygienic practices, the communist regime drew a clear boundary between the past and the present – between backwardness and ignorance on the one hand, and progress and modernity on the other.

This modernizing and transformative logic of the state had entered Albania with the establishment of the modern state under Zog, was reinforced during the Italian occupation, and consolidated during state socialism. In the early 1920s, with the help of the International Red Cross, the Albanian state began to develop its sanitary infrastructure. Especially during the 1930s, (Brisku, 2023) efforts focused on providing basic healthcare services, particularly in urban areas. Major initiatives included the prevention of infectious diseases through vaccination campaigns. During the Italian occupation, a significant part of the health-related efforts was undertaken by the *Opera Nazionale Maternità e Infanzia* (ONMI), one of the welfare institutions through which fascism tried to replicate the penetration of the intimate life of women and children in Italy (AQSH, F. 164, V. 1943, Dos. 17, Fl. 2).

Hygiene campaigns were common in the early years of communism. From 1945 onward, the regime sought to promote hygiene and basic personal care, particularly among pregnant women and young mothers. In the absence of adequate healthcare institutions and sufficient medical personnel, the state often relied on the Union of Albanian Women (U.A.W.) and its local chapters to promote basic hygiene practices.

Although the regime's primary policy objective was the emancipation of women – especially through their integration into the workforce – post-war Albania remained an extremely underdeveloped country. As a result, the efforts of the U.A.W. also focused on eradicating illiteracy among women and providing child-rearing education for young mothers (AQSH, F.723, V. 1947, Dos. 4, Fl. 15). Driven in part by the interest of young mothers themselves, the U.A.W. promoted several initiatives focused on education and basic practices of hygiene and childcare. These efforts were aligned with broader state policies aimed at achieving the ultimate goal of women's emancipation, which was to be realized primarily through full employment. In the early 1960s, due in part to the gradual increase in state investment and industrialization, there was a growing need to expand the presence of women in the workforce. Consequently, attracting women to the labor force became the principal objective of the Union of Albanian Women (U.A.W.), alongside its hygiene campaigns.

The demand for workers, rising levels of education, and state-led labor initiatives significantly increased women's mobility. This made it both necessary and feasible to promote hygiene standards through campaigns focused on bodily care. The standardization of such practices had a dual impact: it not only improved the well-being of women themselves but also enabled them to act as agents of transformation by disseminating these practices within their communities of origin.

Hygiene was promoted and enforced through coordinated campaigns directed by the Central Committee of the Party. These directives were implemented in parallel by public health agencies and mass organizations such as the Union of Albanian Women (U.A.W.), ensuring influence across both institutional and grassroots levels (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1963, Dos. 107, Fl. 28). The latter played a pivotal role in supervision, in mobilizing activists, and in disseminating the so called "new/modern way of life". The purpose of this article is to assess the role of the U.A.W. in facilitating and conducting propaganda cam-

paings targeted at women, who were portrayed in various roles throughout different periods as mothers, housewives, and workers. Propaganda and hygiene campaigns primarily targeted children, working mothers, and housewives. Because the regime lacked the capacity to extend the network of health institutions, the U.A.W., through its agents and volunteers, promoted and advocated hygiene norms from the late 1940s onward. Efforts doubled those of the state, thus enforcing the idea and the presence of the Party, through its controlled organizations such as the U.A.W. On one side, state authorities such as the Ministry of Health and its various local agencies would work especially on vaccination campaigns, the construction of infrastructure, or dissemination of information about various epidemics, while on the other the U.A.W., would enforce such policies by monitoring their implementation, overseeing sanitary structures and supervising households (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1946, Dos. 15, Fl. 76). These campaigns primarily targeted women's bodies – particularly in their roles as mothers. Through women, the state extended its reach into the household and the family, and ultimately workplace. By regulating aspects such as women's personal hygiene, childbirth, child-rearing, and household organization, the state effectively penetrated and asserted control over private life.

In the last decade a few books authored by Albanian scholars have begun to shed light on the structure and society-state relations during the dictatorship. These works briefly mention the role of state structures in enforcing top-down hygiene policies which led to widespread societal transformation (Mëhilli, 2015; Lelaj, 2015; A. Hoxha, 2023). While literature on women's emancipation and gender relations is relatively abundant, (Papa-Pandelejmoni and Kera, 2013; Ikonimi and Woodcock, 2014; Këlliçi and Danaj, 2016, 2023, 2024) it often overlooks the role of the Women's Union (U.A.W.) in implementing state policies concerning hygiene, women's education, and the oversight of health institutions. Although hygiene campaigns had a broader public scope, they primarily aimed to transform the lives of women and children, improve the living conditions of the family as a whole, thus also reshaping gender relations. By intervening in the private sphere, the state actively reorganized the domestic space of the socialist household (Verdery, 1996: 65; Massino, 2019: 63).

Healthcare was a major concern in post-war Albania. The communist regime, established in 1944, aimed to fulfil its wartime promises of improving living standards and uplifting marginalized classes such as peasants and workers. Admittedly, the pre-war healthcare system

was rudimentary. Despite the existence of a state hospital in Tirana and a few smaller ones in other cities, rural areas lacked access to healthcare (Brisku, 2023). Basic hygiene, living conditions, and amenities like clean water and sewage systems varied greatly depending on local circumstances and traditions, and remained largely unchanged in some regions and rudimentary in others. The U.A.W. built a relatively strong network from the late 1940s onwards and assisted the state in establishing basic sanitary control over the population, especially in rural areas. Although focused on women and their emancipation, the organization perpetuated certain entrenched ideas about women's roles in society. A 1965 report described women as "by nature, being a heart caring housewife, who knows how to manage (the household), and sacrifice more than anyone" (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 75, Fl. 19). It was no coincidence that in totalitarian regimes, motherhood was conceived not simply in terms of procreation, but as a fundamental duty, through which maternal love could instill essential social and political values in the young (Balmas Neary, 1999; Hofman, 2000: 36). Although hygiene campaigns had a broader public scope, their main purpose was to improve the lives of women and children and the family as a whole – thus reshaping gender relations and reorganizing the private domain of the socialist household.

Women were thus recognized as key agents of social and political transformation and made central to the implementation of change. Since child rearing and household management were seen as women's exclusive domain, any policy concerning children or living standards had to be channeled through them. The state placed strong emphasis on child-birth and infant survival, actively pursuing policies to reduce premature deaths and safeguard the health of future citizens. Following Party directives, women were also expected to educate their children and instill in them official socialist values. To do so, they had to adopt a new lifestyle – one that aligned with the ideals of the socialist state. Embracing what was defined as modern or representative of the new socialist way of life often involved visible bodily changes and the adoption of new habits. Women were expected to introduce these practices within their households and to serve as personal examples within their communities, thereby reinforcing and spreading the new norms through everyday behavior. Once personal hygiene and bodily care were internalized by women as daily habits, these practices were gradually extended to other members of the household. Children were the first to be targeted, particularly with regard to bodily cleanliness, the regular use of soap, and

general grooming. Attention then expanded to encompass domestic hygiene: the cleanliness of the home, the washing of clothes, the preparation of nutritious meals – which required women to learn and cook new dishes – and the overall maintenance of the household environment (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1966, Dos. 6, Fl. 169).

Meanwhile, during the late 1950s and mid-1960s, the U.A.W. also focused on integrating women into the workforce. In urban areas, this often meant replacing men with women in sectors such as services, preschool and primary education, and the primary healthcare system. In rural areas, women's integration typically meant working in agriculture, reflecting both the economic needs of the countryside and the broader gendered division of labor promoted by the state (Këlliçi and Danaj, 2016). By the mid-1960s, the U.A.W. conducted several campaigns aimed at the full integration of women into the workforce, particularly in the context of full collectivization which was completed by 1966 (Lelaj and Bardhoshi, 2023). Moreover, the organization launched initiatives to eliminate so called 'old habits and manners', following Enver Hoxha's call for a revolutionarization of life (E. Hoxha, 1968), mimicking the Chinese cultural revolution campaigns (Marku, 2017) which culminated with the banning of religion in Albania in 1967.

Such campaigns aimed to further and extend modernization across the country – a planned modernization through which the state expanded control over the means of production, integrated local economies into the national one, and rendered the countryside dependent on the state (Lelaj, 2015: 121). Women were made dependent – encouraged or forced to rely on state agencies for childbirth, primary care, children's health. By this logic, the state assumed, or claimed to assume, part of the family's responsibility for childcare, thereby intruding, controlling and standardizing basic child-rearing practices (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1946, Dos. 42, Fl. 21).

Following this intrusion came intervention in the household, where, through the responsibilities of childcare and with the help of U.A.W. activists, women introduced new spatial arrangements and domestic norms. Women also had to be drawn into the workforce, either voluntarily or under institutional pressure. In the countryside, however, collectivization redefined family relations, leading to the demise of patriarchal family structures. The new, nuclear family was expected to comply with new socialist norms of hygiene, cleanliness, presentation and household reorganization. By the end of the 1960s, at least at a Party level, the circle was closed.

Hygiene, which from the late 1940s to the late 1960s was a matter of transforming private life, became from the 1970s onward, a means of managing public space. It was not only about preventing disease outbreaks, but about disciplining behaviour and introducing a new way of life. New institutions and practices radically reshaped the perception of everyday experience (Szpak, 2023).

The challenges were formidable, given the extreme underdevelopment of Albania's rural areas. The economy remained heavily reliant on agriculture, even as the post-war communist plans promised rapid industrialization and sweeping improvements in living and material conditions (A. Hoxha, 2023: 6). The countryside was thus the key focus: first for integration into the national economy; second, for food production; and third, for supplying labor to the Party's projects of transformation. This penetration would have been impossible outside the logic of building state socialism: collectivization, emancipation and industrialization. Despite many obstacles, the regime was proud of its healthcare achievements. By 1967 the State/Party claimed major progress compared to the pre-war period. Since 1944, the number of doctors increased had from 1 in 8527 inhabitants to 1 in 1430, and life expectancy had increased from 38 to 68 years – almost on par with other European countries (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 46, Fl. 70).

“Warriors of the New” (Way of Life)

Although most of the U.A.W.'s efforts tackled childcare or domestic responsibilities, personal hygiene was not neglected. In this area too, activists were expected to lead by example. A 1967 guideline described hygiene as “... a condition to secure a cultured life in the village”, and issued detailed instructions on how to address the issue, especially among women (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1967, Dos. 53, Fl. 13). Hygiene was perceived as a multidimensional process encompassing bodily care, domestic cleanliness, and childcare. Women were expected to adopt new hygiene habits and instill them in other family members, transforming both routines and household space. The rules laid out by the document reflected the increased mobility of women, as they moved from the home to schools, factories and dormitories. As one of the main problems of hygiene was lice, activists were asked to cut their hair short – both for hygienic reasons and as a symbolic break with tradition. Long hair was traditionally a sign that a woman was unmarried. U.A.W. activists therefore almost always wore short hair as a marker of hygiene

and modernity. The new Albanian woman was, in many ways, both different from and more ‘modern’ than her Western counterpart. In Albania, modernity was expressed through practicality: trousers and short hair suited women who worked, replaced men, or performed the same jobs as men. This form of modernity stood in contrast – if not outright opposition – to the wave of cultural and social changes that women experienced in Western Europe during the 1960s.

Returning to personal hygiene, the 1967 guidelines outlined a “method of work” for the campaign. Activists were expected to check each other for lice and then submit to the control of the local head of the U.A.W. branch. Women activists were required to clean parts of the body daily and wash fully on weekends, establishing Saturday body-washing as a ritual in nearly every Albanian household.

In urban areas, washing was facilitated by newly built single-family apartments with indoor bathroom. In rural areas washing had to be improvised in so called “*banjas*” or public baths. Although the Albanian public was familiar with the concept of a public bath, due to the Ottoman heritage and the persistence of such structures in urban areas (Castiglia and Bevilaqua, 2008) the collective socialist public baths were a totally different, in terms of modernity, practicality and access, especially in rural areas. In Nivicë, a small mountain village in Southern Albania, a local teacher and U.A.W. member had to demonstratively bathe herself and then bring her pupils to do the same to convince other women to follow (AQSH, F. 723, Dos. 46, V. 1969, Fl. 70). These actions targeted not just children, but their parents, especially mothers. Teachers were expected to monitor and enforce hygiene by assessing how parents cared for their children.

Control extended to underwear, which was largely absent in rural areas, and introduced via propaganda, especially in working places. Since it was difficult to discuss intimate clothing publicly, propaganda avoided direct references to underpants and instead promoted replacing unsuitable traditional garments with new, more practical ones. New garments made of lighter fabrics, produced locally by the Tirana *Stalin* Plant or *Mao Ce Dun* Plant in Berat, were promoted in contrast to older woolen clothing. This clothing shift had both political and practical functions: it signaled acceptance of new norms and allowed for freer movement – particularly for working women. Above all, it introduced new hygiene norms. Traditional clothes were unhygienic, difficult to clean and take care of, and often handmade. They were gradually

pushed to the realm of folklore culture, worn only during special occasions.

On the topic of intimate body care, U.A.W. activists were instructed to carry two pairs of underwear and two small pieces of “hygienic cotton cloth” – the latter likely serving as a makeshift menstrual pad. In a still deeply traditional society where menstruation was rarely discussed – even in practical guidelines on women’s health – Albanian women were often left to improvise sanitary solutions on their own.

Demonstrative actions, top-down interventions, and regular inspections formed one part of the state’s efforts to reshape rural lifestyles. However, meaningful change from above was also expected to be reinforced from below. Women and youth were the primary targets of these transformative efforts. At various times, they were called upon to voluntarily participate in construction projects, symbolizing their role in both the physical and ideological building of socialism. Thousands of youngsters, women and men alike were mobilized in the late forties onward to build railways, roads, plant trees and so on. *Aksioni* (action, voluntary work), progressively became *rite de passage* (Tomka, 1982) for every Albanian youngster above 15 years old (Zëri i Rinisë, 1967: 1). Initially following the Yugoslav model, (Bakovic, 2015) and later the Soviet Stakhanovite movement (Siegelbaum, 1988: 1), forcing youngsters into voluntary work provided cheap labor and acted as a form of mass education (Mëhilli, 2015: 111) and internal migration from rural to urban areas, especially for youngsters and women.

A 1968 propaganda film, “*Përse bie kjo daulle/Why Is this Drum Beating*”, depicts changes occurring during the period of industrialization. The plot revolves around the encounter and love story of two youngsters in a factory building site (Williams, 2023: 178). The girl comes from North Albania while the boy, a seasoned worker comes from the city. She is a volunteer worker who undergoes a radical personal transformation during her time at the construction site. The young girl recalls her first encounter with the camp: she arrives as part of a larger group of young women, all volunteers like herself, dressed in traditional clothing and extremely shy. Their unease grows as they encounter female volunteers in trousers, T-shirts, and cropped hair, with a foulard covering their heads. These garments are both practical for labor and reflective of modern ideals. Soon after their arrival, two U.A.W. activists approach the new arrivals and invite them to wash in the shower cabins. Though some resist at first, one girl steps forward, and the others follow.

Once bathed they shed their heavy clothes and emerge fresh and changed. Modernized and cleansed women were expected to return to their villages and spread new living standards. Their old clothes disappear, never to be worn again. Having undergone a profound transformation, they were now tasked with transforming their places of origin. Labeled “warriors of the new”, these women, mobilized by the U.A.W., were expected to act in loco as agents of change. By 1967, Party directives had designated the household as the primary focus of modernization. Hygiene was the standard by which transformation would be judged. In Lezhë, many returning volunteers were recruited by the U.A.W. to modernize their family homes. They were expected both to reorganize their living space to inspect others’ households (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 48, Fl. 220).

Groups of three or more women would take responsibility for a set of households to visit on a regular basis, giving advice and often assisting with chores. Local teachers and/or medical staff often participated in these visits, giving advice or criticism. This form of sociality was judged to be invasive but necessary. It appealed to women’s sense of responsibility and shame regarding the care of their homes and children.

The U.A.W. could not enforce specific behaviors, but it worked to establish a shared understanding: that norms of hygiene and household organization should be evaluated not politically, but socially, that is, the political principle had to become a social norm. These inspections generated examples – both positive and negative – that were discussed and judged collectively. This contributed to what Nicole Nixon calls familial shame in the Albanian context (Nixon, 2009: 2). Because household standards were enforced through women, both good and bad examples were feminized, and women’s activities came under scrutiny, both politically and socially.

Women and Child: Hygiene, and Mother’s Care

To implement these policies, the State and the Party needed to exert their influence to achieve their transformative goals. Hygiene was central to this strategy and depended on the collaboration of all state agents active in the territory. While state presence needed to be gradually built, the presence of U.A.W. was easier to establish. The organization boasted an impressive semi-compulsory membership of 200,000 women. From the 1950s onward, it included the wives of Politburo members and other party officials. While this detail may seem minor, it

reveals the Party's control over the organization – its scope and activities. The U.A.W.'s 1946 statute committed it to elevating women's status in socialist society, guiding them toward emancipation and providing a range of support services such as nurseries, kindergartens, and social restaurants (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1950, Dos. 1, Fl. 155). While many of these tasks were shaped by policymakers, local Party officials or state bureaucrats, the organization itself became highly effective at managing propaganda and control. Over the years, U.A.W. organized a wide array of educational conferences, largely targeting women (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1950, Dos. 11, Fl. 17).

Education focused first on eradicating illiteracy, which was widespread among rural women, and second on courses on childcare. While women's roles expanded over time, their primary duty remained motherhood. No matter how progressive the agenda of emancipation became, childbearing continued to legitimize women's role in Albanian society. In public discourse, women were depicted as mothers or future mothers. Even the prospective of young women working was framed through their presumed roles as mothers (Danaj and Këlliçi, 2024). Through U.A.W., the state worked to redefine motherhood – bearing children was presented as a public rather than a private affair. (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1946, Dos. 42, Fl. 21). Propaganda campaigns targeted young mothers, appealing to them, or emotionally pressuring them, through the idea of unconditional love for their children. If love was truly unconditional, then the state should be trusted to have the superior knowledge of raising their offspring. As a result, childcare courses grew popular, especially in areas with high rates of infant mortality. Control over child/women-focused health institutions, allowed the state to disseminate childcare norms, while asserting tutelage over motherhood.

From the late 1940s, propaganda around motherhood sought to detach mothers or mothers to be from their family culture. U.A.W. discourse cast older women as wicked and ignorant elders, incapable of understanding science or modernity and thus life (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1948, Dos. 50, Fl. 39). This messaging found fertile ground in a country with high birth rates but alarming child mortality rates. Nearly half of children aged one to five died either shortly after birth or due to ignorance, lack of medical care, or refusal to seek it (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 93). This was especially true in remote rural areas, where women relied on traditional knowledge for childbirth. In the early postwar years through the early 1960s, the village was a site of backwardness and ignorance, sustained by “religion, superstition and

reliance on elderly women” (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1968, Dos. 118, Fl. 13). In the later years of socialism, and especially after 1967 – Albania’s own version of cultural revolution – rural areas were depicted as a socialist heaven. Despite being a mostly agricultural society, Albania’s rural landscape remained varied. An U.A.W. report divided the countryside into three broad subregions: north, centre and south, each exhibiting different cultural and hygienic conditions.

The north for example suffered from geographic isolation and minimal state penetration. U.A.W. activists attributed the north’s backwardness to the influence of religion, especially Catholicism (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1968, Dos. 118, Fl. 13), even though not all inhabitants were Catholic. Identifying religion as the main cause of backwardness came at a time when religious institutions were gradually being dismantled (Pandelejmoni, 2011; Giakoumis and Premović, 2022). Central Albania’s backwardness, by contrast, was seen as rooted in social norms and conservatism. Southern Albania was seen more positively, as an area where hygiene, both personal and domestic, had become more embedded due to modernization and proximity to urban areas. Thus, hygiene campaigns targeted more intensely the northern part of Albania.

In parallel, propaganda identified childbearing and childcare as the main problem in rural Albania. Pregnant women would never see a doctor or a midwife and gave birth at home (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1963, Dos. 107, Fl. 28). In 1967, more than 38,9% of women gave birth without any medical supervision; in some areas that figure reached 70 % (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 46, Fl. 59). Child birth was typically overseen by the eldest women of extended households. Nearly 30 % of children died within the first five years of life, and 92 % of these deaths occurred without the child ever having been examined by a doctor. Even in relatively developed regions, like Vlorë (South Albania), the situation was dire: nearly half of all children died without being diagnosis or identified cause of death (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 80).

In many remote rural areas, women gave birth without qualified assistance. Although the state began to introduce healthcare infrastructure, uptake was slow. Ignorance of basic norms of hygiene was alarming. In mountainous regions, for example, umbilical cords were sometimes cut with the same scissors used for shearing sheep, significantly increasing the risk of infection. Child nutrition was another concern. Breastfeeding often continued to age three, after which children were fed diets consisting of bread, dairy brine and pickled vegetables. High

child mortality was a longstanding concern of the U.A.W., and although it had been prioritized since 1947, (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1946, Dos. 42, Fl. 21) by the 1960s it was tied more directly to the Party's desire to get women into the workforce. The absence of qualified childcare threatened not simply the process of reproduction, but also that of production. By 1957, almost 70% of the land had been collectivized, and women were increasingly drawn into the rural workforce, comprising as much as 50-60 % of agricultural laborers. In response, efforts – though often insufficient – were made to provide rural areas with basic medical infrastructure. Yet, even where such facilities were available, women were often reluctant to seek medical care (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 46, Fl. 78).

From 1962 to 1965, U.A.W. launched its “Mothers and Child Schools” initiative to educate of women on childcare (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 93). The program consisted of a 10-week course designed for young and expectant mothers but were also extended by mothers with multiple children and grandmothers. In 1965 alone, over 1,000 such schools were established, symbolically beginning on March 8th (International Women's Day) and concluding on June 1st (International Children's Day). The curriculum consisted of six concise, easy-to-understand lectures on various phases of child development (particularly for ages 1-3), nutrition, and household organization. Women were told how to diversify their children's diets, particularly by incorporating vegetables, as well as how to organize their homes to meet children's needs, including the use of single beds. In urban areas, courses were led by doctors or nurses, while in rural areas, by midwives. A 1963 U.A.W. report claimed that 14,000 women had participated in these courses (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1963, Dos. 107, Fl. 28).

The courses were held primarily in schools and outdoor venues. School personnel – mostly women – were also involved, facilitating regular interaction between women and state institutions. As women became more prominent in education and healthcare, they were expected not just to do their job but to also uphold hygiene standards in their workplaces and beyond. In one instance in Vlorë, a U.A.W. delegate reprimanded a local nurse for failing to report the unhygienic condition of a household near the village clinic (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 93).

The U.A.W. strongly emphasized cooperation, especially between school personnel and local sanitary institutions on childcare, ma-

ternal education and prevention. Despite efforts, these initiatives suffered the shortcomings of the state socialist logic of urgency. The mother and child schools proved effective in attracting women's attention, whenever the schools had capable lecturers and adequate materials. In 1965, U.A.W. inspectors found out that in some areas schools had never been launched (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 93). In rural areas where oversight and staff were lacking, courses were delivered by local school teachers and often lacked course materials. Nonetheless, such initiatives coincided with the gradual expansion of state institutions and the adoption of new hygiene norms. Where implemented properly, the schools encouraged women to seek prenatal medical care. Preventive care was particularly popular in rural areas where healthcare for pregnant women was supervised by a midwife and a nurse, or at best by a general practitioner.

By the mid-1960s, doctor visits, institutional births, and use of kindergarten and nurseries, had become normal in urban areas. In Vlorë, for example, 99 % of children were born in a maternity hospital. While maternities became popular in urban areas, rural women faced distance as a barrier. Local authorities proposed building rudimentary maternities on every collective farm, but the lack of medical personnel was an issue.

A 1965 report noted that nearly 30% of the 1,000 midwives needed in rural areas were lacking. Although this figure might seem small, it reveals that even in the late 1960s, some parts of Albania remained difficult to access and offered little to no basic healthcare. Despite overall improvements and broader access to medical services for women, in certain remote mountain areas nearly 38.9% of children were still born at home (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 93).

The Hygienic Household

Detaching childcare from the grip of tradition and turning it into a public, rather than concern meant that state had to intervene in the organization of the household and daily life. This was especially evident in rural areas. While there was a wide variation in living conditions in the countryside, certain characteristics were common across the country.

Living under the same roof as animals was widespread in a society that functioned as a largely autonomous economic unit, producing almost everything needed within the confines of the household. Houses varied in construction, ranging from stone to mud, but were considered

by U.A.W. delegates as dangerous environments for family members, especially children.

A 1964 issue of “*Shqiptarja e Re*”, the official organ of the U.A.W., published a layout of what was presented as a model country house (Shtëpia, *Shqiptarja e Re*, Janar, nr.1, 1964: 24). The magazine suggested the project as a prototype for future rural homes. Intended for two families, the house featured two floors, with separate entrances. The ground floor contained two rooms: a hearth room and a small kitchen, while the upper floor had two additional room, intended as sleeping quarters for the couple and their children. The article also described how the rooms could be furnished and so on. In essence the project reflected the logic of the Soviet ideal of “*kulturnost*” borrowed in the Albanian context (Meksi, 2012: 49).

Typically, a traditional Albanian household, especially in rural areas partly also in urban ones, was organized in two distinct spaces: a private and a public one. The public space consisted of a guest room, and was usually the best part of the house, while the private, everyday living quarters of the family were often poorly maintained. It was precisely this private part of the house that the state aimed to transform and elevate to the standards of the public one. In a speech, Enver Hoxha observed that despite many changes, hygiene and modern furniture were still reserved for guests, while rural households still clung to old habits. To enforce transformation in the private domain, Hoxha called not simply for intervention but for the deployment of shame – specifically, public shame (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 46, Fl. 220). Exposure and public denunciation of bad habits or collective criticism gradually became part of Albanian daily life, influenced by the experience and practices of the Chinese Cultural Revolution. This occurred even though the concept of public shame was already deeply embedded in Albanian society. It is precisely in this framework that hygiene and domestic transformation were to be instilled – not merely as a matter of health, but as a condition of socialist morality which extended into the private sphere and subjected it to constant judgement.

In 1964, the Fifth Congress of the PLA (Party of Labor of Albania), called for the total collectivization of the peasantry and rural areas. Alongside this effort, the U.A.W. was asked together with other organizations like the U.L.Y.A., (The Union of Labour Youth of Albania, BRPSH) and the Fronti Demokratik (Democratic Front, F.D.), to run a campaign of hygienization of homes and push for the transformation of living quarters in line with the new way of life (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1964,

Dos. 83, Fl. 150) The U.A.W. devised an action plan, which consisted either in demonstrative actions and campaigns, inspections or the preparation of model homes as examples of spatial organization. The model house model proposed by the “*Shqiptarja e Re*” remained more of an aspiration than a reality. As a result, U.A.W. activists concentrated on the reorganization of existing domestic spaces rather than insisting on the development of new types of homes, which fell outside the organization’s mandate and scope (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1965, Dos. 76, Fl. 39).

One strategy used to popularize the new way of living was an exposition titled “*Women and Household Economy*”. This event combined live demonstrations with educational content focused on the organization and management of household space. On one hand, women were taught basic principles of home care and spatial organization; on the other, they were instructed in how to prepare vegetable preserves and cook new dishes, with the aim of diversifying the limited and monotonous rural diet (Njohuri për ekonominë shtëpiake, Botim i Kryesisë së BGS, Tiranë, 1957). The exposition also promoted the organization of interior household spaces, recommending separate sleeping areas for children, the use of beds instead of shared sleeping arrangements, a model kitchen, and the creation of a “corner of the child” – a designated space in the home for study and play. Still, most rural and urban homes were small and rarely allowed for separate spaces for all household members.

In rural areas, new ways of living were popularized through demonstrative actions led by U.A.W. activists, supported by local authorities. Working alongside local officials and residents, activists would whitewash a house, build makeshift cesspits, and thoroughly clean the premises. They then held live demonstrations on how to use the newly reorganized spaces. The model home served as an example for other families in the village to replicate.

U.A.W. activists also advised abandoning the traditional practice of eating from a shared dish, promoting individual eating both as a hygienic measure and as part of adopting modern habits. Yet, tradition proved difficult to change: in Lezhë, many villagers objected, arguing that eating from separate dishes would “tear apart the family” (AQSH, F. 723, V. 1969, Dos. 48, Fl. 83). In Ersekë, the local U.A.W. chapter, distributed a questionnaire on the penetration and absorption of the new way of living. Although all women responded positively, a follow-up inquiry by a local schoolteacher tasked with asking their pupils about their home conditions, revealed that old habits persisted. Resistance

drew not only on tradition but also on practicality. In Ersekë and Gramsh, for example, women objected to having to clean the dishes which had multiplied by the number of family members. New norms meant a better and cultured life but they also increased women's domestic workload.

Conclusion

By involving women, state authorities aimed not only to challenge the deeply rooted conservative attitudes of the local population but also to reshape family relations. The U.A.W. advised their activists to use their spare time after work to implement new hygienic standards: washing clothes, preparing meals for the following day, boiling water for dishwashing, and cleaning the house. Household maintenance remained – and was expected to remain – a woman's domain, as women were the primary bearers of the new standards of living and hygiene. Although there were calls for a more equal distribution of domestic responsibilities among family members, housework largely stayed within the female domain. Emphasizing women's control over this new way of life reflected broader concerns about formalism and the persistence of tradition.

While kitchenware, personal dishes, single beds, and modern furniture gradually made their way into many rural Albanian homes, their adoption was often limited. The U.A.W. found it easier to work with women and promote new lifestyles because much of the state-built infrastructure in rural areas was directed specifically at them. Medical ambulatories primarily focused on prenatal care and child vaccination, while schools – staffed mostly by women – oversaw children's basic hygiene and self-care. Alongside these public institutions, intensive campaigns to improve living conditions centered largely on the woman – child relationship.

This focus became particularly significant at the height of collectivization, when collectivized land provided peasants with increased income that was expected to translate into better household conditions. Although persuading peasants to purchase furniture and kitchenware was challenging, linking hygiene and child care to the broader project of modernization – and highlighting women's central role in this transformation – proved a more effective strategy.

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Zëri i Rinisë

Shqiptarja e Re

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Anthropology and Psychoanalysis in Ernesto de Martino’s Ethnopsychiatry¹

Abstract: *This paper aims to understand how Ernesto de Martino’s work became the epistemological basis of ethnopsychiatry in Italy, especially through the dialogue between anthropology and psychoanalysis. Demartinian theory can be considered as a foundation for cultural readings of subjectivity and ways of expressing and managing psychological suffering. In this article, I will analyze some of his publications regarding the mythical-ritual aspects of the Italian South (Meridionalist trilogy), specifically his book entitled “La terra del rimorso” (The Land of Remorse), published in 1961. De Martino is not only recognized for his historical contributions to ethnopsychiatry and transcultural psychiatry, but also as a forerunner in the Italian context of what I call a “decolonization of mental health”.*

Keywords: *Ernesto de Martino; ethnopsychiatry; anthropology; psychoanalysis.*

De Martino and the Epistemological Basis of Italian Ethnopsychiatry

My aim here is to understand how Ernesto de Martino can be considered the foundation of Italian ethnopsychiatry for developing some theories about the relationship between culture and subjectivity, the mythical-ritual apparatus and psychopathology. It is not my intention to carry out a hermeneutic of his works and theories, but to identify how they contribute to interpreting subjective suffering from an (ethno)psychoanalytic and cultural perspective. Following a theoretical discussion

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on this subject, I will analyze his ethnographic research published in 1961 (de Martino, [1961b] 2023), which is central to this paper.²

Anthropology and psychoanalysis are fundamental themes in de Martino's work and in the elaboration of his ideas on ethnopsychiatry (Bartocci and Prince, 1998). Although he did not call himself an ethnopsychiatrist, there is a great tendency to consider him the first author in this field (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015). After all, his ethnographic research in southern Italy in 1959 was conducted by a transdisciplinary team, including a psychologist, psychiatrist, musicologist, and anthropologist. One of the main concepts and theories is the "crisis of presence" and the resolute and rescue capacity promoted by mythical-ritual practice. In this sense, authors such as Freud, Jung, and Heidegger were important to him.

De Martino recognizes Carl Jung and Károly Kérenyi as significant authors for thinking about myth as a "model of the past" for dealing with the present, although he does not align himself with Jung's isolation in the theory of archetypes, possibly because of its unhistorical nature. According to de Martino, Jung would have recognized the symbol as a mediator and bridge between the passage from crisis to reintegration. Heidegger's concept of *Dasein* was fundamental to de Martino's theoretical development, especially when discussing the "crisis of presence." However, I believe that Freud's work is aligned with Heidegger's *Dasein* in de Martino's theory in the following way: "being in the world" is not guaranteed and, therefore, there is a permanent risk of losing oneself. In the Freudian interpretative line, this refers to the risk of an inauthenticity of self, the possibility of becoming mentally ill (the dissociation of the "self").

De Martino entered the ethnopsychiatric field by incorporating psychoanalysis, anthropology, and philosophy in his understanding of culture and the human psyche: the permanent risk of becoming mentally ill by losing oneself. His theory of the mind, suffering and culture concatenated in the idea of the "crisis of presence" is authoritatively aligned with the discussions in the field of mental health of his time. De Martino established a rupture in the interpretation of disorders of the mind and

² Other publications by Ernesto de Martino could be included, such as his texts on the psychopathology of cultural apocalypses (e.g., de Martino 1964, 1977). However, for this paper, I chose his ethnography on tarantism in Southern Italy because it presents important aspects of ritual practice ("loss of presence") as a cultural language for dealing with subjective suffering. This was a fundamental transdisciplinary work for the constitution of the theoretical basis of Italian ethnopsychiatry.

the way subjective pain is managed given the extreme biologism of mid-twentieth-century neurology and psychiatry. This was the beginning of Italian medical anthropology, one could boldly say (*Ibid.*).

The “crisis of presence,” according to de Martino, is the loss of the ability to act according to sociocultural values, as if the subject remained in a state of “inauthenticity of self,” to use a more psychoanalytical conception. In cultural terms, this is a subjective and social paralysis, a repetitive imprisonment of the traumatic or distressing situation. For de Martino, presence in the world is not guaranteed, and the risk of losing it is a constant in human life. Thus, from his ethnography in Southern Italy in 1959 (de Martino, [1961b] 2023), he was able to recognize this existential risk of subjectivity becoming ill as something of human history, and not just a situation of the precariousness of the *Mezzogiorno*. Of course, there is a historical-anthropological basis to his theory that distances him from the religious phenomenology of Mircea Eliade or Jung, given that each historical context defines not only the modalities of the crisis of presence but also its resolving techniques: mythical-ritual, therapeutic, or psychoanalytic, among others.

I would go further in this Demartinian definition of losing the ability to act according to sociocultural values, by adding the idea of the loss of the “ego” as an organizing function, the loss of the self, and the fading of subjectivity. The individual becomes detached from their subjectivity and cannot act according to their desire, falling into a repetitive emptiness of anguish. In this way, the loss of presence is not just an inability to act according to cultural values, but also the loss of the subject’s ability to align themselves with their desire and their language: what speaks in the individual, as if it were a possession (or dis-possession of the self), is another “self” (the suffering that does not go away and repeats itself).

The concept of “loss of presence” can be inserted into a broader debate about psychopathology, about a possible cultural translation of mental illness. According to Demartinian theory, subjective suffering is caused by a traumatic or distressing event, and not by a physiological or genetic illness. Although the author does not rule out the possibility of a biological illness caused by imbalances in the body (by internal or external agents), his research points us in another direction: the possibility of culture and life in society making the subject ill, causing bodily suffering (physical and mental).

The “loss of presence” is understood by de Martino (1961b) as an “irrelative de-historicization,” the very distressing and paralyzing situation that the subject goes through without institutional and ritual support. The other possibility is “institutional de-historicization,” which consists of a technique of cultural control and resolution of subjective pain, such as the rite of tarantism,³ a cultural and ritualistic phenomenon in Southern Italy associated with the bite of a spider. For de Martino, “the risk of ‘not being’ is linked to external conditions and brings with it the possibility of overcoming them” (Pompa, 2022). We cannot understand this idea without first understanding the category of “de-historicization.”

De Martino defends the idea that magical-religious rituals can take the subject out of history, a place of anguish and suffering, where trauma happens. It is not a metaphysical or supernatural reality, but a technical, symbolic-ritual apparatus capable of creating an environment and a narrative in which suffering is resignified (Beneduce and Taliani, 2001; Carignani, 2004; de Martino, [1961b] 2023). The internal conflict thus finds a horizon for naming, managing, and resolving (Pires, 2024). This exit from history (de-historicization) is not definitive during the ritual, as there is a return to social and cultural life, which de Martino (1961b) calls “cultural reintegration.”

In a rite of possession and exorcism, as in the phenomenon of tarantism analyzed by de Martino, ([1961b] 2023), there is a state of loss of self, induced by the ritual (institutional de-historicization), which occurs only in that context. In the end, the subject returns to themselves because they do not remain possessed all the time. In this way, the ritual makes it possible to remove the subject from the place of their pain from a shared and resolute symbolic horizon, bringing the individual back into their history, and making them recover their capacity to act in the society.

It is interesting to note that the loss of presence is a psychopathological risk that is not only found in rural societies, an idea that de Martino took some time to elaborate and which becomes clear in his *La terra del rimorso* (The land of remorse, 1961) and *Furore simbolo valore* (Fury symbol value, 1962). The risk of becoming disconnected

³ Tarantism is an Italian cultural and ritual phenomenon in which a person manifests symptoms of possession and trance following the real-symbolic bite of a poisonous spider. The “exorcism” of these people (*tarantati*) is performed by a band playing musical instruments, and the *tarantato* (the person bitten by the spider) may dance for hours and days.

from oneself and the world and the fading of the power to act has occurred in both the past and the present of different societies, marked by their historical specificities. However, de Martino does not remain in this tragic position of subjective sickening and the ever-present risk of the fragmentation of the self.

Just as the loss of presence accompanies sociocultural and historically determined situations, the techniques for rescuing this imminent crisis follow the same path. For de Martino, there is an external cause (historical, sociocultural) located in the traumatic situation that impacts subjectivity in different ways, paralyzing or eliminating “presence.” In this sense, he identifies magical-religious rituals as a technique for culturally rescuing this risk of nonbeing (subjective illness), a cultural language for suffering and, as such, marked by its historicity. His dialogue with anthropology and psychoanalysis is deeply marked by a historical perspective.

Ernesto de Martino’s importance in the field of ethnopsychiatry lies in his epistemological break with the understanding of mental disorders as exclusively biogenetic products (Bartocci and Prince, 1998; Beneduce, 2007; Pires, 2023). In addition, he elaborated a cultural theory of subjectivity, suffering, and ways of dealing with it (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015). The figure of the “madman” or schizophrenic, to use a psychiatric term, is constituted as someone who has escaped from what is considered normal within a sociocultural code. The subject who possesses this “split mind” (*schizo* = split, *phrenia* = mind) is someone unable to act according to the values established by culture and the subjective language of each individual. In his dialogue with Pierre Janet during the 1940s,

de Martino revived from oblivion the French school of “dynamic psychology” founded by Pierre Janet, for whom the person is not a substantial being characterized by aptitudes and functions, but a “dynamic” form, that is, a set of interdependent conducts, hierarchized according to a scale of energy levels: from the most automatic to the most conscious. This conception allowed him to distinguish different degrees of “feeling of the real” to imagine a plurality of successive or simultaneous “psychological existences” and to formulate, through this theater of primary and secondary personalities, an early version of the conceptual pair “presence/loss of presence.” (Charuty, 2015, “The Sick Live Their Own Apocalypse”)

The history of culture would be the history of the languages through which subjects reinvent themselves and ensure their presence in the world. This psychopathological risk, found in different societies

throughout history, takes on different forms of manifestation and resolution. In this sense, magical-religious rituals are understood by de Martino as cultural techniques for managing suffering and the risk of the mind becoming ill (Carignani, 2004; de Martino, [1961b] 2023). The rite is capable of incorporating anguish and trauma into its narrative, shifting them to a resolute symbolic horizon (Pires, 2020; 2024). Human pain would find in ritual not only a cultural-historical meaning, but also the possibility of being undone, of passing away, and of recovering the disturbed presence.

In this way, culture is understood as a nominative and resolute possibility for subjective suffering, rather than a singular carapace for the disorders defined by psychiatric discourse (Beneduce, 2007). There is a rupture in the way mental disorders are interpreted, escaping from the psychiatric biologism of the time toward psychopathology. The autonomy and depathologization of some cultural phenomena, such as tarantism, appeared in de Martino's work long before *DSM-III* (1980), *DSM-IV* (1994), and *DSM-V* (2013), which gradually incorporated cultural discussions into the nosography of mental disorders (Pires, 2023; 2024). De Martino broadened the boundaries between the normal and the pathological, understanding the phenomenon of tarantism no longer as a pathology caused by a venomous animal but as a resolute symbolic-ritual horizon, a cultural language for suffering.

Jervis argues that tarantism cannot be explained within psychiatric nosography. In the ethnographic context analyzed by him and de Martino, there was another way of living and interpreting reality that cannot be reduced to an idea of "primitive mentality" (Jervis, [1961] 2023: 315-16). The symptoms of the *tarantati* – individuals under the influence of tarantism (also *tarantata* or *tarantato* in the feminine or masculine singular forms of the noun in Italian) – were close to some diagnoses of delirium, psychosis, or neurosis. However, they took on modes of subjective suffering and symbolic-ritual resolution that could only be understood within that historicity and that cultural apparatus. Suffering is universal, but the languages used to handle pain are historical and cultural. Any universalist reductionism on the part of the psychiatry of the time, according to Jervis, (Ibid., 316), would be insufficient to understand the specificity of this phenomenon:

The hypothesis that the *tarantati* are preferentially subjects of low intelligence and low culture compared to the average population has little value so long as statistical confirmation is lacking; the high number of illiterates among them is not necessarily significant since the cases studied are few concerning a region where illiteracy is high. For the same

reasons, the data collected so far are not such as to substantiate the hypothesis that tarantism groups individuals predisposed to constitutional psychopathies or nervous diseases.... Tarantism is a phenomenon with multifaceted aspects, which cannot be resolved in exclusively psychiatric terms; its future study can probably be continued only on the basis of interdisciplinary convergence.

De Martino's importance to the field of Italian and European ethnopsychiatry lies in his capacity for historical-anthropological and psychoanalytical understanding of cultural phenomena that had previously been interpreted as physiological or exclusively psychiatric pathologies. As well as working with psychiatrist Giovanni Jervis on his ethnographic expedition to southern Italy, de Martino also chose a psychologist, Letizia Jervis Comba, to form part of his transdisciplinary research.

Using the Rorschach psychological test, Comba found that although this type of test can be used in a variety of cultural contexts, it lacks a conceptual and symbolic translation tool. Applying a test developed for a particular white European society in a diverse cultural context can be risky when trying to interpret the causes of subjective suffering. This diversity can even appear within the country in which the test was constructed. When discussing the Rorschach methodology, Comba ([1961] 2023: 339) states that "numerous experimental studies show us how even within one culture, even within one society, situations exist or can be created, which can lead to different paths that reflect on the results."

Regarding the results obtained with the Rorschach test, "they are rather reactions to a situation that does not have the same meaning for those living in a different existential context from the one in which the test was studied" (Ibid., 340). In this way, Comba supports one of the core ideas of Demartinian ethnopsychiatry: the cultural specificity and symbolic autonomy of ritual and its ability to resolve suffering, a technique for recovering presence and reinsertion into history.

One of the great contributions of *La terra del rimorso* (1961) to ethnopsychiatry was its ability to depathologize a legitimate and creative cultural practice, appropriated in southern Italy as a tool for managing existence and psychological suffering (Castelnuovo and Riso, 1982; Riso and Böker, [1964] 2000). De Martino's ethnography questioned the universality of the methods and diagnoses of psychiatry at the time, characterized by a markedly biological and genetic interpreta-

tion of mental disorders. Culture, then, was not a social mask for a universal diagnosis such as schizophrenia or other psychoses. It was understood as a legitimate way of naming, through its own grammar, and managing subjective pain in a metahistorical and ritualistic context where the cause of anguish is given an interpretative and resolute horizon (Beneduce, 2019; Pires, 2023; 2024). The “decolonial” tone of his approach in the field of mental health lies precisely in this perspective that decentralizes the hegemony and sovereignty of the official knowledge of psychiatry (read Western European and Anglo-Saxon), opening the way for other modalities of healing and psychic manifestations (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015; Pires, 2023; Zinn, 2015).

It is interesting to observe, however, that de Martino does not fall into absolute cultural relativism. There is a dialogue, a mediation, between the established knowledge of psychiatry, anthropology and psychoanalysis, and the specificities of cultural languages. There is no dichotomy between these two dimensions, just as there is no absolute separation between “high” and “low” culture. De Martino deconstructs these polarizations in favor of an unequal circularity without hierarchies of value, recognizing in the rural culture of southern Italy a space of resistance and existential creativity (Cannarsa, 1992; Dei, 2023).

The medical discourse of pathologizing subaltern culture, or not recognizing it as a legitimate way of dealing with suffering, is a question of class and power. The folklore and ritual narrative of the Italian South in the mid-twentieth century was erased or left out of scientific studies. The failure to recognize the power of culture (in this case of the rural South) in addressing human suffering presupposes a hierarchization and exclusion of everything that was not legitimized as an effective method capable of healing, namely psychiatry and gradually psychology.

Although it was a legitimate strategy, de Martino ([1961b] 2023) and his team knew that tarantism would soon come to an end and that other forms of healing and management of suffering would be needed. In this way, there is a recognition in his theory of the legitimacy of subaltern cultures as a creative and effective way of coping with pain, but at the same time, there was an idealized project of providing the population of the Mezzogiorno with better social and cultural conditions and alternatives for managing psychic suffering (Beneduce and Taliani, 2015; Gallini, 2005). De Martino did not exclude the importance of psy-

chiatry, psychoanalysis, and psychology in the process of treating subjective suffering; however, he believed that there should be a nonethnocentric and nonhierarchical mediation of this knowledge.

Ernesto de Martino's work is vast, and his southern trilogy – *Sud e magia* (South and magic); *Morte e pianto rituale* (Death and ritual mourning); and *La terra del rimorso* – addresses many of the themes I analyzed earlier, making him a forerunner of ethnopsychiatric theory in Italy. However, I believe that the transdisciplinary ethnography carried out by him and his team in Southern Italy in 1959, concatenated in *La terra del rimorso*, is the most emblematic and important for the discussion of this article. For this reason, I have chosen this research, published in 1961, as the main document of analysis below, bearing in mind the limits that this choice implies regarding the amplitude of de Martino's theory and intellectual trajectory.

The Land of Remorse and Bites: Case Studies with the *Tarantati*

In the winter of 1959, Ernesto de Martino and his transdisciplinary team prepared an ethnography to be carried out in Southern Italy in June of the same year, during the days when the tarantism ritual would take place in the chapel. There was, however, a central question to be investigated: was this ritual an autonomous cultural and symbolic phenomenon or the physical manifestation of a disease caused by the bite of an arachnid? This medical hypothesis has permeated the history of tarantism since the Renaissance: “In the literature on tarantism, from the seventeenth century onward, the *medical* interpretation stood in the foreground, according to which it was a *disease*, to be attributed either to a toxic syndrome from a poisonous arachnid bite or to a psychic disturbance dependent or independent of arachnidism” (de Martino, [1961b] 2023: 23). The second hypothesis was confirmed throughout the research and its results, as I will explore throughout this topic.

The team formed by de Martino was fundamental in investigating the complexity of the phenomenon of tarantism beyond the pathologization of medical discourse. One of the members was Giovanni Jervis, a doctor specializing in clinical neuropsychiatry at the University of Rome. The team also included a psychologist, Letizia Jervis Comba, who in 1956 obtained her master's degree from the Department of Psychology at Cornell University. Although he was not part of the group, Doctor Sergio Bettini, from the Higher Institute of Health, was an important consultant on the toxic syndrome caused by the bite of the

Latrodectus tredecim guttatus. To analyze the musical aspect of tarantism, de Martino invited the ethnomusicologist Diego Carpitella. He also asked the anthropologist Amalia Signorelli-D'Ayala to contribute to the discussion in the field of cultural anthropology (Ibid., 23-24).

Between June 28 and 30, 1959, during the days of the festive celebration in Galatina, in the province of Lecce in Puglia, the team identified 35 *tarantati*, 19 of whom were visited successively in their hometowns. Two cases were subsequently added. De Martino (Ibid., 37) wanted to prove or disprove the medical hypothesis about this phenomenon, which consisted of “limiting tarantism to a form of arachnidism and reducing it to a psychological disorder.”

Tarantism is a cultural phenomenon that circulated in the European and Mediterranean world since medieval times, changing throughout modern history (Ibid.; Pompa, 2022). The diachronic aspects of this ritual are explored by de Martino, but will not be the focus of my investigation, which seeks to understand the anthropological and psychoanalytical interpretation of this case and not its historical genealogy. What the researchers witnessed in 1959 in Southern Italy was a remnant of this cultural practice, adapted to local specificities and the historicity of the time. It was a rite in decline, about to disappear, as the team identified at the beginning of the ethnography. Throughout modern times, this phenomenon was interpreted from a medical and biological perspective, in which the symptoms presented by the *tarantati* were the consequence of the actual bite of a poisonous arachnid. The etymology of tarantism comes from the name “tarantula” for the venomous animal, the material and symbolic root of a narrative that de Martino and his team identified as something far beyond (psycho)pathology.

The physiological explanation defended by most doctors and scholars is concatenated in the definition of “toxic latrodectism syndrome.” After being bitten by an arachnid of the genus *Latrodectus*, the subject experiences symptoms of an altered mental state, subjective suffering, pain, and other physical consequences:

the crisis of tarantism approximately mimicked the toxic syndrome of latrodectism.... The falling to the ground, the sense of exhaustion, the anguish, the state of psychomotor agitation with obnubilation of the sensorium, the difficulty of keeping upright, the stomachache, nausea, and vomiting, the various paresthesias and muscular pains, the exaltation of the venereal appetite.... (de Martino, [1961b] 2023: 46)

This explanation was the most widely accepted during modern times and even when de Martino began his ethnography in Puglia. He

and his team suspected, however, that something from the symbolic field was involved in this apparently pathological phenomenon. Given the long biological and positivist tradition of medicine and psychiatry, it was not surprising that tarantism was considered exclusively a disease caused by a *Latrodectus*.

Tarantism occurred during the summer, between May and August. Exactly at harvest time and during the intense work in the fields. This was when the “first bite” occurred, and from that moment on, the symptoms of the “bite” were repeated constantly and seasonally during the same period. For example, a person bitten in July or August would show symptoms during the summer; the following year, the same symptoms would recur, repeating the behaviors and intensity of the physical and subjective suffering. Through this and other findings, de Martino (Ibid., 40) began to suspect that it was not just something to do with the physiology of the spider bite:

the toxic syndrome from the bite of *Latrodectus tredecim guttatus* was absolutely incompatible with the recurrence of the crisis for dozens of years. Instead, this repetition, so characteristic of tarantism, hinted at cultural conditioning, respect for a tradition, the seasonal repetition of a rite, the calendrical celebration of a ceremony.

The author’s question arises from the repetition of the symptoms of tarantism. How could the symptoms caused by the “first bite” be repeated every year? Every summer, the anguish, delirium, loss of self, and states of agitation and fainting return. All this is repeated in the same summer context for years and decades. Every summer, a “re-bite” (*ri-morso*). In Italian, *rimorso* means re-bite or remorse. Both represent a subjective state and a symbolic action of tarantism on the body. Gradually, de Martino (Ibid., 46) came to the conclusion that tarantism had a symbolic autonomy and could not be reduced to a disease caused by the poisoning of a tarantula, “escaping any attempt to ‘naturalistically reduce’ tarantism to a somatic or psychic illness.” However, this cultural phenomenon was connected to the narrative of physiological illness, caused by the actual bite of the *Latrodectus tredecim guttatus* or another venomous animal.

Among the many cases analyzed by Ernesto de Martino and his team, I have selected three that offer an in-depth view of tarantism, based on the biography and suffering of these individuals: Maria di Nardò, Filomena di Cerfignano, and Pietro di Nardò. From these cases, it will be possible to understand the family, subjective, sociocultural,

and psychic aspects of the plot that made up tarantism, that is, how tarantism was constituted as a horizon for resolving and accommodating the mental suffering of those subjects.

Maria di Nardò

The first case concerns Maria di Nardò, a *tarantata* who worked in the tobacco harvest and in the fields. She was married for nine years to a peasant. Orphaned by her father 13 years ago, she was taken to her aunt and uncle's house and had little contact with her mother. De Martino reports that Maria di Nardò spent her adolescence in constant anguish due to this situation of non-place and contempt from her family. When she was 18, she fell in love with a young man; however, for financial reasons, his family opposed the marriage, and he left her. "Maria suffered greatly from this abandonment because she was in her first love: and so 'one Sunday at noon' she was bitten by the tarantula while at the window and was forced to dance" (Ibid., 70).

The mother of another boy considered Maria de Nardò to be a good partner for her unemployed and sick son, even though she was a *tarantata*. This title did not carry good connotations in that society, as it meant someone who showed a certain emotional instability. The mother asked Maria if she would like to marry her son, but "still having her first love in her heart, [Maria] did not utter a word, and to take her time she made the excuse that she had no money for the trousseau because of the tarantula, which forced her to dance and continually run up debts with the musicians" (Ibid., 71). As mother and son continued to insist with their marriage proposal, "a new character, St. Paul, came on the scene, who appeared to Maria and commanded her not to marry, calling her to a mystical wedding with him" (Ibid.).

In order to advance the situation and the proposal, the mother and son sent a woman to Maria's house and invite her to talk to them. Maria was taken out of town, where they were waiting for her and proposed that she live with her potential husband for a while to see how the situation would develop. Maria accepted this request and, after a while, when her partner addressed her in a rude tone asking her to iron the bed linen, they fought. After this event, Maria met St. Peter and St. Paul in her "vision" and they both said to her: "Leave the iron behind and come with us." She replied: "And who do I leave my husband with?" The saints responded: "Don't worry about your husband" (Ibid.). The situation continued as follows:

It was on a Sunday, at noon, the very same day and hour when she had first been bitten by the tarantula and received her first call from St. Paul.

Maria, after wandering around the fields for three days, returned to her parents: St. Paul, displeased with her for disobeying his order not to marry, let her be bitten a second time, forcing her to dance for nine days. Meanwhile, the whole neighborhood knew that she had been in the farmhouse with the young man, and to repair the misdeed it was now necessary to get married, even if it was unwelcome to her and the saint. The conflict thus came to a compromise: Maria consented to the wedding to the new suitor – that is, to her current husband – but at the same time maintained her seasonal relationship with the tarantula and the saint, renewing the crisis and the dance every year, with a marked preference for the warm months, for the menstrual period and the approach of the Galatina festival. (Ibid., 71-72)

The St. Paul element is interpreted by de Martino as a sublimated figure of unfulfilled first love. We can also understand the vision with the saint as a Super-egoic self-punishment for the nonfulfillment of Maria's desire or, on the contrary, as the radical expression of her unrealized desire. St. Paul's order not to marry her current husband symbolizes, on the narrative level of tarantism, a deep unfulfilled desire, resulting in the punishment of dancing for nine days. However, this is not just a symbolization of an unsatisfied will, but an operation to resolve the situation and the anguish felt by Maria di Nardò. Maria's psychic conflict is accommodated in the ritual repetition of tarantism, finding meaning and a horizon of resolution in it.

The repression of desire creates a constant psychic conflict, generating a symptom that found meaning and resolution in the ritual of tarantism, not just because of the scarcity of languages for pain, but as an authentic and creative way of elaborating suffering through the cultural grammar present at that time. Thus, by marrying a man she did not love, "Maria continued periodically to pay her tribute to the tarantula and the saint, each time reciting in the symbolism of the ritual the story of the love bite" (Ibid., 72). The resolute operation, according to de Martino (Ibid.), took place

in the mythical-ritual horizon of tarantism – and of the Christian grafting of the figure of St. Paul – Maria periodically released her conflicting energies and symbolically enacted her frustrations, thus relieving the interceremonial periods, that is, daily life, from the burden of unconscious tensions that would have been extremely dangerous if she had not found in tarantism a socialized and traditionalized framework for calendrical and festive treatment. Through the mythical order of "tarantula," "bite," "poison," and St. Paul, Maria gave shape to conflicting and frustrating psychic content.

Through tarantism, Maria managed her subjective conflicts, creating a way of dealing with the fact that she had married unwillingly and had to endure the presence of her husband and the absence of her family. Her anguish was displaced into a resolving ritual circumstance, in a cathartic and symbolizing way. It was resolute not as a total cure or disappearance of symptoms, but as a therapeutic and soothing function, as de Martino mentions. In other words, it was a way of seeing her pain publicly recognized, resolved collectively by the gaze of others and by the expulsion of her suffering through the musical exorcism of tarantism:

At the same time, Maria channeled her aggressive energy against her unwelcome husband in an alienated form, putting a strain on marital life, financially harming the unloved family, and clamorously calling attention to her personal drama from people who normally did not pay attention to her....

Among other things, the case of Maria di Nardò highlighted how tarantism provided a symbolic device for a conflicting psychic content, which had found no resolution on the level of consciousness, and which operated in the darkness of the unconscious, risking being asserted as a neurotic symbol. It was evoked and configured on the mythical-ritual plane. There, it could be periodically discharged and enacted, relieving the interceremonial periods of its stresses, and facilitating a relative psychic equilibrium during those periods. (Ibid., 72-73)

Although this was not the only example they investigated, the case of Maria di Nardò was one of the most complete in biographical, anthropological, and psychoanalytical terms, with the greatest possibilities for interpretation. Its qualitative and ethnographic material allowed us to visualize the hypotheses of de Martino and his team. The next shorter analyses will illustrate other sides of the complex subjective and cultural phenomenon of tarantism.

Filomena di Cerfignano

On June 24, 1959, just before de Martino's team left for the town of Nardò, they observed an interesting case in the St. Paul's chapel in Galatina concerning tarantism's symbolic autonomy. It was a 71-year-old peasant woman called Filomena di Cerfignano, who was sitting at the altar on a bunch of chickpeas, ceremonially repeating the disaster that had befallen her:

Filomena lamented her aching abdomen, legs, kidneys, head, and precordial oppression – using the mimetic modes and melodic structure of Cerfignano's funeral lament – and scattered her lament with invocations

to St. Paul: “My beautiful saint, grant me mercy! I have done nothing to you! Do not use poison one more time!” (Ibid., 74)

Filomena told the team, as confirmed by her daughter and her husband, that it was a first-bite episode, which took place in front of the couple’s house. Five days earlier, at midday, she had fought with her husband while she was collecting chickpeas from a branch, which she had placed at her feet when she was in the chapel. Just then, a spider bit her. Filomena saw the animal slide down her legs, and when she got home, she saw the green arachnid on the bed, the same one that had bitten her a short time before. There was not enough time for the spider to take off into the house on the bed, but her husband confirmed that this type of animal “flies like the wind” and is capable of such speed and agility. De Martino asked her why she had not killed the spider. Filomena replied that it was “a creature of St. Paul” and that killing it would be an offense to the saint. Her husband confirmed that the arachnid had been sent by the saint. This case illustrates how important family and cultural narratives are for maintaining the ritual and symbolism of tarantism. An environment, historicity, and sharing are necessary. The pain was resignified collectively.

The same day she was bitten, Filomena went to St. Paul’s chapel, as she knew she was in a frightened state. The visit had no effect. According to a baptismal godmother who was there, the cure would only come if Filomena dressed as she had when she was bitten, bringing with her the object that had been found at the scene of the bite (in this case, the bunch of chickpeas she had been carrying). Filomena went back to the house to follow the instructions of the lady from Galatina and returned to the chapel soon after. Her husband reported the following about the episode of the bite and the symptoms of his *tarantata* wife:

The husband explained that his wife had not been bitten by a “dancing” or “singing” or “libertine” tarantula and therefore did not dance, did not feel stimulated by joyful songs, and did not indulge in lascivious mimicry: it was simply a “sad and mute” tarantula that disdained the rhythm of the tarantella folk dance and induced in its victim a melancholic mood, which could at most be expressed through a funeral lament. (Ibid., 75)

The spider represents, within the unique narrative of tarantism, the symptom that the victim suffers and from which she must rid herself through musical exorcism, performed by the paid community band. In Filomena’s case, these were sadness, melancholy, and the inability to

speak. These symptoms, however, are located within the subject's trajectory and through a traumatic or distressing situation that has not been resolved psychically, inaugurated in the scene of the "first bite." The psychic conflict, in this case, was not explored as much due to the lack of information gathered during the interview with Filomena. The only clue was the fight with her husband, which was probably linked to problems, repressions, and anguish in her marital or family life.

As de Martino (1961b) concluded, it is interesting to observe that the language used to express and elaborate Filomena's suffering existed within the shared grammar of tarantism, constituting what he calls the "symbolic autonomy of the ritual." Going to St Paul's chapel without the objects and clothes she had been carrying when she was first bitten had no therapeutic or calming effect. Although the team does not exclude the real presence of the bite and the arachnid, the process of resolution and elaboration of the pain follows different paths, autonomous from the reality of latroductism.

Pietro di Nardò

On July 5, 1959, the team visited Pietro di Nardò on a farm. Pietro was a 50-year-old farmer who was bitten at night while sleeping in 1955. The doctor at the Nardò hospital said it was a real case of latroductism: "the patient presented with psychomotor agitation with sensory obnubilation, extremely violent pain in the head, widespread pain in the whole body and limbs, pronounced painful rigidity of muscle masses, conjunctival hyperemia, and urinary retention that lasted for two days" (Ibid., 76). He was the only real victim of *latroductus toxicus* syndrome caused by arachnid venom, but even in his case the symbolic autonomy of tarantism was present.

After having been bitten by the arachnid in 1955, Pietro visualized the spider and began to repeat bodily movements following the traditional model of tarantism. Pietro became a publicly recognized *tarantato*, dancing to the sound of the musical exorcism and the colors presented to him. The ritual narrative is made up of a specific symbolic and corporeal apparatus, but also of a collective and individual recognition of being "possessed" or "commanded" by the "spider entity" responsible for the first bite (in this case, real and symbolic at the same time). De Martino (Ibid.) reports:

Discharged from the hospital in Nardò, where he had been admitted, and despite this diagnosis, he had now become a *tarantato*, stimulated by music, dance, and colors. In fact, he danced for four days, to the

sound of the tarantella, while the audience threw ribbons of various colors at him “for proof”: but Pietro wanted a multicolored rag, and wrapped his head with it, like a turban.

Pietro’s crises occurred in and out of the typical season of tarantism (summer). However, there was always an element that provoked this altered state of consecutive dancing, whether it was sound or colors. One day, when he went to the barber-violinist in his town, he had another crisis, caused by someone playing the guitar. It is unknown whether it was out of malice or just an accident. From then on, Pietro began to show movements of the traditional dance of the *tarantati*. He was taken to the house, where he asked for the musicians (those responsible for playing the songs that made the *tarantati* dance and free themselves):

In fact, the group of players arrived from Nardò, led by the barber-violinist. Pietro indulged wildly in the dance: he went dancing through the fields, on the ground, or on his feet, followed by the group of players who tried as best they could to discipline this frenzy with rhythm, and to prevent their client from falling into some ditch and hurting himself. In January ’56, still out of season, another crisis and another dance. Then nothing more, until this year. The crisis had occurred just two days before our visit, roughly corresponding to the time of the “first bite,” in the right season, according to all the rules of tarantism. (Ibid., 77)

In addition to the dance and the musical exorcism, the figure of St. Paul was also present in Pietro’s imagination. His relationship with the saint consisted of a search for healing, to expel the interference of the “tarantula” in his life. The saint, however, forced Pietro to dance for hours and days, threatening him if he did not follow his orders. De Martino (Ibid., 78) reports:

Once the saint ordered him to dance “until noon” and to go to the chapel in Galatina the next day: in fact, at the tolling of the noon bell, Pietro stopped dancing, but since he did not feel like going to Galatina the next day, because of the great fatigue that usually follows dancing, the implacable saint threatened him, “I’m waiting for you: if you don’t come, the worst is yours.” Pietro and his family (his wife, three daughters, and sister) reported these facts to us, showing a certain resentment toward the tarantula, which forced its victims to such eccentric behavior and unbalanced the family budget with heavy spending.

Pietro’s subjective suffering, however, is not clear from the accounts collected by de Martino’s team. However, there is a clue in the passage quoted above that points to some interpretative directions: the existence of a tarantula entity that forced a family man to behave like

this and obey its movements and characteristics. To do what was not socially authorized, to break with what limited Pietro in his position as a father who must behave: “At one point, while narrating his dance through the fields accompanied by the little orchestra, Pietro commented with a melancholy sigh, ‘But just see what a family man like me gets up to!’” (Ibid.).

Tarantism repositions the psychic suffering that afflicts the subject, moving it into a symbolic narrative where the *tarantato* follows the orders of St. Paul and the spider. In this context of ritual dance and dis(obedience), Pietro let flow what he was not allowed to do as a family man, within that community and historicity. As de Martino reports, unbalancing himself and assuming an eccentric position was at the heart of Pietro’s anguish. The discomfort was probably located in family relationships. The ritual offered, even under the dictates of a possessing entity, a transgression of a forbidden position (getting lost, dancing for hours and days, getting out of his father’s social role). The ritual could move anguish to a symbolic context different from social reality, in which it was possible to identify a therapeutic horizon and a resolution to suffering.

The repression of desire found its possibility of symbolic realization in the ritual within the language of tarantism. In this operation lies the resolute horizon that this cultural phenomenon provided. It was a topic developed, for example, by contemporary ethnopsychiatry in Europe through various approaches. Nevertheless, de Martino and his team opened a space for this debate at the end of the 1950s.

Final Considerations

De Martino was a key author in the development of Italian ethnopsychiatry. The debates listed in this paper present the beginning of the process of incorporating culture as an autonomous and effective language in the management of suffering, without disregarding the validity of and dialogue with the established psy field. In this way, his work initiated, at least in the Italian context, a process of decolonization of psy-knowledge, which was based exclusively on Anglo-Saxon and European psychiatry.

Decolonization, in this case, would be the opening up to other modalities and operations for managing suffering that were not completely aligned with psychiatric manuals and politically legitimized psy theories at a global level. De Martino presented us with a cultural lan-

guage (tarantism) that accommodated the suffering of the subjects participating in this narrative and ritual. Tarantism displaced anguish into a mythical-symbolic field in which the bite of the arachnid and the musical dance-exorcism incorporated a horizon of meaning and resolution of the problem.

De Martino's work became the basis of Italian ethnopsychiatry and transcultural psychiatry from the 1960s onward (Stanghellini and Ciglia, 2013). The most emblematic example was Risso and Böker's ([1964] 2000) *Sortilegio e delirio* (Sorcery and delirium), a study of Southern Italian immigrants in Switzerland who presented symptoms and explanations for their subjective suffering based on the symbolic-cultural reality of the Mezzogiorno: magical works, enchantments, possessions, and states of "loss of self." Vittorio Lanternari (2000: 14) states:

It could be said that de Martino opens the way of ethnopsychiatry in Italy at the time when Risso opens that of transcultural psychiatry: and by that I mean that ethnopsychiatry presents itself as that section of anthropological science that opens up to the psychiatric perspective, in order to identify and interpret the relationships between behaviors and collective representations from cognitive and scientific intents.

Working with subjectivity means working with difference, with singularity, with Otherness. De Martino, in his anthropological-psychanalytical approach in dialogue with Gramscian Marxism, believed that change and social equality in southern Italy would bring relief and new ways of dealing with suffering beyond tarantism. If Fanon had an engaged clinic, de Martino proposed an engaged ethnography, a new humanism present in his concept of "critical ethnocentrism." His political and intellectual work began in the 1950s but is still in vogue in contemporary social and clinical discussions, whether in psychiatry or anthropology. This debate is not over, and these authors identified a problem that is still present today: a clinic that is alienated from social changes is very limited.

Recent research has emphasized the importance of the humanities (history, anthropology, sociology) in considering mental health at a global level, as well as how culture and society cross our minds (Antić et al., 2023). This is still a current debate in transdisciplinary studies of the mind, with its roots in the twentieth century. De Martino, as my analysis has shown, was fundamental to the foundation of Italian eth-

nopsychiatry and is closely connected to this debate, which is researched worldwide in transcultural studies of the psyche (Antić et al., 2023; Beneduce, 2005, 2011; Beneduce and Taliani, 2015).

Whether or not Ernesto de Martino was a pioneer in these discussions, locally or globally, was not the aim of this article. However, what I would like to highlight is how, at the end of the 1950s, he developed a historical-anthropological reading of mental suffering and its management, moving away from biologizing psychiatric paradigms that dismissed the role of culture and the psychogenesis of mental disorders. This debate is still in vogue, full of contradictions and open questions.

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The Dialectics of Marxism and Neo-Freudianism: Ideological Dogmatism and the Limits of Criticism in Socialist Albania¹

Abstract: *This article analyses the book Neofrojdzimi: filozofi e njeriut të tjetërsuar [Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human] (1989) by Artan Fuga, in which Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism are criticized from the standpoint of Orthodox Marxism. By situating Fuga's book in the political and ideological context of 1989 and comparing it to an earlier work by Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto (Neo-Freudianism: One of the Theoretical Bases of Bourgeois Liberalism, 1974), the article investigates whether there was any ideological evolution between generations of Albanian philosophers. The analysis shows that, despite the softer political climate of the late 1980s, Marxist dogmatism continued to shape the treatment of Freudian and Neo-Freudian ideas. Ultimately, the article argues that the rigid ideological framework of Albanian Marxism-Leninism left little room for theoretical synthesis or critical engagement with alternative schools of thought, including psychoanalysis. This contributes to a broader understanding of philosophy, political thought, and ideological continuity in socialist Albania.*

Keywords: *psychoanalysis; Marxism-Leninism; ideology; intellectual history.*

Introduction

This article examines a work written in 1989, on the eve of the fall of Albania's socialist regime, on the topic of Neo-Freudianism, *Neofrojdzimi: filozofi e njeriut të tjetërsuar* [Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human] by Artan Fuga (Fuga, 1989). Fuga is currently one of the most renowned Albanian philosophers, known

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both domestically and internationally, with a long academic career as a lecturer and researcher in philosophy and communication sciences at the University of Tirana and in Paris. This article, however, does not seek to provide a general account of his philosophical thought. Rather, it focuses on a work in which he critiques Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism from the perspective of Orthodox Marxism.

This study continues a previous work by the author that examined the official position of the Albanian political leadership regarding Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism (Brisku, 2024). It is worth noting here that, while psychologists in the so-called West generally regarded Freudianism/psychoanalysis as a method of treatment in clinical psychology (American Psychological Association, 2023) and Neo-Freudianism as an approach derived from Freud's psychoanalysis that emphasized social and cultural over biological factors (APA, 2018), in socialist Albania, Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism were considered "currents within bourgeois idealist philosophy and psychology," (Universiteti i Tiranës, Fakulteti i Shkencave Politike dhe Juridike, 1981: 146).

This perspective is evident in the discourse of the Albanian political leadership, in official philosophical texts of the time, and in the writings of Artan Fuga.

My aim, therefore, is to analyse and critique Artan Fuga's criticism of Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism. Although the title suggests a focus on Neo-Freudianism, Fuga begins with Sigmund Freud and continues with authors he categorizes as Neo-Freudians – such as Carl Jung, Erich Fromm, and, to a lesser extent, Herbert Marcuse, Gilles Deleuze, Alfred Adler, Melanie Klein, and Karen Horney (Fuga, 1989: 3-5). The main reasons for the greater focus on Jung and Fromm likely include, first, their broader popularity, including within Albania, and second, the fact that, alongside Freud, they had been criticized by the Albanian political leadership. Fuga's book was written on the eve of the regime's collapse in 1989, a period when the Albanian state-socialist regime was no longer at the height of its violence and repression (Fischer & Schmitt, 2022: 167). Furthermore, in the spheres of education, arts, and culture, the regime had begun implementing a policy of tolerance. Yet, in official ideological discourse, Albania never abandoned its claim to uphold the Orthodox Marxist-Leninist line. So, in addition to analysing and critiquing of Fuga's treatment of Freud and the Neo-Freudians, this article also offers a comparative overview of his work in relation to that of Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto. Their earlier study, *Neo-Frojdianizmi – Një nga bazat teorike të liberalizmit*

borgjez [Neo-Freudianism: One of the Theoretical Bases of Bourgeois Liberalism] (Riska & Zoto, 1974) was examined in detail in my previous article (Brisku, 2024). The purpose of this comparison is to determine whether, over the span of fifteen years, there was any evolution in the official political stance or in Albanian philosophical thought regarding Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism, particularly across different generations of philosophers.

In this way, the article seeks to contribute to the study of the history of philosophy, political thought, and ideology in socialist Albania. By examining Artan Fuga's critique of Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism, it aims to highlight the dogmatism and rigidity of Marxist thought in Albania, which precluded meaningful engagement with other philosophical currents. Moreover, by situating Fuga's book – published in 1989, on the threshold of the regime's collapse – alongside the earlier work written during the most repressive years of the system, this study also contributes to the political history of Albania, shedding light on the (lack of) change in ideological discourse during the state socialist period.

The Dialectical Relationship Between Marxism and Psychoanalysis

It is worth noting that neither the Albanian authors nor the country's political leadership were the first to criticize Sigmund Freud from the perspective of Dialectical and Historical Materialism. The critique of Freudian theories from a materialist, Marxist perspective was first developed by one of Freud's contemporaries, the Soviet linguist Valentin Voloshinov (1895–1936). As a linguist, Voloshinov placed great importance on the study of language, which he regarded as an ideological instrument. In his view, understanding human psychology requires the study of language and verbal communication, since language, being ideological in nature, shapes both human thought and psychology (Voloshilov, 2012 [1927]: 60).

For Voloshinov, Freud's principle flaw was his emphasis on the "sexual drive" as the primary impulse behind social and political phenomena. This, he argued, reflected Freud's unfamiliarity with contemporary psychology and his reliance on an unscientific method. Freud based his work largely on observation and empiricism, which led to erroneous conclusions. As a Marxist, Voloshinov stressed the important

role of external factors in - particularly language as an ideological instrument - in shaping human thought and psychology (Voloshilov, 2012 [1927]: 87-90).

Another critique of Freudianism came from the Soviet psychiatrist Dmitry Fedotov (1908–1982), who wrote in 1959 that Freudianism was not a psychological theory but rather a manifestation of idealist philosophy within psychology. Fedotov argued that it sought to formulate laws explaining the evolution of human society based on this idealist framework. For him, the most telling sign of Freudian idealism was its claim that unconscious sexual instincts are the fundamental drivers of human and social behaviour (Fedotov, 1959: 35-38).

As noted, Albanian authors had addressed the critique of Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism well before Artan Fuga's book. Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto put forward a critique similar to Fedotov's, describing Freudianism as a reflection of idealist philosophy within psychology that explains human behaviour, both individual and social, on the basis of innate sexual instincts, thereby making it a reactionary approach. In their view, despite its ostensibly critical stance towards Marxism, Neo-Freudianism in fact retained its core premise by treating sexual instincts as the primary driver of human behaviour. As such, it sought to explain the problems of capitalist societies not by addressing their economic roots but by focusing on the human psyche, which, they argued, rendered this philosophy equally reactionary (Riska & Zoto, 1974).

An important feature of Riska and Zoto's work, which is also reiterated in Artan Fuga's book, pertains to their explanation for engaging with Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism. This interest can be traced, first, to the spread of Neo-Freudian theories in capitalist and revisionist countries, which could also influence Albanian society; and second, to the role Neo-Freudianism had assumed globally in philosophy, the arts, and culture where, as already noted, it serves to justify the problems caused by capitalism. Furthermore, given Albania's self-proclaimed role as a defender of Marxism-Leninism, Albanian authors saw it as their duty to produce a Marxist critique of any ideology or philosophical current they deemed bourgeois and revisionist (Ibid., 3-4).

As mentioned, beyond Freud's theories, Fuga's book focuses more heavily on authors he considers to be Freud's followers, labelling them as Neo-Freudians. Most of his attention is devoted to two authors he considers the most significant: Carl Jung and Erich Fromm.

Carl Jung emphasized the exploration of the unconscious mind and the role of symbols, archetypes, and individuation in understanding human psychology. He believed that the unconscious mind contains not only personal experiences but also collective and ancestral memories that shape an individual's behaviour and personality. Jung was highly sceptical of Marxism and never engaged with Marx as a thinker. While both Marx and Jung sought to uncover invisible layers of reality and were ultimately concerned with human flourishing and forms of healing, their approaches could not be more different. Marx's politico-economic project was mainly concerned with the material conditions of human existence, whereas Jung's psychology focused on the subjective and unconscious dimensions of human experience. Marx emphasized the importance of collective action and the struggle against exploitation and oppression, while Jung stressed individual self-discovery and the integration of the unconscious (Gerber, 2021: 3-5).

Unlike Jung, Erich Fromm attempted to reconcile the theories of Freud and Marx (Cheliotis, 2011: 439). Fromm believed that Freud's psychoanalytic theory could help explain the psychological effects of capitalism, while Marx's historical materialism could account for its economic and social effects. Fromm argued that capitalism creates a society in which people are alienated from themselves, from each other, and from nature – an alienation that leads to psychological problems such as anxiety, depression, and narcissism. Fromm also contended that ruling elites in capitalist societies use their power to legitimize their position and maintain their own sense of self-worth, rather than to serve the interests of the masses they govern (Fromm, 1970: 60-82).

While Soviet psychiatrists such as Dmitry Fedotov dismissed psychoanalysis as a therapeutic approach, the broader landscape of psychoanalytic practice and attitudes toward Freud in socialist states during the second half of the twentieth century was far more complex. As Dagmar Herzog has shown, psychoanalysis evolved and was reinterpreted in both East and the West throughout the Cold War, shaped by the traumas of the Second World War and by differing political and cultural contexts. In the West, psychoanalytic discourse was often employed to critique or interpret the political dynamics of the socialist bloc, while in socialist countries – even when marginalized or officially repressed – psychoanalysis continued to play an influential role, particularly among cultural and intellectual elites (Herzog, 2017).

In this regard, the Yugoslav case stands out as distinctive. Due to the comparatively greater openness of the Yugoslav socialist regime –

especially in terms of scientific and cultural exchange with both blocs – psychoanalysis experienced a more sustained development. As Ana Antić writes, Yugoslav psychiatry and psychoanalysis were not only tolerated but also integrated into broader state strategies, including efforts to extend influence within the so-called Third World (Antić, 2021). This shows the variability of socialist engagements with psychoanalysis and contrasts with the more repressive model seen initially in the Soviet Union and later in Albania.

The Development of Psychiatry and the Marginalization of Psychotherapy in Socialist Albania

In Albania psychoanalysis was primarily regarded as a philosophy of bourgeois idealism rather than as a psychotherapeutic treatment. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that in the introduction to his book, when discussing Freudianism and psychoanalysis, Artan Fuga writes that in its early stages as a psychiatric method, psychoanalysis had achieved some positive results in treating certain mental disorders and had led to improvements in patients treated by Sigmund Freud (Fuga, 1989: 5-6).

However, psychoanalysis was not officially permitted to be practiced in Albania, even though it is likely that most people at the time would not have sought out psychoanalytic treatment – something attributable less to the socialist regime than to the stigma surrendering mental illnesses in Albanian society. In fact, the origins of psychiatry in Albania are linked to the socialist period, as before this, psychiatric treatments were virtually unknown in the country (Vehbiu, 2023).

Despite having a broader legacy in (bio)medicine – dating back to the Ottoman period and especially the monarchy – psychiatry remained almost entirely unfamiliar in Albania (Hoxha, 1962). Until the socialist period, mental illnesses were mostly treated by so-called “local healers,” which included Orthodox and Catholic priests who performed exorcisms, Muslim imams and dervishes who recited ruqyah (spiritual healing prayers), and other folk practices such as charms or chants intended to ward off evil spirits or the “evil eye.”

The first steps toward the institutional treatment of mental illness in Albania occurred during the socialist period, led by a generation of psychiatrists educated in the Soviet Union and other Socialist countries. In the early years, due in part to the underdevelopment of psychotherapy worldwide at the time, treatments for psychiatric patients primarily involved electroshock therapy, cold-water baths, and insulin shock ther-

apy. However, it is important to note that by the 1950s, Albanian psychiatrists trained in Moscow and elsewhere had introduced the widespread use of pharmacological drugs for the treatment of mental illness (Vehbiu, 2023).

Ulvi Vehbiu (1931-2010), a pioneer of Albanian psychiatry, played a key role in this development by introducing new medications for the treatment of schizophrenia, depression, and neuroses – ranging from chlorpromazine and haloperidol to tricyclic antidepressants, lithium, and benzodiazepines – as well as initiating the practice of psychotherapy. This represented a genuine revolution in the treatment of mental illness in the country. First, it improved the conditions and quality of care in psychiatric hospitals, and second, it made it possible for many patients – after a period of treatment and continued medication – to return to their families and lead “normal” lives. This not only reduced the burden on families but also helped mitigate the social stigma associated with mental illness (Ibid.).

In addition to revolutionizing pharmacological treatment, Dr. Vehbiu also worked to introduce psychotherapy in Albania. In the early 1970s he specialized in psychotherapy in France, training in Schultz’s method of autogenic therapy. Upon returning to Tirana, he established a psychotherapy cabinet where he began treating patients using this method. It is likely that his dispatch to France for psychotherapy training, as well as the official approval to open a psychotherapy cabinet, were made possible by the relatively more open cultural and scientific atmosphere in Albania during the 1970s (Brisku, 2024).

However, in 1974, following the Fourth Plenum of the Central Committee of the Albanian Party of Labour, Dr. Vehbiu was sharply criticized for allegedly incorporating bourgeois ideological influences into psychiatry. Psychotherapy was deemed to be tainted by Freudianism, even though Schultz’s autogenic training was not psychoanalysis. Nevertheless, the psychotherapy cabinet was shut down, and patients could be treated only with medication. Despite the official prohibition, in some exceptional cases he continued to treat select patients with psychotherapy in his private home – particularly those more likely to benefit from such treatment than from pharmacological interventions (Vehbiu, 2023).

Ideological Orthodoxy and Political Discourse in Socialist Albania

The state socialist regime in Albania (1945-1991), both in the international reputation and in much of the scholarship on socialist regimes in Eastern and Central Europe and beyond, has consistently been regarded as highly repressive – severe in its punishment of opponents and, most importantly, highly dogmatic and rigid in its interpretation of Marxism-Leninism (Meksi, 2015).

However, a closer examination reveals that the forty-five years of state socialism in Albania were not marked by unbroken rigidity. Rather, there were distinct phases in which the regime's strictness eased, particularly in the cultural and social spheres, allowing for limited forms of openness. For instance, after the 20th Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union in 1956, although Albania neither pursued de-Stalinization nor changed its political leadership, certain repressive elements of the regime were relaxed. (Mëhilli, 2011) A similar softening occurred in the early 1960s following Albania's break with the Soviet Union, when the regime sought to build broader popular support for its new political direction. (Meksi, 2015)

The mid-1960s to the 1970s, however, represented a period of deep contradictions. On one hand, influenced by China's Cultural Proletarian Revolution, Albania witnessed a heightened extension of collective control over the individual, orchestrated by the central authorities. This process culminated in the 1970s with measures such as the educational reforms of the 1960s, the proliferation of *fletërrufe* (public denunciation posters), youth mobilizations, and the 1967 campaign that forcefully abolished religious practices (Mëhilli, 2017). On the other hand, the regime also made certain concessions. Italian television broadcasts were permitted in parts of the country, and there was increased exposure to Western scientific and artistic literature. Between 1969 and 1972, Enver Hoxha himself encouraged a more open atmosphere and greater freedom for the youth (Lubonja, 2010).

This relative openness came to an abrupt end in 1973. The following decade, lasting until 1983, marked one of the harshest periods of the Albanian socialist regime. It was characterized by a series of purges targeting supposed "hostile elements" in various sectors, including the arts and culture, the military, the economy, the oil industry, and ultimately even the Ministry of the Interior.

In April 1985, Albania's leader of forty years, Enver Hoxha, passed away and was succeeded by a significantly younger figure,

Ramiz Alia, the former Secretary for Ideological Affairs and Propaganda of the Central Committee of the Party of Labour of Albania. Although at the 9th Congress of the Party of Labour of Albania (November 1986), Alia affirmed the continuation of Hoxha's policies, the prevailing public perception in Albania is that the regime's repressive policies weakened during the 1985-1991 period, leading to a liberalization of everyday social and cultural life (Fischer & Schmitt, 2022: 270).

Nevertheless, despite moments of relaxation in the regime's repression or improvements in daily life, the official discourse of the Albanian political leadership remained committed to defending the "ideological purity" of Marxism-Leninism (Akademia e Shkencave e RPS të Shqipërisë, Sektori i Enciklopedisë, 1985: 927). As part of this "battle," the Central Committee apparatus, the Institute of Marxist-Leninist Studies, and the Faculty of Political and Juridical Sciences produced articles and studies on both domestic and international matters, criticizing so-called philosophical currents and bourgeois and revisionist ideologies, including Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism (Akademia e Shkencave e RPS të Shqipërisë, Sektori i Enciklopedisë, 1985: 825). Such critiques intensified at crucial moments in the Albanian history, such as the breakdown of relations with the Soviet Union, the initial rift with China, and after the 4th Plenum of the Central Committee of the Party of Labour of Albania (in 1973), when "liberal views" in art and culture were condemned (Isufi, 2020: 76). Yet, these critiques continued throughout the regime's existence, including the late 1980s, when Artan Fuga's book (1989) was published.

Importantly, the official ideological ban on Freud and other authors did not mean that their works were entirely absent or unread in Albania. In fact, one of the reasons such critical texts were written was precisely their popularity among the general population – especially among students – who read them in French, Italian, and English. Some works were even translated into Albanian and published by *Rilindja* in Kosovo, which, as part of the former Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, enjoyed greater cultural freedom during the 1970s to translate and publish works that were officially banned in Albania.

Artan Fuga (1954) belonged to the second generation of philosophy scholars in socialist Albania, graduating in 1978 from the Faculty of Political and Juridical Sciences with a specialization in philosophy. From 1981 onward, he lectured at the same faculty. Unlike the previous generation, educated largely in the Soviet Union, this later cohort was trained primarily in Albania, but maintained closer connections to

mainstream Western philosophical currents through increased cultural exchanges with Western countries, particularly France and Italy. This is evident in the works he cited in *Neofrojdzimi: filozofi e njeriut të tjetërsuar* [Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human], which were primarily French publications contemporary with his own. In addition to this book, which critiques Neo-Freudianism, Fuga published other works on bourgeois ideology, including *Filozofët e rinj, shërbëtorë të bindur të kapitalit* [The New Philosophers, Obedient Servants of Capital] (1982), *Ekzistencializmi i Sartrit, filozofi e reaksionit imperialist* [Sartre's Existentialism, Philosophy of Imperialist Reaction] (1986), and a general textbook, *Kritika e filozofisë borgjeze* [Critique of Bourgeois Philosophy] (co-authored with Kristaq Angjeli, 1988).

For a broader public – particularly those unable to read foreign languages or without access to restricted books – such ‘critiques of bourgeois philosophy’ were often the only available window into the thought of these authors. Though saturated with ideological language such as “bourgeois,” “idealist,” and “reactionary,” these texts nevertheless offered a general introduction to their ideas, thereby making them accessible to the wider Albanian public, which otherwise would have had no access even to the basic tenets of their thought.

***Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human,*
by Artan Fuga**

The book’s introduction explicitly states its aim as providing a Marxist-Leninist critique of Neo-Freudian philosophy within the framework of the Party of Labour of Albania. It focuses primarily on Neo-Freudianism’s treatment of the human subject, identifying this as the clearest expression of the philosophy’s “reactionary, idealist, and anti-scientific” character. (Fuga, 1989: 3).

Although the book concentrates on Neo-Freudianism, it addresses Freud himself in its first chapter, focusing on the “reactionary and anti-scientific bases” of his philosophy. Critically examining Freud’s philosophy, Fuga asserts that individual liberty cannot be achieved in society’s absence” in contrast, he emphasized the Marxist-Leninist idea of society’s continuous progress and its path toward true freedom, which can only be realized under socialism (Ibid., 26).

“...Human freedom can only be attained in society, as it is through society that tools of labour can be perfected, human reason developed,

and consequently, humans can subjugate nature for their needs and self-improvement,” (Ibid., 28).

According to Fuga, the emphasis on biological instincts, particularly sexual ones, as determinants of the Albanian worldview and human behaviour leads to the theoretical justification of the flaws of capitalist society. Militarism, aggressiveness, imperialist politics, violence and repression, as well as political and national oppression, are seen by Freud as detached from their “class nature,” and instead as manifestation of human nature itself, driven by instincts (Ibid., 18).

Fuga acknowledges that, as a medical treatment method, psychoanalysis has achieved results in curing patients in clinical settings. However, he does not intend to address the validity of psychoanalysis as therapy for mental disorders. To him, the main issue with Freudianism arises when attempts are made to apply clinical data to society. In attributing individual psychological phenomena to society as a whole, and depicting social development as a struggle between instincts and morality, Freudianism becomes an idealist philosophy. It is here, Fuga argues, that its reactionary essence lies – serving to justify the dominance of ruling classes (Ibid., 21).

Even as a clinical method, however, Fuga identifies a problem in Freud’s explanation of psychological issues as rooted in internal spiritual traumas, especially the repression of instincts, and in particular sexual ones. From a materialist perspective, this approach denies two significant aspects that are considered crucial to the origins of psychological problems: first, biological causes; and second, socio-economic conditions. While the denial of the first cause is, according to Fuga, scientifically flawed, the denial of the second is deliberate, aiming to justify the injustices of capitalism, which produce mental illness in oppressed classes, but are reframed by Freud solely as the result of individual internal trauma (Ibid., 22).

This explains the ban on psychoanalysis as a medical treatment in socialist Albania: even as therapy, it was influenced by idealist philosophy, locating the causes of mental disorders as in the unconscious, instincts, and human nature, rather than in the biological processes of the brain and the external material conditions affecting mental health.

The remainder of the book focuses on a critique of Carl Jung and Erich Fromm whom Fuga regards as the founders of Neo-Freudianism.

According to Fuga, Carl Jung marks the onset of the Neo-Freudian school, representing an evolution from Freudian philosophy. Following the 1940s, Freud’s theories, in Fuga’s view, required reform and

could no longer be sustained in their original form. Jung's efforts, whether in the Zurich School of Psychoanalysis or the International Psychoanalytical Association, were aimed at undermining Marxism-Leninism and quelling revolutionary aspirations among the masses (Ibid., 35).

Despite Jung's modifications to Freudian theories, Fuga contends that Jung remains a worthy successor because he doesn't contradict their essence. According to Fuga, the core of these theories is that human life is governed by irrationality, which has shaped historical events, social processes, and mass movements throughout history. However, Fuga argues that a proper Marxist-Leninist critique of Neo-Freudianism requires noting the distinctions between Freud and his followers – in this case, Jung. For instance, Jung expands Freud's concept of the unconscious to include the spiritual world of the primordial human, which he calls the "archetype" (Ibid., 38). Moreover, Jung transcends Freud's opposition between biology and society, reframing it as a conflict between the spiritual world of antiquity (the archetype) and modern civilization.

"...Unlike Freud, Jung argues that human collective unconsciousness shares common traits across all people since it's collective. This collective archetype also assumes a religious nature, embracing ancient human beliefs and myths, which, despite appearing in different religious forms, fundamentally remain the same" (Ibid., 40).

Fuga writes that Jung's variant represents a regression from Freudian theories, delving deeper into idealism, metaphysics, and mysticism. According to Fuga, Jung's theories defend religion, treating dogmas and religious beliefs as inherent and coexisting with humans from birth to death. He criticizes Jung for presenting religion as a form of psychotherapy, portraying it as a therapy that serves the oppressor and slave-owner, by subduing the oppressed and encouraging acceptance of the slave condition as a natural state of human relations (Ibid., 42).

This return to religion within Neo-Freudianism, as part of an undivided idealistic philosophy, is seen by Fuga as a deliberate move to attack materialist, Marxist-Leninist philosophy and progressive cultures worldwide. Its purpose, he argues, is to convince the working masses that they can never liberate themselves or overthrow religious dogmas that sustain the capitalist order of oppression and exploitation (Ibid., 49). Drawing on Marxist-Leninist ideology and Enver Hoxha's speeches, Fuga critiques Jung's concept of the archetype by challenging

Jung's idea that these archetypes originate with humanity and evolve alongside it.

"...The collective religious archetype, according to Jung, passed down from generation to generation, contradicts the fact that many past dogmas are no longer believed in today's society. In the case of the youth in socialist Albania, they do not subscribe to any religious dogmas or beliefs" (Ibid., 58).

The third part of the book focuses on Erich Fromm, whom Fuga regards as the most important representative of Neo-Freudianism of the time. Fromm sought to adapt Freudianism to the social conditions of the post-1960s era. Neo-Freudianism, according to Fuga, serves bourgeois philosophy not only by strategically serving its interests but also by tactically adapting to changes within the bourgeois order.

"...Following World War II, the bourgeois order was no longer interested in Freudian theories' social pessimism; instead, it needed a philosophy that promoted the optimism of life and the well-being achieved under capitalism. Fromm accomplished this with his Neo-Freudian theories," (Ibid., 67).

Fuga examines Fromm's attempt to synthesize Marxism and Freudianism, observing a shift away from Freud's emphasis on biological determinants toward a focus on social influences. Fromm acknowledges the presence of human contradictions within both the conscious and unconscious realms, thereby affirming Freud's philosophical insights. However, according to Fuga, Fromm claims the discrepancy lies in methodology: like other Neo-Freudians, Fromm adapts Freudianism to suit contextual needs while upholding its foundational philosophical underpinnings (Ibid., 68-70).

Fromm's attempt to merge Marxism with Freudianism is futile, as in his work "The Concept of Man According to Marx," Fromm misinterprets Marxist philosophy:

"...While striving to separate ideology from social psychology, Fromm openly admits his Freudian influences. He claims that social psychology is more influenced by subconscious impulses than conscious aspects of rational human life. While in his conscious activities such as art, literature, philosophy, and politics, he feels liberated, in his subconscious, he comprehends the absence of freedom. Thus, he believes ideology, understood as the entirety of superstructure production and institutional creations, is illusory, while psychology comprehends the core of human problems," (Ibid., 78).

The final part of the book addresses the influence of Neo-Freudianism on contemporary arts and culture. According to Marxist thought, such influence is detrimental to art, which ought to serve to foster political and class consciousness among the masses. Any form of art that exists outside class consciousness is regarded by Fuga as decadent (Ibid., 95-97).

Beyond this, he argues that Neo-Freudianism has negatively impacted art not only in terms of content but also in form. Its emphasis on drawing inspiration from the unconscious, and on conceiving art merely as the product of emotions rather than of technique and rational thought, has, in his view, diminished the quality of contemporary art in comparison with classical art (Ibid., 100-102).

A Critique of Neo-Freudianism's Criticism

As mentioned at the beginning of this article, Artan Fuga belongs to a new generation of philosophy scholars in socialist Albania. Along with his colleagues, he pursued his studies in the Department of Philosophy at the Faculty of Political and Legal Sciences in the mid-1970s, a highly selective programme admitting only about ten students per year. This did not prevent them from engaging with Western philosophical works – labelled “bourgeois philosophy” – through their knowledge of foreign languages. Such engagement is evident in the works Fuga cites in *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human* (Fuga, 1989). Furthermore, his familiarity with so-called bourgeois philosophers, in this case Freud, Carl Jung and Erich Fromm, is more extensive, in-depth, and detailed than that of Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto (Brisku, 2024).

Nevertheless, despite this extensive familiarity with these authors, it is noteworthy that even in 1989, when his book was published, Fuga's critiques of Freud and the Neo-Freudians remained fundamentally similar to those written by Riska and Zoto fifteen years earlier, following the Fourth Plenum of the Central Committee of the Party of Labour of Albania – the most repressive period for literature, arts, and culture in socialist Albania. This is not to suggest that by 1989 the level of state repression, or the prevailing social and cultural constraints, remained unchanged. However, as I have argued earlier, ideological dogmatism – at least in terms of rhetoric concerning the defence of Marxism-Leninism on a global scale – remained a persistent characteristic of the socialist regime in Albania until its end in 1991.

Since the previous article analysing “Neo-Freudianism: One of the Theoretical Bases of Bourgeois Liberalism” by Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto already provided a detailed critique of their arguments against Freud’s, it is unnecessary to conduct a similar analysis of Fuga’s work here (Brisku, 2024). What is worth mentioning is that, Fuga’s approach closely aligns with that of Riska and Zoto, whose own critiques bear the influence of Soviet authors such as Dmitry Fedotov and Valentin Voloshinov.

In *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human*, Fuga leaves no space for any form of “theoretical collaboration” between Marxism and either Freudianism or Neo-Freudianism – whether to highlight their common aspects or to construct a “revolutionary theory,” which, according to the official discourse of socialist Albania, should have been the ultimate goal of philosophy. This notion aligns with Marx’s Eleventh Thesis on Feuerbach: “Philosophers have only interpreted the world in various ways; the point, however, is to change it,” (Marx & Engels, 1968). The rejection of Freudianism or Neo-Freudianism, as well as any attempt at a theoretical synthesis between it and Marxism, stemmed from the ideological dogmatism of Albania’s political line, which regarded any critique or deviation from Marxism-Leninism as an act of “ideological betrayal.”

The second author, after Freud, with whom Fuga engages and whom he considers a disciple of Freud in terms of his theories, is Carl Jung. According to Fuga, with his concept of the collective archetype – as irrational forces shared by a society – Jung goes even further than Freud in the direction of idealist philosophy, ultimately justifying religion and mysticism. What Fuga overlooks is that the collective religious archetype doesn’t imply that all human societies share the same religious beliefs and myths but rather that the sense of religious belief exists within all human societies. The Albanian example of eradicating religious dogmas during socialism, when religious belief was legally prohibited yet practiced by individuals despite the risk of punishment, and the revival of religious practices and beliefs post-regime collapse, possibly as a reaction to its repression, also elucidates this point.

Karl Marx’s quote, “Religion is the sigh of the oppressed creature, the heart of a heartless world, and the soul of soulless conditions. It is the opium of the people,” used to situate class relations within religion, signifies the existence of religious beliefs in all societies founded on exploitation, providing some sort of solace in a repressive society (Marx, 1970: 63). Moreover, even in a Stalinist society like Albania,

where religion was legally banned, it was replaced by the cult of the leader's personality and Party cult. This kind of personality cult had its liturgy and rituals, publicly performed through parades and iconography of the Stalinist leader, in Albania's case, Enver Hoxha (Dani, 2023).

Jung's theories stand in sharp philosophical contrast to Marxism. Marxism focuses on societal structures, economics, and class conflicts, rooted in materialism and emphasizing tangible, communal factors. Conversely, Jung delves inward, exploring the individual mind, emphasizing subjective experiences, symbols, and personal development. While Marx envisions a classless society, communal ownership, and shared prosperity, Jung guides individuals toward inner integration and self-realization. Their views on religion diverge, with Marx critiquing it as a tool for societal control, while Jung acknowledges the importance of religious symbols in shaping human psychology (Gerber, 2021: 3-4).

Therefore, it can be argued that Fuga's criticism of Jung is valid from a Marxist perspective. Compared to other Neo-Freudian authors who critique Freud for neglecting cultural, economic, and social contexts, Jung criticizes Freud for his "materialism", and so Fuga does observe that Jung's philosophy leans more towards idealism than Freud's. The problem arises when Fuga attempts to understand the purpose of Jung's move towards idealism, which, according to Fuga, "serves bourgeois interests and undermines Marxist-Leninist revolutionary movements," (Fuga, 1989: 36). He therefore concludes that such theories are reactionary, serving bourgeois interests. Another problem with Fuga's argument is that for him, Jung's inclination towards idealism, as well as Fromm's towards materialism, represent different sides of the same coin, the interests of the bourgeoisie (Ibid., 12). This reasoning reflects more the orthodox propaganda of socialist Albania's ideology than a Materialist critique of Jung.

Another contradiction in Fuga's argument emerges in the first part of the book, where he traces the evolution of Neo-Freudian theories to the discrediting of Freud by Marxism-Leninism. This discrediting highlighted the fundamentally unscientific nature of Freudianism, which focused solely on instincts and the unconscious as guides to human life and activity, classifying it as idealist philosophy (Ibid., 14). For this reason, the bourgeoisie needed new theories that, while acknowledging the role of some economic and social factors in shaping humans, essentially retained the core of Freudianism. The contradiction lies in the fact that if the bourgeoisie required Neo-Freudian theories to

depart from Freud's idealism, it should have not also encouraged and promoted Jung's theories, which are as idealist as Freud's, if not more so.

As previously noted, Marx and Jung present distinctly different theories. However, in exploring these contrasting theories, Julien-François Gerber offers a compelling reconciliation. He highlights their shared concerns for human well-being and liberation, noting points of convergence between Marxism and Jungian thought that hint at their potential integration for a deeper understanding. Gerber argues that synthesizing their approaches could foster genuine emancipation. He underscores the unique contributions of the Jungian viewpoint, including its emphasis on the soul, its positive engagement with the unconscious and spirituality, and a Jungian-Marxian anthropology that explores social struggles, ideology, archetypes, and the impact of capitalism (Gerber, 2021: 1-2).

Gerber also delves into “degrowth” – a movement aimed at reducing unnecessary economic activity and reshaping societies to promote human and nonhuman well-being. He suggests that degrowth aligns with the proposed Jungian-Marxian synthesis, advocating for a radical reorganization based on sustainable, egalitarian “human economies” (Ibid., 14-15).

When Artan Fuga wrote *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human*, Julien-François Gerber had not yet attempted to offer a synthesis between Marx's and Jung's ideas. Fuga, therefore, cannot be “accused” of failing to integrate Gerber's ideas into his work.

Furthermore, in a country like Albania, where the official ideology prioritized perpetual economic progress and growth, primarily defined through the development of heavy and mining industries, the concept of “degrowth”, which Gerber proposes as a Jungian-Marxian synthesis, would have been foreign. That said, there may have been limited points of potential alignment. During the 1980s, the Albanian leadership became aware of environmental damage caused by its industries and occasionally acknowledged it as a problem, though financial constraints prevented substantial improvements. While this does not indicate that Albanian Marxist-Leninism tended toward “degrowth”, it suggests that, in a more open intellectual and political environment, Albanian theorists might have found common ground between the official ideology and the views of the authors they were tasked with critiquing.

Fuga highlights Fromm's underlying "anti-Marxist stance". While Fromm attempts a synthesis, Fuga discerns an anti-Marxist sentiment in his core beliefs. He emphasizes the significance of Marxist-Leninist ideology not only in politics or economics but also in literature, as a means of unveiling the oppression of the working class. Such revelations, Fuga contends, have historically sparked revolutionary movements, much like Marx's own interventions. By contrast, he notes that socialist Albanian society sustained a widespread belief, both ideological and psychological, that individuals possess the capacity to attain complete freedom (Fuga, 1989: 80).

Fuga links Fromm's work, and the Neo-Freudian attempt to merge Marxism with Freudianism, to the rise of revisionism in the Soviet Union and other socialist nations. This revisionist trend pursued a peaceful coexistence between opposing ideologies and a compromise between capital and labour – an approach that distorted the core tenets of Marxism-Leninism. As the Soviet Union embraced this reconciliatory approach, Albania, a staunch advocate of Marxism-Leninism, found itself at odds with this stance. Neo-Freudianism, therefore, was seen as a direct assault on socialist Albania as well (Ibid., 72).

Another significant aspect of Fuga's critique of Fromm concerns the latter's adaptation of the psychoanalytic concept of "transference" to society. Fuga argues that this leads to a submissive attitude of the proletariat and the underprivileged classes, whose only recourse under such oppression is to worship their oppressors. Moreover, Fromm goes as far as to say that ordinary people do not desire freedom, implying that the capitalist classes maintain power not through inherent class-based oppressive relationships but because the oppressed wish to remain in subjugation (Ibid., 95).

The criticisms levied by Fuga against Erich Fromm bear similarities to those previously articulated by Riska and Zoto, who, in their work, seemed to misunderstand, or more accurately, to distort Marxism in their attempt to reconcile it with Freudianism (Brisku, 2024).

Certainly, an analysis of Fromm's work reveals that, alongside from his criticisms of Freud for overemphasizing the individual and neglecting the social and economic dimensions of psychological problems, Fromm also critiques Marx. He argued that Marx's theory was lacking in adequate psychological insight, and that Marx's heavy preoccupation with the economic aspects of capitalism prevented him from paying sufficient attention to the passions and strivings which are rooted in man's nature. Fromm also believed that Marx's theory did not

provide a convincing remedy for the ills of capitalism, as it did not explain how the economic basis of society comes to be translated into the ideological superstructure. Finally, Fromm argued that Marx's theory did not adequately address the issue of individual freedom, as it focused primarily on the collective struggle of the working class against the ruling class (Cheliotis, 2011: 450-52). Nevertheless, this does not mean that his intention was to discredit Marxism in favor of Freudianism; rather, the objective was to perceive both theories as complementary frameworks for analyzing the ramifications of capitalism. While Marxism offers insights on a systemic level, Freudianism provides a lens through which to examine its effects on the individual scale.

Conclusions

This article aimed to analyse a work on Neo-Freudianism through the lens of Albanian Marxist-Leninist philosophy. The primary focus was the book *Neofrojdzimi: filozofi e njeriut të tjetërsuar* [Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human] (1989) by Artan Fuga, a renowned Albanian philosopher both within and outside the country. The article builds on a previous study that similarly examined perspectives on Freudianism and Neo-Freudianism in socialist Albania, focusing on the book "Neo-Freudianism: One of the Theoretical Bases of Bourgeois Liberalism" (1974) by Viktor Riska and Marianthi Zoto.

Although these works address similar themes, the historical context and the individuals writing them differ significantly. The year 1974 marked one of the most repressive periods in the history of Albanian socialism, particularly in literature, philosophy, arts, and culture. This ideological rigidity also resulted in purges at all levels of cultural and intellectual institutions. In this context, the dogmatism of Riska and Zoto's work is understandable.

By contrast, the year 1989, when *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human* was published, represented a significantly different political and social climate in Albania. Since the conclusion of internal Party purges in 1983, and particularly after the death of Enver Hoxha in 1985 – who had ruled the country for forty years – the overall political and social environment had softened, and state repression had somewhat diminished. However, as the analysis of Fuga's book demonstrates, this political shift did not translate into a relaxation of dogmatism within Albanian Marxism-Leninism. Despite a deeper engagement with and analysis of Sigmund Freud and Neo-Freudian au-

thors such as Carl Jung and Erich Fromm, Fuga's approach and criticisms largely remained aligned with those of Riska and Zoto. These, in turn, reflected the positions of Soviet critics of Freud. This dogmatism evident in *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human*, prevents Fuga from identifying any common ground or theoretical synthesis between Marxism and Freudianism or its Neo-Freudian variants.

As mentioned, following the fall of socialism, Artan Fuga emerged as the most prominent Albanian philosopher. He has authored numerous philosophical works and articles, demonstrating a clear departure from the dogmatism of Orthodox Marxism. Nonetheless, to my knowledge, he has not written any self-critical reflections on the works he produced during the period of state socialism in Albania – perhaps assuming it is self-evident that those writings were produced under the dictates of a repressive regime. In a personal interview, however, Fuga has acknowledged that he studied during a highly dogmatic era in Albania with regard to philosophy and the humanities. According to him, this also explains why, in his late thirties when he already had a Candidate of Sciences degree² in Albania, he went to France after 1991 to pursue postgraduate studies in philosophy. He considers himself, in his own words, a “lifelong student” (Fuga, 2015).

Additionally, this article aimed to provide a critique of Fuga's criticisms of Freud and the Neo-Freudians Jung and Fromm. To do so, it draws upon Western scholars associated with Marxism, many of whom share similar critiques of psychoanalysis as Fuga. However, many of these thinkers converge on the argument that while Marxism seeks social liberation, Freudianism seeks individual liberation, and a synthesis between the two is not merely a theoretical exercise but can serve as the foundation for a revolutionary theory capable of driving radical social change.

Such a synthesis, however, was strictly rejected by Orthodox Marxism. In *Neo-Freudianism: The Philosophy of the Alienated Human*, any attempt at theoretical integration between Marxism and psychoanalysis is regarded as a “betrayal” of Marxism – not only as a philosophical tradition but, more importantly, as a revolutionary theory. As a result, Neo-Freudian authors such as Erich Fromm – who explicitly sought to synthesize Marxist and Freudian thought, viewing them as

²According to the system of education and scientific degrees established in the USSR – and subsequently adopted in most countries of the so-called Socialist Camp – the Candidate of Sciences degree was considered equivalent to the international PhD.

complementary frameworks for analysing the effects of capitalism – are criticized and ultimately dismissed.

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***MEDICAL HERITAGE AND MEMORY: INSTITUTIONS,
INFRASTRUCTURES, ARTIFACTS***

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**Re-Ottomanizing Modernity: Domesticating
Balneology in Early to Mid-20th-Century Bulgaria¹**

Abstract: *The decades after Bulgaria’s liberation from Ottoman rule (a continuous process beginning in 1878) were marked by the construction of a new national identity across multiple terrains: the state apparatus, political alliances, the social and cultural realms, and most visibly – the built environment. Bulgaria’s transformation during this period is described as simultaneously de-Ottomanization and Europeanisation (Lory, 2015), connoting the erasure or replacement of one system of governance by another. By looking at two important instruments of the modernizing state – healthcare and hygiene, I demonstrate that rather than abrupt replacement of the “Oriental” by the “Western”, a gradual adaptation took place, with resilient cultural practices often persisting in less visible ways. I focus on several case studies of Ottoman public baths and the tensions emerging around the control over thermal waters. While this natural resource was seen by authorities and citizens as a catalyst for urban renewal, such aspirations often clashed with the perceived symbolic dissonance of existing infrastructures dating from the Ottoman period. I argue that the heterogeneous solutions produced by this friction blur the modern/archaic, hygienic/unclean, Western/Oriental binaries and illustrate how Bulgaria’s modernization was a non-linear process of adaptation and absorption of*

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preceding cultural practices, which aligned modern technology along the contours of pre-existing ecologies of care and healing.

Keywords: *architecture; Balkan nationalisms; Balkans; balneology; de-Ottomanization; Europeanization; healthcare; hygiene; modernization; public baths; water.*

Introduction

Public baths, one of the most remarkable accomplishments of the Ottoman architectural legacy, were erected in the vicinity of dozens of thermal springs² and freshwater sources across the territory of present-day Bulgaria between the 14th and 19th centuries. These complex infrastructures mediated public access to a valuable natural resource and defined the boundaries of its uses. After Bulgaria's liberation from Ottoman rule in the late 19th century,³ the country embarked on a course of modernization that saw the rapid elimination of many of these buildings. The architecture and urban planning policies implemented by national and regional governments became a cartography of tensions between the country's Ottoman past and its European aspirations. The changes to the physical environment in early to mid-20th-century Bulgaria form the backbone of this inquiry. It focuses on the public bath as a building typology of primary civic importance, which resides at the crossing between healthcare policy, natural resource exploitation, and architecture and urban planning visions.

Engineers, medical practitioners, and municipal representatives commonly attached comparisons such as archaic vs. modern or unclean vs. hygienic to the Oriental/Western dichotomy in various documents concerning the fate of Ottoman-era buildings. The experts' evaluations of Ottoman baths prior to their demolition reflected identical political-ideological binaries. Yet, the everyday utilitarian functions of these centuries-old structures depended on quite the opposite: elaborate engineering of water flows and air currents, documented in the field sketches of Bulgarian architects and engineers – often the only record produced before their razing.

Balneology is a medical discipline which gained prominence in mid-19th-century Western Europe by promoting the medicinal and therapeutic use of thermal waters. Its introduction in Bulgaria involved

² “Thermal” and “mineral” will be used interchangeably. While these qualities do not coexist in certain cases, thermal baths are called mineral in Bulgaria. They are always supplied by thermal springs with mineral content.

³ A continuous process starting in 1878 and formally concluding in 1908. See Lory (2015).

the taming of the country's hydrothermal resources, or in other words, embedding them within an institutional and legal framework. This process extended into the practices of healing and bathing in public baths, which were to be "Europeanized" by means of infrastructural iterations intended to better reflect the healing methods of Western balneology.

"Re-ottomanizing modernity" refers to the uneven results produced by these parallel and mutually constitutive processes. While the Ottoman architectural legacy was visibly and largely obliterated across most of the country, I argue that the resilient customs of utilizing thermal waters for healing and hygiene were carried from the Ottoman period into the post-liberation decades and foregrounded the planning of Bulgaria's "modern" balneotherapeutic facilities. The public baths became an unlikely contested terrain between government policies and demographic realities and underlined the important civic function these infrastructures continued to perform.

Fig. 1. Diagram of Ottoman public baths on the territory of present-day Bulgaria.⁴

⁴ A short list of referenced resources: Boykov (2012, 2015, 2018); Boykov, Kirpovska (2020); Çelebi (2014); Gyuleva (2019); Dundarov (1958); Mikov (2012); Yalamov (2010); Yanchev, Kirpovska (2019); Vakif.bg (last visited 2022); in addition to articles in local periodicals, online resources, cadastral data and fieldwork conducted

Literature

While the period of Ottoman rule remains outside the scope of this article, a number of studies were essential for understanding the architectural and social legacy inherited by the Bulgarian state in the late 19th century. Harbova's research (1991) on architecture and urban planning in the Ottoman Empire (15th – 18th century) in the former and present-day territories of Bulgaria provides a detailed overview of the elements comprising the Ottoman urban fabric. The catalogue of several dozen diagrammatic floor plans and sections of steam and thermal baths (*hamam* and *kaplica*) illustrates the technological complexity and functional diversity within the typology and serves as an important comparative tool. Mikov (2012) offers a more versatile overview of Bulgaria's Ottoman baths, including a brief discussion of their social function. Case studies by Boykov (2008, 2015, 2018, 2021), Boykov and Kiprovskva (2020), Dimitrova (2017), Gradeva (2023), Tabakov (1986), Yanchev and Kiprovskva (2019) provide an informative reference for the history of individual buildings and development of towns under Ottoman rule. The above, in addition to primary sources such as Azmanov (1940), Çelebi (2014), Dimitrov (1939), Dundarov (1958), Klisarov (1969), Monedzhikova (1946) and fieldwork conducted across more than twenty sites, became the foundation of a map of Ottoman public baths across the territory of present-day Bulgaria. This reference tool supports my argument that Bulgaria's extensive network of 20th-century balneotherapeutic facilities rests upon a pre-existing network of Ottoman public baths.

Kiel's seminal research on the Ottoman legacy in Bulgaria and the Balkans (1985, 1990, 2013) addresses multiple domains – art and architecture, settlement and demography, the economy and administrative structures. Most importantly, he offers a critical perspective on Bulgaria's 20th-century “vehemently anti-Turkish [historiographic] current”, and challenges persistent mythological narratives embedded in the national historical canon. Kiel locates the negative perception of the Ottoman legacy in the context of Balkan nationalisms, a theme I explore in conjunction with the construction of the Muslim as the “other” (Ar-etov, 2011; Todorova, 2011). In a similar vein, Hartmuth's illuminating essay (2008) is a concise overview of major inconsistencies in Balkan historiography of art and architecture. Through a series of examples, he outlines future research trajectories to address the center-periphery

between December 2020 and August 2024. On diagram making, see Burrows et al. (2025).

power imbalance in the assessment of monuments, the “nostrification”⁵ of heritage, and crucially for this article – understanding architecture as a significantly richer source of evidence and an “expression of legacy”, as opposed to the prevalent descriptive and stylistic approach which tends to de-contextualize buildings.

The relegation of the Ottoman to the ambiguous categories of the “backward” and the “unclean” was formalized through state-sanctioned policies designed to liberate the country from traces of its Oriental past. The concept of *de-Ottomanization* was first introduced by Lory (2015) as the process of “[e]radicating the markers of an Ottoman memory,” which unfolds in parallel to a process of *Europeanization*. Stanoeva (2013) examines the modernization of Bulgaria’s capital, pointing to the erasure not only of the physical traces of the “Oriental,” but also of places seen as a “symbolic arena of urban life in the Ottoman town”, such as outdoor markets. This process was not unique to Bulgaria and affected multiple domains, as demonstrated in the edited volume by Keridis and Kiesling (2020) on Hellenization and the exodus of the Muslim community in Thessaloniki (Vogli, 2020; Tsitselikis, 2020; Bastéa and Hastaoglou-Martinidis, 2020, see also Lagopolous, 2005). These studies illustrate the misalignment between formal pledges for protection of the rights of ethnic minorities and the structural challenges which led to the ethnic homogenization of the city (Zarakol, 2020). The links between nationalism and urban transformation across several locations in Greece are further explored by Koumaridis (2006), who describes identical patterns of urban “regeneration” through de-Ottomanization that employed ‘Turkish’ as a synonym for “backward”.

The Europeanization projects of the young Balkan nation states were subject to internal criticism and tensions, emerging from the adoption of Western institutional models and cultural and social practices perceived as alien and “modernization from above,” as examined by Mishkova and Daskalov (2013). Todorova (1994) categorizes different spheres of Ottoman legacy in the Balkans and analyzes their lasting presence or abrupt disappearance, placing the built environment in the latter category. In this article, through a series of microhistories, I examine what appears to be an exception – a gradual departure from what was perceived as “Oriental” architecture within a specific building ty-

⁵ “Nostrification” as the appropriation of an “otherwise externalised heritage” and its embedding into a historical narrative portraying it as part of a different national tradition (Hartmuth, 2008).

pology. Following Hartmuth's methodology (2008), I approach architecture as a convergence of resources, policies and institutional and civic actors – *a process*, rather than a fixed material entity.

Finally, these diverse fields of scholarship are contextualized within Bulgaria's healthcare policies and demographics to better understand why one architectural typology proved significantly more resilient than others originating from the same period (Sudár, 2004). I propose a hypothesis based on studies by Angelova (2008), Baloutzova (2011), Dimitrova (2018) and Popov (2009), which examine the urban-rural divide, levels of access to healthcare and health insurance, and importantly, sanitation policies enacted through architecture and urban planning initiatives (see also Stoilova et al., 2014; 2016) framing the Ottoman buildings as sources of disease to be removed. Whether the objectives of "Europeanization" were achieved, I examine by looking at the history of two balneoresorts in Germany, often mentioned in early to mid-20th-century periodicals in Bulgaria – Bad Nauheim and Baden-Baden (Coenen, 2008; Hamm and Kübler, 2007).

The analytical lens suggested in this article, while seemingly drawing on versatile spheres of knowledge, has its limitations given the complexity of histories woven into the body of a building. At its current stage, this research explores the potential of material traces to unveil neglected continuities.

Methodology and Sources

This article proceeds from the premise that architecture and its social history are mutually constitutive and should be examined in parallel as two elements of a single unit. It comprises a series of case studies and examples falling into three categories: preserved, transformed and demolished (or rebuilt) public thermal baths. Central to this study are the transformed buildings, exemplified by the extended case study of the Ottoman bath in Yambol, which I chose for the relatively well-preserved records of its adaptation. The documents at the regional archives in Yambol contain evidence of the struggles over the control of a newly discovered natural resource (a thermal spring), the different agency permitted to different ethnic and religious groups, the structural discrimination and the volatility of the de-Ottomanization and Europeanisation claims.

An interdisciplinary approach foregrounds this research, amplifying a polyvocal historical narrative based on diverse material traces.

The main body of primary sources consists of municipal archives, examined alongside popular local periodicals reporting on the same events.

Visual ethnography and the young field of digital humanities are important components of this research, providing both original investigative tools and uncovering valuable data inaccessible through textual documents alone. In addition, various digital tools were deployed in synthesizing otherwise voluminous data in simple diagrams. Mapping the network of Ottoman public baths across the territory of present-day Bulgaria provided an important layer of information on the significance and density of these infrastructures. 3D modelling and isometric diagrams proved to be effective tools for comparative analysis. The exploration of architectural morphologies, while not central to this research, also benefits from the above methods.

A key challenge of this ongoing research is the expanding scope of disciplines that could potentially be drawn in “reading” the processes under discussion, as the newly uncovered data open new discursive and disciplinary perspectives. In this context, the article aims less to offer firm conclusions than to invite further debate about possible avenues for inquiry.

De-Ottomanizing Hygiene. The Case of Yambol Mineral Bath

In 1933, Müniver Rasimova Sadıkova, a woman from the Muslim minority in the town of Yambol, rented a water drill from the town’s municipality in order to excavate a well in the yard of her property. She owned a functioning Ottoman public bath,⁶ inherited from her late husband, and hoped its operational costs would be reduced if a water source were found. The drill reached an aquifer, which unexpectedly produced hot water. In the following months, she corresponded with experts in the capital, trying to determine whether the water source was mineral, whether she could claim ownership, and if she could obtain rights over its exploitation (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 1, 2).

⁶ In his 17th-century travelogue, Evliya Çelebi mentions three public baths in Yambol near the river Tundzha, the largest built in the 15th century (Çelebi, 2014), likely the one still preserved today. The location of another is recorded in a cadastral drawing from 1947 (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 6), marked as the “Roman bath” or “Karanazh kurna” (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 2). Its remains are currently buried under a road. The author was unable to find data about the third building by the time this article was completed.

News of the discovery, leaked by her assistant, spread across the town. A citizens committee was established shortly after, with the generous aim of assisting the Municipality in planning the construction of modern infrastructure to facilitate public access to the newly discovered “natural treasure.” By that time, Bulgarian law had declared hot and cold mineral waters state property (*Durzhaven vestnik*, January 13, 1891), subject to exploitation rules designed to protect the public interest while limiting the possibility for private use. The progress of the ensuing construction campaign was reported in nearly every issue of the local newspaper “*Trakiets*”, usually on the front page, often in more than one article per issue, and covered in meticulous technical detail.

ТУРСКАТА БАНЯ И ОКОЛНОСТИТЪ Й

Мѣстото, кждето се правятъ проучванията и издирванията за минерална вода въ града ни. Пробити сж вече въ квартала около банята 12 сонди и една шахта. Гражданството спонтанно проявява своето единопдушие и самодейность, за пръвъ пжть следъ толкова години на бездействие и разруха следъ войната.

Това може само да радва всѣки ратуващъ за напредъка на Ямболъ.

Fig. 2. The public bath owned by Müniver Rasimova Sadıkova (behind the bridge, on the left) (*Trakiets*, January 28, 1934). The text reads “The Turkish Bath and its surroundings. The place where surveys and probes of the thermal water of our town are being carried out. 12 boreholes and one shaft have been drilled in the neighborhood near the bath. The citizens spontaneously expressed their unity and self-initiative for the first time after so many years of inertness and ruination after the war. This could only cheer up those who long for the progress of Yambol.”

Dozens of articles covered the endeavors of the municipality and the citizens' committee as they embarked on erecting the new city landmark – a modern public mineral bath. Yet despite this regular flow of information amplifying the voices of municipal officials, experts, and prominent citizens (in both disagreement and collaboration), an important development was omitted from the official storytelling. The name of Ms. Sadikova, the legal owner of the property where the water source was found, was mentioned only once in the reporting (Trakiets, January 27, 1935). Her participation in the construction of Yambol's modern urban identity, if an involuntary one, remained invisible. How “past” was woven into “future” could be recovered from a small number of entries in the municipal archival records consisting of letters of complaint, fines, a report on the legal proceedings that eventually led to the expropriation of her property, and a set of architectural drawings.

“The progress of Yambol” (see caption of Fig. 2), as Ms. Sadikova's complaints make clear, was constructed upon repeated infringements of her private property and obstructions of its operations – actions initiated by the citizens committee and Yambol municipality. Shortly after the aquifer's discovery, they organized the drilling of a second well close to the one she was already using, lowering the flow rate of her supply. Following her complaint, her own well was sealed off by the municipal doctor, citing potential health hazards from the older infrastructure. A modernist drinking pavilion was then erected in front of the bath's entrance, obstructing access from the street. In order to authorize this encroachment, the town's cadaster was amended and a new land plot demarcated, infringing on the original boundaries of her property. In a municipal session, her bath was proposed for demolition as a preventive measure against the possibility of grey water leaking from the “old Turkish bath” into the spring. When Ms. Sadikova refused to allow municipal employees to enter her property for further investigations, the Municipality issued a series of fines for obstruction. As a widow with two underage children, she could not pay. The fines, compounded by late-payment interest, eventually forced the sale of her property at a public auction to cover her growing debt to the Municipality (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 1). While mentions of her name gradually disappear from the official documents as her agency diminishes, a substantially different narrative emerges on the pages of Trakiets (January 27, 1935). The bath was described as having been purchased by the Municipality after successful negotiations with the own-

ers, thanks to the diplomatic skills of Yambol's mayor, while all lawsuits filed by them at the administrative courts in Plovdiv and Burgas were framed as a stubborn attempt to retain their ownership of the natural resource and portrayed as voluntarily settled.

A year earlier, five members of the citizens' committee pursued the obtaining of exclusive rights for the exploitation of the hot spring by secretly registering a new legal entity in Yambol's regional court (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 2). Their scheme was uncovered to major public outrage but led only to minor consequences. A public apology and a promise to continue their campaign with the best public interest at heart sufficed to defuse tensions (Trakiets, February 20, 1934).⁷

Дали една МИНЕРАЛНА вода е годна за пиене, решава само МТТТ. Това министерство ръководи по свои специални планове каптирането на минералната вода във Ямбол за пиене. Маса народът от цялата страна продължава да се стича и взема от водата.

Fig. 3. “Whether a MINERAL water is drinkable can be decided only by the Ministry of Trade, Industries and Labor. This ministry manages, according to special plans, the capturing of Yambol’s mineral water for drinking. Masses of people from the entire country continue to arrive and take from the water.” (Trakiets, March 18, 1934)

In the meantime, the newly discovered thermal water was already proving its miraculous qualities – everyone who drank or bathed in it

⁷ Three articles on the topic were published in a single issue. At that time the newspaper consisted of only four pages.

experienced improved health (January 28, 31, 1934) while weekly visits to the springs reached more than 35,000 people (Trakiets, September 25, 1935).

The unexpected emergence of a valuable resource produced a major rupture. A new set of civic relations formed and disrupted the existential order of one actor, leading to substantial material loss and possibly the loss of livelihood, in what could be described as a restructuring of the town's hydrosocial territories (Boelens, 2016). In the internal discussions of Yambol's municipality, Müniver Sadikova's attempts to retain access to the spring were energetically derided. There was a clear preoccupation among the municipal representatives with her ethnic/religious background and her gender. In official documents, Ms. Sadikova is rarely mentioned by name, while others – who appear to be Bulgarian Christian men – are formally addressed. Despite being the legal owner of one of the most prominent buildings in Yambol's town center, she was repeatedly and pejoratively referred to as “kadına”, derived from the Turkish word *kadın*, meaning a woman.

Yambol's urban regeneration campaign, built around a newly found “natural treasure”, was preceded by a similar development near the neighboring town of Sliven, though in a rural setting. Thirty kilometers north of Yambol, dozens of properties had been expropriated about three decades earlier for the creation of the balneoresort⁸ of Slivenski Mineralni Bani. Sliven Municipality set out to transform an area consisting of arable land, pastures, and marshes into a public park surrounding a modern thermal bath and hotels. Municipal records indicate prolonged negotiations with landowners, some of whom hesitated to sell their land, disputed the buying prices, or, in some cases, proved difficult to reach if living abroad. Yet, unlike Yambol, no records of forceful expropriations were found in the reviewed sets of documents.⁹ On the very contrary, minutes from municipal sessions indicate patience on the part of the Municipality and willingness to accept delays caused by difficult communication with some of the owners. The list of property owners indicates they were ethnic Bulgarians and Christians (DA-Sliven, F. 46K, op. 1, a.e. 352; F. 46K, op. 2, a.e. 13) and their properties contained no infrastructure remaining from the Ottoman period.

⁸ A resort providing treatment and leisure with mineral water facilities.

⁹ The communication is split between several archival units, and it is possible that documents contradicting these findings exist elsewhere.

— Нуждаещи се отъ всички страни, присъединявайте се,
но не се натискайте — има за всички!

Fig. 4. “People in need from all countries, come join in, but don’t crowd – there is enough for everybody!” The flag on the drinking pavilion reads “Drink and say – thank you” (Trakiets, March 18, 1934). Symbols of modernity – aircraft, cars and a streamlined public bath.

The “de-Ottomanization” of Yambol’s town center appears as a two-fold process, firstly targeting the individual who carried the “Oriental” past into the present, and then the physical infrastructure which contained it. The laying of new wastewater collection system around the old bath was described as “healing” of the neighborhood (Trakiets, July 4, 1934), the drinking pavilion under construction in front of the

old bath's entrance was satirically described as "surpassing the Americans" (March 25, 1934), and once completed was celebrated for its "European appearance" (June 10, 1934). In the debates over the future of the thermal spring, the existing bath was mostly absent outside internal administrative correspondence. The so-called "Turkish bath" or "hamam" appears sporadically in periodicals, mostly depicted as a potential source of pollution and disease (Trakiets, December 31, 1933), threatening the health of the entire town. Only a single article (Trakiest, August 19, 1934) by Yambol-born member of parliament Nikolay Savov criticised the plans for renovation of the old bath, describing it as a mistake and calling for the building to be preserved and restored. The ensuing reports indicate this proposal provoked no further debates.

This well-preserved snapshot of Bulgaria's post-liberation urban renewal endeavor illustrates how architecture and urban planning were mobilized as sanitation tools, both literally and metaphorically, in response to seemingly apolitical considerations. While the campaign led by Yambol municipality and the citizens committee aligned with Bulgaria's modernization policies which pursued the removal of Ottoman era infrastructures for practical hygienic reasons (Dimitrova, 2018), it took place in a context of nationalist ethnopolitical urban regeneration aspirations which imagined the path towards the new nation state through erasing the physical remnants of the "Oriental" past and symbolically replacing it with Western architecture (Kiel, 2013; Koumaridis, 2006; Lewis, 2010; Stanoeva, 2013).

Transitioning Infrastructures

The events preceding the construction of Yambol's new city landmark – the modern public bath – suggest that the old hamam¹⁰ would inevitably be demolished. It was considered a major obstruction to progress, a health hazard, and a symbol of cultural backwardness, prompting several proposals for its removal and replacement with a public park (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op.2, a.e. 2).

The structure, however, was preserved and carefully "de-Ottomanized" externally. Based on the limited archival documents related

¹⁰ While the building later came to perform the function of a *kaphica*, in the official documents it is referred to as "hamam". From the documents reviewed for this article, it is unclear if a pool existed previously or if it replaced a hypocaust, typical for the steam baths (hamams). A pre-existing pool would mean a thermal water source was accessible in the past. Thermal springs can suddenly emerge or vanish due to geological and seismic processes.

to the construction process,¹¹ consisting primarily of the final architectural drawing set (Ibid., F. 218K, op. 2, a.e. 17) and product catalogues, I would speculate that the decision to retain the old building was made for pragmatic reasons – cost reduction, reuse of valuable resources, and resumption of operations within a shorter timeframe. The existing bath was reassigned as the women’s section, and a new men’s compartment was added where a changing room previously stood. The main space of the old bath, which still exists, has a simple internal layout consisting of a central pool and stone benches lining the perimeter of the space with wash basins embedded in them.¹² The ornamental geometry of the interior has been sanitized beneath neatly clad white tiles. No hint of the enclosed inheritance is visible from the outside. The exterior of the building, with its streamlined modernist openings, wraps around the old hamam, concealing it completely behind a curved façade.

The example in Yambol is one of many microhistories woven into the uneven process of modernization in the Balkans, described in detail by Mishkova and Daskalov (2013). It spanned political, social, cultural, and economic realms of the young nation-states in the region, creating frictions across multiple spheres – from administrative structure to the planning of the physical environment. Across Bulgaria, a number of re-utilization initiatives reveal the different fates of the building typologies inherited from the Ottoman period. They indicate that the de-Ottomanization of infrastructure was not a linear process but was often adjusted according to perceived utility. The public baths performed essential social and utilitarian functions, directly contributing to the health and wellbeing of local communities¹³ regardless of their confessional affiliation. Dozens of baths were preserved, unlike caravanserais or khans, which disappeared entirely, or mosques, which were almost completely erased in most larger cities.¹⁴ The Ottoman public baths, and especially those in the vicinity of thermal springs, underwent varying degrees of adaptation and “Europeanization,” which concealed the visible features of their “Ottoman-ness” while retaining their internal functionality.

¹¹ Available at the regional branch of the State Archives in Yambol.

¹² These appear to be modern replacements of an element which most certainly existed in the old bath. The wash basins with adjacent seating are a mandatory component.

¹³ Similarly to Hungary. See Sudár (2004).

¹⁴ The list of surviving mosques in Bulgaria may seem numerous but it is a fraction compared to the demolished buildings. According to Kiel (2013) 98% of the Ottoman urban fabric in Bulgaria was decimated.

Fig. 5 and 6. Interior and exterior of the Yambol Mineral Bath. Above: the Ottoman bath, transformed into the modern bath's women's compartment. December 2020. Below: the exterior of the new bath, northeast façade. Behind it is the old Ottoman bath. January 2021. Images courtesy of the author.

Fig. 7. Ground floor plan of Yambol mineral bath, designed by architect Alexander Kurtev and completed in 1936. The preserved structure of Ms. Sadikova's property is highlighted in black. Diagram based on the original drawing (DA-Yambol, F. 47K, op. 2, a.e. 6). The author added minor iterations based on the complete project, e.g. the chamfered corners of the women's compartment are not reflected in the drawing set.

At the turn of the 20th century, a hydrogeological pre-condition of exceptionally abundant hydrothermal resources across Bulgaria nurtured the ambitions of successive national and local governments and professional communities to adopt western balneology and establish balneoresorts.¹⁵ Building initiatives unfolded across many towns and villages, providing opportunities for extensive Europeanization campaigns.¹⁶ But beyond the celebrated novel projects such as the Central Mineral Bath in Sofia, the thermal baths in Bankya, Ovcha Kupel, or Varshets, there was a gradient of adaptation, of working with different scales and resources in places perceived as less important. There, continuity took the shape of infrastructural modification, and I would call

¹⁵ See the periodical *Kurortno delo*.

¹⁶ In Gorna Banya, Sliven, Varshets, Banya Karlovska, Kyustendil, Velingrad, Yagoda and other places.

the result of this process “transitioning” typologies, such as in Alay Banya in Kyustendil (NINKN, KN-103-56-IV), Radonovi Bani in Velingrad (Ibid, Pz-513-464-51), or Starozagorski mineralni bani (DA-Varna, F. 1317, op. 1, a.e. 143; DA-Stara Zagora, Op. 7, f. 261, a.e. 65), all of which comprising an Ottoman thermal bath embedded into a 20th-century enclosure.

Fig. 8 and 9. Competition entry for the thermal baths in Starozagorski mineralni bani by Petar Karasimeonov (1937, unbuilt). Ground level and south elevation. According to the competition brief, the existing detached Ottoman baths (highlighted in black) were to be preserved and inscribed within a single volume. In this project proposal, the south façade of the male Ottoman bath remains visible, while the rest of it is incorporated into a modernist building. The dome of the female bath should be visible on the left behind the extension but was not drafted in the original drawing set. Diagrams based on DA-Varna, F. 1317, op. 1, a.e. 143. A similar concept was realized in the mid-1970s and is still standing today.

Beyond the structural and stylistic curiosity which the “transitioning” typology presents to the architect, these buildings are a conceptual paradox. The ornamental, neo-classical façades of “modern” public baths, or the streamlined modernist ones for that matter (as in Yambol and Stara Zagora), hardly delivered the desired distancing from the “Oriental” past, but promoted continuity along two lines: utility and spatial arrangement. Travel notes by two German scientists compare bathing practices and the interiors of public thermal baths in Bulgaria to balneotherapy as practiced in their home country. In a brief report from his resort excursions across Bulgaria, climatologist Prof. Linke remarks that unlike in Central Europe “not only the affluent and the middle strata uses the baths, but precisely the poorest, who are pressing themselves onto the nearest mineral baths, which is why according to a German measure, they reach an unusually high number of visitors, which comes in parallel to the great abundance of thermal waters across the country”¹⁷ (Kurortno delo, 7(3), 1942). During his visit a year earlier, the balneologist Prof. Vogt described the differences between German and Bulgarian balneotherapeutic infrastructures, noting that it would be appropriate to preserve the “local bathing culture” of taking baths in a common pool, but the use of bathtubs should also be administered in accordance with contemporary balneology. He continues, “it is not only unaesthetic, but also unhygienic [...] for wash basins to be in the same space, or immediately next to it, not entirely separated from the healing pools and bathtubs” (Ibid., 6(4) 1940). These accounts offer two important observations. Firstly, public thermal baths were widely used and were essential in a country with more than 80% rural population at the time (Baloutzova, 2011; Angelova, 2008). Secondly, the floor plan of the public bath described by Prof. Vogt resembles the interior of an Ottoman thermal bath. It could be the contested building in Yambol, or the baths at Starozagorski mineralni bani (DA-Varna, F. 1317, op. 1, a.e. 143; DA-Stara Zagora, Op. 7, F. 261, a.e. 65), the demolished kaplıca next to Banya Bashı in Sofia¹⁸ (CDA, F. 1638K, op. 1, a.e. 207), Alay Banya (NINKN, Kn-103-1616-175) and Dervish Banya (NINKN, Kn-103-2115-219) in Kyustendil, Radonovi Bani in Velingrad (NINKN, Pz-513-464-51), or the bath in Vetren, now Burgaski mineralni bani.

¹⁷ Translation by the author of this article.

¹⁸ This list could be easily extended by several dozen examples. The bath near Banya Bashı in Sofia was demolished about 30 years before their visit.

Fig. 10-15. Floor plan diagrams. *10, 11.* The thermal baths of Starozagorski mineralni bani. Based on measured drawings from 1937, part of the competition brief for the renovation of the baths (DA-Varna, F. 1317, op. 1, a.e. 143). The internal layout is carefully drafted, indicating the shape of the pools, the position of the benches and the wash basins. *12.* The former women's (now men's) bath

in Radonovi bani, Velingrad. Based on a renovation project from 2012 by architect Boris Borisov (NINKN, Pz-513-464-51). 13. Dervish banya, Kyustendil. Based on a concept proposal for renovation from 2006 by architect Margarita Zhivkova (NINKN, Kn-109-502). The proposed extension corresponds to the outlines of a structure which had previously occupied the same space. 14. One of the Ottoman thermal baths in the vicinity of Banya Bashı mosque in Sofia. Possibly the one that used to be located immediately behind the mosque to the east (DA-Sofia F. 1423K, op. 1 a.e. 8), demolished after the completion of the Central Mineral Bath (1912-13). Based on a sketch from the personal archives of hydrogeologist Pavel Petrov (CDA, F. 1638K, op. 1, a.e. 207). 15. Alay Banya, Kyustendil. Based on measured drawings by architects Y. Farkov, S. Goshev, and K. Krondeva from the 1990s (NINKN, Kn-103-2115-219) as part of a renovation project proposal. With the exception of the last example, all floor plans consist of a central octagonal or square pool surrounded by benches and wash basins. In all six examples, washing areas share the same space as the pool. The majority of the extensions (highlighted in grey) were built or modernized in the early 20th century and possibly replaced lightweight structures used as changing rooms. Extensions were added at different times, also during the Ottoman period, as reported for Srednata banya in Sliven (NINKN, Sl-896-1975-214), where such was added in the 19th century (now demolished).

Bathing infrastructures, while substantially more important for the Muslim community during the Ottoman period (Ianeva, 2014; Kotseva, 2012), were also used by other ethnic and religious communities, including Bulgarian Christians, who later formed the population majority of the contemporary Bulgarian state. In Ottoman Sofia, a cluster of thermal springs supplied several public baths. Hygiene and healing were accessible for different religious communities in separate buildings – Muslim, Christian and Jewish (DA-Sofia, F. 1423K, op. 1 a.e. 8; Stoilova et al., 2014). The so-called “Bath neighborhood” was an important node in the center of the town and a crossroad, populated by religious buildings, markets, and khans (Gradeva, 2023; Monedzhikova, 1946;¹⁹ Stoilova et al., 2016). While the “Europeanization” of the neighborhood radically transformed its street layout and architectural vocabulary, the program of the spaces or the functions they performed within the urban fabric were largely preserved.

The continuity between the extensive Ottoman network of thermal public baths across Bulgaria and their “modern” replacements is also bound by the fixity of the resource itself. At the turn of the 20th century, when large-scale construction initiatives began transforming the built environment, proximity to the water source was still difficult

¹⁹ Monedzhikova’s volume provides valuable visual data from the heritage of Ottoman Sofia and its demolition.

to circumvent, and new balneotherapeutic facilities were erected either directly upon the sites of former Ottoman public baths or very close to them. Increasing the distance would have meant higher costs for underground infrastructure and the risk of heat loss during the transfer of hot water. While the enclosures of public baths changed their geometric parameters, completely or partially, pre-existing bathing and healing practices remained anchored to the same locations and this is where gradual adaptation occurred.

Domesticating Balneology

The public baths mentioned by the two German researchers are difficult to identify as they could easily be describing an authentic Ottoman thermal bath, a “modernized” one, or a completely new 20th-century infrastructure. The similarities in their architectural layouts and uses are so significant that even a more detailed description would make them hard to tell apart.

The thermal bath in Slivenski mineralni bani, the first “modern” balneotherapeutic facility in Bulgaria, was erected in 1902²⁰ and extended in 1941. It consists of two symmetrical areas for female and male visitors, where the main bathing halls are designed as spacious domed structures, surrounded by several niches for hygienic bathing. The project resembles the spatiality of earlier bathing practices contained within a neo-classical enclosure, with the modest addition of several individual bathtubs and a small therapeutic pool in each compartment. Architecture and planning initiatives across the country attempted to draw from leading examples in the field of balneology in Western Europe, particularly Germany (*Izvestiya na Balneolozhkoto Druzhestvo v Bulgaria*, 1(5,6) 1932; *Kurortno delo*, 3(2) 1934; 4(4) 1936; 5(1) 1938). The realized projects, however, differed substantially from their intended precedents. The project for the Central Mineral Bath in Sofia underwent a dramatic transformation that clearly illustrates this trajectory. After winning the commission, French architect Antoine-Eugène Bertaud submitted a fully developed set of concept drawings, which were then revised several times and eventually rejected by the local government. His project proposal prioritized medical treatment over hygiene, whereas the latter was considered a priority by the municipal representatives (Stoilova et al., 2014). In Sofia, private baths and running water in individual homes were a luxury at the time.

²⁰ Designed by Jacob Henri Meyer and Petko Momchilov.

Fig. 16. The modern thermal bath in the balneoresort of Slivenski mineralni bani, built in 1902²¹ and extended in 1941. Isometric diagram courtesy of the author (2021) based on measured drawings by Petar Cherninkov / Sliven Municipality (2015).

While a small hydrotherapeutic wing was eventually included in the plans of the Central Mineral Bathhouse in Sofia (DA-Sofia, F. 1K, op. 3, a.e. 208), most modern thermal baths in the country reflected the limited resources available for healthcare initiatives. By the late 1930s, 3,500 doctors provided treatment for approximately 6,500,000 people (Popov, 2009). A culture of comfort and leisure at the balneoresorts existed for a small part of Bulgaria's urban elite (Azmanova-Rudarska, 2016). For the majority, affordable access to the hot springs meant basic means of maintaining hygiene and offered alternative treatment for ailments, given for the lack of easily accessible medical care.

²¹ Spisanie na Bulgarskoto inzhenerno-arhitekturno druzhestvo v Sofia, (7-9) 1902.

Fig. 17. Capturing of the thermal springs in Starozagorski mineralni bani in the 1950s. In the foreground are the remains of the Roman thermae; behind them, to the left, are two Ottoman public baths. The concrete columns in the center of the image are the shafts of the captured springs, drilled right into the marble pools of the ancient thermae (NINKN, St. Z.-64-37-IVA).

The architecture of Bulgaria's modern baths was "domesticated" by complex factors – the country's demographic structure, its healthcare policies (or the absence of such), and the persistent vernacular bathing and healing practices that had flourished for centuries.²² What appeared architecturally to be a step forward was adapted to existing bathing practices, leaving architectural gestures largely ornamental while the new buildings performed familiar functions. In this context, the typology of the thermal baths of Bad Nauheim,²³ consisting of more than two hundred private bathtubs (Hamm & Kübler, 2007), or the Roman-Irish bath at Friedrichsbad in Baden-Baden with its sequence of hydrotherapeutic pools, steam baths, and medical showers (Coenen, 2008), remained unattainable aspirations. The construction,

²² A fascinating historical account of an annual visit to Starozagorski mineralni bani in Dimitrova (2017).

²³ Visited by Tzar Ferdinand in 1918. Similar is the building typology of Apolo and Neptune baths in Băile Herculane, although they have several rather small common pools.

maintenance, and operational costs of such projects would have made them completely inaccessible for the majority of Bulgaria's population.

Instead of Conclusion

The development of Western balneology in Bulgaria involved surveying the natural and built environment and mapping the resource distribution across the country. From the late 19th century onward, hydrogeologists, mining engineers and architects inspected the thermal springs and produced reports that contained ethnographic notes about Ottoman infrastructures and their uses at the time (CDA, F. 1638K, op. 1; *Izvestiya na Balneolozhkoto Druzhestvo v Bulgaria*, 1(2) 1930; *Kurortno delo*, 6(1) 1940; *Spisanie na Bulgarskoto inzhenerno-arhitekturno druzhestvo*, 28(14) 1928). The recording of Ottoman baths often preceded their demolition and replacement by “modern” infrastructures; however, the loss of historical strata extended to earlier periods, with instances of Roman infrastructures removed or damaged during the capturing of thermal springs (*Kurortno delo*, 5(1) 1938).²⁴

Both the advances in hydrogeology and the development of transportation infrastructure across Bulgaria contributed to the mapping of a countrywide network of “healing places”. A series of maps and travel guides provided information on accessibility from major Bulgarian towns (Azmanov, 1940; Dimitrov, 1939). Yet, these maps were novel only to a limited extent. They traced over springs already known and utilized throughout the Ottoman period (and possibly earlier), which were frequented despite the long journeys their visitors had to take before the advent of vehicular and railroad transportation (Dimitrova, 2017). Public baths and thermal springs were thought of as culturally and socially significant nodes in the past (Çelebi, 2014) and formed the foundation for modern balneology in Bulgaria. The dissemination of Western technological expertise at the turn of the 20th century solidified the perceived incompatibility between the Ottoman architectural legacy and the modernization aspirations of Bulgaria's experts. Yet, the surveying of thermal springs and the quantification of their properties rep-

²⁴ Mining engineer and hydrogeologist Pavel Petrov sketched himself or commissioned draftsmen to draw Ottoman baths before their demolition (CDA, F. 1638K, op. 1, a.e. 207). His and Bogomil Radoslavov's hydrogeological surveys (see *Kurortno delo*) produced an unlikely source of ethnographic observations that offer a glimpse, if a biased one, into the cultural and social uses of old thermal baths and springs across the country.

resented another continuity, built upon existing knowledge of channeled springs already flowing through infrastructures from a disputed past.

Fig. 18. A map of Bulgaria's thermal springs and its transportation network (Vatev, 1904).

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Small Museums, Singular Figures – Curating Medical Breakthroughs in Public Exhibitions

Abstract: *This article investigates how three small, independent European medical museums use person-centred narratives to construct national and cultural understandings of medical innovation. Focusing on the Semmelweis Medical History Museum (Budapest), the Pharmacy Museum (Lisbon), and Livets Museum (Lund), it explores how biographical storytelling, object selection, and spatial design work together to produce emotionally engaging exhibitions that serve broader symbolic purposes. The study combines field research conducted between 2020 and 2025 with literature analysis, interpretive reading of exhibition strategies, and visual documentation.*

The article identifies three main curatorial strategies shared across the museums: presenting scientific progress as a singular achievement; using the scientist as a synecdoche for national identity; and drawing on cultural memory to create local emotional resonance. In each case, a central historical figure – Ignaz Semmelweis, Maria Odette Santos Ferreira, or Nils Alwall – is positioned as both an innovator and a symbol of national values. The exhibitions frame their stories through emblematic objects and simplified narratives that foreground personal dedication while omitting scientific collaboration, failure, or international complexity.

These findings highlight how small medical museums operate not only as educational institutions but also as sites of memory and identity formation. They translate historical knowledge into accessible, emotionally powerful stories aligned with national narratives. The article concludes that while these strategies are effective in public engagement, they also reflect selective curatorial choices. It calls for future research on museums in underrepresented regions to further understand how biography and national identity are constructed in medical heritage displays.

Keywords: *history of medicine; medical museums; Livets Museum; Pharmacy Museum; AIDS; medical humanities*

Introduction

“What we are trying to do is create a venue that will engage visitors in the exciting journey of how scientific discoveries are made and how they are translated into medical advances that change our world.”

– Dr Mace L. Rothenberg

This vision, articulated by oncologist Dr Mace L. Rothenberg, captures an ambition shared by many medical museums: to present science not as a static archive of facts but as a dynamic human endeavour, shaped by clinical practice, personal insight, and public engagement. This article examines how small, independent medical museums in Europe construct person-centred narratives that highlight individual contributions to medical and scientific progress. Situated outside major metropolitan or academic centres, these institutions often rely on biographical storytelling and locally resonant displays that link singular breakthroughs to broader cultural and national frameworks.

While museum studies have increasingly examined how medical knowledge is displayed and communicated, most scholarship focuses on large, university-affiliated museums (such as the Josephinum in Vienna, the Hunterian Museum in London, or the Berlin Museum of Medical History at the Charité). Smaller, independent institutions – despite their unique practices and strong local ties – remain underexplored. Their exhibitions tend to foreground specific figures and places, offering decentralised narratives that challenge dominant, institution-based histories of medicine. Unlike academic medical museums that prioritise anatomical collections for teaching purposes (e.g. the Gordon Museum of Pathology at King’s College London), these public-facing institutions emphasise the human dimensions of medicine: how medical and pharmaceutical practices have evolved in relation to society, identity, and lived experience.

The three case studies examined in this article – the *Museu da Farmácia* in Lisbon (Pharmacy Museum, hereinafter **MF**), the *Semmelweis Orvostörténeti Múzeum* in Budapest (Semmelweis Medical History Museum, hereinafter **SOM**), and *Livets Museum* in Lund (Museum of Life, hereinafter **LM**) – offer three distinct approaches to the presentation of medical history. This article analyses how biography, spatial design, and material culture are employed in these institutions to communicate scientific innovation.

Methods and Literature

This article is based on a combination of literature analysis and field research carried out between 2020 and 2025, as part of a larger project on the cultural representation of medical knowledge in European museums. Although the overarching aim of that project were different, it provided a valuable foundation for investigating how small museums present biographical narratives and frame medical innovation.

Following a review of relevant scholarship on medical and pharmacy museums – as historical institutions and as spaces of knowledge transmission – these three museums were selected for their national and institutional diversity, their focus on individual figures associated with medical breakthroughs, and their status as independent institutions, operating outside academic or clinical environments.

I conducted fieldwork at each site, documenting the exhibitions through photographs, spatial sketches, and observational notes. I analysed the structure and content of each display, paying particular attention to object selection, spatial arrangement, use of visual material, and the way scientific achievements were narrated. I also collected and reviewed supporting materials such as exhibition leaflets, guidebooks, and interpretive panels. My analysis focused on three main questions: how is the featured individual positioned within each museum's narrative? How are material and visual elements used to communicate specific aspects of medical history? And how do the exhibitions relate to broader themes such as national identity, cultural memory, and the idea of progress. I also considered how each institution addressed questions of accessibility – such as caption language, visual clarity, and intended audience.

Academic research on medical museums covers several key themes, many of which are relevant to this study, though some aspects remain underexplored.

One recurring theme is the role of medical history museums in medical education. Historically, museums served as extensions of medical schools. They provided students with direct access to anatomical specimens, wax models, and surgical tools that were used for teaching anatomy and clinical procedures. Despite technological changes in medical education, some researchers argue that these historical collections still support learning, particularly through their materiality and realism (Marreez, Willems, and Wells, 2010; Zanatta and Zampieri, 2018).

Another major area of interest is institutional history. Scholars have studied the development of medical museums from Enlightenment-era anatomy collections to their formal establishment in the 19th century and their transformations in the 20th century. These studies often focus on how museum priorities shifted from pathology-focused displays to broader themes such as public health, medical ethics, and social history. Most of this literature, however, concentrates on major university museums in large cities (Turk, 1994; Reinartz, 2005; Jarosz, 2023).

Exhibition practices also form a distinct field of inquiry. This includes research on how medical museums select and interpret objects, arrange space, and combine visual and textual materials to guide visitor understanding. Scholars highlight that exhibitions do more than present facts – they construct interpretations and shape how audiences perceive science and medicine. Yet, person-centred narratives, such as biographical exhibitions, have received less attention (Alberti, 2011; McLeary, 2001; Jarosz, 2020).

Ethical and representational issues are increasingly discussed, especially in relation to the display of human remains. These debates often address the respectful treatment of remains, sensitivity to cultural beliefs, and the ethical implications of displaying individuals without consent. Redman (2016) and Alberti (2016) highlight how colonial-era collecting practices continue to shape current displays, often without adequate contextualization or community involvement. Institutional guidelines such as those by the British Museum (Department for Culture, Media and Sport 2005), the ICOM Code of Ethics (ICOM, 2017), and the Vermillion Accord (1989), advocate for transparency, consultation with descendant communities, and, where appropriate, repatriation. In parallel, Rodéhn (2019) and te Hennepe and Wingen (2024) emphasize the importance of inclusive curatorial practices that incorporate marginalized voices and patient perspectives. Participatory methods, such as co-curation and narrative sharing, are increasingly seen as essential tools for democratizing interpretation and promoting ethical representation.

Technology in medical museums is another growing field. Scholars have examined the use of augmented and virtual reality, interactive media, and digital archives to enhance visitor engagement and expand access, especially in remote or educational contexts (Erbay, 2008; Mikami et al., 2022).

A final theme concerns the medical object itself – how it is defined, preserved, and interpreted. Researchers explore how institutions decide what to collect and display, and how these choices reflect broader assumptions about science, medicine, and cultural value (Alberti, 2016; Eveleigh and Horry, 2025).

The museums discussed in this article reflect broader trends in the representation of medical history, but they have received uneven scholarly attention. The *Museu da Farmácia* in Lisbon (FM) features in studies on Portuguese scientific heritage (Delicado, 2014; Diogo, 2008; Lourenço and Dias, 2017). The *Semmelweis Orvostörténeti Múzeum* in Budapest (SOM) has been examined in Hungarian academic literature, particularly with regard to collection policy and institutional development (Kapronczay, Magyar and Kéki, 2011; Szvák et al., 2023). In contrast, *Livets Museum* in Lund (LM) has not been referenced in any major academic publications to date, indicating a gap in the study of small, independent medical museums in Europe.

Although the scientific contributions of Nils Alwall, Maria Odette Santos Ferreira, and Ignaz Semmelweis – dialysis, HIV-2 research, and infection control respectively – are well documented (Hansson et al., 2023; Kurkus and Ostrowski, 2019; Cameron, 2018; Clavel et al., 1986; Salzedas, 2021; Martins, 2021; Pittet and Boyce, 2001; Best and Neuhäuser, 2004; Stewardson et al., 2011) – their representation in museum contexts remains largely unexamined.

Background and Selected Museums

The three case studies examined in this article form part of a wider constellation of small and mid-sized medical museums across Europe. Examples include the Old Operating Theatre Museum and Herb Garret in London (publicly accessible since 1962), the Thackray Museum of Medicine in Leeds (1997), the Basque Museum of the History of Medicine and Science in Leioa (1982), the Gothenburg Medical History Museum (1946), the Stadtmuseum Gütersloh's medical collection (developed in the 1990s), the Museum of the History of Medicine at the Medical University of Warsaw (1955), the Musée Laënnec in Nantes (a small collection dedicated to the inventor of the stethoscope), the Museo di Storia della Medicina in Padua (1995), or the Museo delle Arti Sanitarie in Naples (2010). Although varied in scale and scope, these institutions share a commitment to presenting medicine through site-specific, personal, and often nationally inflected lenses.

The Museum of Life – Livets Museum (LM)

Located in Lund, Sweden, Livets Museum (LM) and was established in 2012 as a joint initiative between Region Skåne and Medicon Village, a biomedical innovation centre. Housed in a former anatomical theatre, the museum was conceived to bring together cultural engagement, public health education, and biomedical innovation (Hyttfors, 2014). Its founding concept is shaped by the work of sociologist Aaron Antonovsky, whose theory of salutogenesis emphasises the importance of the conditions that support human health – particularly a sense of coherence, grounded in comprehensibility, manageability, and meaningfulness. The museum is built upon these theoretical foundations, and its location in Lund carries added resonance, as Antonovsky himself spent a sabbatical year in the city.

Rather than focusing exclusively on illness or pathology, LM approaches medicine as a human-centred practice, highlighting the broader social and personal dimensions of health. The Swedish approach to public health – strongly focused on individual wellbeing, social equity, and preventive care – is reflected in the museum’s interactive format. Visitors are encouraged to engage with exhibits through hands-on, experiential displays that make complex medical topics accessible and relevant.

One of the museum’s permanent exhibitions is dedicated to Nils Alwall, a physician and professor known for his pioneering development of clinical dialysis. The display centres on a cardboard prototype from 1941 and a working dialysis machine built in 1943, accompanied by a large photograph of Alwall in surgery and a panel describing his collaboration with engineer Holger Crafoord. (*Fig. 1*)

Fig. 1. Dialysis machine designed by Nils Alwall ca. 1943 Displayed at Livets Museum Lund. Photo K. Jarosz, private collection.

Additional materials – including a model arm illustrating the arteriovenous shunt technique and a diagram of the fistula method – expand the story. (*Fig. 2*)

All exhibition materials are presented in Swedish. The museum positions itself as an educational space dedicated to health, technology, and public engagement, aligned with the country's broader commitment to health literacy and social wellbeing.

Fig. 2. Model of an arteriovenous shunt for dialysis treatment. Displayed at Livets Museum Lund. Photo K. Jarosz, private collection.

Pharmacy Museum – Museu da Farmácia

The MF is located in Lisbon, Portugal, with an additional site in Porto. It was founded by the National Association of Pharmacies in 1981 and opened to the public in 1996. The museum's permanent exhibition traces the global history of pharmacy through artefacts, reconstructions of historical pharmacies, and collections representing medical traditions from multiple cultures and periods. Although named a pharmacy museum, it presents pharmacy not merely as the preparation of medicinal compounds but as a broader practice of healing. In effect, it functions as Portugal's de facto museum of medicine – there is no

other public institution dedicated exclusively to medical history in the country. Visitors can trace changing approaches to treatment over the centuries, as well as the social histories of major diseases, from the Black Death to contemporary conditions such as AIDS.

A dedicated section focuses on the virologist Maria Odette Santos Ferreira, whose display was officially inaugurated on World AIDS Day in December 2018 as a tribute following her death that year. Later presented as a travelling display, including at the Museum of Pharmacy in Porto, the exhibition features a range of personal and professional objects, such as her fluorescence microscope (*Fig. 3*), white laboratory coat, handwritten notes, personal photographs, medals, and her favourite coat. The section also includes posters from national HIV/AIDS awareness campaigns and documents related to international public health initiatives. All interpretive texts and object labels are available in both Portuguese and English.

Fig. 3. Fluorescence microscope used by Maria Odette Santos Ferreira in her HIV-2 research. Displayed at the Museu da Farmácia, Lisbon. Photo K. Jarosz, private collection.

The museum highlights Ferreira's role in identifying HIV-2, a less common and less aggressive strain of the Human Immunodeficiency Virus, primarily found in West Africa. Unlike HIV-1, which is responsible for the global AIDS pandemic, HIV-2 progresses more

slowly, is less transmissible, and is less likely to develop into AIDS. Ferreira's work was crucial in clarifying ambiguous serological results in patients arriving from former Portuguese colonies in Africa. Her insight led to the recognition of HIV-2 as a distinct type, shaping both national and international approaches to diagnosis, treatment, and prevention. The exhibition also emphasises Portugal's leadership in HIV response: in July 2018, the World Health Organization recognised the country as "an exemplary country in the prevention, detection, treatment and care of HIV patients," noting that Portugal had met nearly all of the UNAIDS 90-90-90 targets ("Odette Ferreira - Building Futures", 2018).

Semmelweis Medical History Museum

The Semmelweis Medical History Museum is located in Budapest, Hungary, in the former residence and birthplace of Ignaz Semmelweis. It originated from the Royal Society of Physicians in Budapest and its affiliated library – institutions that gradually evolved from serving practicing physicians to preserving historical medical knowledge. It was established as a museum in 1965 under socialist cultural policy and became part of the Hungarian National Museum in 2016 (Kapronczay, 2011: 256-259).

In the late 1980s, the museum was directed by medical historian József Antall, who later became Hungary's first democratically elected Prime Minister. As director from 1974 to 1990, Antall transformed the museum into a modern centre for the study and public presentation of medical history. He prioritized scholarly research, the systematic collection and cataloguing of historical medical objects, and the cultural significance of Semmelweis's legacy (Szállási, 2009). During this period, the museum expanded its holdings significantly, acquiring manuscripts, instruments, anatomical models, and rare documents. The permanent exhibition was reorganized to integrate biographical and institutional narratives: the life of Semmelweis was presented within a reconstructed 19th-century domestic setting, while surrounding galleries explored broader themes in the development of obstetrics, surgery, and public health.

Antall also promoted international collaboration, positioning the museum as a respected contributor to the European discourse on medical history. His approach combined historical scholarship with civic and national values, treating medical history as a tool for cultivating a shared cultural identity rooted in science, ethics, and public service. As

Antall and his co-editors wrote in their edition of Semmelweis's manuscripts: "even when prioritizing the content value and the value of the manuscripts as sources, one must not forget their importance as museum materials of historical documentation" (Antall, Harkó and Vida, 1968: 185).

The permanent exhibition occupies several floors of the historic building. The biographical core is arranged within a reconstructed 19th-century domestic interior, featuring a desk, chairs, oil lamp, portrait, and decorative furnishings (*Fig. 4*).

Fig. 4. Study of Ignaz Semmelweis, featuring 19th-century furnishings and personal items. Displayed at the Semmelweis Medical History Museum, Budapest. Photo K. Jarosz, private collection.

Surrounding rooms display surgical instruments, obstetric tools, anatomical models, and preserved specimens from the 18th and 19th centuries. Notable exhibits include a surgical stapler designed in 1908, a wax anatomical model of a pregnant woman, and a scale model of a dental laboratory from the 1896 Budapest Millennium Exhibition.

The museum's collections have grown over time and now include anatomical torsos, trepanned skulls, wax heads, and other historical

medical artefacts. Captions and explanatory texts are provided in both Hungarian and English.

Approaches to Presenting Medical History

Before turning to the analysis, it is worth noting that the three museums make use of different exhibition approaches that serve distinct purposes – such as attracting visitor interest, generating emotional engagement, affirming national narratives, simplifying complex histories for wider audiences, or expressing institutional identity. These functions are common across many museums and reflect the practical and symbolic goals of public display. The approaches are not mutually exclusive – they often overlap or support one another. In what follows, I focus on three ways of organizing meaning that appear across all three museums and shape how medical knowledge and memory are communicated: (1) presenting scientific progress as a singular achievement; (2) using the figure of the scientist as a symbol of the nation; and (3) evoking cultural memory to create emotionally resonant and socially anchored narratives.

Medical Progress as an Individual Achievement

Across the three case studies, medical innovation is consistently presented as the result of individual insight and determination, rather than the outcome of collaborative, institutional, or cumulative processes. This portrayal mirrors how medical breakthroughs are commonly depicted in popular culture – as heroic, personal triumphs. Numerous books and films celebrate the lone doctor or scientist overcoming adversity to achieve a major discovery. The Polish film *Bogowie* (Gods), which dramatizes the career of pioneering cardiac surgeon Zbigniew Religa, is a clear example of this narrative tendency (Łazarkiewicz, 2014). As Robert B. Taylor notes, nineteenth-century medicine is remembered through its “Great Doctors” such as Semmelweis, Lister, and Pasteur – figures who have become synonymous with singular moments of medical advancement (Taylor, 2008: 3).

At LM, the section devoted to Nils Alwall presents his contribution to dialysis through a small number of objects: a cardboard prototype from 1941, a functioning dialysis machine from 1943, and a photo of Alwall at work. The accompanying text describes him as a pioneer who treated his first patient in 1946 and promoted dialysis at a time when others still supported dietary approaches such as mixtures of butter, sugar, and water. While his innovations are clearly highlighted, the

exhibition omits the broader historical context of dialysis. There is no mention of earlier figures such as Georg Haas, who performed the first human dialysis in 1924 in Germany, nor is there reference to international developments that shaped the field. The display presents Alwall's achievement in isolation, without situating it within a larger scientific or clinical timeline. This selective focus may reflect the museum's orientation toward a wide general audience, including children, and its goal of communicating basic medical knowledge in a straightforward, accessible format.

In the MF, Maria Odette Santos Ferreira's role in the identification of HIV-2 is shown through objects directly connected to her scientific and public work. These include her fluorescence microscope used in research, her white laboratory coat, handwritten notes, personal photographs – also depicting her at work in the laboratory – and a selection of national and international medals and decorations displayed prominently in a central glass case. Among these distinctions are the *Ordre national du Mérite* (France), the Grand Cross of the Order of Prince Henry (*Ordem do Infante Dom Henrique*, Portugal), and several medals awarded by scientific and public health organisations, reflecting international recognition of her contributions to virology and public health. These elements construct a narrative of scientific dedication, perseverance, and civic recognition. The exhibition highlights her decision to pursue ambiguous serological results that led to the identification of HIV-2. The accompanying materials acknowledge that the virus was found in patients from Bissau, the capital of Guinea-Bissau, thereby situating the research in a postcolonial context. However, while this geographic origin is mentioned, the broader political and historical dimensions of Portugal's colonial involvement remain undeveloped, and the emphasis stays on Ferreira's personal achievement and its national significance.

The display also emphasises her contributions to public health. Ferreira was the initiator of *Troca de Seringas* (Syringe Exchange), launched in 1993 as the first harm reduction programme in Portugal. It allowed intravenous drug users to anonymously exchange used syringes for sterile ones in pharmacies, aiming to reduce the spread of HIV and other blood-borne infections. In addition, she initiated *Boas Férias* (Have a Good Holiday), a seasonal HIV/AIDS awareness campaign designed to promote safer behaviour during the summer period (*Fig. 5*).

Fig. 5. Boas Ferias Have a Good Holiday. HIV / AIDS awareness campaign poster initiated by Maria Odette Santos Ferreira. On display at the Pharmacy Museum Lisbon. Photo K. Jarosz, private collection.

The campaign used direct language and accessible visual design to encourage prevention across a wide audience. Through these combined elements, the museum presents Ferreira not only as a pioneering virologist, but as a public figure who helped shape Portugal's scientific, preventive, and educational response to the HIV/AIDS epidemic.

At the SOM the figure of Ignaz Semmelweis is depicted through a reconstruction of his study, which omits surgical tools and laboratory equipment. Instead, the emphasis is on intellectual and moral labour, portraying Semmelweis as a solitary thinker whose insight defied prevailing medical norms. The lack of reference to the resistance he faced from the medical establishment, or the eventual confirmation of his theories through germ theory, reinforces a simplified narrative of individual discovery.

In all three museums, emblematic objects – Alwall's prototype, Ferreira's microscope and personal belongings, Semmelweis's desk – serve as focal points that translate complex developments in medical science into emotionally accessible stories of individual heroism.

Lives of Scientists as a Strategy for Shaping National Identity

Public figures – including scientists – often become symbols of collective values and aspirations and the portrayal of individual scientists extends beyond their research to reflect national identity. Christiaan Barnard in South Africa, Louis Pasteur in France, and Alexander Fleming in the UK are examples of how personal medical achievement can become part of national self-narratives. Christiaan Barnard's 1967 heart transplant was not just a medical milestone, it also elevated him to the status of a national symbol in apartheid-era South Africa (Dubow, 2006). Louis Pasteur is widely commemorated in France as a national hero whose scientific legacy is central to representations of French intellectual and moral leadership (Greene, 2008). Alexander Fleming's discovery of penicillin has been absorbed into British national memory, where he is portrayed as a figure of ingenuity and humanitarian progress (Bud, 2007).

This is also the case in two of the museums studied here. Ignaz Semmelweis is explicitly presented as a national figure in Hungary. The Semmelweis Museum in Budapest, which bears his name, describes him as “probably one of the best-known Hungarians” and “the most famous Hungarian doctor.” His legacy is communicated through public commemorations, statues, exhibitions, and narratives that highlight his ethical commitment and scientific determination. These forms of recognition place him within a broader context of national pride and historical significance. On the centenary of his death in 1965, the Hungarian Ministry of Health inaugurated the Semmelweis House as a memorial museum, referring to him as “a great Hungarian physician honoured by all the world” (Fekete, Farkas and Palla, 1965: 744).

Maria Odette Santos Ferreira is similarly commemorated in Portugal. Her identification of HIV-2 is linked to her broader contribution to public health, and her display connects this achievement to Portuguese efforts in combating AIDS. A national newspaper described her as “an essential figure in science and public health in Portugal... a symbol of fearless resistance to the stigma of the disease” (Público, 2018). However, the exhibition avoids situating her work in an international or postcolonial context.

In contrast, the presentation of Nils Alwall in Lund does not adopt an overtly nationalistic tone. While his achievements in dialysis are central to the exhibit, they are not used to express national pride. Rather, the emphasis is on his contribution to the scientific and cultural heritage of Sweden. This approach foregrounds the historical and educational

value of his work, avoiding the symbolic fusion of individual achievement with national identity.

Medical History as Cultural Memory

In all three museums, cultural memory plays a key role in how the history of medicine is presented. According to Jan Assmann (1992), cultural memory is a socially sustained form of remembering the past, shaped by institutions, symbols, and narratives that respond to the current needs and values of a community. Its aim is not to reconstruct the past with factual precision, but to assign it meaning that resonates with contemporary audiences. In museums, this is achieved through the selection of specific individuals, objects, and themes, the way these elements are presented and interpreted, as well as through the omission of others deemed irrelevant or inconvenient.

At the SOM, a reconstructed 19th-century interior features a desk, oil lamp, books, and a portrait, evoking a space of moral reflection rather than scientific work. This presentation casts Semmelweis as a solitary figure guided by ethical conviction. It suggests that his discovery emerged from personal insight rather than collaborative work or engagement with contemporary scientific debate. Omitted, however, is a crucial part of his biography: that his call for handwashing was ignored by many medical professionals, that he was ridiculed and marginalised, and eventually declared mentally unwell and committed to an asylum, where he died after being beaten. By excluding these facts, the exhibition loses both its dramatic depth and its critical edge. Instead, it presents Semmelweis as a fully recognised national hero – “the greatest Hungarian doctor,” a moral authority, and a figure whose story fits neatly into a national historical narrative.

At LM, cultural memory takes the form of a narrative that frames medicine as part of social care and public education. The exhibition dedicated to Nils Alwall focuses on his contribution to the development of dialysis, but avoids national symbols or references to scientific heroes. Instead, it presents his work as part of a broader system working for public health, reflecting Aaron Antonovsky’s concept of salutogenesis. This model understands health not as a static condition but as a process, where a person’s sense of coherence – the ability to understand, manage, and find meaning in experience – is central. The Lund exhibition, with its emphasis on prevention, accessibility, and education, reflects this vision of health as a shared social responsibility.

In all these cases, cultural memory does not serve an archival or documentary function. Rather, it works through selective interpretation – shaping the past in ways that align with contemporary values and expectations. These museums do more than display the history of medicine; they help shape public ideas about what medicine was, what it is, and what role it should play in society.

Conclusions and Directions for Further Research

Small, independent medical museums are a rich but often overlooked source of historical knowledge. Their main purpose is not to impress with design, but to preserve and share the stories of medicine in ways that are meaningful to the public. These museums show how medical discoveries are remembered, explained, and connected to broader ideas about science, identity, and society.

This study asked three main questions: how each museum presents its central figure; how it uses space, objects, and visuals to tell its story; and how these stories relate to ideas such as cultural memory, national identity, and medical progress. The analysis shows that all three museums – SOM, the MF and LM – follow a similar pattern. They build clear and focused stories around individual achievements, using personal objects and selective details to create simple, engaging narratives.

At the same time, there are important differences. The SOM presents its figure as a heroic and morally driven individual, while avoiding the more difficult parts of his biography. The Lisbon Museum highlights Maria Odette Santos Ferreira's role in national health achievements but leaves out the international and colonial aspects of her work. Yet these aspects are essential for understanding the scientific and historical significance of her contribution. Ferreira's identification of HIV-2 was based on serological anomalies in patients arriving from Guinea-Bissau, a former Portuguese colony. This geographical and epidemiological context – rooted in postcolonial mobility and the legacy of empire – was critical to the breakthrough but is not addressed in the exhibition. The patients from West Africa, whose biological material enabled the discovery, remain anonymous and absent, while Portuguese science is celebrated in isolation. No reference is made to African public health systems, local knowledge, or research infrastructures. This omission reflects a broader pattern of scientific extraction, where data and prestige are drawn from the global periphery to reinforce metropol-

itan narratives of achievement. In Lund, the exhibition about Nils Alwall takes a broader view, placing his work within a public health and education framework.

In all three cases, the museums they present simplified, emotionally appealing stories that match national or local narratives and leave out topics such as scientific disagreement, failure, and collaboration across borders.

The result is a coherent but selective portrayal of science, where medical progress is streamlined into emotionally charged and culturally aligned narratives. Topics such as ethical ambiguity, scientific failure, or patient perspectives are excluded.

Future research should include comparative studies of lesser-known institutions, such as the Polish Museum of the History of Medicine (Warsaw), the Medical History Museum in Cluj-Napoca, or the Museum of Medical History of Catalonia (Barcelona). Investigating how different political and educational systems influence frameworks could clarify whether the patterns identified – biographical focus, national framing, symbolic materiality – are specific or general.

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BIOPOLITICS AND REPRODUCTIVE GOVERNANCE

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“Everything for the Benefit of Man, Everything for the Sake of Man!”¹: Genetic Counselling in Socialist Bulgaria

Abstract: *This paper examines the process of introduction and popularization of genetic counselling and prenatal diagnosis in socialist Bulgaria, and the efforts of human genetics experts to “bring these practices closer to the population”. In keeping with the preventive spirit of the socialist model of public health, these practices were declared to be forms of “prophylaxis” – a term that largely obscures and mitigates the fundamental moral dilemmas associated with the fact that, in this context, “prophylaxis” often meant selective abortion. This practice, with its clear eugenic implications, has long been a focal point of critique from bioethicists, disability activists, and academics. Drawing on both scholarly and popular publications by leading Bulgarian geneticists, as well as on archival documents, the paper traces how this preventive undertaking unfolded, how it was framed by experts, and what images of disability were mobilized to promote these practices and to responsabilize socialist citizens in the sphere of reproduction.*

Keywords: *genetic counselling; disability; selective abortion; socialism; prophylaxis.*

Introduction

Genetic counselling is a key nexus within clinical genetics, serving as an essential part of a decision-making process that is both literally

¹ The full quote reads: “The prophylactic activity of medical-genetic counselling is the fullest expression of the aspiration to realize the call “Everything for the benefit of man, everything for the sake of man!” (Georgieva, 1988: 79).

and metaphorically a matter of life and death. Historically, such decisions primarily concerned an individual's reproductive future – whether to abstain from having children in high-risk situations or to terminate a pregnancy following a fetal diagnosis of disease or disability. However, as advances in genetics have provided an ever-growing wealth of information, the scope of dilemmas and controversies has expanded accordingly. Genetic counselling is now available in cases of presymptomatic testing for late-onset disorders such as Huntington's disease and certain cancers, or when patients need help to navigate the ambiguities generated by unanticipated findings and results of uncertain significance provided by the new genome-wide technologies (Clarke, 2020; Kaneva, Dimitrova, 2023). At the same time, another feature that adds immense complexity to these situations and decisions is the fact that their implications are obviously not limited to ourselves or even to our children – they invoke population-wide images that claim to affect the well-being of future generations. In this sense, genetic counselling is a very peculiar encounter whose stakes can be framed on multiple scales: it is involved both in determining which lives are worth living within individual families and in envisaging grand demographic and public health projects. But whatever the scale, images of desirable and undesirable futures play a key role, and they are negotiated and renegotiated in this seemingly small and intimate setting where genetic and medical information is conveyed.

Central to these images is disability or chronic illness, commonly thought of as a life that should be avoided – one associated with suffering and viewed as a burden on families and societies. Prenatal diagnosis and selective abortion – the most common outcomes of genetic counselling in affected pregnancies – allow this to happen in the early stages of fetal development, reinforcing the conviction that these practices are morally unproblematic. Furthermore, the eugenic rationality underpinning them is effectively concealed by the advent of the new biotechnologies. When this powerful industry is combined with state-sanctioned prenatal and other screening programmes, and this complex is framed as the epitome of autonomous, informed choice and responsible parenting, it becomes especially difficult to challenge. This system operates effectively because it can govern at a distance, beyond constant state surveillance (Rose, 1996; Rose, Miller, 1992), relying on the production of a regime of expanded responsibility for ourselves, our health, and our future. In this regime, the prudent self can “manage its present in the light of knowledge of its own future” (Rose, Novas, 2005: 441-

442). This notion of self-management is often construed as an essential aspect of liberalism and neoliberalization – a multifaceted process in which citizens actively shape and enhance themselves through various practices of self-optimization (Dean, 1999; Rose, Miller, 1992). However, research on reproductive genetics and genetic counselling within the socialist bloc (Schmidt, 2024; Doetz, 2023; Petermann et al. 2017; Dimitrova, 2012) demonstrates that similar technologies of self-governance were being cultivated and internalized in these contexts as well, the purpose being to nudge citizens into directing their choices and adopting lifestyles aimed at managing risky futures.

This paper examines the introduction and enforcement of genetic counselling in socialist Bulgaria, and the efforts of human genetics experts to incorporate these practices into the socialist biopolitical project of optimizing the collective body and cultivating responsible socialist citizens in the sphere of reproduction. The main focus is on the images of disability as the embodiment of an undesirable future that were mobilized to promote genetic counselling, followed – when possible – by prenatal diagnosis and selective abortion. In practice, experts invariably referred to and constructed the profile of a “life unworthy of living”, whose undesirability was never problematized. The normalization of selective abortion was further reinforced by the absence of voices advocating for alternative images of disability. In other contexts, such spokespersons are mainly the communities of people with disabilities and their allies, who struggle for the demedicalization of genetic counselling. However, in socialist Bulgaria, there were no such spokespersons, and this determined the limited epistemic resources available for deciding which lives were unworthy of living.

The paper draws on data from several sources. The most important among them are the monographs, collective works, and articles of socialist experts in genetics, as well as popular pamphlets – such as the series *Talks on Health* [Беседи за здравето] and *The Doctor Advises You* [Лекарят ви съветва] – dedicated to the prevention of hereditary diseases. The archives of the Department of Medical Genetics headed by Maria Tsoneva, her personal archive, as well as the archives of the Scientific Institute of Paediatrics at the Medical Academy and its affiliated clinics have also been studied. Since the main focus of the article is on the representations of disability mobilized in genetic counselling as a tool for responsabilization, the socialist history of the National Genetic Laboratory (NGL) is not addressed in the present analy-

sis. It played important role in introducing metabolic and enzymatic diagnostic methods for the most common inborn errors of metabolism, as well as in implementing mass neonatal screening for phenylketonuria and galactosemia, but prior to 1989 was not involved in genetic counselling.²

In the first part, I will briefly outline the emergence of genetic counselling, addressing the fundamental principles that ostensibly guide it, as well as its critiques – particularly from a disability perspective. The second part focuses on the situation in socialist Bulgaria, where genetic counselling, in line with the preventive spirit of the socialist model of public health, was considered a key component of genetic “prophylaxis” – which often meant selective abortion. I will pay particular attention to how medical geneticists framed the nature, objectives, and broader social role of their work, as well as to the moral imperatives they saw as guiding their practice. Finally, I will conclude by linking the socialist legacy to the postsocialist framing of prenatal diagnosis and selective abortion, and the persistent poverty of epistemic resources regarding living with disability in Bulgaria.

The Moral Anxieties around Genetic Counselling

The term “genetic counselling” was first used by Sheldon Reed, who introduced it in 1947 and later, in 1974, published a book on the early history of the practice. He defined it as “a type of social work intended for the benefit of each family rather than for the state or the population” (Clarke, 2017: 543), aiming to categorically distance genetics and genetic counselling from the legacy of eugenics. For this reason, the so-called non-directiveness was taken as the foundational principle: “an approach to genetic counselling that aims not to guide the patient (or client) to an outcome predetermined by the counsellor or the genetics service but instead to support the patient in reaching their own decisions” (Clarke, 2017: 543). This basic requirement is still valid today, although the transformations in the tasks and tools of medical genetics have made it less relevant in certain fields, such as oncology and cardiology (Clarke, 2017: 541-542). Within reproductive genetics, the principle of non-directiveness stems from the idea that clients should maintain as much autonomy as possible, with the counsellor’s role limited to providing relevant information. However, the ability to achieve this neutrality within the actual encounter and communicative exchange

² This changes after 1989. For a reconstruction and analysis of the more recent history of NGL, see Dimitrova, 2012.

has been the subject of many critiques. Critics point out that when purely medical information about disability is conveyed, it simply cannot be neutral – it is always negative, and even those genetic counsellors who strongly endorse patient autonomy and informed consent nonetheless tend “to present genetic conditions likely to produce a physical or mental disability as biological errors to be avoided for medical, psychological, and economic reasons” (Stern, 2012: 3). Moreover, the counselling encounter itself takes place within a broader medical setting, where “power relations [are] at play” and “medical professionals perpetuate epistemic injustice when they offer their patients distorted [...] or limited information” (Knight, Miller, 2012: 2). Additionally, the very fact that the healthcare system offers prenatal screening for a number of diseases “inevitably conveys a recommendation to pregnant women that accepting the test is the responsible course of action” (Clarke, 2009: 253). Although the discourse around such programmes emphasizes reproductive autonomy and the right to informed decision-making, their very existence conveys this message and normalizes the prenatal elimination of life with disability (Clarke, 2009: 253). Acknowledging these complexities, some genetic counsellors (e.g., Clarke, 2009), disability activists, bioethicists, and disability studies scholars coalesce around the argument that genetic counselling cannot avoid its inherently political nature (Patterson, Satz, 2002). Thus, a persistent collective voice has emerged, highlighting the problematic nature of genetic counselling as – in most cases – a gateway to selective abortion.

Critics, particularly activists and scholars in disability studies, see a fundamental contradiction in the normalization of selective abortion on the one hand, and formal public and legislative demands that claim as their priority the support, integration, and non-discriminatory treatment of people with disabilities, on the other. As a countermeasure, they do not advocate for banning such abortions, but instead propose ensuring that prospective parents receive more balanced information during genetic counselling sessions. This, for example, could be achieved by supplementing medical information with insights into the everyday lives and personal experiences of parents and people living with disability. To put it another way, it would be fair to balance strong ableist prejudices against disability with more information stemming from lived experience. This third approach, sometimes referred to as the pro-information movement, focuses solely on the conditions under which prospective parents make their decisions. As Rob Sparrow (2008)

points out, given the radical nature of the critique of the power structures that determine which lives are worth living and which are not, such demands are more than modest: they call only for the provision of relevant firsthand information about life with disability by those who have actually experienced it. In other words, the reaction is not against the dominant decision itself, but against the way it is made, from which disabled people are excluded (Sparrow, 2008: 122).

Genetic Counselling in Bulgaria: Institutionalization and Problems on the Ground

Within the socialist bloc, the first genetic counselling centres emerged in the second half of the 1960s in Hungary, Czechoslovakia, the GDR, and Yugoslavia. By the end of the 1970s, a network of regional prenatal screening centres was already in place (Schmidt, 2024: 1). In Bulgaria, early interest in genetic counselling seems to have arisen in the context of psychiatry: in 1965, Vassil Milev, one of the prominent Bulgarian psychiatrists, published two articles advocating for the establishment of medical-genetic clinics, arguing that “medical genetics is a science with broad prospects” and that counselling centres would “help integrate [it] into concrete medical practice” (Milev 1965: 123). According to the geneticist Maria Krachunova (1983: 109), the first genetic counselling office in Bulgaria was opened the same year at the Scientific Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery, focusing exclusively on mental illness. It is likely that its establishment was driven by Vassil Milev himself, who in his 1974 monograph *Clinical Genetics in Psychiatry* notes:

In this book, we report some of our experience with the genetics of mental illness, acquired over more than ten years of work. This responsible and difficult task was undertaken, it may be said, for the first time, and, in fact, we have remained so far alone. The practical impossibility of exchanging scientific experience and, especially, the absence of opponents with genetic expertise has undoubtedly affected its quality. (Milev, 1974: 7)

Genetic counselling in Bulgaria was regulated by order of the Ministry of Public Health in 1975, following the establishment of the Department of Medical Genetics at the Institute for Specialization and Improvement of Physicians (ISUL) in Sofia by Maria Tsoneva in 1971. In her autobiography, Tsoneva recalls that in 1969, “I was tasked with establishing and organizing [the Section for Genetic Prophylaxis and Population Genetics] at the Centre for Hygiene,” and in 1971, “with

organizing the country’s first Department of Medical Genetics at ISUL.”³ It is worth noting that her biography contains no elements that could suggest any ideological contradictions in relation to the communist regime. On the contrary, as a high school student, she was a member of the RMS (Union of the Workers’ Youth). Because of this, she was expelled from high school and sentenced to 15 years in prison under the Law for the Protection of the State and served time in the prisons of Shumen and Varna. Her memoirs from the time she spent in Varna’s prison, as well as the poems she wrote there, have been preserved in the archives.⁴

Her expertise was shaped by specializations on both sides of the Iron Curtain – beginning in 1965, she specialized in Switzerland, the USSR, Britain, Denmark, Sweden, and France. Later, she served as a consultant to the World Health Organization.⁵ In a report on the occasion of Tsoneva’s sixtieth birthday, Bratan Bratanov, one of Bulgaria’s most eminent paediatricians at that time, stressed that she always possessed “an acute sense of the needs and problems of practical healthcare. This approach is reflected in her views on medical genetic counselling as the highest form of unity between theory and practice in the field of medical genetics. Professor Tsoneva is the most zealous propagandist and organizer of the network of medical genetic counselling centres in our country.”⁶

In order to achieve this unity, the research activities of the Department of Medical Genetics focused on “major theoretical problems of medical genetics [that are] of great applied importance for practical healthcare: 1. Research on the genetic status of the Bulgarian people; 2. Research on the factors causing mutations in humans; 3. Genetic polymorphism and its clinical significance.”⁷ However, publications and archival materials consistently highlight as the Department’s major achievement “its role in the development of new units in practical

³ SA – Sofia, F. 2561, Inv. 1, a. u. 1, p. 1, “Autobiography”, May 4, 1984.

⁴ SA – Razgrad, F. 990, Inv. 1, a.u. 7, “Memoirs of Maria Tsoneva from the prison”.

⁵ SA – Sofia, F. 2561, Inv. 1, a. u. 2, p. 5, “Autobiography”, May 4, 1984.

⁶ SA – Sofia, F. 2561, Inv. 1, a. u. 6, p. 4, “Report on Prof. Maria Tsoneva”, May 7, 1984.

⁷ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv.15, a. u. 5, p. 5, “In response to letter number 179, dated March 29, 1983, to the Director of the Scientific Medico-Biological Institute.”

healthcare, such as medical-genetic counselling and cytogenetic laboratories.”⁸ In 1984, the Department was tasked with assisting the Maternal and Child Health Department of the Ministry of Public Health in developing Bulgaria’s first national programme and regulatory framework for the establishment of a comprehensive system of medical-genetic consultative care and prenatal diagnosis by 1990. The programme was adopted in 1986. During this period, regulations on pregnancy termination for medical reasons were also updated to include genetic conditions detected by prenatal diagnosis as a “method of prophylaxis of hereditary diseases”, which was introduced in 1983.⁹ In practice, this opened up a completely new horizon for disability governance in the form of selective abortions.

From that moment on, the Department became increasingly involved in counselling and educational activities. In the second half of the 1980s, it actively assisted the healthcare services in the capital Sofia by providing genetic counselling in various hospitals and polyclinics “through the brigades set up for this purpose”¹⁰ and by “actively promoting the achievements of medical-genetic counselling through popular brochures, articles, lectures, etc.”¹¹ Maria Tsoneva emphasized the need for direct contact with communities, urging: “those who can [must] go into the neighborhoods through women’s organizations to give talks, so that it [medical-genetic counselling] will not remain limited to articles and pamphlets. Propaganda work is necessary and useful.”¹² The Department’s Measures for the Implementation of the Decisions of the 13th Congress of the [Bulgarian Communist] Party¹³ set as its main objective “improving the initial identification, registration, and dispensarization of patients and timely referral to medico-genetic counselling and prenatal diagnosis, resulting in a reduction in births of children with malformations and chromosomal diseases – by 1989.” Despite these efforts, in 1990 Maria Krachunova wrote: “In our country, medical-genetic counselling is still not popular enough, and the popular beliefs about its tasks and methods are too incomplete and, to some extent, even wrong” (Krachunova, 1990: 138). Additionally, inadequate

⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 4, “In response to letter number 144, dated March 16, 1983, to the Deputy Director of the Scientific Medico-Biological Institute.”

⁹ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 7, p. 4, “Counter-plan for 1986 of the Collective at the Department of Medical Genetics”, 1985.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, p. 6.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 10.

¹² SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 1, p. 5, “Minutes”, December 19, 1986.

¹³ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15 a. u. 10, p. 19.

prophylaxis coverage was reported, reaching “no more than 30-40% of the country’s population needs” (Simeonov, Krachunova, 1993: 17).

Archival documents reveal significant challenges on the ground in terms of resources – staff, materials, and equipment – which made the implementation of wide-reaching and effective activities difficult and dependent solely on the enthusiasm of the twelve members of the Department. Maria Tsoneva undoubtedly stands out as a tireless, disciplined, and demanding leader. Department meeting minutes document her frequent reprimands regarding poor work discipline. As she pointed out, for example, the office for “medical-genetic counselling is often left open and unstaffed [...] it is high time everyone understood that they must stay at their workplace.”¹⁴ Another apparently persistent problem was the timely service of patients. Repeatedly, including in the so-called counter-plans (*насрещни планове*), criticism was levelled at the slow return of screening results, which were sometimes delayed by 45 days, and the occasional “failed” laboratory results.¹⁵

The Guidelines for the Activities of the Department of Medical Genetics for the 1986–1990 Period, dated October 25, 1985, provide insight into its resource constraints:

The implementation of the Department’s intended activities [...] is directly dependent on the provision of the necessary material and personnel resources [...]. In the first place, the Department lacks sufficient premises [...] the classrooms are extremely undersized and do not meet modern teaching requirements. The conditions in the genetic counselling room are also inadequate. The available laboratories are undersized. We work with chemicals which, due to the unfavourable conditions, cause allergic reactions among staff [...]. It is also essential to secure the necessary amount of chemicals and equipment, especially microscopic equipment, which the Department clearly needs. It has made repeated requests, but has not received a single research microscope suitable for precise diagnostics in years.¹⁶

In addition to these constant shortages, all counter-plans from the second half of the 1980s consistently emphasize the need for cost-saving measures, including reductions in electricity, water, and chemicals usage, and regular submission of recyclable materials.

Even more critical was the shortage of qualified geneticists. In a 1988 letter to the head of the Medical Academy’s Education Department, Maria Tsoneva wrote: “To strengthen the front line, we need to

¹⁴ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 4, p. 7, “Minutes”, March 22, 1985.

¹⁵ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 14, a. u. 3, pp. 20-22, “Minutes”, September 23, 1981.

¹⁶ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 8, p. 5.

improve qualifications in [genetic counselling] offices, none of the heads of these offices have a specialty in medical genetics, and some do not even have a clinical specialty.”¹⁷ Immediately after 1989, this issue was further acknowledged: “the training of specialized personnel working in medical-genetic counselling does not meet the requirements of the World Health Organization”, and “the system of personnel training is inadequate [... as they] undergo only one or a few specialized short-term courses” (Simeonov, Krachunova, 1993: 18). In this regard, there is an interesting difference between the Bulgarian and certain Western contexts – particularly the United States. Before the 1970s, genetic counselling there was performed by medical professionals. However, as certified master’s degree programs were introduced, the field began recruiting people without medical training, primarily women (Stern, 2012: 4). This is assessed as the generation that transformed genetic counselling in the United States and turned it into a “feminized health care profession that combines scientific knowledge, empathic communication, and information delivery” (Stern, 2012: 5).

The fact that genetic counselling remained a purely medical activity is pointed out by Susanne Doetz (2017: 412) as a reason for its directive nature in the GDR: “Counselling was performed by physicians or biologists. Thus, counselling had a different focus, and it was not primarily considered a communication process as in the USA, where the client-centered approach of psychotherapist Carl Rogers (1902–1987) had a crucial impact on the practice of genetic counselling.” In Bulgaria – apparently following the same model – any deviation from medical expertise was similarly rejected outright. This is evident, for example, in Maria Krachunova’s 1983 book *Genetics of Mental Illness*, where she references Russian authors who argue that “the counselling physician must be prepared to answer a wider range of questions that are not among their direct tasks: the educational possibilities of children with an inherited defect, vocational guidance, early diagnosis, etc.” Krachunova (1983: 109-110) concurs, but notes that “this widens the field of medical-genetic counselling with tasks not specific to it” and that such a move is “an attempt to replace existing medical services” which ultimately “makes the help for patients with inherited diseases less qualified.”

The medicalization of disability during state socialism – and the persistence of this medical model after its demise – is a phenomenon

¹⁷ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 9, p. 10.

whose harmful effects have been repeatedly discussed (Mladenov, 2018; Mladenov, Dimitrova, 2012). Genetic counselling adds another touch to this picture, revealing how such medicalization begins even before birth. In the absence of alternative models and voices, the medical narrative remains the only legitimate one, generating a situation of epistemic deficits.

“Prophylaxis” of Disability: Governing Risky Futures

As already mentioned, within the framework of socialist healthcare, genetic counselling was considered a component of “genetic prophylaxis” aimed at “combating the spread of hereditary and chromosomal diseases” (Tsoneva, 1984a: 316). This activity had several main tasks: “1. Genetic prognosis; 2. Limiting births in cases of severe and incurable hereditary diseases; 3. Restricting marriages between heterozygous carriers of severe hereditary diseases; 4. Limiting consanguineous marriages; 5. Introducing [...] modern methods of diagnosing, preventing, and treating hereditary diseases” (Tsoneva, 1976: 37). The well-known from this period ritualistic mobilization of comparisons of socialist and capitalist realities, which was also “a major aspect of health propaganda” (Schmidt, 2024: 10), was invariably applied to genetic counselling in Bulgaria. In the socialist context, genetic counselling was defined as a much larger-scale activity than the “bourgeois-capitalist” one, which remained confined within the family and was “passive”. Socialist genetic counselling, by contrast, was active: “a comprehensive activity of searching out, diagnosing, and dispensarizing the identified sick people and carriers” (Tsoneva, 1984b: 14-19), with “the ultimate aim [...] of taking appropriate measures to prevent or limit the creation and birth of sick and defective children” (Ibid., 11-13).

The key practice that made genetic prophylaxis effective was prenatal diagnosis, which enabled detecting fetal defects before birth and, consequently, undertaking abortion for medical reasons: “In the work of genetic counselling, prenatal diagnosis is the most effective tool for reducing hereditary diseases and defects in the population, and hence for reducing infant mortality, disability, and disturbed reproduction. Therefore, knowledge of its possibilities and indications for its application is the duty of every physician and a necessity for the widest range of the population” (Georgieva, 1988: 58). In this way, “the question of protecting the family and society from the birth of sick children is radically solved” (Tsoneva, 1986: 107).

As mentioned above, there were no available epistemic resources at that time that would allow for questioning the notion that disability is solely a misfortune to be eliminated. Across the literature – textbooks, monographs, scholarly articles, popular pamphlets – from the late socialist period, disability is invariably framed as misery, threat, suffering, and burden. As is typical in socialist rhetoric, military metaphors are frequently used: prophylaxis is described as a “fight”, and genetic counselling teams are referred to as “strategic units” (Tsoneva, Zlateva, Kolev, 1987: 124). The family and society, in turn, must be “protected” from “defective, crippled, and imperfect children” (Tsoneva, Genkova, 1976: 87). The emphasis on society and the quality of the population plays an important role in framing these practices. The economic burden of chronic illness and disability is consistently highlighted: “These children are not only a misfortune for the family but also a burden for society, which supports and must support special institutions for their care, rehabilitation, education, etc. All of this requires a lot of resources and care [...]. These hundreds of prevented misfortunes have a considerable effect on society as well” (Tsoneva, 1984a: 318-319).

In 1987 cystic fibrosis, a rare and incurable genetic disease affecting the exocrine glands but not cognitive abilities, was discussed in a collective work. During the socialist period – and in Bulgaria, long after its end – it was classified as a childhood disease due to the lack of appropriate care necessary for ensuring longer life expectancy. Regarding its incidence, statistics for 2024 indicate that approximately 280 people in Bulgaria have cystic fibrosis. It can be reasonably assumed that during late socialism, this number was smaller due to the even lower life expectancy and less effective case detection and diagnosis. However, the economic argument remained central:

In the overall assessment of the social problems associated with cystic fibrosis, the economic problems must be highlighted. The state provides large funds and there are substantial costs for the hospitalization, treatment, and social support of patients and their families. Naturally, [providing] care for affected individuals and families is an inescapable duty of our health service and society. The general strategy with regard to cystic fibrosis as a health, social, and moral-ethical problem should focus on limiting this disease in our population through the active and effective implementation of the methods of medico-genetic counselling and prenatal diagnosis. (Tsoneva, Zlateva, Kolev, 1987: 143).

Another objective indicator highlighted is infant mortality. As Maria Tsoneva (1984a: 318-319) notes, this is “an indicator of enormous health and social importance for every society” and prenatal diagnosis “guarantees [its] real reduction”. Doetz’s research on the history of genetic counselling in the GDR reveals a similar framing, emphasizing the “improvement of the nation’s health as well as a reduction in infant mortality” (Doetz, 2017: 406).

By the mid-1980s, alongside this argument, concerns about escalating genetic risk and the need for its more adequate management had begun to emerge as a rationale for intensifying “prophylactic interventions”:

Recently, there has been an increase in the relative proportion of malformations and other congenital diseases [...]. Mastering this pathology is an additional reserve for lowering infant mortality and reproductive failure. For this purpose, early detection of patients, provision of medical-genetic counselling, and application of prenatal diagnosis in future pregnancies in at-risk families are necessary.¹⁸

Such considerations are quite unambiguously reminiscent of the arguments traditionally advanced in favour of eugenic practices. It should be stressed that socialist rhetoric was relatively favourable towards the eugenic project in its basic aim of improving the health and “quality” of populations, although its capitalist “perversions” were always noted. In Maria Tsoneva’s writings, we see a largely positive view of “[eugenics] rational and scientific essence” which, she argues, can be developed “under conditions of social and economic equality of man” (Tsoneva, Genkova, 1976: 96). In her view, “there are dark pages in the history of eugenic teaching that have discredited the concept” (Tsoneva, 1984a: 317-318). However, they “cannot divert the attention of geneticists and sociologists from the search for a scientifically and morally sound regulation of these problems in the interests of the whole society and the individual” (Tsoneva, 1980: 34).

As Victoria Schmidt (2024: 10) aptly notes, “eugenic ideas softly passed through socialist filters”, whereas the same cannot be said for “the increasingly complex concept of disability”. In Bulgaria, for example, Vassil Prodanov – recognized as one of the country’s first bioethicists – unequivocally questioned the reproductive autonomy of persons with disabilities. More specifically, he argued that it should be subordinated to the collective interest:

¹⁸ SA – Sofia, F. 2243, Inv. 15, a. u. 8, p. 20, “Plan of the Department of Medical Genetics in Honour of the 13th Congress of the BCP”, 1986.

According to some data, about 20 percent of the people on Earth should not have offspring because they would be genetically disabled, which, in the long term, deteriorates the overall genetic stock of humanity. Once it is known that reproduction poses certain dangers, [such a person] should have a sufficient sense of responsibility to refuse to have genetically related children. This, in turn, requires that the corresponding biosocial value be actively asserted through public opinion and various mechanisms of personality education. (Prodanov, 1988: 237-238).

In such a general normative context, it is quite clear that the principle of non-directiveness could not guide genetic counselling. While it was officially endorsed in the WHO's 1969 report on genetic counselling, in Bulgaria – just as in the GDR, for example – “human geneticists [...] deviated from the report's suggestions [...] in their beliefs that counsellors should give a clear recommendation to their patients” (Doetz, 2017: 411). Bulgarian medical geneticists used the phrase “giving advice” (Tsoneva, 1976: 37; Lalchev, 1988: 27), and statements like “the final decision always belongs to the family” were rare (Lalchev, 1988: 27).

Maria Tsoneva formulated the basic dilemma as follows: “Does the physician in the genetic counselling office have the moral right to ‘suggest’ a certain solution to the patient, or should he limit himself to mere enlightenment?” (1984a: 312-313). What is special in this practice, she asserts, is that

the person who comes to the medico-genetic counselling room is not ill in the ordinary sense of the word, but is passing on a hereditary disease to his children [...]. This specificity of the task determines the great responsibility of the patient and the doctor towards the future individual [...]. The future child whose fate is being decided is not yet born, but society is indirectly involved in the decisions concerning its birth [...]. In solving these problems, both doctor and patient are responsible not only before their own consciences but also before society. (Tsoneva, 1984a: 312)

Maria Krachunova further emphasizes the possibility that medical information may not be adequately understood. However, her concern is not that this could undermine real informed choice, but rather – that the affected families might underestimate the risk. The counsellor should, therefore, do everything possible to ensure a genuine understanding of the information provided, namely “the essence hidden behind one or two numbers” (Krachunova, 1983: 119). This essence, in her view, is most effectively explicated through the notion of *cost* – the burden that will be borne upon the birth of a “sick offspring”. The cost

is “relatively low when the disorder is so severe that it ends in intrauterine or early infant death, or when the disease is long-lasting but only slightly impairs normal bodily functions. The burden will be the heaviest, and the cost the highest, in conditions that begin in childhood or young adulthood and lead rapidly to severe disability, combined with a relatively normal life expectancy. Such are, for example, oligophrenic conditions and schizophrenia” (Krachunova, 1983: 119). She then directly recommends that, depending on the family’s resources – such as education, intellectual level, and family climate – the counsellor should tailor the way this cost is presented, i.e., “present the same risk in different forms – emphasizing either the 75% chance of giving birth to a phenotypically healthy child [...] or the high genetic risk of 25%” (Krachunova, 1983: 120). This sharply contrasts with the pro-information approach mentioned in the first section, which values and respects the lived experience of disability, particularly in revealing its non-medical aspects. Conversely, Krachunova (1983: 121) explicitly stresses that it may be advisable to meet with families who have a patient with the same disease as the expected one, especially when there is a tendency “to underestimate the risk”.

It is important to note, however, that the rejection of the principle of non-directiveness in genetic counselling in the socialist context was additionally motivated by the socialist notion of the physician’s duty towards patients. As Tsoneva (1984a: 313) states, “In the conditions of socialist society, the doctor must assist the patient in choosing a solution.” In other contexts – for example, in psychiatry – the phrase often used was that the doctor “should not abandon” the patient to face their suffering alone.¹⁹ Undoubtedly, this attitude could be interpreted as paternalistic. At the same time, however, we should not forget that the radical shift towards individual autonomy in medical settings has been convincingly criticized for eroding good care and relationships of trust – precisely by abandoning the patient to their “right to choose” when they are too vulnerable, simply unable, or reluctant to exercise it (Mol, 2006; Conly, 2013). Or as Onora O’Neill (2003: 49) puts it, “When we are patients, we are not well placed to exercise any very demanding form of autonomy.” Unfortunately, in the case of socialist genetic counselling – which was so strongly motivated by ableist attitudes – this otherwise beneficial departure from radical autonomist approaches led to too easy justification of selective abortions.

¹⁹ See, for example, Dimitrova (2021) for an exploration of the negative effects of this type of attitude, particularly in relation to service users in the field of mental health.

Conclusion

As an expanding sociotechnical system, reproductive genetics cannot avoid centrifugal effects, i.e. shaping environments and subjectivities – a process that is also called more broadly “genetization” (Lippman, 1992). In this sense, successful technological networks and the actors circulating within them design “not only devices but societies within which these devices might be successfully located” (Bijker, Law, 1992: 12). In this paper, I have attempted to show the introduction of the tools of reproductive genetics into the late socialist context in Bulgaria – which, until this point, had been “technologically innocent” in this respect – and the efforts of experts to apply and affirm these tools as broadly as possible – or, literally, to design societies. This did not happen until 1989, not only because such processes unfold slowly but also due to insufficient resources – people, infrastructure, and equipment. The gradual cultivation of subjectivities embracing the selective package of reproductive genetics continued after the demise of socialism in Bulgaria, maintaining the basic tenets of socialist rhetoric while further benefiting from the intensifying processes of (neo-)liberal responsabilization (Dimitrova, 2012). Unfortunately, what remains unequivocally intact is the entirely positive framing of the “prophylaxis” of genetic diseases and disability through selective abortions. The continuing absence of disability activism, which challenges this strategic substitution, has led to the sheer normalization of the simplistic perception of selective abortion as a means of maximizing health, while portraying life with disability as a life not worth living.

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Between Ideals and Reality: Contraception in Socialist Yugoslavia

Abstract: *This study examines the evolution of contraception in Yugoslavia, focusing on the state's policies, medical perspectives, and societal attitudes toward birth control. It explores how government initiatives and prevailing cultural norms influenced the acceptance of contraceptives and identifies the factors that led to the population's hesitancy in adopting them. It draws upon sources from the Archives of Yugoslavia, the Croatian State Archives, and the Archives of Serbia, as well as selected periodicals and relevant medical, demographic, and historiographical literature.*

Keywords: *Yugoslavia; socialism; contraception; counselling centres; abortion; educational campaigns.*

Introduction

Despite the substantial body of literature on love, sexuality, and sex under state socialism (David, 1999; Frejka, 2008; Herzog, 2011; McLellan, 2011; Lišková, 2018; Lišková, Holubec, 2020; Kościańska, 2021; Kassabova, 2023; Kościańska, Kurimay, Lišková, Renkin, 2025), the topic of birth control has been largely overlooked or inconsistently examined in Yugoslav and post-Yugoslav historiography. This gap persists despite the availability of valuable sources, particularly documents from the Family Planning Council kept in the Archives of Yugoslavia. Additionally, relevant periodicals and demographic and medical literature provide further insights. Demographer Mirjana Rašević conducted a study on abortion, focusing on data collected through a representative survey conducted in gynaecological clinics in Belgrade in 1989 (Rašević, 1993). In her study, she explored her interlocutors' perspectives on contraception, offering insights into societal attitudes toward birth control. In her unpublished PhD thesis, Branka Bogdan discusses clinical trials and the development of IUDs in Yugoslavia (Bogdan,

2020). Anthropologist Rada Drezgić has examined reproductive policies, primarily focusing on public discourse surrounding declining fertility rates during the 1980s (Drezgić, 2010a; 2010b), while only sporadically addressing the introduction of the pill. In her overview of family planning policy in Yugoslavia, Nila Kapor-Stanulović briefly discusses contraception, highlighting its limited popularity among the general population (Kapor-Stanulović, 1999). Chiara Bonfiglioli and Sara Žerić have researched contraception counselling and local debates surrounding contraception, focusing on the Croatian towns of Karlovac and Varaždin (Bonfiglioli and Žerić, 2023). Aida Ličina Ramić centered her study on Bosnia and Herzegovina, highlighting the prevalence of abortion and contraceptive use in that Yugoslav republic (Ličina Ramić, 2024).

In this essay, I aim to address gaps in our understanding of contraception in socialist Yugoslavia by examining two important and intertwined themes: first, the political, medical, and societal attitudes toward contraceptives; and second, the promotion and market availability of contraception. Specifically, I will investigate how governmental policies and societal norms influenced the adoption of modern contraceptives and identify the factors that contributed to the population's reluctance to use them. Using historical research methodology – drawing on archival sources, medical journals, and newspaper articles – I intend to critically examine how contraception was understood, discussed, and distributed. I will provide a pan-Yugoslav perspective and show that practical implementation failed due to political, economic, and social factors, despite the progressive framework that guaranteed reproductive rights. While the laws were liberal and granted couples a high degree of autonomy over their reproductive choices, the state was neither willing nor sufficiently organized to ensure that these rights were fully implemented in daily life. Due to distribution issues, contraceptives were often difficult to obtain, especially outside urban centres. This inconsistency between policy and accessibility meant that many Yugoslavs, particularly in rural areas, lacked reliable contraceptive options, undermining the state's commitment to reproductive rights.

Sex education, when it did occur, was vague or moralistic rather than practical, leaving people without the necessary knowledge to use contraceptives effectively.¹ Everyone anticipated that someone else

¹ As early as the 1950s, public debate in Yugoslavia began to address gender relations, sexuality, and the sexual education of young people. Although elements of sexuality were included in the social and moral education programs introduced in primary and

would undertake this significant responsibility: parents expected teachers to provide it, teachers looked to doctors, and doctors held both teachers and parents responsible.² As a result, individuals, especially young people, had inadequate knowledge about contraception and reproductive health, contributing to a rise in teenage pregnancies.³ This discrepancy between policy and practice revealed the shortcomings of the Yugoslav family planning policy, which, despite its progressive appearance, lacked the crucial institutional support necessary to ensure citizens could exercise their proclaimed rights in practice.

Sex and Sexuality: The Birth of New Morality

The rapid pace of industrialisation and urbanisation, combined with the mass migration of young men and women to cities and their growing economic independence, encouraged a more open expression of emotions, the liberation of sexuality, and shifting attitudes toward extramarital relationships. For those who had come of age before the war and were shaped by a different era, the growing sexual freedom among youth was a source of considerable unease. Public discourse frequently stressed the belief that Yugoslav youth ‘lacked restraint in their sexual lives’, often engaging in intimate relationships not out of love or mutual respect, but primarily for ‘physiological experiences’.⁴ The sexual revolution, mirroring similar developments in Western Europe, further liberated female sexuality, making the ‘break with traditional sexual morality’ (Marković, 2007: 125) increasingly visible. These cultural shifts manifested in public spaces: fashion moved away from the conservative styles of the 1950s toward bolder, more provocative trends, and public displays of affection between couples became commonplace in streets and parks. Party leaders no longer condemned or denied youth

secondary schools in 1952–1953, there was little clarity, up until the early 1970s, on what sex education should entail. By 1963, a prevailing attitude emerged that would eventually undermine efforts to introduce comprehensive sex education: the decision that it should not exist as a standalone subject but instead be incorporated into existing curricula such as biology, sociology, hygiene, and social studies. However, this strategy failed to meet the genuine curiosity of young people (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022a).

² Archives of Yugoslavia (in further text AJ), 142/II – 293; Savetovanje „Odnos polova i vaspitanje“, Beograd 23 – 24. 10. 1968.

³ AJ, 142/II – S 274; Neautorizovane magnetofonske beleške sa sastanka Saveta savezne konferencije SSRNJ za planiranje porodice održanog 28. 10. 1985; AJ, 142/II – S 274; Rezime rasprave o radu službi za zdravstvenu zaštitu žena na planiranju porodice koja je održana 20. juna 1985. godine u Beogradu.

⁴ Anka Matić, „Seksualni odgoj omladine“, *Naša deca*, 11–12, 1955: 18.

sexuality as harshly as before; instead, it became a topic of open dialogue in counselling sessions and the press. The earlier onset of romantic and emotional lives prompted authorities to advocate for the introduction of sex education in schools and to work toward making modern contraceptives widely available, primarily through counselling centres and irrespective of marital status. Yet, despite these progressive changes, old prejudices remained. Health education campaigns aimed at preventing unwanted pregnancies were directed exclusively at women, inadvertently reinforcing the notion that unplanned pregnancy was solely a woman's 'problem' (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022a).

In addition to mass migration, the sexual revolution, and the influence of popular culture, the changing living conditions for Yugoslavs who came of age in the 1960s and 1970s contributed to a gradual 'demonopolization' of marriage. The memories of war and poverty that had shaped earlier generations began to fade, giving way to new life expectations – extended education, delayed financial independence, and expanded opportunities for socialising and leisure. The rise of discos, seaside holidays on the Adriatic, and a more vibrant youth culture encouraged young people to embrace the period between finishing school and marriage. Most people formed emotional relationships before the age of twenty. With the wider availability of contraception and the gradual liberalisation of abortion laws,⁵ premarital sexual relationships became increasingly socially acceptable, marking a period of near-complete sexual liberation. A more tolerant social climate emerged in which young people could engage in sexual activity before marriage without fear of social condemnation or serious consequences.⁶

By the mid-1960s and throughout the 1970s, premarital sex had become common, and young people were entering puberty and becoming sexually active at earlier ages. However, inexperience and lack of

⁵ While there was broad societal agreement that reducing the number of abortions required promoting contraception. According to the Regulation on Procedure for Permitted Abortion (1952), abortion could be legally performed in hospitals with the commission's approval if there were medical, moral-ethical, or socio-medical indications. In February 1960, a new Regulation on Conditions and Procedures for Permitting Abortions was enacted, making social indications a sufficient reason for abortion approval, and sex education, systematic educational initiatives were lacking. The Family Planning Resolution (1969) marked the onset of complete abortion liberalization and established a national initiative to ensure that every child was born wanted (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022a).

⁶ AJ, 142/II–658; Stenografske beleške sa seminara Porodica u savremenom jugoslovenskom društvu 12–16. 12. 1968.

adequate information often led many to neglect contraception entirely (Domicelej, 1982). Despite the growing openness and public demystification of sexuality, parents rarely discussed the topic in any meaningful depth with their children. From their perspective, young people were always 'too young' to discuss relationships between the sexes. When the subject did arise in Yugoslav households, it was typically limited to warnings about the 'dangers of sex', 'prostitution', or cautionary tales of girls who had been 'seduced and abandoned'. Rather than offering guidance and support, many parents resorted to instilling fear, often because they avoided or felt unequipped for open discussions about sexuality. As one reader of the journal *NIN* observed, 'They neither know nor have any idea about their children's sexual lives'.⁷ The few conversations about gender relations that did occur tended to focus on the harms of premarital sex, reducing sex education to 'moralising and intimidation'. Schools provided little more. Formal sex education was minimal, leaving young people to rely on superficial or incomplete information. As one 19-year-old girl from a study on youth sexuality conducted in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1967/68 noted: 'We are at the age when families are being formed, yet we still don't know enough about sexual relationships between men and women, conception issues, contraception, or sexually transmitted diseases' (Mandić, Erceg, 1977: 61; 65; 119-120).

Up until the very breakup of the country, Yugoslav society maintained an unusual coexistence of 'old' and 'new' moralities. These parallel worlds occasionally intersected but did not always intertwine. In larger cities, it was no longer uncommon for mothers to accompany their daughters to obtain contraceptives, or for young couples to seek consultations before engaging in sexual activity. In the more developed parts of Yugoslavia, tens of thousands of young women were eager to move beyond the restrained sexual norms of their mothers' generation. Yet, a strong undercurrent of conservatism and puritanism persisted. For instance, a 1978 survey found that 60% of adolescent girls in Skopje who sought abortions disapproved of premarital sex. When asked how they became sexually active, many replied that they had 'hoped for marriage but made a mistake' (Demerdžijev, Antonovski, 1978: 155). While conservative attitudes toward gender and sexuality were primarily preserved in rural, economically underdeveloped regions – particularly in Bosnia, parts of Macedonia, Montenegro, southern Serbia, and Kosovo – uncertainty about sexual freedom was also evident among

⁷ „Tabu-tema“, *NIN*, 4. 2. 1979.

segments of the urban student population. This confusion was likely exacerbated by the contradictory messages young people received: while liberal, even pornographic, content was readily available in the media, conversations about sex, whether at home or in school, were still often marked by discomfort, shame, or outright embarrassment.⁸

In cases of unplanned pregnancy, societal pressure often pushed unmarried girls and women toward abortion, whether legal or illegal. Pregnant high school girls were routinely expelled ‘in the name of preserving morality’, and doctors faced pressure to perform abortions for social reasons, even for women who were already in their fifth month of pregnancy.⁹ It became increasingly clear that a woman’s level of education did not necessarily equate to adequate – or even basic – knowledge of reproductive health. As a result, even medical students, teachers, and high school girls sometimes sought abortions during the later stages of pregnancy (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2019a). Many concealed their unwanted pregnancies, naively hoping the issue would somehow resolve itself. ‘They come to us after returning from vacations’, explained Mira Đorđević, a social worker on the abortion commission in Belgrade, in an interview with *NIN*. ‘Most girls come from rural areas to attend high school, university, or vocational courses. Here, they quickly meet people. The big city they once dreamed of soon overwhelms them and leaves them behind. Then, when it’s already too late, they come to us. And us? We feel helpless if we strictly follow regulations and turn them away. In that case, they have no choice but to turn to unqualified individuals or pay up to 20,000 dinars for an abortion performed privately by a doctor.’¹⁰ Despite the evident failure of both parents and schools in providing adequate sex education and the clear need for support, secret abortions were often seen as the only socially acceptable solution. Even though attitudes toward premarital sex had liberalized to some degree, strong patriarchal norms continued to shape the social landscape. Fear of parental reaction was one of the main reasons young women delayed seeking legal abortion services (Šukarov, Lazarov, Stankovski, Čurčijev, Kalamas, 1972). In some parts of the country, the level of intolerance was so severe that cases of

⁸ „Otvrdnjavanje srca“, *NIN*, 21. 1. 1979.

⁹ *AJ*, 142/II–623; *Savetovanje o problemima prekida trudnoće i kontracepcije* (1963).

¹⁰ „Šta mislite o abortusu“, *NIN*, 28. 7. 1963.

murder and suicide due to unwanted pregnancies were reported in Montenegro as late as the early 1970s.¹¹

Contraception: Navigating Ideals and Reality

Contraception as a primary means of preventing unwanted pregnancies began to enter public discourse in Yugoslavia in the early 1950s, primarily within gynaecological circles and among government officials. This relatively open approach was considered liberal by European standards at the time, especially when compared to countries like France and Italy, where even medical professionals were often hesitant to discuss contraception (Herzog, 2011). Thanks to the efforts of Dr. Franc Novak, the first contraceptives were introduced in Yugoslavia in the early 1950s. During a three-month study visit to Great Britain and the USA, he familiarized himself with the most advanced contraceptives of the time. Demonstrating both initiative and personal commitment, he purchased several complete sets of diaphragms – the most effective form of contraception available then – at his own expense and brought them back to Yugoslavia (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b). To engage Yugoslav authorities in the production and distribution of contraceptives, Dr. Novak delivered one set to the Federal Ministry of Industry, another to Franc Leskošek, the Minister of Industry of the People's Republic of Slovenia, and a third to the rubber factory *Sava*. Both ministries expressed interest in supporting the initiative, and the management of *Sava* pledged to begin production as soon as they could procure the necessary springs from Switzerland and Sweden (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b). In the meantime, Novak acquired several kilograms of steel spiral springs, or steel rims for the diaphragms (Petrić, 1981), which temporarily kick-started production. However, it soon became evident that the rubber processing machines were outdated and unsuitable for manufacturing diaphragms. New machines were purchased, enabling diaphragm production in Yugoslavia to begin in 1954. Although assessments at the time claimed that the diaphragms produced in Kranj 'do not lag behind' their more expensive foreign counterparts,¹² their overall quality remained somewhat inferior (Mojić, Kokić, 1966). Initially, production levels were sufficient to meet the needs of the Slovenian market, and the newspaper *Borba* reported that output could be

¹¹ AJ, 142/II–391; Magnetofonske beleške sa sednice Saveznog saveta za planiranje porodice održane 18. 2. 1972.

¹² Croatian State Archives (in further text HDA), 1234 – 17 – 195; Uspesi i teškoće savetovališta za kontracepciju

increased ‘tenfold’ if demand rose.¹³ However, the *Sava* factory – the sole manufacturer of diaphragms in Yugoslavia – faced significant technical challenges. Due to outdated and heavily worn machinery, approximately 60% of the material was lost during production, leading to reduced output and increased costs. In addition to these technical inefficiencies, the supply chain was poorly coordinated, resulting in a paradoxical surplus: by 1958, the factory’s warehouse contained more than 35,000 diaphragms, both domestically produced and imported.

Despite the natural deterioration and deformation of rubber over time, the factory opted to distribute older, lower-quality diaphragm models to contraceptive counselling centres, aiming to offload outdated stock in which it had already invested considerable resources.¹⁴ Although the initial quality of domestically produced diaphragms was substandard, they were nonetheless regarded as the most reliable contraceptive available. In both public perception and some medical circles, diaphragms became closely associated with contraception.¹⁵ Concerned that endorsing less reliable chemical alternatives might weaken broader contraceptive efforts, many physicians continued to recommend diaphragms well into the early 1960s (Novak, Šegedin, Krofl, 1965), despite their unpopularity ‘due to overly complicated application and aesthetic reasons’ (Andolšek, Hren, Kralj, 1964: 46).

Despite early efforts to introduce contraceptives, scepticism toward their use persisted within Yugoslav medical circles for a considerable time. While gynaecologists generally agreed that ‘contraception should not be included in the concept of illegal abortion’ (Novak, 1950: 359) when discussing the conditions under which abortion might be permissible, the prevailing attitudes at the Second Gynaecological Congress in 1953 were notably conservative. Contraception was even described as a ‘depopulation measure’,¹⁶ reflecting deep-rooted anxieties about its impact on demographic trends. In contrast, Dr. Franc Novak, head of the Ljubljana Gynaecological Clinic and one of the most vocal and consistent advocates for the affirmation of contraception in Yugoslavia, held a markedly different view. He argued that contraceptives

¹³ „Nauka ima bolja sredstva od veštačkog abortusa“, *Borba*, 14. 6. 1956.

¹⁴ HDA, 1234 – 17 – 195; Uspesi i teškoće savetovaništva za kontracepciju.

¹⁵ „Sprečavanje neželjene trudnoće – jedna od najvažnijih mera za zaštitu ženinog zdravlja“, *Politika*, 21. 3. 1959.

¹⁶ AJ, 142/II–417. F. Novak, L. Andolšek, M. Kuštrin, I. Veter, Prikaz razvoja odnosa do celokupne problematike planiranja porodice u medicinskim krugovima. Savetovanje o izgradnji društvenih stavova o populacionoj politici u Jugoslaviji (1973).

should not be blamed for declining birth rates or reduced population growth. 'Families generally want two or three children,' he wrote, adding that contraception 'will only serve to replace abortion, and nothing more'. Dr. Novak also took what was, at the time, considered highly liberal positions on premarital sex and access to contraception. He opposed restricting contraceptive distribution to married couples, insisting instead that contraceptives 'should be made available to all women who desire them'. He rejected the notion that such accessibility would lead to the moral decline of young women, arguing that, by the same logic, condom sales should also be prohibited. For Novak, contraception was not only a means of preventing unwanted pregnancies, but also a way to strengthen marital relationships and relieve women of the constant fear of unintended conception.¹⁷ Although modern contraceptives remained largely inaccessible to most Yugoslav women in the early 1950s, by 1952, a limited number of patients at the Ljubljana Gynaecological Clinic were able to obtain imported diaphragms and chemical pastes.¹⁸ Two years later, the clinic began testing contraceptives following international standards, reflecting concerns that poor product quality could undermine public trust and hinder efforts to promote modern birth control.¹⁹

The efforts and initiatives of Yugoslav gynaecologists to promote contraception received an institutional framework in 1955 with the establishment of counselling centres at the Central Gynaecological Dispensary in Ljubljana, and shortly after at clinics in Belgrade, Zagreb, Sarajevo, Priština, and Skopje (1955–1957). These centres employed various approaches to engage with women, offering guidance on reproductive health and family planning. However, patients often found it difficult to discuss sensitive topics, such as the frequency of sexual intercourse, experiences of frigidity, or the reasons behind seeking an abortion, in the presence of a third party, even when that person was a nurse. Although it was widely acknowledged that women preferred privacy in such consultations, many counselling centres continued to con-

¹⁷ AJ, 142/II–623; Dr Franc Novak, *Abortus i kontracepcija*.

¹⁸ AJ, 142/II–417. F. Novak, L. Andolšek, M. Kuštrin, I. Veter, *Prikaz razvoja odnosa do celokupne problematike planiranja porodice u medicinskim krugovima. Savetovanje o izgradnji društvenih stavova o populacionoj politici u Jugoslaviji* (1973).

¹⁹ AJ, 142/II–417. A. Milojković, G. Žarković, M. Džumhur, *Historijat liberalizacije pobačaja u Jugoslaviji. Savetovanje o izgradnji društvenih stavova o populacionoj politici u Jugoslaviji* (1973).

duct interviews, data collection, and medical examinations in the presence of administrative personnel. In contrast, some centres adopted more discreet practices, separating the collection of personal information from the medical examination itself. This allowed women to speak privately with a physician during consultations, fostering a greater sense of trust and confidentiality.²⁰

As the social and political climate began to change, public discourse around birth planning grew increasingly prominent, with the press playing a significant role in raising awareness. This broader cultural change, combined with the remarkable dedication of several physicians – Franc Novak, Bogdan Tekavčić, Aleksandar Milojković, Stanislav Sabo, Bosa Milošević, and Angelina Mojić – contributed to a gradual transformation in the attitudes of many gynaecologists. The initial resistance, strongly expressed at the 1953 Gynaecological Congress, began diminishing. Although the network of counselling centres gradually expanded, it remained largely confined to urban areas, leaving couples in rural regions with limited access to information about contraceptive options. Throughout the 1950s and early 1960s, these centres primarily distributed diaphragms and a range of chemical contraceptives, many of which were considered insufficiently reliable due to the limited selection available in Yugoslavia at the time. Despite the formal recognition of contraception as a legitimate prophylactic method at the Third Gynaecological Congress, in practice, its promotion remained inconsistent. Only several physicians possessed both the enthusiasm and the necessary expertise to confidently recommend and support its use (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b). The pharmaceutical industry displayed even greater scepticism and inertia toward contraception. During the heated public and professional debates surrounding the further liberalisation of abortion law in 1958, none of the three pharmaceutical factories based in Belgrade expressed any interest in incorporating contraceptive products into their manufacturing programs.²¹

Broader efforts to integrate contraception into the healthcare system as a routine preventive measure gained momentum following a conference held in May 1958 in Belgrade. The Federal Institute for Public Health and the Secretariat for Public Health of the Federal Executive Council organized the event. For three days, gynaecologists, social

²⁰ HDA, 1234 – 17 – 195; Uspesi i teškoće savetovališta za kontracepciju.

²¹ „Sredstva za kontracepciju nisu u planu. Izjave predstavnika preduzeća za proizvodnju lekova u Beogradu i Zemunu“, *Večernje novosti*, 3. 4. 1958.

workers, and representatives from the Women's Societies of Yugoslavia, the Trade Union Association, the Red Cross, and other organisations convened to discuss the role of contraception in public health. They reached a consensus that contraceptives should be accessible to all women. In response, participants advocated for the establishment of a joint body to address not only contraception, but also sex education, marriage counselling, and the rising number of abortions. They also urged federal authorities to 'find a way' to reduce the cost of contraceptives to make them more affordable and to ensure that all pharmacies maintain an adequate supply.²²

Despite the decision made at the Federal Conference (1958), contraception did not become an integral part of the healthcare system.²³ Following the initial success in promoting modern contraceptives between 1958 and 1960, contraception gradually faded from the public health agenda. While substantial financial resources were directed toward abortion services, significantly less was invested in public education and the promotion of contraception. Moreover, contraception was not recognized as an integral part of preventive care but was instead treated as a 'private matter of the individual'.²⁴ In most healthcare institutions, it remained only nominally included in official work programs, lacking the institutional commitment and financial support necessary for genuine implementation.²⁵

Resistance to contraception remained difficult to overcome. Some gynaecologists continued to oppose its use,²⁶ and although insured individuals were entitled to receive contraceptives by prescription, they still had to pay for them out of pocket.²⁷ The situation deteriorated further following the 1961 shift to a self-financing model for healthcare institutions, which led to the closure of numerous counselling centres under the pretext of austerity measures. In Belgrade, the restructuring of healthcare services saw many counselling centres integrated into gynaecological dispensaries, causing them to lose their status as independent preventive health institutions. This created confusion among women, many of whom no longer knew where or to whom

²² AJ, 142/II–623; Zaključci sa savetovanja po pitanju kontracepcije (7–9.5. 1958).

²³ AJ, 672–323; Materijal za savetovanje „O problemima prekida trudnoće i kontracepcije“ (1963).

²⁴ „Dilema se zove – željeno ili neželjeno materinstvo“, *Borba*, 13. 11. 1963.

²⁵ „Kontracepcija – najefikasniji metod za sprečavanje neželjene trudnoće“, *Politika*, 20. 11. 1963.

²⁶ „Zašto se kontracepcija teško prihvaća“, *Vjesnik*, 24. 11. 1960.

²⁷ „Savez ženskih društava Srbije protiv legalizacije abortusa“, *Borba*, 18. 4. 1958.

they could turn for guidance.²⁸ Doctors attributed the closure of these centres to inadequate reimbursement from Social Insurance, which left institutions struggling with financial deficits (Savetovanje, 1963). However, the issue was not purely financial. A lack of motivation among healthcare providers also played a role; even doctors working in health centres within factories showed little interest in promoting contraception. An exception to this trend was the Zagreb-based factory *Rade Končar*, which took a proactive approach by educating both male and female employees about contraception and distributing contraceptives free of charge. These efforts proved effective, leading to a measurable decline in the number of abortions among its female workforce.²⁹

Paradoxically, even by the mid-1960s, state institutions continued to inadvertently favour abortion over contraception as a method of birth control. Abortions were free of charge, making them more accessible than condoms, which remained a paid item (Zbornik, 1962). In some cases, branches of social insurance – particularly in Bosnia and Herzegovina – were even willing to cover women’s travel expenses to the nearest clinic, as well as the full cost of the procedure, while refusing to fund contraceptives. This was justified by the claim that contraceptives were not classified as medication. The lack of funding for educational materials such as brochures, leaflets, instructional guides, and films further hindered efforts to promote contraceptives. Although numerous consultations and discussions were organized to address the issue, the authorities effectively ignored what was increasingly being described as an ‘epidemic of abortions’ – a growing public health concern. The responsibility for educating the public fell disproportionately on a small group of dedicated individuals, mainly gynaecologists and members of mass organizations. In practice, most couples learned about family planning through informal means, with formal education on the topic being rare, limited to occasional school lessons or isolated community programs. Meanwhile, the rising influence of mass media remained largely untapped. In 1967, for instance, the Zagreb-based *Ris* factory, the sole manufacturer of condoms in Yugoslavia, spent a full year unsuccessfully attempting to secure television advertising space. Although articles about sex and sexuality became more common in Yugoslav newspapers from the mid-1960s onward, they typically lacked any meaningful educational content (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b).

²⁸ AJ, 142/II–623; Pismo Latinke Perović dr Angelini Mojić (1963).

²⁹ AJ, 672–323; Materijali za savetovanje „O problemima trudnoće i kontracepcije“ (1963); „Uredba nije dovoljna“, *VUS*, 18. 12. 1963.

Over time, it became clear that even the sexual revolution could not fully overcome deeply rooted prejudices. While relationships between the sexes grew increasingly open, and topics like sex and love were no longer taboo, many couples still refrained from using contraceptives. A widespread belief persisted that contraception was solely a woman's responsibility – a perception reinforced by the fact that contraceptive services were almost exclusively offered within women's healthcare institutions.³⁰ 'Contraception has been a complete failure in our country', reported the press. 'Those who worked hardest to promote it can claim, at best, that open resistance to this form of prevention has diminished.'³¹ Even in Slovenia, where efforts to promote contraceptive use were most intensive, up to three-quarters of couples relied on coitus interruptus, believing it to be a reliable method (Savetovanje, 1963). Although the Ris factory offered condoms in three-pack boxes branded with the slogan 'Ris No Risk',³² purchasing condoms was often a source of discomfort for men, leading to awkward or even comical situations. 'A pharmacist can usually recognize a man who's there to buy condoms', noted Dr. Nikica Dežulović at a 1963 conference, 'because he lets everyone else go ahead of him, leaving the pharmacist no choice but to hand him the original box without asking anything' (Savetovanje, 1963: 141).

Women, too, often held conservative views toward contraception. Many were reluctant to visit gynaecological clinics, frequently citing a lack of time or money – even for the most affordable contraceptives. A combination of patriarchal values, limited health education, and persistent resistance to modern birth control (including from some healthcare professionals) contributed to a widespread sense of shame and hesitation around seeking contraceptive care. Women also received little to no support from their partners. Men showed minimal interest in issues of unplanned pregnancy or its prevention and often expressed negative attitudes toward contraceptives. As in Britain, Italy, and France during the 1960s and early 1970s, many men feared that contraception would empower women with greater sexual freedom (Herzog, 2014). As a result, contraception was frequently associated with promiscuity, and any visit to a clinic was regarded with suspicion. This atmosphere of stigma extended even to educational materials. Women were only willing to purchase brochures about contraception, sold in workplaces – if no men

³⁰ AJ, 672–323; Angelina Mojić, Olivera Kokić, Priručnik za kontracepciju.

³¹ „Pobačaji rastu, kontracepcija propala“, Večernje novosti, 23. 11. 1963.

³² „Prezervativi“, *Student*, 26.11.1968.

were present. One telling incident underscored the depth of patriarchal control: at one workplace, a man asked the bookseller for a list of women who had bought the brochure, remarking, ‘Let’s see who they are’.³³ Given these social pressures, it is unsurprising that in 1962, only 0.75% of women of reproductive age sought advice from a clinic (Dobrivojević, 2016).

Doctors believed the failure to promote contraception effectively could be summarized in a single sentence: ‘No effort, either from the healthcare services or from social organisations, was carried out systematically, persistently, or with proper planning’ (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b: 113). The promotion of contraception in Yugoslavia predominantly depended on individual initiatives rather than a structured educational system. For instance, in Livno, the ‘Napredna žena’ society, with the active involvement of Dr. Keitner, organized three contraception lectures attended by over 150 women. However, these efforts ceased after his death. Similarly, in Sanski Most, the Women’s Counselling Centre, led by Dr. Dušica Damjanović, provided contraception education through organized lectures, but its activities ended after her departure (Ličina Ramič, 2024). Both cases serve as striking examples of the absence of a systemic educational framework for the promotion of contraception, with initiatives relying heavily on the commitment of individual professionals rather than institutional support. Overburdened gynaecologists prioritized treating illness over preventive work, leaving minimal time or energy for contraception advocacy. Additionally, there were no structured initiatives to improve the knowledge of medical professionals themselves. As a result, even by the mid-1960s, many doctors and nurses in Yugoslav hospitals and clinics remained unaware of the significance of contraception for reproductive health. Although it was increasingly recognized that both partners should be involved in contraceptive decisions, educational campaigns remained exclusively targeted at women, reinforcing the outdated notion that pregnancy – and its prevention – was solely a woman’s concern (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b). The methods used to promote contraception were also poorly thought out. Most citizens were unaware of the existence or activities of the Federal Council for Family Planning,³⁴ and gynaecologists frequently noted that the ‘communication system on

³³ „Pobačaj – najteži napad na ženu“, *Dnevnik*, 10. 5. 1964.

³⁴ AJ, 142/II–279; Stenografske beleške sa I sednice Saveznog saveta za planiranje porodice (13. 7. 1967).

these issues didn't function well if it existed at all'.³⁵ Moreover, understanding scientific lectures or brochures required a level of literacy and basic education that many, particularly among the female workforce, lacked. The experience of the gynaecological clinic at Rijeka's Metallographic factory illustrated this problem: general lectures on contraception had little impact, and it became clear that women needed to be addressed individually, in the workers' gynaecological clinic (Kogoj-Bakić, Randić, 1972). A similar conclusion was drawn at another Croatian factory, where boxes of contraceptives were discreetly placed in a corridor. Workers responded positively to this anonymous access, feeling more comfortable taking contraceptives without being seen by colleagues or doctors. The results were immediate and measurable – the number of work absences due to abortion declined significantly the following year.³⁶

A persistent shortage of contraceptives posed a major obstacle, as the variety of domestically produced options was both limited and inadequate to meet the population's needs.³⁷ There was no planned or consistent production of contraceptives, and reliable products were largely unavailable until the mid-1960s (Savetovanje, 1963). Distribution was uneven across regions: while some areas faced shortages of the most in-demand items, others experienced surpluses. This inefficient supply system contributed to declining demand, creating a self-reinforcing cycle that proved difficult to break.³⁸ The failure to promote contraception was also partly the result of misguided state propaganda. Though newspapers, brochures, and leaflets promised women access to a variety of modern contraceptives, in reality, clinics typically offered only diaphragms and gel pastes.³⁹ This gap between public messaging and actual services fuelled growing public scepticism. Distrust in modern contraceptives was further deepened by the behaviour of certain

³⁵ AJ, 142/II–417; A. Džumhur, M. Žarković G, Džumhur S. M, „Upliv različitih metoda komunikacije na korištenje usluga planiranja porodice u zdravstvenim ustanovama“. Savetovanje o izgradnji društvenih stavova o populacionoj politici. Beograd, 1973.

³⁶ AJ, 142/II–293; Stenografske beleške sa zajedničke sednice Sekretarijata (19. 3. 1968).

³⁷ AJ, 672–323; Materijali za savetovanje „O problemima trudnoće i kontracepcije“ (1963).

³⁸ AJ, 142/II–626; Problemi kontracepcije, prekida trudnoće i obrazovno-vaspitanog rada sa područja odnosa među polovima (1965).

³⁹ AJ, 142/II–623; Stenografske beleške sa sastanka održanog u Konferenciji za društvenu aktivnost žena Jugoslavije u vezi sa pripremom Savetovanja (1963).

pharmaceutical companies, which, by compromising product quality, undermined the fragile trust that had been built among users. These issues collectively hindered progress toward establishing contraception as a reliable and accepted component of reproductive healthcare (Savetovanje, 1963).

Modern Medicine vs Traditional Resistance

Raw materials for the production of contraceptive pills were procured relatively swiftly – by early 1964, placing Yugoslavia just three years behind the United States, where *Enovid*, the first oral contraceptive, had been introduced in 1960 (Blackman, 2013). In February of that year, a meeting of medical professionals was held at the Gynaecology and Obstetrics Clinic in Zagreb, where it was decided that the use of oral contraceptives should be approached with ‘caution’ and that their prescription would be restricted to gynaecologists.⁴⁰ As in Western European countries (Herzog, 2011), medical opinion on the pill was sharply divided. Some doctors expressed strong scepticism, citing concerns over long-term hormone use and its impact on reproductive health. Some gynaecologists openly criticized the pill at professional conferences, arguing it posed a health risk.⁴¹ Others, while more supportive, emphasized through the press that oral contraceptives should be taken strictly under specialist supervision, as they could cause ‘minor functional disorders’ in some women.⁴² Supporters of the pill, however, inadvertently repeated earlier mistakes made with diaphragms. Many gynaecologists began prescribing the pill indiscriminately, based on personal preference rather than clinical assessment. Meanwhile, the pharmaceutical industry began shifting its priorities, discontinuing other contraceptive products to focus on oral contraceptives.⁴³ Despite these developments, general practitioners were not permitted to prescribe the pill for a full decade – until 1973 – due to concerns about their lack of expertise (Vađić, 1975). In some republics, the number of gynaecologists and gynaecological clinics was woefully inadequate; for example, Bosnia and Herzegovina had only 90 specialists in 1967, most

⁴⁰ AJ, 672–76; Br. 444/101 od 3. 11. 1967.

⁴¹ AJ, 142/II–294; Neke aktivnosti službe planiranja porodice.

⁴² „Pobačaj – poslednje sredstvo“, *Večernje novosti*, 4. 3. 1965.

⁴³ AJ, 142/II–626; Problemi kontracepcije, prekida trudnoće i obrazovno-vaspitnog rada sa područja odnosa među polovima (1965).

of whom were concentrated in Sarajevo.⁴⁴ This overly cautious and centralised approach ultimately did more harm than good. By marginalising and excluding general practitioners from actively promoting contraception, everyone suffered the consequences: women found it more convenient to visit health centres instead of specialised clinics; gynaecologists, already facing heavy workloads, had their responsibilities further compounded; and the state, year after year, squandered vast resources – both human and material – on performing abortions and addressing their health consequences. In the end, the opportunity to establish the pill as the cornerstone of birth control, and to reduce reliance on abortion, was missed.

Alongside the pill, intrauterine contraception also began to be implemented in Yugoslavia, initially in Slovenia and later in other republics. The first IUDs were distributed through the Red Cross, and soon after, at the initiative of Bosa Milošević from the Belgrade Gynaecological Clinic, the Galenika factory began producing the ‘Beospir’ (Antonovski, 1976-1977). This device was based on the Margulies Spiral, whose looped, circular design was believed to reduce the likelihood of displacement or expulsion from the uterus (Bogdan, 2019). However, in 1964 and 1965, the pharmaceutical industry faced significant challenges in the production of certain contraceptives. Disruptions in the import of raw materials and foreign contraceptives inevitably impacted users. Profit-driven manufacturers prioritized exports, leading the ‘Ris’ factory to sign export contracts for condoms, thereby leaving the domestic market underserved.⁴⁵ Over time, however, the availability of contraceptives in Yugoslav pharmacies improved. By 1969, twelve contraceptive products were available on the market.⁴⁶ Still, fluctuations in product quality and periodic shortages caused by poor distribution led many women to abandon contraception altogether. Although the Federal Institute for Health Insurance’s 1963 decision to classify contraceptives under the same conditions as medications was intended to incentivize improvements in quality and distribution, low domestic demand made contraceptive production largely unprofitable (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2019b). Even the *Sava* factory, once a pioneer in the field, eventually ceased production of diaphragms.⁴⁷

⁴⁴ „Pobačaja sve više“, *Politika*, 12. 7. 1967.

⁴⁵ „Zaključak: sredstva i propaganda“, *Večernje novosti*, 8. 3. 1965.

⁴⁶ „Istina o seksu – školski predmet“, *Borba*, 6. 6. 1969.

⁴⁷ AJ, 142/II–626; Sastanak grupe za kontracepcijska sredstva (20. 4. 1966).

Despite a broad consensus that reducing unwanted pregnancies – and consequently abortions – depended on education and the expansion of preventive measures such as comprehensive sex education, a wider network of healthcare institutions, improved access to contraception, and the establishment of counselling services, the practical implementation of these strategies remained slow and inefficient. Although contraception was rarely openly discussed, its promotion was, in some ways, impeded by the medical community itself. Negative attitudes among certain physicians toward specific contraceptives proved difficult to overcome. In smaller communities, especially, the (un)popularity of medical contraception was likely influenced by the fact that many healthcare workers' attitudes toward birth control mirrored those of the population they were meant to educate.⁴⁸ Even by the mid-1970s, some doctors continued to oppose contraception, whether due to being overworked and unmotivated to engage in educational outreach, influenced by religious or pronatalist beliefs, or simply unaware of the benefits of modern contraceptives and viewing abortion as the 'easier option'.⁴⁹ Resistance was particularly pronounced in rural areas, where some medical professionals expressed scepticism toward women who did not wish to have many children (Dobrivojević, 2018).

The limited success of state efforts in health education was reflected in a fertility and family planning survey conducted by the Centre for Demographic Research in November 1970. For the first time, data on contraceptive effectiveness were collected from a representative sample (Rašević, 1975), with findings and analysis primarily published in the journal *Stanovništvo (Population)*. According to the survey, 55.9% of married women aged 15 to 49 used some form of contraception, including the traditional and less reliable method of *coitus interruptus*. Usage rates varied significantly across republics, with the highest in Croatia (68.2%) and the lowest in Kosovo (15.1%). Below the national average were Bosnia and Herzegovina (48.6%), Macedonia (42.3%), and Montenegro (41.5%). The majority of women relied on *coitus interruptus* (39%), while only 3.6% used the pill, and a mere 1% used intrauterine devices (Sentić, 1974-1975). Contraceptive use among adolescents remained inadequate (Beluhan, Benc, Štampar,

⁴⁸ AJ, 142/II-417; Dubravka Štampar, *Značajke planiranja obitelji u SR Hrvatskoj. Savetovanje o izgradnji društvenih stavova o populacionoj politici* (1973).

⁴⁹ AJ, 142/II-279; Stenografske beleške sa I sednice Saveznog saveta za planiranje porodice (13. 7. 1967).

Trenc, 1973-1974). Despite widespread awareness – most women reported having heard of contraceptives (Sentić, 1976-1977) – abortion persisted as the dominant method of family planning until the dissolution of the state.

Data from Serbia reveal that most contraceptive users were over the age of 30. Professor Berislav Berić, a respected gynaecologist, observed that many couples turned to contraception only after undergoing multiple abortions, often when they felt they had no other viable options.⁵⁰ It remains difficult to determine definitively why contraception was consistently neglected in favour of abortion over such an extended period. Contributing factors likely included a general disregard for health risks, a failure to anticipate the consequences of unwanted pregnancies, the inconsistent and often inadequate availability of contraceptives, the absence of systematic education, and the persistence of traditional beliefs. Moreover, the perception of abortion as an effective solution that required no male involvement probably reinforced this trend (Petchesky, 1990; Rašević, 1999).

Although counselling centres were established as free services under the 1970 Law on Mandatory Health Care, the cost of contraceptives varied across the Yugoslav republics. In some regions, contraceptives were provided entirely free of charge, while in others, women were required to contribute to the cost, either through co-payment similar to that for prescription medications or by covering the full price themselves. A 1973 survey conducted across 739 healthcare institutions in Yugoslavia (with 360 responses, representing 48.7% of the total) highlighted both the limited availability of contraceptives and the inadequate financial support for reproductive health services. Social insurance covered only 48% of the planned budget for contraceptives, leaving many women to navigate the situation on their own. As a result, 25.1% of women received contraceptives free of charge from doctors who had sourced them from various companies, while 26.9% paid out of pocket. Usage rates differed significantly among republics: Slovenia reported the highest number of contraceptive users, with 104.7 users per 1,000 women, while Kosovo recorded the lowest rate at just 17.3 users per 1,000 women (Dobrivojević, 2018).

By the mid-1970s, pills were available by prescription from general practitioners. Other forms of contraception – excluding intrauterine devices (which required insertion by a gynaecologist) – could be freely

⁵⁰ Archives of Serbia (AS), Đ 75 – 164; Stenografske beleške sa sednice Konferencije žena Srbije održane 29.3. 1968 sa početkom u 9h.

obtained at pharmacies. Condoms were also widely accessible and could be purchased at newsstands and other stores.⁵¹ However, supply issues persisted, largely due to the low pricing of contraceptives and shortages of raw materials. Prices had remained unchanged for over a decade, resulting in products like EMCO foam being sold for merely a quarter of their production value. Despite growing demand, factories struggled to scale up production, hindered by a lack of foreign currency needed to import essential equipment and materials. The production of intrauterine devices was particularly unprofitable, with only around 13,000 units used across Yugoslavia in 1978. Facing mounting losses, an unprofitable production model, and limited access to foreign currency, the pharmaceutical industry began reducing – and in some cases, halting – contraceptive production altogether.⁵² The worsening economic crisis only exacerbated these problems, leading to widespread shortages on the market. Fearing that such instability could undermine the already limited progress in promoting contraceptive use, gynaecologists and the Federal Council for Family Planning urged the authorities to prioritize contraceptives by placing them on the Federal Drug Commission's list of essential items.⁵³

Conclusion

Experts from various disciplines – primarily doctors and demographers – conducted numerous studies to understand the low uptake of contraceptives and the continued prevalence of abortion in Yugoslavia. A combination of low awareness and widespread misconceptions led many Yugoslav women to neglect their reproductive health. However, education levels and economic status played a significant role in shaping attitudes toward contraception. Couples in Slovenia were the most likely to adopt modern birth control, while those in Kosovo showed the lowest rates of usage. Often, women deferred the responsibility for contraception to their partners, driven by a combination of ignorance, fear of potential side effects, and a cultural concern that taking the initiative in such matters might make them appear promiscuous. Although awareness of the health risks associated with abortion was growing, a study

⁵¹ AJ, 142/II–A 837; *Socijalni apsekti planiranja porodice u Jugoslaviji* (1974).

⁵² AJ, 142/II–A 803; *Pregled proizvodnje i potrošnje kontraceptiva* (1975).

⁵³ AJ, 142/II–A 831; Lidija Andolšek, *Dosadašnja saznanja i stavovi u pogledu regulisanja fertiliteta sa medicinskog aspekta*; AJ, 142/II–A 831; *Savetovanje: Aktuelna pitanja zdravstvenog aspekta ustavnog prava čoveka da slobodno odlučuje o rađanju dece* (26. 6. 1980).

conducted in Novi Sad revealed that many couples still considered it a highly 'effective' form of family planning. Negative experiences with contraceptives – whether firsthand or anecdotal – were frequently generalised, contributing to the perception that contraceptives were overly complicated and harmful to health. Paradoxically, Yugoslav women often expressed more concern about the imagined dangers of contraception than the very real health risks posed by repeated abortions (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2022b). Even on the eve of the country's dissolution, the level of misinformation and prejudice surrounding contraception remained alarmingly high (Dobrivojević Tomić, 2019b). While the introduction of the pill – a method hailed by *The Economist* as one of the seven modern wonders of the world (Blackman, 2013: 380) – revolutionized sexual roles and behaviour in Western countries (Burgnard, 2015), it was met with scepticism in Yugoslavia. Only one in ten women could correctly identify their fertile days, one-third believed *coitus interruptus* was a reliable method, and the majority lacked a basic understanding of how the pill or intrauterine devices functioned. The depth of misunderstanding is starkly illustrated by responses from a study conducted by Mirjana Rašević. A few representative examples include: 'The pill speeds up getting your period, so there's no pregnancy' (chemistry professor, sixth abortion); 'The uterus becomes alkaline when taking the pill, so conception can't occur' (Marxism professor, fifth abortion); 'It creates such a chemical environment in the body that sperm die as soon as they enter' (bank employee, second abortion); 'It destroys the membrane of the egg cell (housewife, fourth abortion); It's like you're constantly pregnant, so there's no fertilisation (artist, second abortion); 'The IUD causes a tumour in the uterus, and then there's no pregnancy' (textile worker, fourth abortion); 'It moves around the uterus and hunts down sperm' (shopkeeper, sixth abortion) (Rašević, 1999: 112; 115-117). Even into the 1980s, the condom was still widely regarded as a 'foreign object' that created a 'physical barrier between men and women', one that 'suffocated spontaneity' and 'required preparation' (Rašević, 1999: 161-162). This perception contributed to ongoing resistance to condom use throughout Yugoslavia, with even the spread of AIDS failing to increase condom sales. Newspapers noted that the term condom 'failed to gain acceptance on television'⁵⁴ and ironically observed that 'Balkan macho men react swiftly and

⁵⁴ „Ko reskira, taj dobija”, *Borba*, 25-26.7.1987.

forcefully, and simply don't have time to fuss with rubber'.⁵⁵ As a result, *coitus interruptus* – despite its well-documented unreliability – remained the most commonly used method of 'protection' against unwanted pregnancy until the country's breakup (Kapor-Stanulović, 1999).

At official meetings and policy discussions, repeated calls were made to expand the range of contraceptives, promote their use effectively, and standardize healthcare insurance criteria for covering contraceptive costs. However, these efforts ultimately proved fruitless.⁵⁶ Until its dissolution, Yugoslavia remained, more or less, at the starting point in terms of popularizing modern birth control. The healthcare system continued to prioritize curative over preventive care, while couples largely relied on unreliable, traditional methods of contraception and abortion as their primary means of family planning. Efforts to involve general practitioners in contraceptive initiatives failed to yield meaningful results, as most showed little motivation to engage in public education. Their role was often limited to prescribing birth control pills, and even then, typically only on the recommendation of gynaecologists. By the mid-1980s, the number of women using counselling centres remained negligible.⁵⁷ Many of these centres existed only on paper, and a significant number of men either showed no interest in preventing unwanted pregnancies⁵⁸ or refused to use contraception (Rašević, 1997). Compounding the issue, many gynaecological clinics and hospital departments generated substantial revenue from performing abortions, creating a financial disincentive for medical professionals to promote contraception or engage in broader public education initiatives.⁵⁹

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⁵⁵ „Balkanski mačomen u neprilici”, *Borba*, 23-24.5.1987.

⁵⁶ AJ, 142/II–A 832; Bilten broj 6, Jun 1973.

⁵⁷ AJ, 142/II–S 274; Planiranje porodice

⁵⁸ AJ, 142/II–S 274; Planiranje porodice u ostvarivanju Rezolucije o politici obnavljanja stanovništva na teritoriji SR Srbije van pokrajina (mart 1985); Mirjana Rašević, *Ka razumevanju abortusa u Srbiji* (Beograd: Institut društvenih nauka, 1999), 141.

⁵⁹ AJ, 142/II–S 274; Planiranje porodice.

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DIY Abortion in Context (late 20th – 21st Century)

Abstract: *Reproductive choices are strategic life choices. The decision to continue or interrupt a pregnancy is influenced by personal lifestyle, beliefs, and values, notwithstanding social biases and politics. The choice of the method to achieve an induced abortion might be complex. The national legal context can be crucial to one's decision-making regarding surgical or medical abortion, and in which setting. After the introduction of the abortion pills misoprostol and mifepristone, there has been a steady increase in demand for medical abortion, either with professional assistance or in a do-it-yourself (DIY) way.*

In this article, I will focus on what influences a pregnant person to choose a self-managed medical abortion. I will discuss aspects of the legal, social, and political contexts that favour such a choice, along with the personal motives. Although the state's population policies regarding the availability and access to contraception and abortion impact individual decision-making, the final decision is multifactorial.

We will examine diverse European national contexts concerning abortion and contraception to demonstrate that self-managed medical abortion is supported by women regardless of whether they live in countries with liberal abortion legislation. The historical period under consideration will begin in the late 20th century and continue into the 21st century. The selection of this time frame is based on a series of significant and transformative events that took place during this period, including the demographic repercussions of the Second World War, the introduction of oral contraceptives, the reform of abortion laws, the fall of Communism, and the advent of medical abortion pills.

Keywords: *abortion; self-managed abortion; self-care; self-control; reproductive autonomy; reproductive choices.*

Introduction

In the aftermath of the Second World War, pronatalist policies were implemented in European countries to stimulate population growth by restricting access to abortion and contraception. The ultimate goal was to recover the human losses of the war, rebuild the state, strengthen the workforce, and revive the military sector (Quine, 1996). Inevitably, these policies primarily targeted female bodies and minds,

glorifying motherhood while simultaneously condemning the choice of being childless or having a small family. Population policies reminiscent of Vichy's regime in France, which actively intervened in family life, are an excellent example of pronatalism. Similar eugenic policies originated from the interwar period and flourished in the post-war years (Turda and Gillette, 2014). In a different context, in the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), motherhood was deprioritised because the state needed its female human capital to strengthen its workforce. Not surprisingly, the USSR liberalised abortion as early as 1955 (David, 1992; Flood, 2002).

Although the need or desire to terminate a pregnancy has existed for as long as motherhood itself, the right to a safe abortion in a fully equipped state hospital has only been legally permitted in most European countries since the 1970s. The United Kingdom led the shift toward more liberal abortion legislation in 1968. It paved the way to similar reforms in the German Democratic Republic in 1972, followed by Denmark, Sweden, France, Austria, Luxembourg, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Greece and Belgium by the end of the 20th century (David, 1992).

In countries where abortion was illegal or permitted under exceptional circumstances, often excluding social, psychological or financial reasons, women resorted to self-managed abortion or clandestine surgical abortion due to fear of prosecution. Self-managed abortion has been practised in diverse social and political settings, often posing considerable health risks. Among the range of methods to achieve a self-induced abortion, ingestion of herbal abortifacients has been the most popular (Jerman et al., 2018; Upadhyay et al., 2022). In particular, Delay (2018) notes that Irish women preferred herbal abortifacients, perceived as a 'natural' way to induce abortion. Even though most herbs may not pose significant toxicologic risk, others, such as pennyroyal, blue cohosh, rue, and quinine, can result in adverse clinical events (Feng et al., 2023). Clandestine surgical abortions were a common practice worldwide as well. Predominantly performed by non-licensed obstetrician-gynaecologists, they often resulted in maternal injury and death (Karlin and Joffe, 2023; van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024).

Since their introduction into European pharmaceutical channels, beginning in France in 1988, the medicines misoprostol and mifepristone have been used to induce abortion (Winikoff et al., 2011). Typically, the pregnant person consumes mifepristone, followed by misoprostol 24 to 48 hours later or only misoprostol (Feng et al., 2023). In

countries where abortion pills are legal, women are free to choose this method to terminate an unwanted pregnancy, obtaining them in pharmacies or national clinics.

In contrast, in countries where all methods of abortion are prohibited or permitted only under certain medical conditions, women are often forced to order the drugs online and use them in secrecy, sometimes without any professional assistance (van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024). However, in today's borderless and interconnected world created by the widespread use of the internet, legal barriers could be overcome by those seeking self-managed abortions. Ordering misoprostol and mifepristone online bypasses legislation and avoids the authorities' control. Furthermore, online orders facilitate access for specific social groups, such as women living in war zones or refugees. The major online supplier of abortion pills is the Canadian non-profit organisation, Women on Web (hereafter WoW). This is a group of people who facilitate access to abortion pills by mailing them free of charge to nearly 200 countries worldwide (Aiken et al., 2021). Even so, their website has been blocked in countries such as South Korea and, until recently, Spain (WoW, n.d.).

Access to family planning information and contraception is essential and should be considered in discussions of abortion. As David (1992) argued, legal abortion is most meaningful when it is included in the state's reproductive healthcare services as part of a family planning program. As will be shown, in countries where both contraception and abortion are banned, illegal abortion is used as a contraceptive method, ultimately resulting in higher abortion rates (Marston and Cleland, 2003). Conversely, in countries with liberal abortion legislation and easy access to contraceptives within a culture that supports reproductive freedom, abortion rates tend to remain low. Notably, maternal deaths due to unsafe, illegal abortions are reduced as well (Hord, 1991; Marston and Cleland, 2003). Indeed, the legal liberalisation of abortion alone is insufficient – the freedom and ability to exercise the right to contraception and abortion are multifaceted. As will be argued, shame and stigma surrounding abortion are social factors that equally impact reproductive freedom. For state population policies to be fruitful and effective, they should be implemented within a social framework of acceptance and solidarity, alongside adequate logistics and healthcare infrastructure coordination. As Vedhuis (2022) correctly points out, the decriminalisation of abortion services does not guarantee their wide-

spread availability. Failing to acknowledge abortion care as a component of standard reproductive care and as part of free family planning services renders its legalisation meaningless.

Research in countries such as Romania, which experienced radical shifts in abortion and contraception policies between the 1960s and the 1990s, reinforces the argument that legislation affects individual decision-making, as reflected in changing abortion and fertility rates. However, the decision not to terminate an unwanted pregnancy was motivated by fear of prosecution rather than by persuasive state messaging. The legalisation of abortion and the subsequent reversal of Romania's total fertility rates demonstrate that personal rationale did not commonly coincide with the state's pronatalist policies (Bradatan and Firebaugh, 2007; Benson et al., 2011). At the same time, the fact remains that no legal restriction has ever eliminated abortions.

This article presents a comparative, cross-cultural study focused on European countries and their approaches toward fertility management, abortion, contraception, and reproductive choices. Its purpose is to identify common incentives for self-managed medical abortion among women in politically and culturally diverse European regions. Since individual reproductive decisions are intertwined with state population policies, we will demonstrate examples of legal, political and socio-cultural contexts which were conducive to abortion in general and self-managed medical abortion in particular.

Although generalisations in such diverse cultural settings would be at best inaccurate, our research identified some shared features. Irrespective of the legal status of abortion, there is a universal tendency to obscure the process from the authorities due to stigmatisation (van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024). According to the overview data, when possible, women prefer to undergo surgical abortion in a private practice rather than in a public clinic. Furthermore, the fact that self-managed medical abortion can be carried out in complete secrecy gives the pregnant person the power to decide for themselves without conforming to the legal constraints and sociopolitical biases.

Abortion is a strategic life choice that primarily concerns the pregnant person; as such, its gendered dimensions cannot be ignored. This analysis focuses on women who get pregnant, decide to terminate their pregnancy, and opt for self-managed medical abortion. The methods used may vary, but the underlying desire for self-care and self-control remains the same.

Methodology and Sources

Given that self-managed medical abortion can be carried out in secrecy and anonymity, reliable demographic data are rare or non-existent. In addition, even when there is data on the sales of misoprostol and mifepristone, there is no guarantee that an abortion has occurred. A woman might change her mind and, ultimately, decide not to terminate her pregnancy. There is also the possibility of taking the medication after 12 weeks of gestation, when the process may fail (WHO, 2022). As a result, research on self-managed medical abortion is primarily based on published fieldwork studies, rather than official statistics.

In this context, the use of anonymised data provided by the Google platform has gained traction among researchers studying self-managed medical abortion. Some publications are almost exclusively based on Google Analytics, as it offers a way to capture the global or national trends in the demand for self-induced abortion (Jerman et al., 2018; Upadhyay et al., 2022). Following this methodology, non-academic publications in lay journals and newspapers have also emerged. The fact that the number of Google searches for abortion pills increases is alarming (Butterly et al., 2018). Findings showed that people primarily search for abortion pills, information about abortion, potential implications, and how to access abortion care (Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021). Anonymised data coming from the WoW platform is also valuable for researchers. To a certain extent, data from Google and WoW is a method to overcome the unreliability of official data and help capture the real position of self-induced abortion within the broader spectrum of abortion choices.

Although studies based on Google Analytics and the WoW platform statistics have been used in this article as secondary sources, the core methodological approach and sources are based on a bibliographical review. The bibliography includes published scholarship in medical humanities, gender studies, demography and legal studies. Although the article focuses on the European context, relevant qualitative and demographic studies from other parts of the world are also considered. The following sections outline key aspects of the historical trajectories of abortion and contraception from the post-war period to the 21st century, intending to elucidate the social, political and legal factors that influence individual reproductive choices. The particularities of the COVID-19 pandemic will also be addressed due to its effects on the rise of telemedicine and DIY abortion at home.

Definition of the Process and Access to Abortion Pills

The process of terminating one's pregnancy outside a formal clinical setting or healthcare institution is commonly referred to as Do-It-Yourself or self-managed abortion (Moseson et al., 2020; Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021; Hoggard et al., 2024). As previously mentioned, historically, attempts at self-managed abortion involved the use of herbal abortifacients or other non-medical means (Delay, 2018; Feng et al., 2023). In this article, however, I will focus on self-managed medical abortion. Depending on a woman's preference and accessibility, there are two main types of medical abortion: a clinical one, which involves a healthcare professional – either a gynaecologist or lay healthcare professionals – and an autonomous one with no medical assistance. In the former case, abortion can be initiated or completed in a clinical setting or remotely via telemedicine. In the latter, the woman may complete the process independently or with support from non-medical staff (Vedhuis et al., 2022).

As a non-surgical method, medical abortion allows women to avoid the health risks associated with surgical intervention. It is seen as a more 'natural' way to induce abortion, as it resembles a miscarriage (Delay, 2018; Moseson et al., 2020). Not to mention, self-managed medical abortion is much cheaper than surgery or even free of charge in countries where the medication is state-subsidised and prescribed by a physician. However, self-managed medical abortion might fail if the gestational age is more than 12 weeks, in which case a surgical abortion becomes necessary (Moseson et al., 2020; WHO, 2022).

Determined by the legal context, access to abortion pills can be obtained in a clinic or pharmacy in countries with liberal laws, by online order in countries where abortion is restricted, or by travelling to a country where abortion pills are legal. Medical tourism for abortion, either to have it in a clinic or to buy the pills, has been done for many years. In Europe, notable examples are women travelling from Northern Ireland and Malta to England and from Poland to Germany (Delay, 2018; Dibben et al., 2023; Kuźma-Markowska and Kelly, 2022).

Since the 1990s, abortion medications have been approved in several European countries, beginning with France in 1988, followed by Great Britain and Sweden in 1992, and then Belgium, Denmark, Finland, the Netherlands and Germany in 1999 (Winikoff et al., 2011). Medication abortion became officially available more widely after the World Health Organisation declared it safe in 2005. According to the latest 2022 list of nationally authorised medicinal products, misoprostol

is authorised in Austria, Poland, Belgium, Denmark, Spain, Finland, Greece, Ireland, Iceland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal and Sweden (European Medicines Agency, 2022). As of the latest 2024 list, mifepristone is authorised in Finland, Lithuania, Iceland, Bulgaria, Romania, Estonia, Cyprus, Greece, Netherlands, Spain, Austria, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Ireland, Norway, Finland, Germany, Sweden, Slovenia, Croatia, Portugal, Latvia, Italy, Belgium, Luxemburg (European Medicines Agency, 2024).

The Legal, Social and Political Context of Abortion and Contraception

Specific periods in modern European history have influenced reproductive health, placing it at the centre of health policies and public concern. These were the aftermath of the Second World War (1950s), the introduction of oral contraceptives (1970s), and the fall of Communism (1990s). These periods coincided with urbanisation, the resurgence of feminism, and advances in biomedicine and technology.

In the 1950s, the political situation in Europe was still unstable. Seeking social and political stability, most European countries were in the process of reconstruction of infrastructure, policy-making, and population management. To recover from the significant losses of the war, widely disseminated pronatalist policies promoted big and healthy families that would restore the number of workers and soldiers (Quine, 1996). As a result, we witnessed the resurgence of eugenics in many European countries during the post-war period (Bashford and Levine, 2010; Barmpouti, 2019). In the name of demographic growth, abortion laws became stricter, and access to contraceptives was often banned. Subsequently, in the 1960s, many Western European countries, such as France, faced overpopulation during the so-called ‘baby boom’ (Brée, 2017), while Southern European countries experienced a high number of illegal abortions (David, 1992; Sedgh et al., 2007).

In the late 1960s, the arrival of ‘the pill’, the first hormonal oral contraceptive, marked a groundbreaking change to the long-standing insecurity of traditional contraceptive methods. This so-called modern contraceptive offered reliability and reassurance to the user. Its widespread use in some countries resulted in a gradual decline in abortion rates (Marston and Cleland, 2003). The link between abortion and contraception is demonstrated in the pattern suggesting that in countries where contraceptives are readily available, abortion rates are lower. In reality, this rule is often complicated by factors such as the cost and

type of contraceptives available and the prevailing national attitudes toward contraception. Accordingly, in low-income countries, where ‘modern’ hormonal oral contraceptives and intrauterine devices (IUDs) are too expensive to buy or in short supply, poorer couples use traditional, less reliable contraceptive methods, such as condoms or withdrawal, which can result in unwanted pregnancy. During Căușescu’s regime in Romania, for instance, wealthier women could afford to buy contraceptives illegally or bribe doctors to perform abortions under the guise of a life-threatening condition. At the same time, poorer women risked their lives and freedom by undergoing backstreet abortions (Haliliuc, 2013). In Bulgaria, modern contraceptive methods were not introduced until 1975. In line with the above-mentioned correlation between abortion rates and effective contraception, Bulgaria witnessed a decline in abortion in the late 1980s and 1990s – a pattern similarly observed in Denmark and the Netherlands (Marston and Cleland, 2003).

In the absence of contraceptives, safe reproductive control relied heavily on repetitive abortions. A 1969 demographic field study in Greece found that abortion was considered and used both as a contraceptive and as a remedy for an unwanted pregnancy (Barmpouti, 2015). Couples interviewed for the study categorised abortion alongside other contraceptive methods (Valaoras et al., 1969). Similarly, in the context of the USSR, where both abortion and contraception were legal, the availability of contraceptives was low. Factors, such as cost, logistics and availability, could be crucial to the access and consistent use of contraceptives. In addition, given the vast geography of the USSR, not all regions had healthcare facilities capable of providing contraception or performing abortions, despite both being legal. As a result, abortion was frequently used as a contraceptive, raising its incidence in the country (Marston and Cleland, 2003). In terms of the socio-political environment, Marxist ideas and values emphasised intense labour, materialism, and atheism, framing women’s roles more as workers than as mothers. As Flood explicitly put it, ‘legalised, state-funded abortion was a way to encourage women to devote their energies to build socialism, not families’ (Flood, 2002: 191). Romania and Poland followed the same route, legalising abortion in the 1950s (Flood, 2002).

Romania, only a decade after legalising abortion, shifted to stricter legislation on abortion and contraception (Bradatan and Firebaugh, 2007). In 1966, Ceaușescu’s regime passed a law that made abortion illegal for women under forty or those with fewer than four

children. Creating large families became a national duty (Haliliuc, 2013: 113). After Ceaușescu's overthrow, the government of Romania liberalised abortion legislation again (David, 1992). The change of regime impacted broader family planning policies. Former communist countries, including Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania, embraced a more pro-natalist perspective, thus restricting access to both abortion and contraception (Flood, 2002).

European legal frameworks commonly permit abortion when the life of the mother or the fetus is at risk, except Iceland, which was the first country to introduce the concept of medicosocial indications, followed by the United Kingdom, Denmark, and Sweden (David, 1992). During the post-war period, when pronatalist policies were widely disseminated, the emotional and psychological health of the mother was often neglected. As mentioned earlier, a global trend toward liberalising abortion laws emerged only after 1975. The majority of European countries replaced their strict abortion regulations with new laws permitting broader grounds for terminating a pregnancy, including socio-economic reasons (UN, 2002). This wave of legalisation at the end of the 20th century acknowledged the psychological, social and financial burdens of an unwanted pregnancy and provided greater protections for the pregnant person.

A striking exception was the Republic of Ireland, which legalised abortion as recently as 2018. The anti-abortion movements that formed in the second half of the twentieth century played a key role in limiting social acceptance of abortion and sustaining abortion stigma. In 2020, Poland saw a significant legislative shift when abortion for foetal defects and abnormalities became illegal. Kuźma-Markowska and Kelly's (2022) research showed that anti-abortion activism was decisive in this respect.

Between 1996 and 2003, several Eastern European countries – Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, the Russian Federation, Hungary, and Slovakia experienced a decline in abortion rates, most probably due to increased use of modern, safe contraceptives. Nevertheless, these countries still report the highest abortion rates in Europe (Sedgh et al., 2007). David (1992) attributes high abortion rates to persistent taboos around sexuality, even if these countries implemented liberal laws on abortion long before oral contraceptives. In contrast, he argues that open attitudes toward sexuality and the introduction of sexual education in early school years have been critical factors for the low abortion rates in the Netherlands and the Scandinavian countries (David, 1992). During the

same period, abortion rates in Northern, Western and Southern Europe remained relatively stable except in the Netherlands, where the rate increased by 31%. This was mainly due to women seeking abortions from ethnic minority groups (Sedgh et al., 2007). Demographic research has shown that maternal mortality rates have dropped significantly following the adoption of liberal abortion laws. Culturally diverse countries such as Sweden and Hungary witnessed the same sharp decline in maternal deaths after legalising abortion in the 1970s (Marston and Cleland, 2003).

It is undeniable that women undergo abortions everywhere, regardless of legal context, but illegal abortions carry a high risk of maternal mortality. According to Hord, nearly 87% of maternal deaths during Ceaușescu's regime were the result of unsafe abortions (Hord, 1991; Marston and Cleland, 2003; Haliliuc, 2013). Maternal deaths tend to decrease significantly when abortion is performed in a safe environment by trained professionals (Benson et al., 2011). Furthermore, self-managed medical abortion is safer than clandestine surgical abortion in countries with restrictive laws (Aiken et al., 2017; van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024).

Not surprisingly, DIY abortion is more common in countries where relevant legislation restricts or entirely forbids abortion anywhere in the country, even within healthcare institutions. In such contexts, both the pregnant woman and the healthcare professional who assists with the abortion face prosecution and incarceration. In Malta, for example, a woman who induces abortion risks three years in prison, while the healthcare provider who assists her risks four years of imprisonment and, if they are a physician, the loss of their medical license. As a result, self-managed abortion or travelling to another country remains the only option for those facing unwanted pregnancies. The main difference between the two options is that when travelling abroad, the home country has no legal jurisdiction; on the contrary, if self-medication abortion is discovered, the woman will face prosecution. Dibben's research on Maltese abortion seekers indicated an ongoing shift toward self-managed medical abortion, particularly following the COVID-19 travel restrictions (Dibben et al., 2023).

Incentives for Self-managed Medical Abortion

Paradoxically, research shows that even in countries with liberal legislation, there is a trend to choose at-home abortion. Hospital care is often rejected by women who prefer to undergo an induced abortion in

the comfort of their own space. Just as some women choose to give birth at home, to be with their partner and relatives, they may decide to undergo a self-induced medical abortion at home with their loved ones, even when the country they live in permits abortion at a clinic (Moseson et al., 2020; Hoggart, 2024).

The recent COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated this trend while demonstrating the safety and effectiveness of self-managed medical abortions. The fear of infection during the COVID-19 pandemic heightened demand for abortions outside of clinical settings, promoting DIY abortions. To avoid potential infection, pregnant women and healthcare practitioners choose self-medication abortion at home, often supported by online guidance and physicians via telemedicine (Aiken et al., 2021; Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021). Before the pandemic, England, Wales, and Scotland had already incorporated the procedure into medical protocols, allowing women to take mifepristone in a clinic and misoprostol at home. Therefore, during the COVID-19 pandemic, women and physicians in these countries were already familiar with self-managed medical abortion at home. According to Hoggart et al. (2024), this was not the case for their neighbours in Northern Ireland, where the legislation continued to restrict abortions even during the pandemic. That self-managed medical abortion proved to be safe and effective was then more widely recognised, particularly due to the widespread use of abortion pills during this period (Fay et al., 2023). According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), when self-managed medical abortion is performed according to the guidelines and particularly with the aid of a healthcare professional, it carries minimal risk (WHO, 2022).

Combining data on abortion rates and the growing acceptance of medication abortion suggests that the availability of abortion pills has not increased the overall incidence of abortion (Sedgh et al., 2007). Medical abortion partly replaced surgical abortion, mainly due to shifting attitudes toward reproductive issues. Abortion has been socially and individually reassessed in light of modern values, beliefs and lifestyles. Women have taken their reproductive decisions out of the hands of physicians and politicians and into their own, exercising reproductive freedom alongside rights to self-care, self-control, and autonomy. A pregnant person takes control of their life because an unintended pregnancy may disrupt life plans, including education or career goals, not to mention the financial burden of raising a child (Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021; van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024).

Recent scholarship suggests that the freedom to exercise reproductive autonomy and self-care is the leading incentive for self-managed abortion, followed by the emotional safety and comfort of home, and the ability to undergo the process with a partner or family, or all alone (Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021; Feng et al., 2023; van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024). Furthermore, it allows for complete secrecy and anonymity, which may be necessitated by legal constraints but may also stem from social stigma or personal choice. A pregnant person is entitled to end a pregnancy without disclosing it.

In addition to the feeling of safety and security, women may prefer self-managed medical abortion because they consider it better for their health and well-being than surgical abortion (Aiken et al., 2017). Medical abortion is perceived as less invasive than a surgical one (Delay, 2018; Moseson et al., 2020).

In terms of the patient-doctor relationship, self-managed medical abortion can be interpreted as a way of resisting medical paternalism (Pizzarossa and Nandagiri, 2021; Karlin and Joffe, 2023; Hoggart, 2024). Doctors' authority often influences women's attitudes and final decisions. In addition, self-managed medical abortion is a way to overcome the reluctance or objection of health professionals to perform an abortion on moral grounds (David, 1992). Ultimately, as Karlin and Joffe argued, self-managed medical abortion challenges medical authority by contributing to the 'demedicalisation' of abortion. The process involves ingesting pills which are accessible online, thus making the physician's involvement optional (Karlin and Joffe, 2023). Nevertheless, professional involvement in assessing one's medical history and counselling is deemed essential for the procedure's safety.

Furthermore, self-managed abortion is often free of charge, whereas the operation, particularly in private practice, can be costly. In rural areas, access to surgical abortion may involve travel to a clinic, time off work, travel and accommodation costs, or even the need for childcare if the pregnant person already has children (Upadhyay et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2023). Therefore, it is crucial to recognise the financial aspect, which encourages women to prefer medical to surgical abortion.

It is important to note that not all people think and feel the same way about abortion. There is no single profile of an abortion seeker, but many. They may be single women who want to avoid or delay the birth of a child for medical, personal or social reasons. Moreover, couples may choose abortion to space or end childbearing. Generally, desired

family size depends on socioeconomic status, individual aspirations, or medical reasons (Marston and Cleland, 2003). Undeniably, women have multiple roles, and society expects them to manage all of them optimally. As discussed in the context of pronatalist policies, giving birth has been a unique mission as it is subject to familial, social and political pressures. Legislation, social shame and stigma frequently determine decision-making (van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024).

Anti-abortion legislation often reflects anti-abortion sentiments of a given society (van den Dungen and Gomperts, 2024). Stigmatisation is reinforced by anti-abortion activism, which has recently been revived in the US and now influences Europe (Kuźma-Markowska and Kelly, 2022). Furthermore, in countries where the Christian Church is powerful, such as the Catholic Church in Ireland and Poland and the Orthodox Church in Greece, having an abortion is highly stigmatised and condemned as it is equated with murder. The Church's condemnation of abortion does not necessarily mean that all citizens are practising believers or strongly influenced by its moral teachings. However, it is indisputable that religion plays a vital role in a society's culture. Particularly in countries such as Greece and Ireland, where a dominant religion is officially recognised, its teachings exert direct or indirect influence on abortion seekers (Valaoras et al., 1969; Barmpouti, 2015; Kuźma-Markowska and Kelly, 2022).

Conclusion

The transformative events of the mid-20th to early 21st centuries reshaped both population policies toward abortion and contraception and individual reproductive choices. Self-managed medical abortion is not simply one method among others. It can be understood as a means of exercising reproductive autonomy and self-care. The introduction and dissemination of abortion pills challenged ideas regarding reproductive issues, reduced social stigma and lowered the cost of the procedure. It has been shown that this form of abortion is increasingly accepted by women, particularly after the WHO confirmed its safety when performed under the guidelines. It seems a reasonable choice in countries with strict abortion legislation, yet recent research shows it is increasingly preferred in countries with liberal legislation, too. As discussed, the incentives behind the preference for self-managed medical abortion over surgical abortion are rooted in the desire to exercise self-control and reproductive autonomy and the physical and emotional comfort it encompasses.

All in all, self-managed medical abortion offers precisely what its name implies: the ability of the pregnant person to manage their condition in a way that feels dignified, comfortable and safe. It succeeded in protecting women from social biases, legal prosecution and stigma, simultaneously giving them the freedom to terminate their pregnancy in a way that aligns with their attitudes, lifestyles and values.

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MARGINS OF CARE: SILENCE, RISK, AND CONTESTED ETHICS

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Medicalization of Death and Dying in Post-War Hungary and the Netherlands. *Taboo and Transparency in Legal Thinking*¹

Abstract: *Medicalization of death and dying after World War II represented a significant shift in both Eastern and Western Europe, with implications for medical law and ethics. Death and dying became subjects of medical decisions and interventions. Increasingly, death occurred in hospitals and was preceded by various medical procedures aimed at prolonging life, sometimes artificially. Along with the process of medicalization, families and communities became less involved in the last phase of their loved ones' lives. In this paper, we explore the repercussions of this process in two post-war societies that took very different paths in addressing doctors' involvement in end-of-life decisions: Hungary and the Netherlands. The Netherlands is widely known for granting access to physician-assisted dying, including euthanasia and assisted suicide, following decades of legal cases, empirical reports, and legislative changes. In Hungary, although the issue has surfaced repeatedly in public discussions, it still constitutes a medical and legal taboo. Patient autonomy in Hungary developed much later and the legal progress has stagnated since 1997. Patients can*

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refuse certain types of treatment, but only through a bureaucratic procedure. To understand the sharp contrast between the current laws in the two countries, we trace and compare legal developments and ethical thinking in both jurisdictions. We examine changes in the approach to the patient-doctor relationship, the role of information disclosure, patient autonomy, transparency, and the obstacles to these. Our analysis shows that striking the right balance between doctors' professional responsibilities and patients' rights remains a challenge in both countries.

Keywords: *medicalization; end-of-life decisions; Hungary; the Netherlands; law; ethics.*

Introduction

This paper examines and contrasts legal developments and ethical debates on end-of-life decisions in post-war Hungary and the Netherlands. After World War II, these two countries followed diverging judicial and medical approaches towards decisions related to death and dying. To understand the sharp contrast between the current rules on this matter, we trace and compare legal and ethical thinking in the two jurisdictions.

Following World War II, medicalization of death and dying became a widespread phenomenon in Europe (on the concept of medicalization, see Conrad, 1992). Some authors argue that medicalization has replaced religious interpretations of illness (Bull, 1990). The development of intensive care and changes in the family structure contributed to the growing practice of hospitalizing the terminally ill. As death and dying became a medical issue, it was mainly institutions that provided nursing and pain relief. Within the debate on medicalization, decisions on who cares for terminally ill patients and how, have become central issues. Specifically, if dying is regarded a medical issue, how are the patients' wishes responded to?

Comparing the legal approach in Hungary and the Netherlands, one can ascertain that at the end of World War II, the situation in both countries was similar. While people were increasingly dying in institutions, physicians' involvement in life-ending acts constituted a criminal offence. Moreover, health professionals were not expected to disclose a terminal diagnosis to patients because telling the truth was regarded cruel and possibly harmful to their condition (on the Dutch experience, see Weyers, 2004, 2006). Death was a taboo topic and the process of dying was to be kept out of sight.

The evolution of the legal norm of informed consent has played an important role in both countries. However, in Hungary, therapeutic privilege was understood very broadly prior to 1990. The bioethics and

legal literature define therapeutic privilege as the withholding of relevant health information from patients if non-disclosure is deemed to be in their best interest (Hodkinson, 2013). In case of a terminal or incurable illness, therapeutic privilege provides an exception to informed consent. As a result of its broad interpretation, doctors in Hungary usually tried to avoid providing full information to the terminally ill until 1990² (Sándor, 1991). The practice of secrecy excluded patients from end-of-life decisions. While patients' rights were incorporated into the Hungarian Healthcare Act in 1997, requests for physician-assisted dying were not recognized. The right to refuse medical treatment and the right to leave the medical institution, however, were included as patients' rights. Although there have been very few legal changes in the field of the end-of-life decisions since 1997, the issue has been repeatedly discussed in public debates and in Hungarian professional and intellectual circles.

The Netherlands followed a different path. In the early 1950s, Dutch courts began developing jurisprudence on end-of-life decisions by examining cases from medical practice. Small-scale studies conducted during the 1980s showed that despite the criminal law prohibitions, Dutch physicians sometimes complied with patients' life-ending requests (Weyers, 2006: 805). In ruling on such cases, judges created the possibility for physicians to be exempted from prosecution under specific conditions. In doing so, they were willing to be guided by the views of the medical profession (Buijsen, 2024). For decades, physicians could not rely on statutory provisions to justify life-ending acts, but the courts ensured that the Dutch legal system did not remain entirely unresponsive. Judges helped lift the taboo and paved the way for increased transparency. By shifting the focus from the threat of prosecution to procedural justice and patient autonomy, the courts laid the groundwork for the adoption of Dutch statutory law enabling physician-assisted dying under due care.

It is thought-provoking that while some form of end-of-life decision (euthanasia, assisted suicide, or physician-assisted end-of-life planning) is accepted in several Western European countries and particularly in the Netherlands, the issue remains taboo in Central and Eastern Europe, including Hungary. However, this does not mean that such decisions are not made in practice. Rather, it reflects that the practice of

² Parliamentary Act No XII. of 1990 modified Section 45.(1) of the Healthcare Act of 1972.

self-determination is less established and the situation is “resolved” differently. Our paper highlights these differences and contrasts the approaches to the patient-doctor relationship, the role of information provided to patients, autonomy, transparency, and the obstacles to achieving these.

In this paper, we use the term *euthanasia* to denote the act of deliberately ending another person’s life with the intention of relieving suffering. The term *assisted suicide* (or *assistance in suicide*) refers to a life-ending act carried out by the individual with the help of another person who provides medication or other assistance. *Physician-assisted dying* covers both euthanasia and assisted suicide and was used in this way in the judgment delivered by the European Court of Human Rights in 2024 in the case *Dániel Karsai v. Hungary* (see Sándor, 2024 for analysis of the case). Furthermore, we use the term *patient autonomy* to refer to the capacity to decide for oneself and to pursue one’s chosen course of action in life. Respect for autonomy is listed among the four major principles of bioethics (Childress and Beauchamp, 2001). We argue that information and autonomy are essential to the development of patients’ rights, including the rights of dying patients, and that patients cannot act autonomously in the absence of adequate information about their medical condition.

After World War II, Hungary and the Netherlands experienced significantly different trajectories in the development of political, religious, and societal factors. These divergent socio-political developments left their mark on both the legal and healthcare systems, and the broader societal changes influenced approaches to patients’ rights and options concerning end-of-life decisions. Notably, between the late 1960s and mid-1970s, the Dutch society underwent significant political, religious, and social transformations described as a process of “de-pillarization” (*ontzuiling*), which involved secularization (see for example, Thurlings, 1979) or as a gradual transition from the ideals and practices of “heavy” communities to those of “light” communities (van Dam, 2015). These societal changes paved the way for breaking the taboo surrounding death and dying. Nevertheless, religious arguments continued to be present in the Dutch debates even after the 1970s, while such arguments were virtually absent in the Hungarian context during the state-socialist decades. Whilst we acknowledge these broad societal differences, in this paper we focus on legal developments and contrast the underlying legal and ethical arguments.

Death and Dying in Hungary: Ethical and Legal Debates

There has been a longstanding debate in Hungary about death with dignity, and polls conducted at various times have indicated that people prefer to decide for themselves whether or not to have medical treatment at the end of life. Respect for human dignity involves recognition of personal decisions and implies that no patient can be treated as a mere object of a medical procedure. Opinion polls show that if suffering cannot be alleviated, many people would seek active help in hastening death (Europion, 2024). Yet, when it comes to legislation in Hungary, and generally in Central and Eastern Europe, modesty, caution, or simple avoidance tend to prevail.

Human dignity is a basic constitutional legal concept in Hungarian law (Constitutional Court decision 8/1990. (IV.23.)). The current Fundamental Law stipulates that “human dignity is inviolable” and “every human being has the right to life and human dignity”. This principle demands that we regard another human being not as a means but always as an end. It has a passive and an active element: every human being is entitled to equal respect, and human dignity demands respect for the person’s autonomy. In the context of end-of-life decisions, this means that society should respect the dignity of dying persons, including their wish to avoid suffering and their decisions on how to cope with a terminal illness.

The issue of end-of-life decisions has appeared repeatedly in Hungarian public debates, although usually as isolated incidents lasting only for a few days or weeks. Authors like Béla Blasszauer (1984), Alaine Polcz (1993), László Bitó (2014), József Kovács (1997), Gábor Vadász (2020), Mihály Filó (2015), Albert Takács and Ildikó Kmetty (2003), András Sajó and Judit Sándor (1996, 1995), and many others have taken part in these public debates. The topic also features in literary works and films. In 1994, István Jelenczki made a multi-part documentary titled *The Right to Die* (Haláljog), which was shown not only in cinemas but also on television. In 2021, thirty Hungarian writers expressed their opinions on the dignity of death in a book (Demény et al, 2021). Nevertheless, no debate or awareness-raising campaign has generated as much attention and influence in Hungarian media and public discourse as that initiated by the legal case of the terminally ill human rights lawyer Dániel Karsai in 2023 and 2024 (European Court of Human Rights, 2024; see also Sándor, 2024).

Thinking about death and dying and the need to recognize patients' rights directs end-of-life decisions in two different ways: towards claiming medical assistance in dying if life has become unbearable, and towards maintaining control with the aim of preserving life for as long as possible. We have found evidence for both positions: while in public debate people have often claimed the right to decide on the withdrawal of medical treatment when the terminally ill patient suffered, in court cases relatives have often sued hospitals when they lost loved ones due to negligent care (Sándor, 1997). Despite many debates and initiatives, the Hungarian legislature has never accepted medical assistance in dying, whilst several Western European countries, starting with the Netherlands, have made significant changes and gradually accepted euthanasia and assisted suicide. The Dutch example was a frequent reference in the Hungarian debates on euthanasia and the Dutch experience was extensively analyzed by Hungarian authors, such as Bérczes (Bérczes, 2016).

Although the term euthanasia has been repeatedly used in Hungarian legal debates, it has become virtually useless from a legal point of view, since it is now used to cover so many actions and inactions that shorten life (Sajó and Sándor, 1996). As noted above, within end-of-life decisions it is worth distinguishing between self-inflicted actions and those carried out by others. In both legal theory and practice, many consider autonomy to be better expressed through self-inflicted actions or by incurable, agonizing patients ending their life themselves, with the legal focus placed on participation. Due to their condition, many dying patients are unable to commit suicide without some form of medical assistance and prescription, unless they and their relatives are forced to resort to shocking, inhumane acts. An illustrative example for the desperate acts that those who do not receive medical help might resort to is the *Binder* case. In this tragic case from Hungary, a mother killed her sick child at the child's request, after several unsuccessful attempts at home, and then went to the police, reporting the crime herself (Fedor, 2017). Involvement in suicide is also a criminal act under Hungarian law, and a doctor's involvement is no exception.

Parliamentary Act No CLIV of 1997 (the Hungarian Healthcare Act) introduced the right to refuse treatment, albeit limited to narrowly defined cases. However, the circumstances of ending life are always personal. Patients who are about to leave life face different conditions after various treatment and symptom-reduction options. The combina-

tion of autonomous acceptance by the individual and the criminal liability of the doctor or assisting relative usually leads to legal issues. In most cases, medical support, pain relief, and some form of a life sustaining treatment are indispensable. In the wake of the medicalization of dying, it seems that, at this important point in life, the possibility of ensuring dignity has slipped from the hands of those most affected. The medicalization of dying has often even distanced family members from the final struggles of their relatives' lives.

Therefore, the question is what legal solutions can assist in restoring the autonomy and dignity of persons nearing death. The right to refuse treatment, as the term suggests, only gives the patient the right to refuse certain interventions in a narrow range of cases. Explicitly patient-centered end-of-life planning would be more effective if it were allowed not only the refusal of certain interventions, but also the request and consent to end-of-life treatments, which could lead to medical interventions aimed at reducing suffering. But as long as only certain treatments can be waived (in a very complicated way), the autonomy of the incurable patient remains compromised. In 2017, a representative study was conducted on knowledge of the right to refuse medical treatment and was analyzed by lawyers (Kussinszky & Stánicz, 2022).

End-of-life decisions have had a prominent role in the development of Hungarian bioethics. Thanatology is now a recognized field of research and discipline, with its Hungarian periodical titled "Kharón, Thanatology Review", launched in 1997 by Alaine Polcz, Péter Berta, and János Pilling as the first professional, scientific Hungarian forum in the field. The influence of thanatology and suicidology has broadened the context of end-of-life debates in Hungary. At Semmelweis Medical School in Budapest, the bioethics curriculum includes a session on "suicide, euthanasia, and "terathanasia". Suicide, assisted suicide, and euthanasia have become leading topics in Hungarian bioethics and medical law. The high number of committed and attempted suicides in Hungary has led to several sociological research projects on the causes and prevention of this phenomenon (Buda, 2001). Although the number of suicides dropped just after World War II, it began to rise rapidly again in 1957. Subsequently, Mihály Gergely's work on suicide was published in the Journal "Kortárs" in 1969 and later in a book (Gergely, 1972). Since 1958, the Central Statistical Office has been regularly collecting data on suicides and suicide attempts. As health conditions have not been the focus, it is difficult to establish a connection between potential requests for euthanasia and suicide. In the early

1960ies, László Cseh-Szombathy conducted interviews with relatives of 100 people who had committed suicide (Cseh-Szombathy, 1963). Later, Béla Buda referred to the possible connection between acceptance of suicide and euthanasia (Buda, 2001).

As a distinct issue related to death and dying, the term *terathanasia* (Giagounidis et al., 1997) has a clear connection with the legacy of eugenic thinking and medical paternalism. The term refers to the withdrawal of medical care from newborns based on their health condition. The issue has not been discussed in public, and until the recognition of patient's rights, medical decisions did not involve relatives. A shocking criminal case from the city of Tatabánya (Hungary) revealed how medical decisions based on hierarchy and workplace loyalty could lead to the death of a prematurely born baby who was deliberately left without proper nursing and medical care (case No BF-III-640-1984). In this case, several doctors were charged with neglecting the baby. So far, this has been the only reported case in Hungary where the term *terathanasia* was mentioned.

Since euthanasia was, and still is, prohibited in Hungary, we could not find legal cases using this term, although several medical malpractice cases have questioned treatments provided to seriously ill patients with the effect of hastening death. There have been some controversial cases of the alleged killing of the terminally ill, such as the so-called Black Angel case, which resulted in criminal charges against a nurse (Frenkl, 2001). In this case, the actual number of deaths remained unclear, partly because of the lack of transparency regarding medication given to patients at the end of life. Unlike in the Netherlands, Hungarian cases have not contributed to legal development, although they strongly argue for greater transparency. As in other Central and Eastern European countries, Hungary has not decriminalized any form of physician-assisted dying. During the COVID-19 pandemic, hospitals became black boxes and decisions made at the end of life were not transparent (Munk, 2020). Opinion surveys (Europion, 2024) and scholarly debates, however, call for change.

Death and Dying in the Netherlands: Pragmatic Approach with Focus on Procedural Justice

Similarly to Hungary, in the Netherlands, the criminalization of euthanasia and assistance in suicide dates back to the 19th century. The 1886 amendment of the Dutch Penal Code inserted two relevant provisions. Article 293 addressed killing on request, i.e., depriving another

person of life “at the person’s explicit and earnest desire”, and set a sentence of up to 12 years’ imprisonment. Article 294 addressed assistance with, or inducement to commit suicide, or providing means thereto, and set a punishment of up to 3 years’ imprisonment if the suicide followed (Penal Code, 1886, Title XIX: ‘Crimes against life’). The criminal ban is still in force.

After World War II, legal developments in the Netherlands took a very different path from those in Hungary. In the absence of any societal consensus that could have enabled legislative initiatives for decades, Dutch courts gradually filled the legal vacuum through judgments concerning doctors who complied with their patients’ life-ending requests. An analysis of post-1950 case law reveals a lenient approach by Dutch courts to violations of Articles 293 and 294, as shown by the relatively light sentences imposed.

The first court case involving a physician dates to 1952. Acting upon his patient’s repeated request, a medical doctor from Eindhoven terminated the life of his brother suffering from tuberculosis. The doctor invoked necessity (*noodtoestand*), meaning a conflict between the simultaneous duties of preserving life and ending unbearable suffering, and the need to follow his conscience. Although the doctor was found guilty of deprivation of life on request, the sentence imposed was a one-year suspended prison term (District Court of Utrecht, 1952; upheld by the Court of Appeal of Amsterdam, 1952; see also Buijsen, 2024; Weyers, 1998; 2004).

The lenient approach of Dutch courts continued for years. Another example is the 1966 *Mia Versluis* case, in which an anesthetist doctor recommended the removal of the *trachea cannula* to hasten the death of a 21-year-old girl in irreversible coma. Although the Medical Disciplinary Tribunal fined the doctor for “undermining trust in the medical profession”, the public health inspector appealed the decision arguing medical negligence instead. As a result of the court cases that followed, the doctor was acquitted of the original charge and fined only for insufficient reporting (Court of Appeal of Amsterdam, 1969).

In a 1973 landmark case, Dr Postma, a general practitioner, was sentenced to one-week suspended prison for complying with her severely ill mother’s request to administer a lethal dose of morphine. The ruling constituted a turning point because, for the first time, the court considered the possibility of impunity for a life-ending act on request (District Court of Leeuwarden, 1973; see also Buijsen, 2024). The court followed the expert opinion of the health inspector and held that the

defense of necessity could be accepted in the following cases: the patient was incurable, experienced unbearable suffering, had clearly expressed a wish to die, the act was performed by a physician, and a second doctor was consulted and agreed to the proposed action. In the legal and ethical debate that followed the *Postma* ruling, the patient's self-determination was invoked for the first time in the context of end-of-life decisions. The ruling was followed by civil society action, notably the creation of the Dutch Association for Voluntary Euthanasia (NVVE) in 1973.

Between 1978 and 1981, Dutch courts delivered four judgments in assisted suicide cases (see Weyers, 2004 for details). Among these, the 1981 *Wertheim* ruling is most relevant for the due care and reporting requirements developed therein (District Court of Rotterdam, 1981). Mrs. Wertheim, a 76-year-old (non-medical) activist, was charged with helping a 67-year-old woman end her life. The Rotterdam District Court ruled that if specific due care criteria were met, the interest of the persons wishing to end their life outweighed the legislature's interest in criminalizing assistance in suicide. The court raised the possibility of accepting the necessity defense and referred to the criteria set in the *Postma* ruling. Although Mrs. Wertheim had not met most of the criteria, a lenient sentence was imposed (6 months suspended prison with a one-year probation).

The 1984 *Schoonheim* case reached the Dutch Supreme Court. The ruling confirmed the possibility for physicians to invoke the necessity defense and thereby provided a legal ground for their involvement in voluntary euthanasia (Supreme Court, 1984). It emphasized that physicians could successfully invoke the necessity defense if they had rigorously weighed the duties and interests involved, acted consistently with medical ethics and professional standards, and made an objectively justifiable decision. Later, in the *Rademaker* case, the Supreme Court held that euthanasia could never be regarded a natural cause of death (Supreme Court, 1987). Furthermore, as ruled by the Leeuwarden Court of Appeal, only a physician could successfully invoke the necessity defense; other healthcare professionals, such as nurses, could not (Court of Appeal of Leeuwarden, 1995).

Following the case law, a set of due care criteria was incorporated into the first procedural rules. Other stakeholders also made a significant contribution to the development of Dutch policy on physician-assisted dying. Notably, the Royal Dutch Medical Association (KNMG) called for the removal of legal uncertainty and the establishment of rules

enabling physicians to report life-ending acts performed under due care. By setting out their position on how physicians could professionally address patients' life-ending requests, the Dutch Medical Association helped develop the due care criteria into elements of a professional standard (KNMG, 1984).

The associated legal and ethical debates prompted further momentum for legislative action. In 1982, a State Commission was established to produce a report on the definition of euthanasia and the criteria for its justification. Published in 1985, the State Commission report concluded with a call for statutory rules (Groenhuijsen and van Laanen, 2006). Official, nationwide empirical studies followed to explore the frequency and characteristics of reported euthanasia cases (Rommelink report, Ministry of Justice and Ministry of Welfare, 1991). Following several unsuccessful legislative proposals, an agreement was reached in 2001. The *Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review Procedures) Act* – hereafter, the Euthanasia Act³ – entered into force on 1 April 2002.

The Euthanasia Act sets out the due care and reporting requirements (notification procedure). Unlike other jurisdictions that differentiate between euthanasia and assistance in suicide, the Dutch act treats them alike, as it subjects both to the same requirements. However, it distinguishes them from other medical decisions on ending life – such as withdrawing/withholding life-prolonging medical interventions, or refraining from performing a procedure deemed medically pointless – which remain outside its scope.

As in Hungary, euthanasia and assistance in suicide still constitute criminal offences under Dutch law. Further to the Euthanasia Act, a physician's involvement constitutes a *justifiable and non-punishable exception if and only if the due care and reporting requirements are met*. This exception does not extend to other medical professionals (e.g., nurses) or to non-medical persons (relatives, friends, other laypersons) who risk prosecution, as in Hungary.

The scope of the Euthanasia Act is limited to the termination of life upon the patient's personal request. Actively ending life without the patient's explicit request is outside the scope of the Euthanasia Act, although some borderline cases remain debated, such as situations of extreme urgency, patients unable to express their wishes, and children younger than 12. (The Act also applies to minors aged 12 or older. For

³ Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review Procedures) Act (Wet toetsing levensbeëindiging op verzoek en hulp bij zelfdoding (WtI) (2002).

details on parental involvement and consent, see Verhagen and Buijsen, 2023). Furthermore, a life-ending act can only be justified if the patient's condition has a medical dimension. Initially this encompassed only somatic conditions. Later, in the *Chabot* case, the Dutch Supreme Court ruled that non-somatic (mental) suffering could also be considered, albeit with extra caution. What mattered was the unbearable and hopeless nature of the suffering (Supreme Court, 1994). At present, a medically classifiable illness or disorder must be diagnosed, which may include psychiatric disorders, dementia, and other age-related conditions. However, "tired of life" situations are not considered justifiable exceptions, as ruled by the Supreme Court in the *Brongersma* case (Supreme Court, 2003; on the "tired of life" debate, see Buijsen, 2018).

To meet the due care criteria set in the Euthanasia Act, the doctor must be satisfied that: the patient's request is voluntary, based on appropriate information about his/her condition and prognosis, and carefully considered; the suffering is unbearable with no prospect of improvement; and the patient's condition allows for no reasonable alternative. Furthermore, the doctor must consult at least one other independent physician and ensure due medical care during the life-ending act. For transparency and accountability reasons, the doctor must comply with the notification procedure – meaning they must immediately report the death to the medical examiner (coroner) using a standard form. The medical examiner must investigate the cause of death, verify the completeness and accuracy of the doctor's report, and notify one of the five Regional Review Committees operating in the Netherlands. Comprising lawyers, medical doctors, and ethicists, these Committees review all euthanasia cases. If unmet due care requirements are found, the Committees refer the case to the prosecutorial authorities. Although criminal prosecutions are extremely rare (Groenhuijsen and van Laanen, 2006), other sanctions (e.g., disciplinary) may be imposed.

Dutch case law shows that historically, the defense of necessity (balancing the simultaneous duties to preserve life and alleviate suffering) was pivotal in justifying physicians' life-ending acts. However, some commentators have voiced concerns about assigning to doctors an entirely instrumental role and expecting them to comply with their patients' euthanasia requests whenever the law permits (Kouwenhoven et al., 2019: 46). In this context, it is important to note that the current Dutch legal framework does not create a patient's right that imposes a corresponding obligation on doctors to comply with euthanasia requests. Doctors have a legal right to refuse assistance in dying. They

may refer the patient to another physician but are not legally obliged to do so. While patient empowerment to take and maintain control is emphasized in the legal and ethical debate, the challenge remains to find the right balance between the physician's professional responsibility and the patient's autonomy (see also Kouwenhoven et al., 2019: 48).

Taboo and Transparency in Hungary and the Netherlands

As emphasized in bioethics, fair and proper provision of information and respect for self-determination constitute the basis of other health-related rights. If the former is delayed or poorly developed, other rights are also violated.

In Hungary, patient information emerged first not in the form of a legal right but as a duty imposed on physicians. The Hungarian Doctors' Deontology Code was adopted in 1959.⁴ Article 9 prescribed an exception: if patient information could provoke serious reaction in patients or their relatives, doctors could withhold information or share only some necessary details. Thus, therapeutic privilege was convenient for medical staff as they did not have to communicate the serious diagnosis and face the patient's reaction. It was believed that it was better to tell lies or simply remain silent so as not to cause any psychological distress to the patient. Doctors often used coded language or exchanged envelopes among themselves containing the real diagnosis (Konkoly Thege, 1974).

The first comprehensive Hungarian Healthcare Act was adopted in 1972 (Act II of 1972). Section 45(1) stipulated that the doctor had to inform the patient, the relatives, or – if necessary for the patient's medical treatment – the caregiver, about the illness and the patient's condition in an appropriate manner. In justified cases, the physician could waive this in the interest of the patient. This provision was usually applied in cases of incurable disease, not merely as an exception but as a standard practice. Prior to 1990, information given to patients suffering from incurable diseases was thus considered a case when physicians could withhold information (Sándor, 1991). In 1990, an amendment by Parliamentary Act No XXII of 1990, Section 35(1)(a), invalidated this exception. Since 15 March 1990, all patients must be given full information. This was the first step towards opening up the communication between a dying patient and the doctor. Consequently, once the diagnosis was communicated to patients, they had more opportunities to ask

⁴ Az orvosi rendtartásról szóló 1959. évi 8. tvr.

questions and decide on their treatment. Until then, without proper information, end-of-life decisions could not even be discussed.

While Act II of 1972 specified the obligations of doctors, since 1997, Parliamentary Act No CLIV of 1997 has included patients' rights, among them the right to refuse treatment, including lifesaving and life-sustaining treatment. The regulation was, and still is, very laconic on this matter. Because it has not been given sufficient publicity, there is little awareness of the opportunities for these end-of-life decisions. In practice, very few people seem to avail themselves of this option, and doctors are uncertain about how to implement the law (Busa, Zeller, Csikós, 2018).

Patient information and involvement are prerequisites for end-of-life decisions. Yet, as shown above, until 1990, doctors in Hungary were allowed to refrain from providing information to incurable patients. Although the current law requires proper provision of information in all cases, disclosure of an incurable disease is often inadequate or insufficient, as many treatment options and alternatives need to be discussed. This preparation is called end-of-life planning. It entails longer, multi-stage communication between the doctor, other health professionals, and the patient. As the last stage of a patients' life can last for months or even years, during which their condition may change, information should be given more than once. As it is now rare for someone to die following the natural course of the disease, the onset of a hopeless condition is usually preceded by countless medical interventions, which in some cases attempt to prolong life but also inadvertently increase suffering. For this reason, doctors should not abandon their patients in this last phase, even if they feel helpless. Reducing suffering and accompanying the patient through the last stage of life is not incompatible with a healing role. The lesson of the Binder case from Hungary, mentioned above (Fedor, 2017) is that abandoned patients and their relatives can find themselves in a hopeless situation. This case shows that acts by laypersons can cause unnecessary suffering due to a lack of professionalism, and that assistance provided by a relative may resemble murder committed in the absence of medical help. It can also be a source of conflict among relatives with radically different views on the matter.

As shown above, the current Dutch system strives for transparency and accountability pursued through due care criteria and the notification procedure. It values patients' and doctors' joint involvement in end-of-life planning. Some commentators argue that doctors should be

trained in and equipped for end-of-life planning, and that life-ending acts can only take place in the context of a standing relationship between the patient and the physician (Fontalis et al., 2018). In the Netherlands, it is mostly in the context of general practitioner (GP) care that standing patient-physician relationships develop (Janssens and ten Have, 2001), and GPs perform most life-ending acts. For example, in 2015, 93% of euthanasia cases were performed by GPs (van der Heide et al., 2017). Patients may formulate their request in an ‘advance directive’, and GPs must include these in the medical records. Furthermore, end-of-life care is often provided at the patient’s home. Studies have shown that 65% of cancer deaths occur in the patient’s home environment (Cohen et al., 2008; Rietjens et al., 2009). Nevertheless, the law strictly requires the involvement of physicians, and the current legislative framework has kept death and dying within the realm of medical care.

Transparent and joint end-of-life planning is seriously obstructed in Hungary and other jurisdictions with no legal ground for physician-assisted dying. Research shows that in such countries, patients also request for their life to be ended (van der Heide et al., 2003), yet physicians remain largely untrained regarding professional responsibilities and the challenges posed by end-of-life decision-making (Fontalis et al., 2018). Yet, there has been no significant development in this field in Hungarian health law since 1997, while criminal law continues to strictly prohibit physicians’ assistance in dying. Hungarian criminal law also applies to acts committed abroad that are considered criminal offences in Hungary, even if they would not constitute criminal offences under the law of that country.⁵

Heroic struggle and dignified endurance of suffering are to be honored in the same way as when someone feels they can no longer fight or maintain dignity. When the hospice movement started in Hungary, Poland served as a good example. Later, Hungarian experts went to Georgia and Bosnia to teach hospice care.⁶

In Hungary, the work of Alaine Polcz and Katalin Muszbek⁷ helped hospice care become established. In the field of bioethics, Katalin Hegedűs has been most involved in hospice care (Hegedűs, 2006). The textbook on palliative care was edited by Ágnes Csikós (Csikós, 2014).

⁵ Section 3(1) of the 2012 Hungarian Criminal Code.

⁶ Interview with Katalin Muszbek on 15 February 2024.

⁷ *Ibid.*

Developing the hospice movement required great effort in Hungary. As part of our Leviathan Project, we conducted several interviews with experts, including a long interview with Katalin Muszbek on 15 February 2024. She pointed out how much resistance she initially encountered when talking to oncology patients. Doctors believed that patients' expressions of emotion were an obstacle to their recovery. They found it easier to treat a patient who was disciplined and unemotional. Later, when hospice care was launched in Hungary, it was modelled on the system already in place in Poland. However, hospice care is still focused only on oncology patients, with many other dying patients not receiving such care.

The process of dying varies greatly, and palliative and hospice care are not effective for everyone. Not only physical suffering, but also emotional suffering is experienced differently by different people. It is important, however, that whether assisted suicide or some form of euthanasia is permitted by law, palliative care must first be available and meet an adequate standard.

Conclusions

Having examined the differences between Hungary and the Netherlands, we note the divergence in the development of the patient-doctor relationship during the second half of the 20th century. At the end of World War II, a paternalistic and hierarchical physician-patient relationship was dominant in both societies. In Hungary, the various forms and manifestations of paternalism created and maintained throughout the following decades an aura of secrecy around medical decisions concerning the end of life. On the one hand, paternalistic healthcare was provided by the state to patients free of charge at the point of delivery, but it did not encourage them to make autonomous decisions for themselves. Moreover, healthcare was often difficult to distinguish from social care. On the other hand, the recorded malpractice cases indicated that patients and their relatives attempted to challenge this paternalistic allocation of rights.

The legal assessment of end-of-life decisions is a particularly sensitive area. While it is linked to important moral and cultural issues, it also requires a combined assessment of many factors. There are differences in the course of diseases, the evolving possibilities of medicine, the degree of trust in the legal system, the status of bioethics, and the availability and quality of palliative care. It is also difficult to assess the

relationship between regulation and actual medical and nursing practice. One consequence of the taboos surrounding death and dying is that we do not know how and in what way medical decisions are made in intensive care units and other wards, where such decisions may partly replace self-determination. The threat of prosecution poses obstacles to the open debate in Hungary. Despite rich literature and opinion surveys, Hungarian medical law developed the right to refuse (certain types of) treatment only in 1997, and neither euthanasia nor assisted suicide have been legalized ever since. Providing information, even in case of the incurable disease, is the first step towards opening the discussion with the patient about choices. In Hungary, therapeutic privilege constituted an obstacle for decades, and although it was legally eliminated in 1990, open communication at the end of life was not followed by recognition of physician-assisted dying. Unlike in the Netherlands, where transparency was an explicit aim of legal reforms, in Hungary, end-of-life decisions remain opaque, and the current challenge of insufficient access to public healthcare makes it even more difficult to reinforce patients' rights in cases of terminal illness.

In the current Hungarian debate, legitimate doubt has been raised as to whether euthanasia or assisted suicide could be appropriately implemented in the present deteriorating healthcare environment with long waiting lists and many patients who have paid public healthcare premiums for decades only to receive timely treatment at private providers. Such concerns are justified, but it must also be recognized that a patient who is suffering now cannot wait for the health system to improve. Elsewhere, euthanasia debates have been used to bring greater attention to the care of dying patients, palliative care, and hospice care, and have served as catalysts for improvements in these areas. Paradoxically, the taboo on end-of-life decisions can also hasten them, as shown in the *Dániel Karsai v Hungary* case, where many questions were raised at the court hearing about the consequences of the applicant travelling to Switzerland to request assisted suicide there (Sándor, 2024). If the overall situation of patients improves, a wider range of end-of-life decisions could be made available to individuals whose condition becomes incompatible with human dignity and unbearable despite receiving help.

In the Netherlands, the Euthanasia Act was adopted following judicial decisions, empirical studies, and initiatives by healthcare professionals and civil society. Together, these contributed to lifting of the

taboo on end-of-life decisions. A gradual shift occurred from a predominantly paternalistic approach towards an emphasis on joint decision-making. It took decades for this shift to materialize. Without attempting any causal inferences, we can highlight several factors in this context. Our analysis has focused predominantly on legal elements, and specifically on case law developments guided by medical ethics, which paved the way for the adoption of professional standards and statutory rules. Clearly, legal developments tell only part of the story, and several authors have discussed why euthanasia was first permitted in the Netherlands and not elsewhere (see for example, Kennedy, 2002, Weyers, 2004). Legal change occurred against the background of broader societal shifts. Since the 1960s, changes characterized by secularism and growing individualism have loosened the taboos on several aspects of life including death and dying. Patient autonomy has become emphasized, together with rights to information and to (refusal of) consent. These developments laid the foundations for the general acceptance of physician-assisted dying as a legitimate topic for debate, which in turn created room for empirical studies providing better evidence-base for policy and legislative action.

The Dutch approach to end-of-life decisions has been characterized as very specific and pragmatic (Groenhuijsen and van Laanen, 2006; Buijsen, 2024⁸). It has also been widely challenged due to the inconsistencies resulting from the compromises it involves: criminalizing whilst making exceptions, ensuring some recognition of patients' self-determination while granting physicians the right to refuse their patients' life-ending requests (Buijsen, 2024: 11). Even so, the Dutch case shows that, with guidance from the medical profession, the judicial system has lifted end-of-life decisions from the realm of taboos, treated them as facts of life, and focused on ensuring procedural justice. The current Dutch system strives to ensure due care, accountability, and transparency of physicians' life-ending acts. Nevertheless, the current legislative framework upholds medicalization and keeps death and dying within the realm of medical care, since physicians may comply with their patients' life ending requests (under regulated conditions) but may also refuse them. Finding the right balance between the physician's professional responsibility and the patient's autonomy remains a challenge in the Netherlands as well as in Hungary.

⁸ An example for Dutch pragmatism is provided by Buijsen (Buijsen 2024: 8): between 1994 and the 2002 enactment of the Euthanasia Act, the legal prohibition of euthanasia co-existed with an official regulation on the method of reporting cases.

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The Fear of AIDS in Late Socialist Poland¹

Abstract: *The emergence of AIDS in the early 1980s, a new deadly disease that attacked the human immune system, caused panic around the world. The fear of AIDS led to the stigmatisation of its victims and even to acts of violence against them. Much of the blame for the spread of panic lay with the media, which hysterically portrayed AIDS as the plague of the twentieth century or the wrath of God. Even the mainstream media perpetuated prejudices against the two main risk groups – men who have sex with men and intravenous drug users. The lack of reliable health education, which failed in many countries, exacerbated the situation. Fear of AIDS arrived in Poland from the West before HIV itself. The article argues that the Polish media exacerbated the panic surrounding AIDS in Poland in the late 1980s. Unverified information and fear-mongering predictions found fertile ground in a society marked by a low-levels of health education and widespread mistrust in the efficiency of the national health service. The communist authorities failed to stem the tide, even though they had a powerful tool at their disposal – censorship.*

Keywords: *AIDS; health; censorship; media; public fear.*

Introduction

In April 1988, the whole of Poland followed a court case that became known as the first AIDS trial (Jankowski, 1988). Elżbieta L., the head of a biochemistry laboratory at the Medical Centre for Higher Education in Łódź, sued the management of the facility for what she believed were wrongfully withheld salaries. Financial penalties had been

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imposed on her and eight other laboratory technicians for refusing to conduct standard blood tests on African students coming to Poland to study. Elżbieta and her colleagues cited fear of contracting the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) as the reason for their refusal, claiming that the clinic's management had not even provided basic protective measures such as rubber gloves. The court handed down a verdict akin to that of King Solomon: it dismissed the claim, stating that laboratory workers had no right to refuse to perform the tests, while also requesting that the clinic's superior authority investigate the operational shortcomings that had led to the dispute. During the trial, it became clear that the clinic not only failed to provide gloves, but also failed to train staff in diagnosing HIV infections.

The nation's first AIDS trial highlighted three key issues that characterised late socialist Poland's response to the HIV/AIDS health crisis: the inefficiency of the healthcare system, the low level of health education – even among medical personnel – and, above all, fear. It also demonstrated what fear, stemming from ignorance and reinforced by a sense of being inadequately equipped to face a threat to one's health, can lead to. Social exclusion and stigmatisation of not only AIDS victims, but also individuals merely suspected of being HIV positive, coupled with racial prejudice, occurred when laboratory technicians refused to perform tests based on patients' African origin rather than their health status. Commenting on the verdict, the Polish legal press equated it with denying medical staff the right to fear.

The refusal of Polish laboratory personnel to work with potentially infected patients was just one manifestation of fear of AIDS, a global phenomenon that has gripped the world since the early 1980s when the first cases of acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS) were diagnosed in the United States. In 1987, Jonathan Mann, director of the World Health Organization's Special Programme on AIDS, was already talking about public fear of AIDS as a "third epidemic", the first being an epidemic of the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection and the second an epidemic of full-blown AIDS (Mann, 1987: 1).

The medical experts were aware of the potential risks that this spiralling fear could entail. As early as September 1985, Dr Dimitri Viza, head of the Laboratory of Immunology at the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Paris VI, warned that the public fear of AIDS could have more devastating consequences than the syndrome itself (Viza, 1985: 281). This was particularly visible in its impact on medical ser-

vices. The fear of accidentally catching the disease at work, as experienced by Polish laboratory personnel, was just one aspect of the issue (Wallack, 1989; Lego, 1994; Gańczak, 2007; Florom-Smith, 2012). Another issue was that the majority of initial AIDS cases were among intravenous drug users (IDUs) and men who have sex with men (MSM). Consequently, many health workers found it particularly stressful to care for patients whose lifestyles and values were quite different from their own (Pleck et al., 1988: 42). For these reasons, many nurses and physicians quit their jobs, which in turn put a strain on local health services. This only added to the huge financial pressure on health systems caused by the extremely high costs of treating AIDS patients. Most likely John K. Watters was right when he said that “no other modern public health issue has aroused more political ardour, fear, and public imagination than AIDS” (2002: 22).

Among the general population, fear of AIDS has manifested itself in various ways: fear of transmission, fear of suffering and death, and fear of the burden of caring for the sick (Maman et al., 2009: 2274-5). But the fatal nature of the disease, coupled with the fact that medicine at the time offered no cure or vaccine, was only one reason for the panic. Another was the fear of being stigmatized and socially rejected (Gilbert, 2010; Wolf, 2014). AIDS was from the outset widely considered to be a consequence of immoral behaviour. This was heavily exploited by various moralist groups, particularly those based on religious beliefs, who considered AIDS to be a divine punishment and a natural consequence of a “sinful” lifestyle (Kowalewski, 1990: 91). As both IDUs and MSMs were generally stigmatised at the time in many countries, contracting HIV or suffering from AIDS carried an additional stigma similar to that associated with venereal diseases such as syphilis. As Susan Sontag explains, “like syphilis a disease of, or contracted from, danger others”, AIDS was perceived as “afflicting, in greater proportions than syphilis ever did, the already stigmatized” (1990: 115-6). Just as the fear of contracting syphilis led many patients to suffer from venereophobia, the fear of AIDS produced a similar neurotic reaction (Frolkis, 1986; Ross, 1988). In the United States, the first country to be hit by the AIDS epidemic, a wave of fear-induced hostility towards anyone associated with the disease spread like “wildfire” across the nation (Patton, 1996: 11). From the early 1980s onwards, the fear of AIDS gripped American society to such an extent that the public reaction was “not always rational” (Hannaway et al., 1995: 3). People with AIDS were evicted from their homes and their children were expelled from

schools (Adler & Weller, 1984: 1177). As Viza warned, there were calls at the time for the detention and quarantine of people with AIDS symptoms, as well as advocacy for mandatory HIV testing. This stigma embraced even medical staff and volunteers involved in AIDS care, as it was believed that they could unintentionally transmit the disease to the general population (Snyder et al., 1990).

The many aspects of fear associated with AIDS have long been studied, primarily in clinical works and sociological surveys. Understanding the origins of the fear of AIDS, its various manifestations and effects, has been and continues to be central to addressing the health crisis it created, and has long been the focus of social and health policy studies (Foreman & Taylor, 1990). Although neither the disease nor the fear it generated has gone down in history, it has already become a subject of reflection from a historical perspective, and a research field within the history of public health, the history of medicine and, more broadly, the medical humanities (Doka, 1997).

On the ground, whether in democratic countries, theocratic satrapies, or communist regimes, the fear of AIDS has manifested itself through characteristics specific to a local mix of political, social and economic conditions, prevailing beliefs, and the degree of openness of public debate. In the case of late socialist Poland, Jill Owczarzak notes that the fear of AIDS was largely the result of inadequate health education (2009: 422). As a result of the lack of sound educational campaigns, the public did not know how the virus was transmitted and how to protect themselves against it. This was true not only for ordinary people, but also for medical professionals, who initially took excessive precautions when caring for the sick. Agata Fiedot links the extent of the AIDS panic in Poland to the prevailing perception among Poles of the inefficiency of the national health service, which for economic reasons was unable to provide basic protective equipment and ensure minimum hygienic standards (2015: 316).

This article provides further evidence for the argument that inadequate health education and inefficiency of national health services were key factors in the spread of AIDS in late socialist Poland. This applied to both the general population but also to two groups that were crucial to the functioning of the state: health workers and law enforcement officials. This article points to the media, particularly newspapers, as being at least partially responsible for instilling and exacerbating the panic, and considers how this fear was mitigated.

This qualitative analysis draws on the most influential daily and weekly newspapers in late socialist Poland. These were official mouthpieces of the ruling Polish United Workers' Party and included *Życie Warszawy*, *Trybuna Ludu* and *Polityka*. Where press debates concerned legal matters, the leading popular legal journal *Prawo i Życie* was analysed. Also analysed were state radio programmes, particularly transcripts prepared by Radio Free Europe based on their daily monitoring of broadcasts from behind the Iron Curtain. To provide an alternative to the official line, the émigré magazine *Kultura*, published by Polish circles in the West, was also analysed. For the final part of 1989, the last year of communist rule in Poland, two of the first independent publications, *Tygodnik Solidarność* and *Gazeta Wyborcza*, were examined.

Polish Media on Fearing AIDS in the West

Unlike in the Soviet Union, where official propaganda claimed that the 'moral foundations' of communist society would prevent the spread of AIDS ('SPID bez sensatsiy', 1987), in Poland, reporting on the health crisis in the West was relatively free of ideological framing. From the very beginning, the overall tone of Polish media discourse was rather gloomy, anticipating a near apocalypse. In May 1983, when the global number of AIDS cases had not yet exceeded one thousand and the cause of the disease was still unknown, the Polish press debated whether the epidemic should be feared. One journal asked "Does AIDS threaten only homosexuals? Is it only in the USA? Will it reach us?" (Mozołowski, 1983). Any illusions were effectively dispelled by Professor Stefania Jabłońska, a dermatologist at the Medical Academy in Warsaw, who said: "[AIDS] is a big problem. It will come to us". This brief statement captured the sense of inevitability and danger conveyed by the article's title, which described AIDS as a "mysterious and deadly" disease. The article, one of the first on AIDS to appear in the Polish press, helped instill an atmosphere of fear that was reinforced a few months later by another text entitled "AIDS Means Fear" (Baszkiewicz, 1983). This was a transcript of an interview with Professor Witold Brzosko, head of the Immunopathology Department at the Institute of Infectious and Parasitic Diseases. Although he acknowledged the high mortality rate of up to 60 per cent, he did not believe it was caused by a new, previously unknown virus. Instead, he attributed it to common pathogens and argued that the disease was first diagnosed in the United States due to the effectiveness of the medical system and the "poor so-

cial hygiene” prevalent among “communes of people living very casually”, by which he meant the gay community. Both fear-mongering articles appeared in *Polityka*, the second most important press organ of the Polish United Workers’ Party. The journal has been considered a government mouthpiece since 1982, following the appointment of its former editor, Mieczysław Rakowski, as prime minister (Pamuła, 1987: 165). In December 1983, the editors of the largest Warsaw-based Polish daily newspaper, *Życie Warszawy*, reassured readers that there was still a long way to go to “the hecatomb that the plague or cholera did in the Middle Ages”. However, these reassurances did not sound very convincing in an article whose title reminded readers that medicine is still helpless against this threat (“Medycyna”, 1983). Paradoxically, the article criticised Western societies’ panic reactions, including fears over infection through blood derivatives such as the hepatitis B vaccine. Indeed, until reliable tests were invented, the risk such a vaccine could be produced from HIV-infected blood was significant. On the other hand, when writing about the phenomenon of “blood fear” observed in the United States (avoidance of blood donation or fear of transfusion), the article essentially transplanted this fear into Poland, even before the virus itself had arrived. Over the following years, as AIDS panic grew in the West, even trivial reports about the epidemiological situation in the United States, France, West Germany or Great Britain were conveyed in a fear-mongering manner by the Polish press. When the editors relayed reports from the foreign press without commentary, the title tended to emphasise the most dramatic element of the message, rather than its essence. This was the case in August 1985, when *Życie Warszawy* reported on the steps taken in the United States to protect the civil rights of seropositive individuals. The article, entitled “Law against discrimination of AIDS sick people,” was given a subtitle proclaiming “The threat of a global plague,” printed in larger and bolder type, even though the article did not discuss AIDS as a public health issue or the extent of it (“Prawo”, 1985).

Comparisons with the great decimators of populations in former centuries, above all the plague, fostered an atmosphere of danger. The phrase ‘AIDS – the plague of the 20th century’ has become firmly embedded in the Polish language, just as it has in English or German (No one has, 1985; Baumgart, 1985). In September 1985, the host of the nationwide Polish Radio One programme said on air that he was terrified by the virus, likening it to the medieval bubonic plague (Radio, 1985: 15). Neither the representative of the National Hygiene Institute

nor the Ministry of Health and Welfare, who were present in the studio, objected to this comparison. Although such ominous opinions appeared frequently in the national media, there was no shortage of voices claiming that the threat of AIDS was being underestimated in Poland. In September 1985, Zbigniew Siedlecki, writing regularly in *Trybuna Ludu*, the most influential organ of the Polish United Workers' Party, cautioned against dismissing the AIDS threat as something distant and unreal. In his view, Poles treated Western reports as fairy tales about "an iron wolf from across seven rivers and seven mountains" (Siedlecki, 1985). Siedlecki warned that if HIV was not yet in Poland, it would arrive any moment, and asked rhetorically whether doctors without any experience with the disease would be able to diagnose it correctly. He called for preparation not only in the medical sphere, which he considered relatively easy, but above all in education, "by calmly and factually informing young people of the potential danger".

Just over a month later, this potential danger became a reality when, in October 1985, HIV antibodies were detected in several blood samples taken from donors ("AIDS dotarł", 1985). Only then did the authorities, who had previously been largely indifferent to the AIDS panic spread by the media, begin to tone it down. On 29 October 1985, government spokesman Jerzy Urban raised the issue of the first HIV-positive cases in Poland at a briefing. But when Kenneth Banta of *The Times* asked for comment, Urban responded with bravado ("Konferencja", 1985). He claimed that Poland had prepared "well in advance" for the challenges posed by AIDS, boasting that the country's health service was addressing the problem before any cases of infection had been detected, while the whole world was "just getting acquainted with the disease". One manifestation of this concern on the part of the Polish government was the distribution of 50,000 copies of information leaflets to medical professionals in 1984. In addition, as soon as HIV tests became available, Poland purchased large numbers abroad and began testing people in the highest risk groups – MSM, IDUs and haemophiliacs who needed frequent blood transfusions.

In fact, Poland was the first country in the communist bloc to appoint a government plenipotentiary for AIDS, with the rank of deputy minister of health – a move which could indeed give the impression of unusual openness, vigilance and, above all, readiness to face the challenges posed by AIDS. The role was given to General Jerzy Bończak, a military doctor and head of the Military Institute of Hygiene and Epidemiology, tasked with coordinating research on high-risk groups. The

next step included nationwide screening of blood donors. Doctors were trained and treatment centres were prepared. A special hard currency grant was made available to enable the import of diagnostic kits (Rich, 1985). Yet the office of government plenipotentiary for AIDS had been created only a month earlier, and at the time Urban was praising Poland's achievements in the fight against AIDS, General Bończak, who was in charge, had little to report. The following months showed that all the assurances that the state was well prepared were exaggerated, and Urban, who, according to a popular saying of the time, 'lied every time he opened his mouth', once again lived up to his reputation (Januszkiewicz, 2007). Almost exactly a year later, in October 1986, the first known death from AIDS occurred in Poland.

Fearful Pillars of the Socialist State

The reality check came quickly, as the press became rife with reports of inadequate health service responses to AIDS. In mid-1987, panic erupted in a Warsaw hospital when surgeons mistakenly assumed that the patient they were about to operate on had AIDS. This information could not be verified, as no one had sufficient knowledge of the disease. As Tomasz Jastrun (writing under the pseudonym Witold Charłamp), an opposition journalist who described these events in *Kultura*, a Polish journal published in Paris, pointed out, the major problem in dealing with AIDS was a lack of trust that existing procedures were being followed. But there was also a broader lack of trust in the state itself. In the same account from Warsaw, Jastrun cited a conversation he overheard between two nurses in another hospital. They believed that the number of AIDS patients in Poland and the contagiousness of the HIV virus were much higher than official announcements indicated. However, they did not expect more reliable information from the authorities, because, in their view, the communist government would never tell the truth (Charłamp, 1987). One nurse concluded that, given the poor state of the health service, Poland 'absolutely cannot' afford an AIDS epidemic.

Describing the AIDS epidemiological situation in Poland in March 1989, *Życie Warszawy* aptly titled its report "The Avalanche" (Nazarewicz, 1989a). According to the author, Poland was completely unprepared for the rising wave of HIV infection and the growing number of full-blown AIDS cases. The blame lay with the authorities, who, as she put it, seemed to be completely immune to AIDS, ignoring all the signals of how the epidemic was unfolding in the West. If, as Urban

claimed, the high risk of infection among intravenous drug users was known from the start, why had no departments been prepared to treat them? Nazarewicz recalled the case of Ward 6 of a psychiatric hospital in Warsaw, the first unit to test patients with a history of intravenous drug abuse for HIV since 1986. The discovery of the first positive case in August 1988 unleashed an avalanche that nearly brought the ward to collapse, exposing how illusory all the assurances of preparedness really were.

The inadequate preparation of doctors resulted in panic among those who were supposed to be on the front line of the fight against the epidemic – the health workers. Their courage and self-confidence were not helped by the poorly equipped and supplied hospitals in which they had to fight this battle. By autumn 1989, the poor state of the health service had become the subject of a lively media debate in which, alongside communist newspapers, media associated with the democratic opposition also took part. Censorship was still in place – it would only be abolished six months later, but press freedom took on a new dimension. It was no longer the controlled, government-inspired ‘constructive criticism’ of earlier years. The debate, or rather the argument over the actual condition of the health service on the eve of the expected AIDS epidemic, was again triggered by Nazarewicz, reporting on the situation in the maternity wards of the Warsaw hospitals, which she considered hopeless. In the absence of basic sanitary equipment, such as gloves or aprons, nurses refused to work with HIV-infected patients – due largely to poor information on how the virus spreads. To prevent paralysis of hospital wards, Nazarewicz proposed isolating pregnant women suspected of being infected, which in the absence of properly equipped isolation rooms in hospitals meant, as she put it, replacing the bathroom with a bucket (Nazarewicz, 1989b). In a similar vein, Teresa Bochwic wrote in the democratic *Tygodnik Solidarność*, criticising the failure of all attempts to introduce a system for isolating AIDS patients (Bochwic, 1989). This example clearly demonstrates that the hysterical way of writing about the threat depended not so much on the political orientation of the newspaper, but on the level of education and responsibility of individual journalists.

The misconceptions about the principles of AIDS treatment contained in these two articles were corrected by Jacek Fronczak, a journalist from the democratic *Gazeta Wyborcza*. He explained that nowhere in the world are HIV positive isolated, but treated in general hospitals (Fronczak, 1989). Characteristically, both he and the two authors

he accused of incompetence, referred to medical authorities by name and function. Thus, the discrepancies in the Polish media discourse on AIDS reflected differences in the views and expertise of the medical community, rather than the political orientation of newspapers or the professionalism of their journalists.

Another professional group particularly vulnerable to HIV infection was the law enforcement personnel. In March 1989, the community of police officers in Poland was shaken by the arrest in Warsaw of a burglar who turned out to be HIV-positive. He informed the police officers who arrested him and temporarily bandaged the head wound inflicted on him by the desperate owner of shop he had robbed. Neither they nor the interrogating inspector knew what to do in such a situation. They did not know how to confirm or deny the information the detainee had given them on his positive HIV diagnosis. This was eventually done by calling the number he gave for his doctor, who confirmed the diagnosis by telephone (Chećko, 1989). The case provoked criticism. It was suggested that by confirming the positive result of the HIV test, especially over the phone, the doctor may have breached medical confidentiality. However, there was no shortage of opinions to the contrary, claiming that the case was clearly covered by the existing Medical Practitioners Act of 1950, which exempted situations where maintaining secrecy could “cause substantial danger to the life and health of the individuals being treated, or to those around them” (Ożegowski, 1989).

As the case unfolded, it revealed not only the lack of procedures, but also the dire state of equipment for dealing with situations where law enforcement personnel risked infection. The station did not even have rubber gloves or disinfectants, let alone tests. The burglar was released because, although his guilt was beyond doubt, the prosecution wanted to avoid the hassle of keeping him in custody. The Health Officer of the Ministry of Internal Affairs ordered that the rooms where he had been held and interrogated be taken out of use until they were disinfected. However, the order was not accompanied by the provision of the necessary supplies, and the station staff carried out the disinfection using spirit and chloramine obtained privately. The only pair of rubber gloves, obtained from the burglar’s doctor, remained in use long after his release. Commenting on the story, the press pointed out that this was yet another professional community, after health care and education, left to fend for itself in the face of the challenges posed by the growing problem of AIDS, despite four years of “official and supposedly serious” interest in the issue from state authorities.

Mitigating Fear

Although most medical experts agreed that education was the most effective way to mitigate this fear, many preferred silence over providing accurate information about AIDS. In communist countries, the common tendency to avoid difficult social topics, driven by a misguided desire to protect morality, was paired with strict media censorship. Following the Second World War, censorship became “one of the pillars of the new regimes” in Eastern Europe (Szulc, 2018: 134). In Poland, responsibility lay with the Main Office for the Control of the Press, Publications and Public Performances (Główny Urząd Kontroli Prasy, Publikacji i Widowisk, GUKPPiW), established in 1946. The primary aim was preventive censorship: blocking the publication of any material that might undermine communist power or damage the alliance with the Soviet Union. Censors were guided by official directives, but also by their own vigilance, reacting eagerly to any deviation from the political line of the communist authorities.

Any wording that tarnished Poland’s image was removed from publications, including criticism of the health service or information about local outbreaks of epidemics or food poisoning. Such information could only be published with the approval of the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare or the Chief Sanitary Inspector. Tomasz Strzyżewski, a censor who fled to the West in the 1970s, believed that the purpose of blocking information on health risks was to prevent “popular panic over an epidemic or a safety hazard by presenting such problems as involving isolated individuals rather than whole segments of the population” (Strzyżewski, 1984: 211). As he saw it, ‘the risk of exacerbating an epidemic by not warning people to avoid exposure’ was one the communist authorities were willing to take.

As it appears, this was also true in the case of AIDS. At a conference on the legal aspects of AIDS in September 1988, Bogdan Michalski noted that, until then, the authorities had not been interested in fully disclosing the truth ‘for fear of creating a feeling of panic or, at the very least, anxiety’ (Michalski, 1990: 280). Censors intervened both locally and nationally, employing various methods. In Szczecin, for example, where medical staff – like those in Łódź mentioned in the introduction – refused to test African students, local authorities effectively prevented the press from covering the case by prohibiting state employees from granting interviews (Michalski 1990: 286). In Warsaw, on the other hand, interference by censors resulted in the first Polish book on AIDS being given a different title. Its author, Zofia Kuratowska, Professor of

Haematology at the Medical Academy in Warsaw, attempted to explain AIDS in accessible terms. Her book, published in 1986, was entitled *AIDS – A New Disease*. Only after the transition to democracy did Kuratowska reveal that the book's original title was *About AIDS Without Panic*, but that communist censors rejected it, claiming that such a title would provoke even more panic. However, the change of title was a rather superficial act; the censorship did not alter the book's tone, which calmly explained the disease while encouraging people to resist "the evils of hysteria, intolerance and obscurantism" (Kuratowska, 1986: 29; Kiełpiński, 2023). Kuratowska's views resonated with those of progressive medical circles in the West, who recognized the dangers of spreading panic (e.g. Viza, 1985: 281; Mann, 1987: 1). It was clear to doctors, psychologists, sociologists and humanists that fear fostered stigmatisation of those infected, leading to social exclusion and, in extreme cases, even to acts of violence.

How, then, did the alarmist reports cited earlier pass the censors? The censorship system in Poland was certainly not leak-proof (Szulc, 2018: 135) and was significantly relaxed in 1986 (Biskupski, 2018: 183). While there is no evidence that the communist authorities intentionally tolerated the alarmist tone of press reports on AIDS to discourage behaviours they disapproved of, such as homosexual relations or intravenous drug use, this cannot be ruled out entirely. Even in democratic countries, fear of contracting incurable, socially stigmatised and fatal diseases has been used in health campaigns (Fairchild et al., 2018). Faced with an impending epidemic and distrustful of the state's ability to protect or reliably inform them about the risk, people of late socialist Poland sought their own ways of mitigating their fear of AIDS. One such method was to insure themselves against the consequences of contracting the disease. In 1988, the first private insurance company in Poland, established under the last economic reforms of the collapsing communist regime, began offering such insurance policies. Effective from 1 August, Poles could take out an insurance policy for a premium of 0.2% of the sum insured, payable as a lump sum or in the form of an annuity if they contracted AIDS, provided they tested negative beforehand. The policy was offered by a newly established private insurance company, Westa, which advertised that it was the first product of its kind in the world ("Westa", 1988). Part of the profits from the sale of the product, the company promised, would be used to fight the disease. Health and catering workers were the first to take out policies. Within

the first month, only 21 people had purchased policies, the highest insured sum being 5 million zlotys – the equivalent of nearly 100 monthly salaries (“Ubezpieczenie”, 1988).

This gave the company extraordinary publicity – it was said that Westa literally insured everything (“Westa” ubezpiecza, 1988). News spread abroad, appearing in Czechoslovakian and Hungarian newspapers and even on U.S. television. A small Canadian company, Joseph Sancroft Insurance Agency Inc., proposed to Westa a partnership in offering the product on the North American markets (“Westa” pierwsza, 1988). At the time, the insurance industry there was grappling with a wave of payouts to AIDS victims under regular life insurance policies. The companies sought to avoid losses and tried to introduce mandatory HIV testing, rather than insuring healthy individuals (Schatz, 1987; Clifford & Iuculano, 1987). Under the terms of the agreement, Westa’s Canadian partner undertook to sell one million policies in Canada and the United States within eight months. For \$500 worth of premiums, clients were offered coverage worth \$250,000, at the same rates as in Poland (“Nasz klient”, 1988). Whether any were sold is unknown, but Westa, already known for its unconventional and risky ideas (including selling insurance against the effects of inflation, which was prevalent in Poland at the time), went bankrupt five years later.

Conclusions

The HIV/AIDS health crisis that hit Western societies in the early 1980s triggered a panic that came to be known as the “third epidemic”. Fear of the disease led to stigmatisation and even aggression against members of the main risk groups – MSM and IDUs. Through media reporting, this epidemic of fear, with all its negative consequences, reached the societies of the communist countries of Eastern Europe. In Poland, the Western fear of AIDS took hold four years before the virus itself arrived.

The Polish authorities did not use this time to prepare – they failed to equip health facilities, train doctors, develop safety procedures for health workers and law enforcement, or provide health education for the general population. Instead, fearing that it would cause panic, the communist authorities suppressed reliable information through censorship. However, they also failed in this respect, as sensationalist publications were quite frequent and found fertile ground given widespread disbelief that the collapsing Polish health service could offer protect

people from the epidemic. Seeking reassurance, some Poles turned to alternatives like private insurance, but these proved equally ineffective.

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FIELDWORK NOTES

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Traditional Medicinal Rituals from Mexico Coming to Bulgaria: The Trip of Huichol People

Abstract: *This paper presents in detail the visits of several Mexican Huichol (Wixárika) shamans and their apprentices to Bulgaria between 2014 and 2018. Most of these visits took place in different villages across the country in the form of gatherings (some of which the author personally observed) with Bulgarians interested in exotic spiritual practices. The Wixárika tradition thus appeared for the first time in Bulgaria and, allegedly, on the Balkan peninsula, with all its ritual paraphernalia – amulets, sacred objects, and the spirit of their sacred chanting as well.*

Against this background, the paper examines how these centuries-old healing rituals from a non-European culture were carried out in a contemporary European context, considering that these shamans were based in Switzerland and have traveled across Western Europe before coming to Bulgaria. In addition, the process of internationalization, globalization and commercialization of these rituals, including the participation of non-indigenous shamans and apprentices alike, is also discussed. Finally, the paper considers the possibility of a dialogue between the Bulgarian Christian tradition and the pagan rituals of the Huichol people.

Keywords: *rituals; medicinal practices; Huichol; shamanism; medicine-man.*

This text draws on my personal participation in and observation of Wixárika (Huichol) healing rituals as practiced in Bulgaria between 2014 and 2018, exploring the themes of authenticity and adaptation in the healing narratives of both ritual leaders and Bulgarian participants. The analysis is also based on interviews with both groups, representing an auto-ethnographic approach to the exploration of traditional medical rituals. This research addresses a little-known case in Bulgaria and raises important questions about the authenticity of ‘Native American

practices' and cultural transformation, such as whether the rituals presented as "traditional" are genuinely so or have been influenced by modern, European, or global trends. Also noted are competitive dynamics and the commercialization of the shamanic scene in Bulgaria. The study offers a description of the ceremonies of the Wixárika (Huichol) people as practiced among Bulgarian participants. One of the aims is to show the interaction and cultural exchange between representatives of individual religious movements and beliefs, who manage to combine and create, at least temporarily, a hybrid form that carries elements of both Christian tradition and pagan ritual. Last but not least, attention has been paid to the adaptation and dissemination of all these practices in Bulgaria.

For the purposes of the research, I draw on my personal impressions from participation, as well as information taken from semi-structured interviews with participants in the ceremonies. Also, some notes and ideas from free conversation during the gatherings are mentioned in the text. I consider myself a researcher conducting participant observation, but my prior personal and professional interest and background experience in distant Eastern spiritual and ritual practices (Zen, Japanese martial arts, Chi-gong, Yoga, Buddhist practices, etc.) may have shaped my personal engagement, ideas regarding my own participation, description and subsequent analysis. This research therefore offers one perspective on processes unfolding in recent decades not only in Bulgaria, but also in Europe more broadly.

Due to ethical considerations and standards, all respondents are referred to by initials, with anonymization or pseudonymization strategies used within the framework of informed consent. Only the names of the main shamans and priests are retained in full as they are public figures known in and outside their communities. This distinction reflects implicit differences between these two groups, based on the uneven 'power dynamics' between leaders and followers, teachers and students, natives and newcomers, "sellers" and "consumers", etc.

The Huichol people (Wixárika, or Wixáritari as well) are known as an ethnic group in contemporary Mexico, located in the states of Nayarit, Jalisco, Durango and Zacatecas – municipalities in the extreme south of the West Sierra Madre. Their population, whose native language is Wixarika/Wixaritari waniuki, numbers 61,000 (2025 data). They practice shamanism, but also Catholicism. The Wixárika are sometimes seen, even in Mexico, as overly conservative and detached from modern life, representatives of a culture in which the distinction

between science, magic and religion is blurred. Fragments of Wixárika culture (rituals and healing practices), were brought to Bulgaria by members of this group living outside their homeland, in Europe (Switzerland), where they had migrated for economic reasons years ago. This raises the question of how much of what is presented as traditional is genuinely so, and whether, at the beginning of the XXI century, these practices have been influenced or transformed by the European, modern or global contexts due to the transnational trajectories of migration and settlement outside Mexico.

The Huichol People in Bulgaria: a Personal Chronicle

The first meeting between Bulgarians and Huichol shamans took place in October 2014, in a house in a small village in Lovech District (north-central Bulgaria). There is some ambiguity about who first contacted the Huichol and who invited them to Bulgaria. From an interview with one participant in the ceremonies (V. G., b. 1982, economist, Sofia), it appears that he may have been among the first Bulgarians to do so, in pursuit of new “spirituality” and the “divine”. However, I do not exclude the possibility that he emphasized this role for reasons of self-promotion and prestige. At the time of the interview, he claimed to no longer be interested in “Indians”, preferring instead to look for his “roots” in the Balkans or Asia. Regarding this and other interviews, it is clear that critical reflection on the healing stories of participants in the ceremonies is always necessary – both of those who present and lead these traditional practices, and of those who engage with them in search of knowledge, help or for personal development – in order to achieve greater objectivity amid the many subjective accounts of people with different backgrounds.

A shaman called Don Andres and his apprentice/assistant Victor led¹ a ceremony representing the peyote² (the Huichol call this plant *abuelo*³). All participants in the first gathering were required to bring with them a long list of mostly personal small items (photos, fresh flowers, candles, coins, round mirror, holy water etc.) along with specific food and drinks to share. Many of these items were placed on a specially

¹ It is customary at these gatherings for everyone to address each other by their first name. Only the leaders are addressed with the respectful “Don” (Span.) before their names, but it means something more than just “Sir”.

² A species of North American cactus of the genus *Lophophora williamsii*, the word “peyote” is from the Nahuatl language, and in the Wixárika language the plant is called “jícuri”, “hikuri”.

³ Grandfather (Span.).

built altar (constructed on a large table, with an arc of three branches and flowers). An important detail is that at this first meeting, unlike in all subsequent ceremonies, there was no Indian tipi set up at the gathering site, which would have required more time and preparation. Right from the beginning, the peyote was referred to by the guests, and soon by everyone else, as “*medicina*”.⁴ The officially declared purpose of the gathering (later called a “ceremony” by the guests themselves), was explained from the Huichol perspective as opening the participants’ connection with the Spirit and revealing the divine essence of the Trinity (Deer-Princess-Peyote). This was the main task to which all participants in the circle were expected to adhere. Healing, it was explained, occurred through this connection with the Spirit. Later, during the ceremony itself, the guests also emphasized the importance of this connection with (and respect for) Pachamama.⁵ They explained that this connection would be drawn into the “inside of a circle” and that they “will adhere to this in all activities that are carried out”. An important detail to note is the presence of an interpreter (from Spanish) at all the meetings and ceremonies, which made this role essential to the process of communication.

The ceremony officially begins after sunset, but preparations start in the afternoon. At the very beginning of the rituals, peyote is distributed – the apprentice Victor places it in the mouth of each participant with a tablespoon. The instructions are that everyone may swallow as much as they want. After each spoonful, the participant drinks juice to help with swallowing. After several such “rounds”, the shaman and his assistant talk, occasionally sing, and the “Keeper of the fire” ensures that the flame does not go out. At times, the old shaman falls asleep, during which his apprentice takes over, speaking about the history and culture of his people. Prayers are offered to the “Supreme Power”, sometimes named “Pachamama”, invoked for health and fertility. This continues without pause until the morning when everyone greets the sunrise, and around 8-9 a.m. the ceremony is “closed” by the leaders, after which everyone goes to sleep. All the objects brought by the participants are used, each with a specific purpose, in rituals unfamiliar to the Bulgarians, yet performed trustingly under the instructions of the

⁴ *Medicina* (Span.) – medicine, cure, medication, solution, outcome.

⁵ Pachamama (Quechua: Pacha Mama) – the name given by the people of the Andes to a deity they worship, considered the personification of the Earth. In Inca mythology and religion, she is a “Mother Earth” type omnipresent goddess, linked to fertility, sowing and harvesting.

visitors from Mexico. This was the first such meeting on Bulgarian territory, marking the gradual and layered introduction of Huichol shamanism to a small circle of Bulgarians seeking healing, spirituality, or simply cultural contact.

My most vivid and transformative experience with the Huichol (Wixárika) people took place in the village of Rozovo (Central Bulgaria) in the summer of 2016, where both the ceremonial complexity and my personal involvement deepened significantly. This time the group was larger – around 30 Bulgarians gathered with a Huichol delegation of ten, including Don Andres, Victor, his wife, and their boy, /J., 8 years old/. With them is another family from South America with their son /M., 9 years old/ along with several apprentices from Europe, transforming these gatherings into more elaborate cultural exchanges. Both children played active symbolic roles during the rituals. This was no longer a simple overnight ceremony – it had evolved into something larger, more orchestrated, and more intense. Few hours before the ceremony, male apprentices paint arrows made in advance from sticks (short ritual arrows placed in the arch with flowers on the altar), while women string beads (men may help if necessary). In addition, dozens of amulets are prepared – small wooden figurines of people and other shapes. The Huichol explain that these serve to recreate the world in miniature as well as possible, so that the Spirit could bless it with health and prosperity when the connection is made during the ceremony. Another key element is the altar which always faces East, towards the rising sun. For foreigners, it was important so that everything had its place inside the circle.

At the very beginning of the ceremony, the shamans instruct everyone to take off their festive clothes and put them back on only at the end, the following morning. Otherwise, it was believed to insult the Spirit. The main figures are Don Andres, Victor and his wife, and they also appoint a “leader” among the Bulgarians – S. (b. 1986, an IT-specialist). Once chosen, the old shaman and his assistants begin to call him „*El Cura*“,⁶ or „*Chamaleon*“.⁷ His was a main “role” in the ceremony – S. is made to “play” the role of the one who heals, helps, all the time – a person with the abilities of a healer, and an intermediary between the participants and the Spirit. He is expected to walk around with a small wooden vessel filled with water all the time, which, Victor explains, hold all the power of the ceremony. Using a brush made of

⁶ Priest; treatment; cure; drunkenness (colloquial) (Span.).

⁷ Variant of the word used for chameleon (Span.).

deer hair, the “healer” sprinkles water first on the altar and then on the people.

Little boy M. plays the role of a young deer (or possibly a bull), adorned with two large bundles of bird feathers attached by a white-green cloth around his head. The night before, the child explained that for this ceremony he would take another, sacred name connected with the animal. Another guest, S., plays the role of “Keeper of the Fire”. The German member of the group (J. J., b. 1977), takes out a whistle that imitates the sound of a birdsong to “call” birds and to connect with their spirit. He explains that some of the feathers used are from a jay. Assistant shaman Victor says at this point: “The medicine goes directly to your heart. If your heart is made of stone – you won’t be able to feel anything! ... You must pray – each for himself... We never guarantee visions.” During the rituals, M. falls asleep in his chair. The old shaman rouses him with a shout, and Victor places into his hands an entire pile of candles to be set in prepared holders – bamboo tubes fixed to pegs in front of the altar, fourteen in total. Half-asleep, the boy staggers under their weight, clutching them in a red tower as if carrying a baby. His mother tells him: “You are working, you are not sleeping, and this is not a dream, act!” He is made to spin counterclockwise before attaching the candles haphazardly to the stands, guided by the shamans’ calls – particularly those of Don Andres. Later, the candles in front of the three leaders are also placed by the child and again after spinning. I interpret this as a cleansing of the space, connected to the sacrifice that was to follow. The ceremony usually continues until shortly after sunrise, but this time the meeting with the Huichols is different, divided into two parts, with the afternoon set aside for rest after the morning rituals.

This sacrifice had been arranged in advance with the Bulgarian organizers, who provided an animal purchased from a nearby cattle farm. Some of the participants leave as soon as they hear of these plans. The Huichols explain that the transition of the soul must happen harmoniously (on a spiritual level), so that the spirits (including those of the ancestors) could accept the soul of the sacrificial animal favorably and it may become one with them. Ancestors, in their social hierarchy, occupy the highest status. According to the shamans, the act of sacrifice will ensure health and well-being for those who participate in it.

The shaman and his assistants are cheerful and give instructions and distribute the roles so that the rite of passage happens smoothly and solemnly, and without surprises. The place is decorated with colourful cloths as if for a festivity, but also for a lavish funeral. The atmosphere

itself suggests joy and cheerfulness rather than sorrow and bloodshed. Each participant is carefully positioned around the center where the sacrifice will take place. The black animal is brought into an improvised tent (made of four carts and a canvas roof), then carried – since it refuses to walk – by M. (in the role of the “young deer”/ “bull calf”) and S. (as the “Priest”/ “treatment”) counterclockwise around a dug hole. The shamans’ instruct that six circles are made, but it looks to me there are nine – Don Andres is not counting very accurately. He enjoys watching them struggle to carry the animal, which, despite being small, is still large relative to the child. Then the shamans rearrange all those present in the space designated for the ritual in a seemingly symbolic pattern with no obvious logic to myself. They then take out a large knife with a wooden handle and a ball of very thick thread. Don Andres takes the ball and starts to untangle it, passing it to the person next to him – in this way the ball passes through all those present. At the end, they wrap it around everyone several times in an imaginary circle. This produces a strange tangle of many threads (coming from one ball), which seem endless and which connect everyone. While everyone stands and holds the threads, as if “hung” on this (one) thread, the shamans have S. grab the bull calf and walk it around the thread around everyone several times around the entire circle, finally bringing it back to the hole in the center. The Huichols explain that this is how they “mapped” the path of the animal’s soul after it left the body, so it doesn’t get lost but goes directly to the ancestors and merges with them.

The sacrifice itself is performed by the assistant shaman, Victor. The blood is left to flow into the hole in the ground. Victor puts a large piece of the animal’s flesh, which he cut off first, into a jar – apparently giving it ritual significance and planning to use it as medicine later. At the same time, M. collects as much of the flowing blood as he can in a plastic box. Then the child takes the container to the altar and smears everything there with the blood. All participants who want to are smeared with it – parts of their body or any of their items from the altar. The shamans stir the blood using a deer hair brush and sprinkle the participants with it. The Huichols’ explanation is that this brings health and prosperity since the blood from the sacrifice is sacred. Then J. J. and another participant take the animal by the legs and walk it nine times around the hole. Next, they take it to a place to the side of the tent, where they strip the skin. Everyone takes turns to throw coins into the hole containing the blood. Then the boy J. uses a shovel to bury the

coins and traces of the soaked blood in the ground. Later, the flesh is cooked into soup and dried meat.

Afterwards, Don Andres and Victor discussed something uttering a word that sounds like “hikaro” or “hikari” – apparently in the context of Huichol culture. A young man, N. who is sitting nearby – explains to me that it is about the Spirit of the Deer (the sacred manifestation of the Spirit), in his communication with the human’s world.⁸ Shamans speak of it as something that you can chase, catch and defeat, but with which you can and must always communicate. During their visits to Bulgaria, shamans always complete the cycle of ceremonies according to their own rules and criteria. Because of the particularities of their tradition, they invest their actions with meanings and emotions that an outside observer can hardly fully understand. It is likely that some of the more experienced Bulgarian participants are informed in advance of the Huichol’s intentions for organizational purposes. After conducting this series of ceremonies, the guests stay in Bulgaria for some time, traveling and seeking to hunt a deer.

One informer (G. A., b. 1983) also recounted that after the ceremony, on the way back from Rozovo, the bus carrying the guests had a flat tire, with even the bolts on its rim falling out. Don Andres explained that this was because the bull calf did not want to leave Bulgaria and had to stay here. This caused tensions among the group, but no meat from the sacrificial animal was taken out of the country. The Huichols work with the energy of the deer in every ceremony, and in their tales, the bull is the elder brother of the deer. From the meat of the sacrificed calf, the group cooked and ate the ears (to hear better), the eyes (to see better), but not the tail (the reason was not given). The ceremony then continued for another day.

G. A. describes Huichol culture as very “earthly and alive”, as well as “authentic”. What I experienced in Rozovo was not a reenactment or performance, but a living ritual, layered with tradition, symbolism, and raw emotion. For outsiders, roles were assigned not merely to participate but to act as mediators between two realities. Personally, I left with more questions than answers – yet also with a deeper recognition of how ritual can transform the self, bind communities, and make visible otherwise invisible and old traditions.

⁸ In fact, it is about *hicouri* or *jículi* (“the divine luminous one”) the Huichol call the peyot, <https://www.artemarakame.com/blogs/news/el-divino-luminoso-jicuri?srsId=AfmBOopyiwCLBUkAf5GOhfJ4cs9iUuwHEQo5kOKGMNeiCiGZ-D4zV1oX>, (last visit 11.05.2025).

Before and after the Rozovo Gathering

The earlier ceremonies (2014-2015) were simpler – typically held in village houses or fields near Lovech. Peyote was the centerpiece, rituals lasted through the night, and healing practices using *muveri*⁹ (one of the most important sacred tools) were introduced. Over time, the gatherings grew more organized: the use of Indian tipi, the inclusion of children in symbolic roles, and a steady blending of Huichol ritual with local Bulgarian context. In one of the gatherings, the shamans recommend watching a short video – “Viaje Huichol”,¹⁰ to better understand their culture.

One recurring figure from the Lovech area, an old man named M. I., (everyone calls him “Bai”¹¹) has had several meetings and conversation with the foreigners. Bai M. even integrated his own version of evangelical-Christian “speaking in unknown languages” into these exchanges, creating unique moments of spiritual crossover. He is Orthodox, wears a cross around his neck, and is already well-known in the area: people come to his house to answer their questions. The old man often blesses them and offers healing – usually talking for hours without stopping and getting tired, frequently using phrases like “arabe”, “abra” and “kharabia”, while mixing them with quotations from the Bible learned by heart. After a long conversation (through the interpreter), he blesses the Huichol visitors too and gives them a cross, while they give him a beaded bracelet, explaining that it is a sacred object that carries much power.

In late 2016, I heard about another gathering with the same shamans, again near Lovech. A friend of mine, (L. B., b. 1979, archaeologist), attended in search of healing for his sister. He described an intense night – doubt, convulsions, and eventually reassurance. In the morning, Don Andres accepted a pullover from him to stay warm and casually mentioned he was returning to Mexico to meet with the “maracami”¹²

⁹ Muvieri (Span.) – a craft with deep religious symbolism. It consists of a bamboo arrow with feathers – from an eagle or falcon at one end, which are connected by a colored thread. It is used in different Wixárika ceremonies.

¹⁰ Animation 12:13 min. long, presenting key moments from Wixárika mythology, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KgDbq8ur5gI>, (last visit: 05.05.2025).

¹¹ Elder brother, uncle, old man, gaffer, goodman (Bulg.).

¹² *Marakame* (Wixarika) is a person intermediary between the world of humans and spirits. It is also believed he is a person who seeks knowledge in order to interpret what is happening in the world. Also known as *masa'akame* it means a traditional Huichol therapist and/or doctor whose role goes beyond the healing sphere and is limited to social relations as a leader and continuer of the group's traditions.

– ancient, powerful shamans of the Wixárika. Later, L. B. began to suspect that his gift of clothing was also an energetic offering, a notion confirmed by others who had studied Huichol practice: such items are often exchanged as part of asking a question to the spirits. In 2017/18 the ceremonies continued, but in smaller, more private circles. Some Bulgarians even traveled to Switzerland to deepen their training with the Huichol. The process, I'm told, became more rigorous: financial pressure, secrecy, emotional strain. It was no longer just about spiritual seeking – it had become a commitment.

Don Andres (1915 – November, 2017; his family name remains unclear to me) died in Mexico, at the age of over 100 – some Bulgarians have seen his passport during his visits. At his first public meeting with Bulgarians, he was very cheerful, though he used crude language all the time. Even the interpreter was often embarrassed and did not translate everything. The old man had lived in Switzerland in recent years, but often traveled to Mexico. Victor (b. 1976) – a student and assistant of the old shaman, lives in Switzerland and works in construction. After the death of his teacher, he went to the keepers of the tradition in Mexico to discuss the future with the families who had previously “worked” with Don Andres.

The Period after 2018

Some informers say that the Huichols came at the end of July 2019 (a group of 18 persons). During their stay they performed again several rituals, toured Bulgaria, and held an “open” deer hunt in the Sredna Gora mountain – ‘open’ here is to mean it was for everyone interested, not just for the Huichols, their guide, or the Forestry Department officer. The 2019 visit of the Wixárika to Bulgaria was coordinated by a different person, a man with extensive experience in ceremonies, connected to the shaman Jose, who was already famous in Bulgaria. Since this change in the organization, I have not been able to follow these shaman visits.

Under the influence of ceremonies since late 2016, participants from the groups that attended Huichol gatherings have begun to organize their own meetings – workshops, ceremonies, and courses, offering “sacred” practices at more affordable prices, with a certain ritualism that affects/copies the traditions the Wixárika representatives had already introduced in Bulgaria.

After speaking with participants in the Wixárika (Huichol) ceremonies in Bulgaria, most of them Christians, I can note that these events

are part of a wider trend: a growing number of Native American-inspired rituals and gatherings have been taking place across Bulgaria – often independently, yet shaped by similar cultural, religious, and socio-economic factors. Traditional practices from Latin America have found new audiences in Europe, often through traveling shamans seeking followers, healing-seekers, or financial opportunities. Many Bulgarians who later attended Huichol events had already participated earlier in ceremonies involving ayahuasca, peyote, etc. The emergence of Huichol ceremonies in Bulgaria fits into a broader landscape of imported indigenous practices shaped by global exchange, spiritual tourism, and the shifting boundaries between healing, belief, and business.

In Conclusion

The Huichol ceremonies in Bulgaria reflect a complex interplay of cultural exchange, spirituality, and commodification, where healing is viewed differently by Huichol shamans and participants. While the Huichols see healing as a secondary outcome of a deeper spiritual connection – “a result” of a deeper spiritual process, rooted in their cosmology, many Bulgarian participants treat healing as the main goal, often shaped by prior New Age experiences. As these rituals are transplanted into Europe, their meanings evolve, leading to hybrid forms and tensions around authenticity and appropriation. The ceremonies are increasingly commercialized, adapted by both indigenous and non-indigenous facilitators to meet the expectations of a growing spiritual consumer base. This evolving landscape underscores the fluid nature of ritual healing in a globalized world, challenging fixed notions of tradition and highlighting the ongoing transformation of indigenous practices in new cultural contexts.

Visual Materials

Fig. 1. Portative altar on a chair, situated in a room, because it's too cold outside. Image courtesy of the author.

Fig. 2. Huichol's handmade amulet and handmade coverlet above the chair altar. Image courtesy of the author.

Fig. 3. Specially arranged construction of sacred objects – mini altar on the room's floor, representing the four directions of the world. Image courtesy of the author.

Fig. 4. Victor takes the cross as a present from his new Christian friend – the shepherd from the village, "bai" M. (the men with the white hair). Image courtesy of the author.

VITA ACADEMICA

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“Transforming Anxieties of Ageing in Southeastern Europe”

Project Overview: Rethinking Ageing in a Rapidly Changing Region

“Transforming Anxieties of Ageing in Southeastern Europe: Political, Social, and Cultural Narratives of Demographic Change” is a comparative, multidisciplinary research project running from February 2023 to January 2027.¹ Funded by the German Volkswagen Foundation under its initiative “Challenges for Europe: The Greying Continent” and coordinated by the Leibniz Institute for East and Southeast European Studies (IOS) in Regensburg, the project brings together research teams from Germany, Austria, Bulgaria, and Hungary. Researchers from Albania, Croatia, Moldova, North Macedonia, Romania and Serbia add to its comprehensive regional coverage. Together, we examine how demographic ageing is perceived, narrated, and politicized across Southeastern Europe.

The region presents a particularly vivid context for investigating ageing and demographic change. Bulgaria, for instance, has experienced a population decline from nearly 9 million in 1989 to just under 6.5 million today – a trend expected to continue. Across Southeastern Europe, persistently low birth rates, high levels of emigration, and deep

¹ See the project’s website <https://transforming-anxieties.ios-regensburg.de/>

socioeconomic shifts have contributed to one of the fastest-ageing populations in Europe.

Rather than accepting ageing populations as inherently problematic, the project explores how demographic change is framed – as a threat, a challenge, or an opportunity – within political, social, and cultural discourses. We aim to move beyond alarmist or crisis-driven narratives and explore how societies can support inclusive, caring, and meaningful lives for older people, including ethnic minorities, migrants, and other marginalized groups. We also ask which policies are informed by the perceptions and framings we encounter in our research, and vice versa.

The project pursues two core objectives. First, it seeks to generate comparative, multidisciplinary research on ageing and demographic change across Southeastern Europe, drawing on insights from ageing studies, area studies, history, sociology, demography, political science, as well as literary and cultural studies. Second, it aims to transform dominant representations of ageing – shifting from narratives of crisis and decline to those that foreground care, interdependence, dignity, and the agency of older people themselves.

In doing so, the project addresses a major gap in existing scholarship. While most research on ageing has focused on Western Europe and North America, this project centers Southeastern Europe – a region whose socialist legacies, post-socialist transitions, migration patterns, and experiences of marginalization make it both distinctive and emblematic of broader European transformations. Our methodology combines qualitative and quantitative tools, with an emphasis on oral history, ethnographic fieldwork, participatory research, and critical discourse analysis. Central to our inquiry is a commitment to amplifying the voices and experiences of older people themselves.

Theoretical Foundations and Methodology: Multi-scalar, Participatory, Comparative

Bridging ageing studies and area studies, the project integrates historical research, discourse analysis, and ethnographic fieldwork. It is grounded in Michel Foucault's notion of population as a constructed object of governance, and in critical gerontology – particularly Stephen Katz's work on how ageing is socially constituted, regulated, and represented.

We understand ageing as a culturally and politically embedded process, shaped by intersecting narratives of gender, economy, and nationhood. Following Katz’s observation that states are increasingly governed through the age structure of their populations, we examine how demographic change is framed in public discourse – often as a crisis or burden. Framing theory (Robert Entman) serves as a key analytical lens, helping us uncover how dominant interpretations of ageing shape the creation of problems, their moral evaluation, and the institutional responses to them. Linking discourses to policies is therefore central to our analytical agenda. We aim to challenge alarmist framings and foreground more inclusive, care-oriented alternatives.

Our methods include critical discourse analysis of policy texts, media coverage, and political speech; literary analysis of representations of ageing; oral histories and life-course interviews; and comparative demographic analysis and public opinion research. We highlight the long historical trajectories of alarmist demographic discourses and explore in particular the socialist period, as a foundational historical moment for the reproduction of demographic nationalism.

Our mixed-methods approach brings together individual narratives, expert perspectives, policy interventions, and demographic and socio-economic data to examine how ageing is experienced and constructed across diverse sociopolitical contexts. Age is treated as an intersectional and dynamic category, shaped by class, gender, ethnicity, and mobility.

A defining feature of our project is its participatory orientation. Through living labs – collaborative spaces for reflection and co-creation – we actively engage older adults, caregivers, service providers, and community stakeholders. These labs are not just data collection tools, but transformative spaces that shape both our research questions and our vision of a more inclusive society. We are attentive to regional specificities: rather than imposing Western frameworks, we explore local traditions, socialist legacies, and intergenerational networks to re-think what it means to age with dignity. By linking micro-level experiences with macro-level structures, the project develops a new comparative lens on ageing in Southeastern Europe.

Rethinking Ageing in a European Context

Southeastern Europe poses urgent challenges and rich possibilities for reimagining ageing. The region is home to some of Europe’s oldest populations (in demographic terms) and features a unique mix of

cultural, ethnic, and generational diversity. Contradictions abound: strong familial care traditions coexist with weak public welfare systems; widespread emigration is counterbalanced by return migration, enduring transnational ties, and growing immigration from outside of Europe; public concerns about ageing exist alongside disregard for the causes of high mortality and low life expectancy in some countries of the region; low fertility is addressed by pronatalist policies, even though they have repeatedly (since the 1960s) proved to be ineffective.

By situating local experiences of ageing within broader transnational dynamics, the project examines how care chains, labor mobility, and EU frameworks shape the social life of ageing. We also explore how demographic anxieties – linked to population ageing, emigration, and minority groups – are mobilized in political rhetoric to fuel nationalism, conservatism, xenophobia, and exclusion. Against such tendencies, we advocate an alternative paradigm. Instead of technocratic fixes or alarmist responses, we emphasize care, participation, and social justice. Ageing should not be feared but better understood. Southeastern Europe – with its underexplored traditions of care and intergenerational solidarity – offers valuable insights for Europe at large.

Research Structure: Five Interconnected Clusters

The project is organized into five intersecting thematic research clusters, each focusing on distinct yet interrelated dimensions of ageing, care, and demographic discourse in Southeastern Europe. Together, they provide a multi-scalar, comparative, and interdisciplinary framework that links individual experiences to policy debates, historical legacies to cultural meanings.

- 1) *Socialist Legacies and Ambivalent Transitions*. Led by Ulf Brunnbauer (IOS Regensburg), this cluster investigates how state socialism and its aftermath have shaped narratives and infrastructures of ageing since the 1960s. It traces policies related to pensions, family obligations, and elder care from the socialist period through the post-socialist transformation. By analyzing archival documents, public discourse, and political debates, the cluster explores how older people were portrayed – as bearers of tradition, beneficiaries of social systems, or as burdens – and how these perceptions evolved with economic restructuring, welfare retrenchment, and changing political ideologies. Another focus lies on the emergence of demography as a policy-oriented science.

- 2) *Demographic and Expert Discourses*. Coordinated by Attila Melegh (Hungarian Demographic Research Institute, HDRI, Budapest), this cluster examines how demographic ageing is constructed within scientific, statistical, and expert frameworks. It critically analyzes how concepts such as “population decline,” “burden,” or “dependency” are deployed in policy discussions, often linked to fears of national weakening or social unsustainability. It develops a longitudinal database of demographic indicators and conducts interviews with experts across the region to assess how demographic knowledge is produced, circulated, and politicized. Again, long term-trajectories (since the 19th century) are addressed.
- 3) *Cross-Cultural Pathways and Life Stories of Ageing and Care*. Led by Galina Goncharova (Department of History and Theory of Culture at Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski), this ethnographically grounded cluster focuses on how older people, caregivers, and families navigate the lived experience of ageing. Drawing on (auto-)biographical interviews and ethnographic observations, it examines how people make sense of ageing in the context of migration, rural depopulation, social inequality, and eroding intergenerational ties. The cluster pays particular attention to care in both institutional settings and informal care networks. It explores older people’s agency, and economies of care across both domestic and transnational contexts. Its regional focus spans Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, and Serbia – complemented by migrant perspectives in Austria and Germany – to enable a comparative perspective on demographic ageing across diverse social, political, and historical settings in Southeastern and Central Europe.
- 4) *Cultural Representations of Age and Ageing*. Headed by Ulla Kriebnernegg (Center for Interdisciplinary Research on Aging and Care, CIRAC, at the University of Graz) together with Dagmar Gramshammer-Hohl (Department of Slavic Studies at the University of Graz), this cluster analyzes how old age is depicted in literature, theater, and film – both historically and in contemporary culture. Drawing on literary gerontology, narratology, and visual analysis, it examines both dominant and counter-hegemonic imaginaries of ageing. It explores how cultural texts reflect or resist narratives of decline, and how representations of old age are shaped by intersections of gender, ethnicity, and memory. Special attention is

given to Southeast European literatures and cinema, including diasporic and transcultural works. Participatory methods, such as living labs, are an integral part of this cluster's research.

- 5) *Public Narratives and Their Politicization*. Coordinated by Florian Bieber (Centre for South East European Studies, CSEES, at the University of Graz), this cluster investigates the instrumentalization of demographic anxieties in political rhetoric – especially in nationalist, populist, and conservative discourse. Using critical discourse analysis, opinion polling, and media representations, it explores how ageing is tied to broader themes such as migration, identity, fertility politics, and geopolitical positioning. The cluster also studies how demographic fears are mobilized to justify exclusionary policies (e.g. against minorities and immigrants) or to resist perceived “Europeanization.”

Research Output: Public Opinion Poll on Ageing

Building on the work of these five clusters, one of the project's major empirical contributions is a comparative public opinion poll that offers crucial insights into societal perceptions of ageing across the region. Conducted between December 2024 and January 2025, the survey covered four countries – Bulgaria, Hungary, North Macedonia, and Serbia – and was commissioned by the Centre for South East European Studies at the University of Graz. Fieldwork was carried out by Ipsos Strategic Marketing.

The survey explores public attitudes toward ageing, demographic change, and care systems. It investigates how older people are perceived, levels of trust in public institutions, and beliefs about the causes and consequences of demographic decline. It also examines how ageing intersects with identity, migration, and inequality – key themes that resonate throughout the project's broader research agenda.

A mixed-methods design was employed, combining face-to-face, telephone, and online interviews. Nationally representative samples were selected using stratified and quota-based methods, with post-stratification weighting to ensure demographic balance. Fieldwork details by country are as follows:

- Bulgaria: 1,000 respondents (70% face-to-face, 30% online)
- Hungary: 802 respondents (telephone)
- North Macedonia: 1,033 respondents (90% telephone, 10% online)
- Serbia: 1,112 respondents (77% telephone, 23% online)

To enhance accessibility and impact, one-page briefs have been prepared for each country. These synthesize the most significant findings and are tailored for academic, policy, and public audiences alike. The results not only provide a robust empirical foundation for the project’s qualitative components but also serve as an important tool for public engagement and evidence-based policy dialogue. For example, across all four countries, ageing populations are a common concern, with most respondents expressing worry about long-term effects. Immigration as a solution is viewed skeptically, and state support is seen as inadequate. Yet, there is broad agreement on the importance of policies that promote economic stability and support for young families – seen as the most effective response to demographic change.²

From Data to Dialogue: Methodology Workshops and Doctoral Training

In parallel with its empirical research, the project places strong emphasis on academic training and knowledge exchange – especially through its integrated program of methodology workshops and doctoral support. “Transforming Anxieties of Ageing in Southeastern Europe” functions not only as a research initiative but also as a platform for preparing emerging scholars to engage critically with the social, cultural, and political dimensions of demographic change. Acknowledging that ageing-related challenges require cross-disciplinary insight and contextual awareness, the project integrates structured PhD training into its core design.

A series of themed methodology workshops has been organized to deepen theoretical engagement, enhance methodological expertise, and foster collaborative scholarship among participating PhD students. These workshops function as intensive academic forums – spaces where draft chapters are critically discussed, research methods are refined, and local insights are exchanged with academic mentors and community partners.

Each workshop is shaped by a specific thematic and methodological focus:

- The kick-off workshop in Regensburg explored digital humanities tools for ageing research.

² See <https://transforming-anxieties.ios-regensburg.de/output/>

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- In Graz, participants examined interdisciplinary and participatory approaches in ageing studies.
 - The Budapest workshop provided in-depth training in historical demography.
 - The most recent session, held in Sofia, focused on comparative oral history and transnational perspectives.

A final workshop, scheduled to take place in Graz in spring 2026, will center on policy engagement, knowledge transfer, and open science – bridging scholarly research with societal impact.

Together, these workshops not only support individual doctoral trajectories but also help build a shared intellectual foundation across the project's diverse research strands. They cultivate a dynamic scholarly network, encourage cross-border dialogue, and align academic inquiry with public relevance. The most recent Sofia workshop offered a particularly rich example of how the project integrates doctoral training with local expertise, public engagement, and transdisciplinary dialogue. It brought together researchers, practitioners, and community organizations in a setting that exemplified the project's broader commitment to bridging empirical research with lived experience and societal impact. The training program will culminate in a final conference in Sofia in September 2026, bringing together researchers, policymakers, and community stakeholders to reflect on findings, exchange perspectives, and chart future directions.

Sofia Workshop Highlights: Tiny Homes, Oral History, and Dementia Advocacy

Our methodology workshop in Sofia, held on 20 June 2025, brought together project members and local experts for a day of vibrant discussion on ageing, memory, and intergenerational life in Bulgaria. The program began with presentations by university professors Iliya Iliev and Daniela Koleva, followed by a chapter workshop in which PhD students shared and discussed their work in a collaborative group setting. In the afternoon, sessions with the Alzheimer Bulgaria Association and a concluding lecture by public health expert Desislava Vankova offered applied perspectives on dementia care and narrative medicine in the Bulgarian context.

In his presentation, ethnologist Iliya Iliev examined changing patterns of intergenerational cohabitation in Bulgaria during the 1970s and 1980s. Focusing on the effects of housing shortages and state policies, he showed how multigenerational living in cramped apartments shaped

family dynamics, privacy, and generational relationships. His research underscored how structural conditions and everyday adaptations influenced experiences of ageing under late socialism.

Oral historian Daniela Koleva offered a conceptual talk on the possibilities and challenges of comparative oral history. Drawing on scholars such as Ronald Fraser, Riki Van Boeschoten, and Gerhard Botz, she outlined the goals of comparative research – mapping similarities and differences, contextualizing case studies, and theorizing across cultural contexts. She also addressed obstacles in cross-national work, including terminological differences, cultural sensitivities, and national norms around religion and secularism. Koleva’s presentation provided valuable methodological guidance for the project, particularly in relation to the comparative analysis of interview data.

In the afternoon, Maya Marinova from the Alzheimer Bulgaria Association presented the organization, its support services, and its advocacy initiatives. In a country where gerontology is not yet formally recognized, the NGO plays a vital role in improving the rights and well-being of people with dementia and their caregivers. Programs such as the “Alzheimer Café” for family members and the “Friends in Memory” group for people in early-stage dementia offer both psychological support and opportunities for social connection. The Association also promotes inclusivity through cultural initiatives, including the Memorable project.

Desislava Vankova, a public health scholar from the city of Varna, concluded the day with a lecture on narrative medicine as an ethical framework for geriatric care. Her talk explored how storytelling can bridge gaps between clinicians and older patients, moving beyond biomedical models toward empathy-driven, person-centered care. Her intervention enriched the workshop with a reflective and ethical perspective on the future of ageing and care in Bulgaria and was an example of engaged academic work.

Altogether, the Sofia workshop offered a multidimensional lens on the intersections of memory, care, and ageing in Southeastern Europe. It also strengthened links between academic research and local practice – demonstrating the value of context-sensitive, engaged, and interdisciplinary approaches at the heart of the project.

Sofia Outreach Event: Sharing Stories of Ageing and Care Through Research and Literature

Extending the spirit of the workshop beyond the academic setting, a public outreach event held the following day created space for shared reflection, storytelling, and community engagement. Titled “Ageing and Care Stories,” the event took place on 21 June 2025 at Sofia University and was organized in collaboration with the Alzheimer Bulgaria Association. Moderated by Galina Goncharova, the event brought together students, researchers, writers, and caregivers for a rich exchange of academic insight and creative expression. For the purpose of outreach, the event was held in Bulgarian.

The program featured anonymized stories based on interviews conducted by the Sofia project team and by students of Galina Goncharova, alongside literary texts – all presented in Bulgarian with English translations. These narratives spanned multiple genres and perspectives, emphasizing the cultural, emotional, and ethical dimensions of ageing.

The event opened with a welcome address by Professor Sonya Karabelyova, Dean of the Faculty of Philosophy at Sofia University, followed by a project introduction by Ulf Brunnbauer. The first panel included presentations by developmental psychologist Michaela Churusinova and Alzheimer Bulgaria Association representative Zhenya Milusheva. Churusinova shared findings from her qualitative research on emotional ambivalence in later life, while Milusheva highlighted the potential for meaning, connection, and self-reflection even in contexts of social vulnerability.

Following this, Cultural Studies (*kulturologija*) students Dalia Nenova and Kristiyana Barzinska presented their nuanced interpretation of an interview with an older woman, focusing on intergenerational themes and the narrative power of storytelling in research. After a short break, the program transitioned into a series of literary performances: journalist and lecturer Rumén Skriniski read a text exploring the ethics of care, followed by poetic reflections from Maria Getova and Vassil Vidinski on memory, ageing, and vulnerability.

The event concluded with a reception and informal exchange. With an audience of approximately 40 to 50 participants from diverse backgrounds, “Ageing and Care Stories” served as a powerful reminder of the value of interdisciplinary, community-based approaches to un-

derstanding ageing. By bridging research and literature, academic insight and lived experience, the event reinforced the project’s commitment to public dialogue, social inclusion, and care-oriented futures.

Summary

In sum, “Transforming Anxieties of Ageing in Southeastern” Europe brings together diverse research perspectives, regional expertise, and public engagement to explore how ageing is experienced, represented, and politicized across Southeastern Europe. Through its interdisciplinary clusters, comparative methods, strong emphasis on collaboration, and its open science ethos, the project not only generates new knowledge but also fosters dialogue between academia, civil society, stakeholders, and communities. With public opinion surveys, local partnerships, lived narratives of older adults and the exploration of experiences, it seeks to reframe demographic ageing as a space for care, inclusion, and critical reflection rather than alarm and apocalypse. As the project moves forward, it continues to build connections – between countries, disciplines, and generations – that point toward more just and thoughtful responses to ageing in contemporary Europe.

VITA ACADEMICA

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Why has it Become so Easy to be Decolonial? Historical Provocations from the Workshop “Culture and Psychiatric Paradigms During the Cold War”¹

The workshop explored the intersection of culture and psychiatry during the Cold War, focusing on the shift from psychosurgical interventions to psychotropic medication and the rise of culturally-oriented therapeutic approaches. I organized this event in partnership with the Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Studies with Ethnographic Museum (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and the Institute for the History and Ethics of Medicine, Charité Berlin. The workshop was part of the ERC Synergy Project “Leviathan.” Here, I briefly share some of the discussions and provocations that took place during the event held from June 18 to 19 this year in Berlin.

The idea for the workshop originated from my recent research on the Brazilian psychiatrist Nise da Silveira (1905-1999) and her relationship with Carl Gustav Jung (1875-1961), art therapy, and the anti-asylum movement. I observed a shift in psychiatric strategies during that period. When the confinement of psychiatric patients and psychosurgery began to be questioned – as early as the 1940s in Silveira’s case –

¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good”. The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

psychiatry changed its strategy of appeasing the subject by using psychotropic drugs. From the 1950s onward, psychosurgery could no longer be sustained as a means of keeping the “mad” calm and within acceptable social standards. One hypothesis is that there was a change in technique, but not necessarily in the psychiatric paradigm: were drugs still being used to control subjectivity toward a socially acceptable “normality”?

One of the main questions was whether the move from psychosurgery to drugs in the 1950s signified a fundamental paradigm shift or just a technical update within the same framework. Drawing on the pioneering work of Brazilian psychiatrist Nise da Silveira (1905-1999), my presentation explored how art therapy and the anti-asylum movements challenged traditional psychiatric approaches during this transformative era, taking into account both gender and decolonial perspectives.

Nine international researchers participated in the workshop. Each was given ten minutes to present their research, followed by thirty minutes for questions, comments, and discussion. Papers had been circulated among participants two weeks in advance, and the sessions’ discussions were based on the brief presentation and reading of the texts. The aim was to foster an environment for in-depth debates on each research project, thereby enhancing the quality of the investigations.

On the first day, we had two sessions of presentations and discussion. **Marietta Meier** opened with “The Emergence of a New Subject Order: Psychosurgery, Psychotropic Drugs and Personality Concepts in Post-war Psychiatry”, highlighting the rise and fall of psychosurgery and the introduction of psychotropic drugs in Switzerland. **Tiago Pires** followed with “Combating Psychosurgery: The Cultural Clinic of Brazilian Psychiatrist Nise da Silveira (1905–1999)”, emphasizing her resistance to invasive psychiatric practices like lobotomy and electroshock in mid-20th-century Brazil.

In the second part, **Gabriel Abarca-Brown** presented “Psychiatric Experiments During the Chilean Road to Socialism (1970–1973): Luis Weinstein and the Center of Medical Anthropology”, addressing psychiatry and utopia in Chile from the socialist era to neoliberal times. Right after, **Romain Tiquet** presented “Culture, Patient Voices, and Imported Psychiatry: The Fann Method Through a Patient File (Dakar, Senegal, 1960s)”, which examined a patient file compiled within the psychiatric care framework at Fann in Dakar during the 1960s. **João**

Tavares concluded the first day with “The Silence Angel” - Haloperidol’s First Official Trial in 1958”, presenting an in-depth analysis of haloperidol trials in different contexts. After the discussions, we spent some time watching a documentary on the medicalization of life, followed by a provocative and insightful debate.

The second day began with **Ketil Slagstad’s** “Making Prognosis, Making Schizophrenia. A Praxiographic Analysis of a Clinical Research Project”, discussing a 1960s research initiative on schizophrenia carried out by psychiatrists in West Germany. We continued the discussions with **Francesco Toncich**, who presented “Reactivating a Shared Psychiatric-Medical Culture: Cross-Border Deinstitutionalization Reforms in the Upper Adriatic During the Détente Era”, analyzing psychiatric reforms across Italy and Yugoslavia during the Cold War from a transnational perspective.

In the second session of the day, **Valentin Kalinov** presented “From Psychotherapy to Parapsychology and Beyond: Nonpsychiatric Mental Health Care in Socialist Bulgaria During the Cold War”, investigating the overlap between psychotherapy and parapsychology in Bulgaria. After that, **Windson Lin** presented “The Making of Culture-bound Syndrome in the Post-war Period: Reassessing the Works of Yap Pow Meng”, reassessing the legacy of Yap Pow Meng in the development of transcultural psychiatry and culture-bound syndromes. After final comments, the workshop concluded with some informal conversations.

Methodological Challenges: The Patient Voice

One of the major challenges addressed was the long-standing difficulty of accessing patient voices in psychiatric records. The workshop emphasized the ways traditional psychiatric documentation has systematically marginalized or filtered patient experiences through medical language, creating significant gaps in our understanding of how individuals truly experienced and interpreted their mental states. This methodological challenge becomes especially visible when studying cross-cultural contexts, where Western psychiatric (particularly Anglo-Saxon) frameworks often obscured non-Western perspectives on psychological distress and healing. The workshop participants debated how to reconstruct patient experiences from incomplete archival materials, institutional records, and therapeutic artifacts, while recognizing the inherent limits of sources embedded in systems of confinement and control. This challenge goes beyond mere historical methodology to raise

fundamental questions about whose knowledge is considered legitimate in the history of mental health. Future research directions include developing methods that can access patient voices through culturally appropriate channels, elaborating on non-Western terminologies for describing mental states that cannot be translated into Western psychiatric categories, and creating therapeutic approaches that originate from specific cultural contexts rather than adapting Western techniques.

Contemporary Implications: The Unfinished Decolonial Project

The case studies demonstrated that recognizing cultural differences was often the primary form of “decolonial” efforts during this period. Mental health professionals would observe cultural differences in symptom presentation or treatment response without questioning the underlying assumption that Western psychiatric categories were the universal standard against which other approaches were measured. This limited cultural sensitivity, while advanced for its time, fell short of deeper decolonial critique.

The workshop revealed that the Cold War era marked significant shifts in psychiatric practice. However, some integration of cultural perspectives remained limited by Western epistemological assumptions. The challenge for contemporary scholars and practitioners is to move beyond the tentative cultural acknowledgments of the mid-20th century toward a more radical reimagining of mental health frameworks that genuinely embraces diverse ways of knowing and healing. Only through such efforts can the decolonial project in mental health shift from aspiration to a more concrete social and intellectual process.

Recognizing cultural differences and the Other, along with alternative ways of dealing with existence and suffering, may be a first step toward decolonizing psy-knowledges. But is this merely a European “decolonial” obligation? I believe that decolonizing subjectivity and psy-epistemologies is a project that demands much more audacity. To avoid being anachronistic, I would say that in the second half of the 20th century, we took the first still hesitant steps in this long and challenging process of decolonizing mental health, its professionals, and its epistemologies. Much remains to be done, not only by historians and researchers in the humanities, but also by health professionals and policymakers.

VITA ACADEMICA**Jakub Střelec, PhD****Postdoctoral researcher, Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine****Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin – Germany****[jakub.strelec@charite.de], ORCID: 0000-0002-4311-7618****Workshop Report: Risk, Health, and State Socialism: Central and Eastern Europe, 1950s-1980s¹**

On 5 May 2025, a one-day workshop was held at the Institute for the History of Medicine and Ethics in Medicine at Charité in Berlin. Organized within the framework of the ERC project *Taming the European Leviathan*, the workshop brought together scholars to explore how the concept of “risk” can be applied to the history of medicine and healthcare under state socialism. The event was prompted by the observation that much of the existing literature on the history of medicine and health has focused primarily on liberal democracies in Western Europe and North America – contexts in which risk thinking and preventive strategies have played a central role in shaping modern health systems. In these settings, “risk” emerged as a key medical category in the post-war decades, initially in relation to the epidemiology of cardiovascular diseases. Risk has come to present a strategy for “dealing with uncertainty based on calculations of probabilities” (Schlich, 2004: 211). Building on this insight, sociologists such as François Ewald, Thomas Lemke, Nikolas Rose and others have shown that risk functions not only as a clinical concept, but also as a broader mode of governance,

¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good”. The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

one that redefined various forms of danger as calculable, and, therefore, manageable (Cf. Ewald, 1991; Lemke, 2000; Rose, 1998).

The workshop sought to situate these debates within the distinct political and institutional contexts of state socialist regimes in Central and Eastern Europe. It explored how health and social problems were conceptualized as “risks” under communism, and what strategies, practices, and expert knowledges were developed to address them (Cf. Balz, 2020; Madarász-Lebenhagen, 2013; Offermann, 2019; Timmermann, 2012). Like their liberal-democratic counterparts, communist states grappled with the complex challenges of industrial and post-industrial modernity – including rising rates of lifestyle diseases, advances in medical science, growing concerns about environmental degradation, and the regulation of new pharmaceuticals. By addressing a range of topics – from occupational health, neurology, health statistics, and nutrition, to HIV/AIDS, legal history, and media representations – the workshop aimed to broaden existing historiographies on the history of risk and health in state socialism and foster comparative dialogue between research on Eastern and Western medical histories.

In her paper, Denitsa Nencheva (Sofia) explored how the Bulgarian socialist state promoted “creative longevity” by applying ergonomics and occupational health knowledge to manage workers’ ageing and productivity. She examined how scientific methods shaped workplace safety and health practices while also fostering individual responsibility. Similarly, Gergana Mircheva (Sofia), in her presentation on “Minimal Brain Dysfunction”, analyzed the state-sponsored “brain programme” focused on managing so-called “deviant” behaviour in children during the 1980s. She argued that the expert management of “Minimal Brain Dysfunction” could be seen as a form of risk optimization, raising broader questions about how discourses on health and risk were operationalized in late socialism. The role of statistics and quantification methods in state socialist medicine and healthcare also gained importance, as noted by Jakub Střelec (Berlin) in his paper on healthcare planning. He studied how health statistics, supported by new computer technologies, were envisioned as a tool for improving healthcare planning in late socialist Czechoslovakia. Mara Marginean (Cluj-Napoca) examined Romania’s 1980s Scientific Feeding Program as both a public health initiative and a mechanism of state regulation to manage food scarcity. She analyzed the intersection of scientific discourses on nutrition, the political instrumentation of health programs, and the risks related to lifestyle diseases in the context of economic

constrains in late socialist Romania. Katarzyna Szarla (Warsaw) analyzed how the response to the HIV/AIDS epidemic in 1980s Poland exposed systemic fragilities within the healthcare system and highlighted how marginalized groups initiated their own forms of self-protection. Her presentation underscored the importance of bottom-up health practices within state socialist healthcare. In his paper, Jakub Machek (Prague) studied representations of health and risk in Czechoslovak television and cinema during the 1970s and 1980s. He pointed out a shift in the portrayal of risk in communist media – from the glorification of heroic labour common in the 1950s toward a more nuanced recognition of the adverse effects of excessive work and the psychological pressures of modern life. The importance of international comparison and differing understandings of risk across East and West was emphasized by Mária Éva Földes (Rotterdam). In her paper on the legal tolerance of risk, she explored unofficially tolerated reproductive health practices in post-war Hungary and the Netherlands. Her analysis revealed that, despite contrasting ideological systems, both nations moved from criminalization toward increasing tolerance, though through different logics: Hungary followed a materialist, state-centred approach, while the Netherlands was guided by secular and individualist ideals.

The workshop primarily served to outline potential avenues for future research and collaboration, but it also highlighted several key issues that will require further clarification. In particular, this concerns the conceptual framing of the term *risk*, which often fluctuated during the discussions between an analytical category and a heuristic tool; the need for a more nuanced analysis of the “crisis” in state-socialist healthcare systems; and the role of health prevention in late socialism.

Workshop Overview

Denitsa Nencheva (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia): In Preserving Creative Longevity: Health Hazards, Ergonomics, and Occupational Safety during Late State Socialism in Bulgaria

Gergana Mircheva (Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia): “Minimal Brain Dysfunction” in Socialist Bulgaria and the Minimization of Psycho-Social Risks

Jakub Střelec (Charité-Berlin): Socialist Automated Healthcare Utopia: Medical Statistics, Risk, and Planning in Late Socialist Czech Republic

Mara Marginean (Romanian Academy, Cluj-Napoca): Nutrition and Health Risk Management in Times of Economic Recession:

The Case of the Rational Scientific Nutrition Program in 1980s Romania

Katarzyna Szarla (University of Warsaw): Risks and Resistance: Prevention and Self-Prevention Practices Related to HIV/AIDS under Late State Socialism in Poland

Mária Éva Földes (Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management, Rotterdam): Legal Tolerance of “Risky” Reproductive Health Practices: A Comparative Analysis of Post-War Hungary and the Netherlands

Jakub Machek (Metropolitan University, Prague): The Representation of Risk and Health in Films and Television Series of the 1970s and 1980s in Czechoslovakia

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RECENT PUBLICATIONS: THE AUTHOR PRESENTS**Mincho Georgiev, PhD****Professor,****„Medical Anthropology” Unit,****Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Studies with Ethnographic
Museum, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences****The Beginning of History
(Anthropological Notes)**

Abstract: *This is an introduction to the book „The Beginning of History”, written by its author. He presents a cultural-anthropological inquiry into the phenomenon of history as ‘history of the human reason’, by tracing its evolutionary-historical types – from pre-verbal, ritual-based to verbal. To demonstrate this, the book critically examines transitions between several types of reason: creative (syntactic); cognitive (semantic); axiological (value-oriented or pragmatic). The author explores the evolutionary and historical transitions between these types, their semi-otic foundations, and respective cultural-historical implications, while also changing the notion of ‘evental history’. The work argues that human history has a productive purpose, the content of which consists of the semeophores of signification, meaning,*

concept, and value, and their material embodiments; the legislation of each type of reason presupposes its own type of long-term historical time, person, reality, and social paradigm; in particular, before the history of time, there is a history of place.

Keywords: *history of reason; types of human reason; evolutionary development; cultural anthropology.*

Georgiev, M. (2025). *The Beginning of History. Anthropological Notes*. Sofia: Publishing House „Prof. Marin Drinov”, ISBN: 9786192455132, p. 322. [in Bulgarian].

[https://press.bas.bg/bg/books-103/show-104\(992\)](https://press.bas.bg/bg/books-103/show-104(992))

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„For the issue is not a trivial one, but the question
of how one ought to live”

– Plato

The new book *The Beginning of History*,¹ published by the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Publishing House „Prof. Marin Drinov”, Sofia, 2025, is the final outcome of my inquiries in the field of cultural anthropology. The impetus for working on it came from my realisation that ritual is both „a precedent to any productive-economic, spiritual-religious, and social activity and the source from which they evolved” (according to V. N. Toporov), as well as a form of nonverbal, creatively-discursive attempt to produce meaning prior to the invention of speech. For example, the structure of the healing ritual consistently features a situation in which the healer, through her hands, produces nonverbal meaning, and through her speech apparatus – verbal meaning, each having the capacity to be translated into the other language-code. That the nonverbal (manual) repositioning of disease-dislocated bodily parts – organs of the patient – is analogous to their verbal repositioning into harmony with the syntactic order of reality under the rule of the proportional metaphor „just as... so too...” is evidenced by an incantation (baene) recorded by A. Popov in 1889: „Heart in place, hens on the roost, sheep on the pasture, grass in the field, and fish in the sea.” Thus, my assumption that I was witnessing a preverbal syntactic reason became undeniable and drove me to seek additional sources attesting to its historical reality. This also gave rise to a number of questions: does ritual as a nonverbal discourse exceed the cultural-anthropological horizon of its interpretation? If only words can designate concepts, and if verbalication dates back no more than around 60,000 years, how could Homo habilis, the Neanderthal, and Cro-Magnon man have exercised any form of cognitive reason over the hundreds of thousands of years before that? Is ritual, as a nonverbal discourse, a relic of pre-cognitive

¹ Георгиев, М. (2025). *Началото на историята. Антропологични бележки*. София: „Марин Дринов“.

creative reason – an evolutionary precursor and condition of possibility for cognitive reason – or what Plato called ‘creative art’ in contrast to the ‘acquisitive’; Do the creative, followed by the cognitive and axiological (value-oriented) forms of reason constitute the content of three evolutionarily distinct long-term historical times within the field of a different (trans-being) history, understood as an evolutionary history of reason?; Does being-based reason originate from an evolutionary predecessor that is other than ‘nothing’, and hence reach its end in the transition to another – value-based – form?; Does the exit from cognitive to axiological reason coincide with the transition between metaphysics and anthropology? These and many other questions are what this book seeks to address.

The cultural fact that at a certain moment in the history of reason people began to use things and words in the same way raises the question of whether this fact is the bridge over the chasm between the two. If „meanings grow around words, rather than word-things acquiring meanings” (per M. Heidegger), if semiotic meanings have „a past of sensory meanings” (per G. W. F. Hegel), whose source lies in things and not in words, and if the creation of material artifacts precedes the creation of verbal ones by hundreds of thousands of years, and the making of artifacts – nests and other shelters – is also an ability of animals, then it is words that inherit their signifying function from things, not the other way around. It is entirely logical for this inheritance to occur at the lowest semiotic level – that of syntax, since only words can denote concepts. It follows, then, that as a semiotic system, reason-as-discourse originates from nonverbal syntax as the necessary and sufficient foundation of a primary, evolutionarily historical sign system.

The intention to view history as a history of reason requires grounding its beginning in ‘nature’, understood as the pre- or proto-historical, understood as the asemantic (signless). In other words, the beginning of history as the history of reason is the beginning of signification as a living being’s ability to mark and differentiate its environment of habitation from the uninhabited, thus drawing a boundary within ‘being itself’ as the prehistorical asemantic and the semiotic as historical. Thus, nature receives its newly created double in the form of history, whose development unfolds as a history of reason in the evolutionary sequence of „semioforms” (in the sense of K. Pomian): signification, meaning, concept, and value, each owing itself to its predecessor and serving as the condition of possibility for its successor.

Before embarking on a critical reflection on the history of historians as a cognitive or interpretative reconstruction of human existence in historical reality after the end of biological and the beginning of cultural evolution, a caveat must be made regarding the possibility of two different histories: an ontological /evental/ history within the horizon of metaphysical thinking, which posits ‘people’ (in the sense of H. Arendt), i.e., human communities as ‘collective persons’ (in the sense of B. Uspensky) and historical subjects in a ‘worldly world’ measured by God (in the sense of Plato); and an anthropological evolutionary history as a history of reason, whose subject is the human being in his human life-world, measured by the historical human themselves (in the sense of Protagoras). In other words, the pathos of the book lies in my attempt to look at the slippage from one type of history to the other as a form of transition from metaphysics to anthropology.

Metaphysical history is evental because its subjects are human communities (peoples, nations, classes, parties, confessions, etc.) capable of producing ‘events’. Anthropological history, by contrast, has as its subject the historical human, capable of performing ‘discursive acts’ and producing ‘discursive results’ (in the sense of A. Greimas and J. Courtés). Evental history presents itself as a temporal chain of cause-and-effect events – from event-causes to event-effects, while historical knowledge retraces the reverse path back to the primeval event-cause. This is also how historical inquiry appears in B. Uspensky’s attempt to present historical knowledge as a semiotic system within the field of cognitive, causal-temporal reason. And this attempt would be indisputable if the semiotic system of reason operated solely in the semantic mode, lacking its syntactic and pragmatic forms. And it is well known that under the legislation of metaphysical (semantic) reason, ‘practice and morality are handmaidens to contemplation’ (per H. Arendt), i.e., that the empirical and axiological forms of reason are turned into distorted imitations of reflection. This makes it possible for the ‘synchronous’ (in the sense of Saussure) functioning of the three semiotic forms of reason to obscure and conceal their diachronic, evolutionary-historical sequence, in which each prior form is the condition of possibility for the subsequent one. And if the semiotic varieties of reason are diachronically stratified, then the ‘unifying principle of history’ (in the sense of K. Popper) is semiotic, in the evolutionary sequence of its creative, cognitive, and axiological forms.

By advancing knowledge of the ‘actors of history’ (peasants, merchants, intellectuals, clergy, etc.), the new ‘history of mentalities’ presents itself as a vivid form of the history of reason. But by remaining alien to the semiotic principle and to reason and its history, the concept of „mentality” turns the historical human into a „ghost” (in the sense of M. Bloch) within the field of social structures.

Global humanity is in need of a universal history in which every distinct culture has a preserved place. The foundation of universal history is ‘the faculty of speech’ (in the sense of Tz. Todorov), or more broadly – reason (logos, ratio, discourse, word). This history begins in the pre-verbal era, dominated by the macrosemiotics of the natural world – the longest period in the human past considered as the history of reason. Universal history is evolutionarily grounded in the three known types of reason: creative (syntactic), cognitive (semantic), and axiological (pragmatic). Among the many hypotheses about types of reason beyond the metaphysical, such as those in Kant, we randomly encounter Plato’s ‘creative art’, creation as an ‘unavoidable’ stage in the history of ancient Greek culture per J. Habermas, the ‘servitude’ of practice and morality to ‘contemplation’ in H. Arendt, Socrates’ and Protagoras’ thesis on the inaccessibility of values to knowledge, and others.

Evolutionary-historical types of reason result from the abstraction of a predecessor and serve as evolutionary conditions of possibility for a subsequent type. Each of them is a revolutionary discovery (‘innovation’ in the sense of K. Pomian), carried out by a specific historical human subject, rather than by a society or community, and its dissemination among the human population results in it becoming the foundation and ‘legislation’ (in the sense of Kant) of a corresponding ‘long-term’ (in the sense of F. Braudel) historical time-epoch.

A primary source for the history of reason is ‘folk culture’, or the culture of the subordinate classes, as the heir of times more ancient than being-time. At the foundation of this culture lies ritual, in keeping with the thesis that ritual is a ‘precedent’ of reason (in the sense of V. N. Toporov).

Among the sources marking the beginning of history, drawn from the archaeological catalogue, of foremost importance are those that delineate the boundary between the reductive ‘division of nature’, characteristic of both animals and the divine (in the sense of Eriugena), and the constitutive form of creative reason, capable of producing an artifact from two bodies and a syntactic relation between them (axe, knife, file,

sickle, etc.), i.e. a tool analogous to the future verbal attributive syntagma as the smallest unit of meaning.

From the sources of the history of philosophy, those are selected which demonstrates an understanding of the distinction between both the constructive (syntactic, multiple, pre-existential meanings) and the hierarchical (semantic, unified, existential) sets, and between things as 'beings' and as 'objects of participation' (including the distinction between concept and value) in ancient Greek and early medieval philosophical thought (Protagoras, Zeno, Parmenides, Plato, Aristotle, Proclus, Plotinus, St. Augustine, Pseudo-Dionysius the Areopagite, etc.). Particularly noteworthy is Plato's distinction between the arts based on the abstraction of sensory meanings into semiotic meanings (as Hegel also distinguishes them), such as cooking, cosmetics, rhetoric and sophistry on one hand, and those based on contemplation (reflection), such as medicine, gymnastics, justice, and legislation on the other. This distinction is an early intuition of the difference between creative and cognitive reason. The distinction between constructive (finite, syntactic) and hierarchical (infinite, semantic, conceptual) sets in the history of counting also points to the difference between creative and cognitive reason. This difference is qualitative, not quantitative, and the boundary between them is marked by the number.

In agreement with James Joyce's thesis that art is intended to reveal ideas to us, historical-literary sources are invaluable in showing the boundaries between types of historical humans as subjects of different types of reason throughout history: the boundary between epic and lyric marks the transition from the creative to the cognitive subject of reason; tragedy marks the possible transition from existential to value-based reason; and the European modern and postmodern novel – the decline of metaphysical thinking and the vacant space for a new value-based reason (Flaubert, Joyce, Kafka, Musil, Sartre, Borges, etc.).

The analytical historical presentation of the three types of reason in this book is uneven – weighted in favour of creative and value-based reason, which today remain insufficiently theorised. Metaphysical thought and the dialectical social necessity for domination and subordination it underpins are subjected to critical scrutiny, while the epoch of this reason, in the stage of its completion (totality), is seen as a catastrophe for the historical human. Its apologetics in the history of philosophy to date, however, has been more than ample.

Existing research on traditional and archaic cultures permits the hypothesis that a necessary and sufficient primordial semiotic-syntactic

type of (creative) reason existed historically among pre-human populations. Prompted by this assumption, the content of the book unfolds in four parts: the first three are dedicated respectively to creative, cognitive, and value-based reason, and the fourth – to history as a history of reason.

The first part is devoted to the creative historical epoch governed by the legislation of syntactic reason, which spans hundreds of thousands of years before the advent of verbalisation and number. It begins with the creation of the first artifacts (tools) through the dividing and combining of parts of natural bodies – wholes (wood, stone, bone) – an analogue to the „dividing and combining of significances” (in the Aristotelian sense) in developed speech activity. It is specifically noted that the creation of one’s own appropriated place – as a kind of ‘self-giving of place’, analogous to the ‘self-giving of time’ (in the sense of Martin Heidegger) through the signifying-dividing of nature – is the first great achievement of prehistoric man. This makes possible the historical creation of the self and of one’s world, forming the basis for domestication, productivity, and the reproduction of populations.

Under the legislation of creative (syntactic) reason, all encounters in reality are syntactic discursive constructs (emergent or created presences). The creative human is a syntactic unity of body and soul, with the body as an analogue of the Socratic body composed of different bodily members-parts in Plato; they are unique and unrepeatable – a semantically multiple syntactic unity, outside number and beyond the metaphysical field of the same; they have received their creative discursive capacity either as a gift from the gods or as an inheritance from a kindred predecessor. In the context of communal life under the gift system (vs. the system of exchange value in hierarchical society), human relations are dominated by reverence for elders and patronage over the younger within the community. Creative historical time is a result of its separation from natural time. It does not fully coincide with the movement of celestial bodies, but is structured in accordance with productive activities, beginning „after the first roosters crow” and ending with the return of the farmer home and the livestock from pasture. This time is a syntactic whole composed of parts, not units: day and night, old and new moon, the sequence of weekdays, an annual whole of season-parts, and so on.

Under the legislation of cognitive (semantic) reason, reality takes the form of the semantic relation between signified and signifier as ‘being’ in its ‘beingness’; the cognitive historical human is a hierarchical

semantic unity of their body and soul (I), and after a second semantic elevation from I to the Second I (Self), they assume the figure of the autonomously existing historical human, whose ability 'to be' is the result of 'being able to be oneself' (in the sense of S. Kierkegaard); metaphysical time-being-representation is the duration of the act of contemplating-measuring-knowing-representing-acquiring the creation of meaning and of meaning itself. „Historical time-being is acquired time and owes its existence to 'having the word' and 'having language' as tools of representation, which are not available to all like the sun and air are to all living beings, but are the possession and property of the man of the ruling classes. The interpersonal (social) relation is thus an analogue to the semantic relation between 'being' and its 'beingness', in the form of domination and subordination (rulers/ruled). In fact, the intrapersonal structure of the being-historical person is the same, insofar as the I is the being as 'possession and property' of the Self (personal beingness in the Aristotelian sense). In turn, the ontological (evental) history unfolds as the work of categorical fictions embodied in hierarchical communities (peoples, nations, classes, states, etc.), and the person is thereby depersonalised and deprived of the role of historical subject.

It is important to note that so-called 'social revolutions' during the epoch of 'beingness' are mere storms in a teacup compared to the fundamental transitions between semiotic-historical types of reason. As for the long-term time of metaphysical reason, its medium-term transitions are realised through the necessary sequence of revolution and counterrevolution. None of its revolutions is 'real' without its counterrevolution, whose driving forces failed to bid a final farewell to an exhausted historical reality: Julian the Apostate, the Counter-Reformation, the ancien régime, national-territorial capitalism... There are grounds for the intellectual-political climate of United Europe – founded on the values of the global order and the rules against changing state borders by force, against violence against civilians, and against threats of nuclear weapons – to be seen as the beginning of a transition to a future epoch of equality in a value-based fellowship of humans and cultures.

Under the legislation of pragmatic (value-oriented) reason, the historical human acquires a personal structure in the form of a freed from personal beingness befriended unity of I, Self, and body under the banner of intrapersonal understanding among them; this intrapersonal

understanding is a precondition for the possibility of interpersonal understanding within communal living; value reality is a fellowship of all (material and ideal) values: a material value is anything (object, being, phenomenon) that is free from categorical determinacy and is available for human participation and co-participation, and an ideal value is any idea that partakes in the boundless fellowship of values, or at least in one other idea from that fellowship. Outside of it, any idea is merely a concept within the composition of conceptual infinity. Value-based historical time is free time – free from being-as-acquisition-time, it is time available to the person, free to live in order to work, and not working in order to live; it is the time of our future. The transition from semantic to pragmatic reason is indicated as the moment of passage from the capacity for knowing-acquiring-destroying to that of creating-valuing-preserving and participating in the human life-world, and as the moment of the transition from metaphysics to anthropology, as discursive anthropology.

The concluding fourth part contains a reasoned critique of evental (cognitive) perverse history with its claim to universality at the stage of its completion. As a possible way out, it proposes an understanding of global history whose subject is not only human communities but also the human being themselves, and whose active organising principle is semiotic: it is the process of alternating discursive capacities as an evolutionary sequence of semiotic forms of reason under whose legislation respective long-term historical times unfold – each with its own type of historical human, historical reality, and social paradigm.

The thematic structure of the book, thus presented, also contains a number of debatable theses with heuristic potential: for example, if creation is „reason before reason,” then the apriority of beingness as ‘nothing’ is illusory, and cognitive reason has no dealings with the transcendent; if the cognitive type of reason is only one among others, then its singularity and its historical finality, together with history itself, are products of misunderstanding; beingness is not in and of itself, but a product of semantic reason; besides beingness, the being also has its own internal ontological structure: autonomous are only those who are capable of being themselves; authorised are the recipients of public time-beingness (slaves, vassals, and proletarians); and those who are being involuntarily are all ‘things with names’. The evolutionary history of reason is visible from the so-called ‘Archimedean’ point of history outside historical time; the aporias of Zeno of Elea serve as illustrations for understanding creative, cognitive, and dialectical types of

reason; created as a result of artifact production, human history has a productive purpose, the content of which consists of the semeophores of signification, meaning, concept, and value, and their material embodiments; the legislation of each type of reason presupposes its own type of long-term historical time, person, reality, and social paradigm; in particular, before the history of time, there is a history of place, which allows things to be accessed and arranged.

In short, history is seen as everything that the human makes of themselves and of the world through the instruments of their reason. And the book seeks an answer to the question posed by Paul Ricoeur, „What is real?": the real is the analogue of the type of reason dominant in any historical epoch. Thus, evolutionary anthropological history places the human before both the alternative of their boundlessness and the „Last Judgment” of their own reason.

*Translated from Bulgarian by Veronika Stoyanova, PhD
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BOOK REVIEW

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Reflections on Reductionism in the Historicization of Eugenics and the Possibility of its Revision

Abstract: *The text reviews A History of British Eugenics since 1865: From Francis Galton to Designer Babies by David Redvaldsen. The book is read through the lens of the many challenges faced by those who historicize the legacy of eugenics. Two key tasks are posed: delineating the boundary-work that defines eugenics and demonstrating the meaningfulness of its historicization. The widely acknowledged ability of eugenics to penetrate the filters of any political ideology and epistemology is seen as a starting point for understanding its past, which is deconstructed in the process of working with the numerous dichotomies used in various historicizations. Working with an extremely narrow range of such dichotomies, Redvaldsen's book provides a systematic example of the inevitable reductionism involved in revising the legacy of eugenics.*

Keywords: *Eugenics; historical reductionism; colonial power; comparative history; entangled history.*

Redvaldsen, D. (2024). *A History of British Eugenics since 1865: From Francis Galton to Designer Babies*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, ISBN 978-3-031-72289-9, p. 331.

<https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-031-72290-5>

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Redvaldsen's book has the ambition to trace the *longue durée* of eugenics in Britain, from the late nineteenth century to the present day. Its five chapters follow the transformation of methods used to implement the mission of social selection, seen by Redvaldsen as a kind of *perpetuum mobile* of eugenics (p. 267). I read it as an attempt to answer a question posed by Alison Bashford in the epilogue to the *Oxford Handbook of Eugenics*: how can we address the various challenges in temporalizing eugenics which has a clear start, but an uncertain present and even future? (Bashford, Levine, 2010: 539-540). The historicization of eugenics faces various complex tasks, but two of them are key for achieving valuable output, namely, delineating the boundary-work that defines eugenics and demonstrating the accuracy of its historicization. As in his earlier (and brief) attempt to compare eugenics in Denmark and Norway, Redvaldsen focuses on its ideological impact on reproductive policy agendas (Redvaldsen, 2012). The authority of eugenics to promote such extreme measures as forced sterilization is the central question for Redvaldsen's analysis, which remains purely comparative in its focus on target groups of eugenic intervention and promoters of reproductive surveillance. This research strategy produces a cascade of historical reductions that seems to be instructive to examine for anyone attempting to historicize eugenics.

Contemporary interpretations of eugenics vary in terms of the composition of driving forces and the interrelations between eugenics and other movements aimed at providing biology-informed arguments for various politics. Also, historians agree in their view of eugenics as slippery, easily accepting new knowledge and penetrating any value systems. Paraphrasing Moreno Figueroa's definition of racism as diverse practices which resurface in different forms and in sometimes imperceptible ways (Moreno, 2006), R. Sánchez-Rivera problematizes such a take on eugenics as a kind of "chameleon" as a result of adhering to traditional linear narrations of eugenics (Sánchez-Rivera, 2024). Sánchez-Rivera is not alone in accepting slipperiness as a methodological challenge. To impose historical 'order', scholars introduce dichotomies that map different flows and help recognize the complex relations within eugenic movements.

The impressive variety of such dichotomies – positive vs. negative eugenics, Mendelian vs. Lamarckian, old vs. new, reactionary vs. liberal, public vs. private, among many others – demonstrates the difficulty of interpreting the legacy of eugenics. The historicization of eu-

genics often involves deconstructing existing dichotomies and introducing new ones considered more fitting in light of newly discovered facts or even shifts in eugenic thinking (Meloni, 2016). Redvaldsen's study is not of this kind – he moves through these dichotomies with three distinct strategies. The methodical recording of the networks of British eugenicists based on archival materials and presented in a style reminiscent of a medieval chronicle, is subordinated to his effort to justify the dichotomies he deems historically significant for the British case.

Firstly, Redvaldsen chooses dilemmas central to his vision and excludes those that do not fit his strategy. For instance, he does not discuss at all the substantial legacy of British debates on the relation between heredity and environment in biological theory. Nor does his interest in historicizing British eugenics extend to their embeddedness in broader nation-building projects or transnational contexts. The suppression of these two dilemmas – heredity vs. environment (or nature vs. nurture), and national vs. transnational eugenics, results in the absence of a (de)colonial focus. This omission is visible in the absence of any mention of Chloe Campbell's *Race and empire: Eugenics in colonial Kenya* by (2007), which highlights the variety of approaches to heredity and environment among Kenyan and British eugenicists as decisive for understanding their complicated relationship. Nor does Redvaldsen engage with the collective volume *Eugenics at the edges of empire*, edited by Diane B. Paul, John Stenhouse, and Hamish G. Spencer (2018), which sheds light on the adaptation of British approaches in different peripheral colonial localities. He practically ignores the role of Vera Houghton, who was not only a leader in several British and international organizations such as the Society for Constructive Birth Control and Racial Progress but also one of the leaders of the British Eugenic Society in the 1960s. The close cooperation between Houghton and C.P. Blacker – another leader among British eugenicists, in promoting family planning in Asian and African countries raises questions about the 'racelessness' of British eugenics, a position shared by Redvaldsen.

Another of Redvaldsen's methods is to embed his analysis within one or another pole of several established dichotomies of eugenics, for example when he develops his stance that 'the role of race and scientific racism in eugenics was downplayed' (p. 185). Redvaldsen is ready to accept only 'a tiny effect' of the new eugenics on the ethnic composition of Britain. His reasoning is likely based on a possible relationship between levels of integration and access to reproductive technologies,

but socioeconomic status as a decisive factor appears to him most likely (p. 278). Resembling his work on Scandinavian eugenics, here too he treats disability, class and race separately. Neglecting the multiple forms of discrimination and stigmatization different groups experience through eugenics results in further historical reduction – ignoring resistance against eugenics’ authority. His claim that, ‘[E]ugenics had deeper consequences on continental Europe and Scandinavia than it ever did on Britain’ (p. 271) invites questions about British society’s sensitivity to the threats of eugenics. To Redvaldsen, ‘[E]ugenics mirrored the society in which it arose in having both a benign and a dark side’ (p. 64). Does this mean that resistance is proportional to eugenic pressure? Is such a view not too reductive for understanding contemporary biosociality and biosolidarity? It is reasonable to recognize the value of historicizing the cases of eugenics application of a ‘modest’ political weight as a unique option to understand what made the application of negative eugenics impossible. Chloe Campbell’s work exemplifies this as she maps the options and limits of accepting the overtly racist medical research conducted by British physicians among Africans to demonstrate how haphazard the formation of anti-racist sentiment was and why it served as a restraining force. The disability rights movement is another example of anti-eugenic resistance. Its public influence would be key to understanding how eugenics operated as a form of ‘authoritative knowledge’ – a central motif in Redvaldsen’s narrative.

Two dichotomies – popular vs. scientific eugenics and public vs. private eugenics, and their interconnection, frame Redvaldsen’s approach to the continuity of eugenics. His stance that ‘there are medical, scientific and popular strands to the ideology’ (p. 286) serves not only as a maxim but also as a filter for selecting data relevant to his historicization, focusing on public policy. Redvaldsen’s interrogation of high- and low-brow eugenics emerges from his adherence to political analysis. The rich history of scientific debates within the British eugenics movement is absent in his narrative, and so is the impressive history of the diffusion of eugenic ideas into popular culture (Hanson, 2012). He traces the interaction between eugenicists and political movements in several campaigns promoting eugenics-informed legislation in different periods. His allegiance to the leading role of the political establishment reverses in the consistent objectification of ordinary as inactive people, often defined as victims of the contemporary popularity of the idea of ‘improvement’: ‘Prenatal diagnosis involves making a choice about

what sort of babies are worth having. The fact that the decision is made by the parents rather than by society does not cancel out the eugenic aspect' (p. 266). Similar stances appear in his discussion of sperm banks, in vitro fertilization (which he claims 'has clear eugenic effects', (p. 261) and even cloning. Limiting the role of modern reproductive technologies to a source of eugenic temptation significantly reduces the scope of the public and private dichotomy. By contrast, Chloe S. Burke and Christopher J. Castaneda have introduced this dichotomy to historicize eugenics in an anti-reductionist manner, including a more nuanced focus on the regulation of reproductive technologies (Burke, Castaneda, 2007).

The book ultimately leaves the reader with a paradox: eugenics is portrayed as an agent of reproductive surveillance that nevertheless proved incapable of advancing its own agenda. The number of filters that exclude evidence of the colonial and racial dimensions of British eugenics from Redvaldsen's narrative are closely tied to his methodological choices. This raises the question: how can the historical revision of eugenics be organised to overcome multiple pitfalls of reductionism? Whether recent trends in entangled and interdisciplinary historicization can be useful remains to be seen.

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BOOK REVIEW

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Sex Work between Agency and Control¹

Abstract: *This review examines Histories of Prostitution in Central, East-Central, and South Eastern Europe, a notable volume that reframes prostitution not as a sensationalist topic, but as a nuanced historical phenomenon. The contributors emphasize the agency of sex workers while addressing systemic constraints shaped by gender, class, medicine, and state control. Drawing on diverse sources and methodologies, the collection spans the 19th century to the Cold War, revealing how sex work intersected with evolving notions of morality, surveillance, and public health. Despite minor editorial inconsistencies, the volume is praised for its scholarly depth, interdisciplinary rigor, and contribution to European gender history.*

Keywords: *prostitution; sex work; public health; control; agency; European gender history.*

Dolinsek, S., Saryusz-Wolska, M. (Eds.) (2023). Histories of Prostitution in Central, East-Central, and South Eastern Europe, Paderborn: Brill, ISSN 2698-5020 ISBN 978-3-506-79047-7 (hardback) ISBN 978-3-657-79047-0 (e-book), p. 278.

<https://brill.com/display/title/64157>

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¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good”. The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

“What do I deal in? Ha ha! Not in Hanukkah candles, my friend, not in Hanukka candles!”² This line from Sholem Aleichem – introducing the evasive, cigar-smoking “Man from Buenos Aires” – typifies the elliptical allusions to prostitution that appear in early twentieth-century Yiddish literature. As one contributor notes, Aleichem’s readers would have recognized this figure as an “admirable gangster” – a pimp whose “commodity” was women (Keely Stauter-Halsted, pp. 75-97). Although steeped in stereotype, the volume under review resists sensationalism and instead offers a subtle, deeply contextualized analysis of prostitution as a social and historical phenomenon.

Histories of Prostitution in Central, East-Central, and South Eastern Europe is not primarily a book about human trafficking, poverty, or sexual exploitation – although these issues appear throughout. Its most striking feature is its sustained effort to recover the agency of women (and men) involved in sex work, portraying them not as passive victims but as complex historical actors. This attribution of agency is not naïve: many contributors emphasize the structural constraints their subjects faced. Keely Stauter-Halsted’s formulation of migrant sex workers as “neither entirely powerless nor fully autonomous” (p. 75) aptly captures the volume’s nuanced tone.

One weakness lies in the editors’ inconsistent terminology. The title employs “prostitution,” while the introduction uses “sex work” without clarifying the distinction. Individual contributors handle this better – for example, Alexandra Skedzuhn-Safir explicitly retains “prostitute” due to the absence of voluntarism in her sources (p. 24).

The range of sources and methods is among the book’s greatest strengths. Contributors draw on diaries, trial records, police files, maps, and more – shedding light on lives usually marginalized or erased. Equally impressive is the volume’s thematic and chronological coherence. Chapters are not only arranged historically but also interwoven methodologically, encouraging comparisons across time and region. The result is a multifaceted, compelling account of how prostitution intersected with gender, class, health, and state power.

Highlights include:

Kim Breitsmoser’s analysis of a Prussian officer’s diary (1805–1827), which documents his encounters with prostitutes, venereal dis-

² The quotation is taken from Sholem Aleichem’s short story “The Man from Buenos Aires”.

ease, and the resulting transmission to his wife and children – illustrating gendered accountability and medical ignorance in early 19th-century military contexts.

Alexandra Skedzuhn-Safir’s study of 19th-century Florence, combining urban history and police regulation. She reconstructs the geography of prostitution using maps and contemporary regulations, even tracing locations in today’s cityscape.

Stefan Wunsch’s microhistory of a Weimar-era Berlin family, prosecuted not for criminal acts *per se*, but for violating social norms: she was a prostitute; he, a “homosexual transvestite” and dancer. Their case exposes how sexual and gender nonconformity invited state surveillance.

The final section examines Cold War socialism. Contributions by Anna Dobrowolska, Priska Komáromi, and Christiane Brenner analyze how “promiscuous” women were cast as threats to moral order – charged with “parasitism” (Czechoslovakia), “criminal indolence” (Hungary), or “national degeneration” (Poland). In 1950s Poland, prostitution in new housing estates provoked moral panic framed as a failure of socialist gender policy. By the 1970s, “hotel prostitution” had emerged – women trading sex for Western luxury goods. Despite this, state tourism still exploited the image of the alluring “Hungarian girls”, and – although not extensively investigated in this volume – secret services used prostitutes to extract intelligence from foreigners.³

Across regimes and eras, prostitution was consistently entangled with public health. Often treated as vectors of venereal disease, women were subjected to state interventions ranging from medical exams and incarceration to sterilization and murder under National Socialism. Yet the picture is complex: sex workers were also among the first to adopt new protective methods and treatments, underscoring the double-edged nature of medicalization (p. 108).

The volume is essential reading for scholars of gender, medicine, and social control in modern Europe. Its inclusion of contributors at different career stages – many non-native English speakers – adds a welcome diversity of perspective.

Some shortcomings remain. Editorial inconsistencies in spelling and terminology – especially regional designations – are distracting. The title uses “East-Central” and “South Eastern Europe” (once with and once without hyphens), but variation appears throughout. More serious are factual and typographical errors: “extra martial sex” (p. 235,

³ See e. g. Brüning, 2020.

fn. 18) should be “extramarital sex”; “frequently having intercourse” (p. 171) seems to confuse the historical phrase “frequently changing intercourse,” a period-specific diagnostic criterion. Orthographic errors in Hungarian – including the misspelling of major figures like Horthy and Kádár (p. 234ff) – are particularly unfortunate. Some lapses in medical accuracy are also notable: for instance, one contribution inconsistently identifies venereal diseases – mentioning hepatitis and syphilis on p. 16, and gonorrhea on p. 17 – without clear diagnostic framing. Medical terminology is sometimes inconsistent or imprecise, e.g., references to “urine in his blood” (p. 17) likely meant “blood in his urine.”

One curious omission is the lack of commentary on the volume’s striking cover image, which features the colorful slogan “Vous pouvez être tranquille, monsieur le préfet, ici, nous sommes toutes de bonnes socialistes!” – a quote left unexplained despite its visual prominence and interpretive potential. Finally, the absence of a concluding chapter or editorial synthesis is regrettable – final reflection could have drawn together the interdisciplinary threads woven throughout the volume.

Still, these are minor flaws in an otherwise exceptional work. *Histories of Prostitution in Central, East-Central, and South Eastern Europe* sets a new standard for the study of sex work in historical context – as a prism through which broader questions of power, morality, and modernity are refracted.

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BOOK REVIEW

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From the Side of the “Weak Opposite”: The Double Stigma on Mental Suffering¹

Abstract: *The review discusses the monographic study The Stigma on Mental Disorders in Bulgaria [Стигмата върху психическите разстройства в България] by Veronika Dimitrova. The book examines how mental disorders are stigmatised in Bulgarian society and explores what it means to be perceived as ‘mentally ill’ or to ‘bear mental illness’ within this context. Dimitrova emphasizes the social construction of stigma and highlights the double burden faced by individuals with mental disorders – stemming both from the condition itself and from the societal labelling and marginalisation it entails. The sociological analysis employs a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to investigate public attitudes toward mental disorders and those affected by them. It also sheds light on the complex relationships these individuals develop with their condition and with their*

¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good” (LEVIATHAN). The project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

identities as ‘ill’, ‘disabled’, or ‘patients’. While the author briefly outlines the legacy of the Bulgarian socialist regime in relation to psychiatric care, she challenges this legacy by giving voice precisely to those who have usually remained unheard until now.

Keywords: *mental disorders; illness; stigma; psychiatric care; disability.*

Veronika Dimitrova. (2025). The Stigma on Mental Disorders in Bulgaria. Sofia: “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Press, ISBN 9789540760858, 280 p. [in Bulgarian].

<https://unipress.bg/stigmata-varhu-psihičnite-razstroystva-v-balgariya>

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Cover art by: Antonina Georgieva.

When discussing the attribution of *affirmative, negative, or deviant identities* as forms of social categorisation, one encounters the binary logic of so-called “strong” and “weak” opposites – such as ‘the rational’ and ‘the insane’, or ‘the healthy’ and ‘the ill’.² The latter are typically framed by normative culture as deprived or inherently lacking some aspect of “normalcy”, and are therefore often positioned outside the bounds of full agency and responsibility within the shared world of the *sensus communis*. This book seeks to unpack the structural mechanisms and discursive predications that place individuals with mental disorders on the “weak side” of this binary divide, while simultaneously creating space for their own voices to emerge. In this respect, Veronika Dimitrova’s monograph “The Stigma on Mental Disorders in Bulgaria”³ represents a significant and timely contribution. Her study is developed within the framework of the project “Mental Health and Social Inequalities”, which engages with mental suffering along three main dimensions: its representation in media discourse, public attitudes toward mental disorders, and, crucially, the lived experiences of those diagnosed with such conditions (p. 9).

Dimitrova continues this exploration within the theoretical framework of stigma – understood as a mark or attribute whose negative social perception may come to dominate or “swallow” one’s identity. In classical academic literature, stigma is often treated as a subject of secrecy, concealment, or impression management, wherein the individual or group attempts to “pass” as ‘normal’. At the very beginning of the book, Dimitrova asks not whether mental disorders are stigmatised in Bulgarian society – an assumption the reader quickly comes to share –

² Or ‘the adult’ and ‘the child’, etc. (cf. Deyanov, 2006).

³ Вероника Димитрова. (2025). *Стигмата върху психичните разстройства в България*. София: УИ „Св. Климент Охридски“.

but rather *how* this stigmatisation operates and with what consequences (ibid). Her focus is especially on conditions that, unlike diagnoses such as ‘dementia’ or ‘mental retardation’ (in the author’s terms), lack an organic correlate – rendering them more resistant to medical ‘taming’. As she argues “there is a dynamic relationship between the disorder itself and the individual, ranging from acceptance to rejection of the diagnosis, from incorporating the diagnosis into one’s identity to limiting it to a distinct social role, from normalisation to normification and information control about the disorder itself in various ways, etc. This relationship is mediated by a number of institutional mechanisms, images and frameworks” (p. 121-122). The author examines these dynamics across two principal domains – theoretical and empirical.

The first part of the book offers a detailed overview of the sociological “scaffold” underpinning the study, structured around an adapted reading of classical works such as Erving Goffman’s “Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity” (1963) and Kai T. Erikson’s “Patient Role and Social Uncertainty” (1957). The author adopts a multi-perspective and updated interpretation of these foundational concepts, engaging with a range of contemporary authors among whom Patrick Corrigan, Bruce G. Link and Ian Hacking.⁴ The study is strongly influenced by the Chicago School of Sociology, as it situates concepts such as *illness* and *mental disorder* within social, cultural, and historical interpretive frameworks that mediate between everyday lay knowledge and (bio)medical expertise.⁵ While the latter is positioned as the official or dominant discourse – analysed primarily through the lens of *medicalisation* – Dimitrova convincingly demonstrates that this field is not

⁴ While in their majority they provide in-depth analyses of the social labels and effects of stigmatisation, it is noteworthy that the used standardised terminology retains, somewhat uncritically, a dominant discursive reliance on the (negative) institutional language of deviation.

⁵ Throughout this review, I will try to adhere to the term ‘disorder’ as the principal designation – both because it appears in the book’s title and because it aligns with the official clinical categorization employed by the “Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders” (cf. APA, 2022). The book does not clarify whether the terms ‘disorder’, ‘illness’, and ‘disease’ are used interchangeably. My impression is that, while these terms represent conceptually differing forms of categorisation, they are operationally treated as equivalent in the study from a narrative point of view, albeit with an implicit differentiation between lay and expert discourses. A more explicit articulation of the research strategy in this regard would be beneficial, particularly in clarifying *who* speaks about the(ir) experience, *how*, and *through what discursive framework* of legitimisation, as such demarcations may also mark nuances in the attitude towards the condition.

insulated from the value-laden implications of everyday thinking. These normative undercurrents shape the entire process of *seeking*, *uncovering*, and *living with* a diagnostic label. In this context, the author engages with the concept of stigma across a broad spectrum of associated terms – such as “label”, “stereotype”, and “deviation” – while attending to the affective dimensions that they carry (e.g., fear, disapproval, suspicion).

The book also critically addresses the institutional logic that governs the diagnostic trajectory, revealing how individuals are positioned within a ‘plexus’ of interlocking roles: for instance, (psychiatric) examination leading to the role of the ill; hospitalisation to that of the patient; and certification of labour incapacity to the role of the disabled. These roles can act as “identity hooks” to which the ‘Self’ becomes tethered. While they may offer certain forms of practical alleviation from one’s societal responsibilities, Dimitrova argues that they can also restrict the individual’s horizon of possibilities. The author tries to illuminate these aspects with regards to the current landscape of the psychiatric care in Bulgaria, which still reflects the legacy of the “[s]ocialist institutional psychiatry [that] was influenced by the main trends in the Soviet Union and was built primarily on the principles of segregation and paternalism, despite declared attempts to create dispensaries” (p. 205).

Since Dimitrova emphasises the range of individual adjustment strategies – or the so-called ‘moral career’, that embodies a reflexive attitude towards the disease, the use of Goffman’s concepts is analytically justified.⁶ In her words, “[t]he stakes of the analysis in this book are to contain the processes that invisibly marginalise people with mental disorders, if we perceive recovery not only in a health sense, but as a process tied to identity – it is the experience of learning to live with the illness despite the illness” (p. 201). As she demonstrates, this relationship is often ambivalent: encountering the label of ‘mentally ill’ can be a stigmatising and even traumatic event, yet adopting the dominant medical framing of one’s experience may also open a path toward what she terms “therapeutic optimism” – the belief that, even if a condition

⁶ While it is evident that she follows the Goffmanian terminological apparatus – particularly through the use of notions such as ‘the Self’ – a more detailed theoretical engagement with the concept could be beneficial. Working with biographical interviews offers the opportunity to explore the attribution of stigma as a *performative act* (cf. Bourdieu, 1991), to explore the dynamic process of *identity construction* in the process of biographical narration, and further – to open space for an existential inquiry into the question of *who* one is beyond a constructivist or psychological interpretation (see Arendt, 1958: 179, 181).

cannot be fully cured, it can be managed or controlled through medical and/or communal means.

The second, empirical, part of the monograph is devoted to such narratives. The first two chapters of this section (Chapters Six and Seven) examine how individuals experience and make sense of their diagnosis. Dimitrova and her team collected 87 biographical interviews with individuals in remission from various mental disorders, as well as with their close relatives, to illuminate this aspect. The author adheres to the widely accepted distinction between ‘severe’ and ‘common’ mental disorders.⁷ Regarding the former, she focuses primarily on individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia or bipolar affective disorder. Based on their testimonies, Dimitrova concludes that in these disorders the degree of stigma internalisation is substantial, and the biographical narratives are deeply marked by the presence of the illness, often perceived as a fate.⁸ In such cases, the family often serves as a protective shell, and the disorder becomes an integral aspect of the individual’s identity. Hospitalisation and pharmacological mitigation of the condition are the main therapeutic strategies.

In contrast to the over-institutionalisation of severe mental disorders, the cluster of diagnoses, referred to as ‘common’ comprises conditions for which “no institutional forms of support exist or [they] are only partially covered by the system for providing mental health services in the country” (p. 165). The primary interlocutors in this section include individuals with alcohol addiction participating in Alcoholics Anonymous,⁹ as well as people experiencing anxiety or panic disorders, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and depression. Dimitrova observes a notable tendency: such experiences might remain unrecognized as a ‘legitimate disorder’ by both laypeople and medical professionals. Alcohol dependence, for instance, is often interpreted not as a psychiatric issue, but as a manifestation of weak willpower or failure, even by physicians and therapists. Similarly, in the case of anxiety and panic disorders, their prevalence and familiarity among the population might dull

⁷ Here, Dimitrova employs the established demarcation, which differentiates between two distinct measurement criteria: quality and frequency.

⁸ The author provides several examples of such framing: adopting biomedical interpretation of the illness as a genetic predisposition; as a consequence of one’s stressful life circumstances or social environment; or as divine punishment by God.

⁹ As noted by the author, this is a group with established forms of organization and a shared narrative framework for making sense of one’s condition. Further research could involve a comparison with individuals that are not engaged in such communities.

sensitivity to the individual experience as a genuine form of hardship and obscure the individual need for professional help-seeking.¹⁰

This notion resonates strikingly with Pierre Bourdieu's concept of *social suffering* – a burden that arises not only from the objective social conditions of one's life but also from its banalisation. Such distress is often seen as “ordinary” and unworthy of special recognition or intervention. As Bourdieu notes: “not even the deepest preliminary knowledge could lead to true comprehension if it were not accompanied both by an attentiveness to others and an openness towards them rarely met within everyday life. We normally tend, in fact, to accord to the relatively ritualized talk of relatively common troubles an attention merely as empty and formal as the ‘How are you?’ which triggers it off. We have all heard stories of struggles [...], which we apprehend through categories of perception which, by reducing the personal to the impersonal, the unique drama to the commonplace, permit a sort of economizing of thought and emotion, in brief, of comprehension.” (Bourdieu, 1996:23).¹¹ This dynamic, as Dimitrova insightfully points out, can lead to what she terms the “stabilisation of the medical model” (p. 262) – a process by which individuals adopt and internalise the clinical framework as a means of explaining and legitimising their condition. The lack of strong institutional grip – since the respondents in this cluster usually turn to private practice or alternative support networks – is described by Dimitrova both as a hurdle and as a condition that loosens the *secondary deviance* (in Howard Becker's terms) associated with being diagnosed and labelled as ‘mentally ill’. Such findings could lead to the assumption that, in the case of severe mental disorders, one's experience may be framed as radically different and, therefore, difficult to comprehend or make intelligible. Nevertheless, the relatively higher level of tolerance (p. 261) and shared experiential similarities in the so-called common mental disorders also do not necessarily guarantee genuine understanding on the part of others.

The final two chapters of the monograph focus specifically on public attitudes toward mental disorders. Dimitrova employs an adapted version of the CAMI III (Community Attitudes to Mental Illness) questionnaire, combined with 15 semi-structured interviews.

¹⁰ In this sense, the dynamics between (opposing) interpretive frameworks – such as ‘moral deviance’ versus ‘medical condition’ – are particularly interesting, especially in light of concepts like the *medicalisation of mood* (cf. Rose, 2006).

¹¹ For an examination of different forms of social vulnerability in that respect, see for example Mineva, Tasheva, 2019.

Through this methodological approach, she aims to explore both how society perceives individuals with mental disorders and how mental illness is constructed through the lens of stigma. The results are difficult to homogenise or generalise; nevertheless, I will highlight two key findings. The first concerns the expressed “need to change the system for serving people with mental disorders” (ibid) and to humanise institutional care – an issue raised both by public opinion and by individuals with mental disorders themselves. This opens up a valuable conversation about the ambiguous place of psychiatric services in contemporary Bulgarian society, and suggests a need for reconceptualising care in more pluralistic and socially responsive ways. The second relates to Dimitrova’s thesis that within Bulgarian society, mental disorders may be stigmatised due to their association with more severe conditions – such as schizophrenia – particularly through the notion of “danger.”¹² However, the collected data exposed another prevailing image, one shaped by affiliation with organic mental disorders – and more specifically, with “mental retardation.” According to Dimitrova, this links the public perception of mental disorder with the notion of *incompetence*. This frames a different form of deviation, one that may align more closely with infantilisation than, for example, criminalisation (cf. Kanoushev, 2020). Such an understanding may be reinforced not only by the closed, paternalistic nature of institutional care but also by a system of social services, which to some extent predisposes the pairing and equating of the categories ‘disorder’ and ‘disability’, and those of ‘social support’ with ‘social benefits’. And, as she also points out, this may relieve individuals of certain social obligations, but at the same time, it can undermine their sense of agency.

In conclusion, Veronika Dimitrova’s book offers a complex study of a complex issue. It tries to challenge common perceptions and draws on the life-trajectories of real individuals, illustrating the diverse ways

¹² A striking recent example of the ‘in principle acceptance under the condition of no real contact,’ as identified by the researcher, can be seen in the protests in late 2024 against the construction of a centre for people with disabilities in a residential neighbourhood in Varna. These reactions were fuelled by social anxieties and (deliberate) misinformation. One of the protesters stated: “We have nothing against this centre, but maybe it doesn’t belong here because it’s right on the boulevard”, and another one adds: “Personally, I am afraid if there would be people with intense or severe mental retardation. What do we do if these people go out and walk around the neighborhood?”, retrieved from <https://bntnews.bg/news/zashto-grazhdani-se-obyaviha-protiv-izgrazhdane-na-dneven-centar-za-hora-s-uvrezhdaniya-vav-varna-1298566news.html>, last visit 22.07.2025.

in which people negotiate their relationship with the disorder. It is an original work conducted within a research community with a clear interest in what is happening on the side of the “weak opposite”.

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BOOK REVIEW

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Understanding State Socialism Through the Lens of Disability¹

Kateřina Kolářová, Martina Winkler (eds.)

RE/IMAGINATIONS OF DISABILITY IN STATE SOCIALISM

Abstract: *This book review examines Re/imaginings of Disability in State Socialism: Visions, Promises, Frustrations (edited by Kateřina Kolářová and Martina Winkler), a volume exploring the history of disability across communist regimes in Central and Eastern Europe. Moving beyond narratives of invisibility or total institutionalization, the book addresses multiple perspectives on disability under state socialism, ranging from expert discourses such as defectology to labour-centred care policies and cultural representations of disability. The volume also highlights intersections with other categories, including ethnicity and family. The contributions span diverse contexts, from the Soviet Union to Czechoslovakia, Poland, the GDR, and Bulgaria, offering a nuanced and comparative picture of socialist disability histories. Importantly, the book focuses not only on the visions and plans of communist dictatorships but also on the limits, paradoxes, and contradictions inherent in socialist disability policies. These tensions reveal both the*

sions and plans of communist dictatorships but also on the limits, paradoxes, and contradictions inherent in socialist disability policies. These tensions reveal both the

¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good” (LEVIATHAN). The project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

utopian aspirations and the structural challenges faced by socialist welfare regimes. Furthermore, the contributions situate approaches toward people with disabilities within a broader framework of welfare state transformation, tracing shifts from the Stalinist period to the era of late socialism. It positions disability as a lens through which broader themes of modernization, identity formation, and social norms can be examined.

Keywords: *Disability history; state socialism; Central and Eastern Europe; care and control; welfare state.*

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https://www.campus.de/buecher-campus-verlag/wissenschaft/geschichte/re_imaginations_of_disability_in_state_socialism-16537.html

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This edited volume examines the position of disabled people within the communist utopia. More specifically, it explores how state socialist regimes, which promised a “healthy, abled, happy and resilient” population (p. 7) and placed labour at the core of their social organization, approached individuals with mental illnesses and disabilities. Rather than reproducing the common narrative of disability under socialism as merely a “dark age” of institutionalization or invisibility, the book aims to offer a more nuanced history. It highlights the tensions between the visions, utopias, and plans of communist dictatorships and the limits, paradoxes, and internal conflicts into which these often culminated. The authors draw attention to a fundamental paradox of disability in state socialism: while disabled people were included in the vision of a new socialist society, grounded in the belief that human nature was plastic and shaped by the environment and material conditions, the persistence of disability in socialist societies posed a continual challenge to, and critique of, this vision (pp. 9–10).

Methodologically, the volume approaches disability as “a useful category” (p. 13), one that not only articulated the utopias and ideals of state socialism but also exposed the underlying “able norm” embedded within these societies. The publication is structured around several thematic clusters that interweave throughout the contributions: the emergence of a new epistemology of disability, the role of labor in socialist care politics, and cultural representations of disability. The first theme examines expert knowledge about disability – in fields such as pedagogy and psychology – shaped by the discipline of so-called defecto-

logy. On the one hand, the defectological model constituted a new epistemological field that redefined understandings of disability; on the other hand, it simultaneously produced new mechanisms of marginalization and exclusion. Another recurring theme is the role of labour as a tool of care and inclusion in socialist societies. Here, too, a paradox emerges: socialist regimes sought to integrate into a labour-centered society those members who, by virtue of disability, were unable to work. The emphasis on labour as an integrative factor was not unique to state socialism; however, while exclusion in the West meant the inability to sell one's labour on the market, under state socialism it meant the inability to participate in the collective project of building a new society. A third key theme explored in the book is the analysis of cultural representations of disability and the broader socialist disability imaginaries.

The edited volume brings together nine studies that explore the disability history of the communist dictatorships of Central and Eastern Europe, with particular emphasis on Czechoslovakia (four chapters), as well as the GDR, Bulgaria, and Poland; one contribution also focuses on the Soviet Union. In the chapter, titled "*Just Like It Is at Home!*" *Soviet Deafness and Socialist Internationalism during the Cold War*, Claire Shaw examines the formation of Soviet deafness as a specific identity shaped by the Soviet model and its subsequent dissemination to other countries in Central and Eastern Europe (p. 30). She analyzes not only symposia, journals, and deaf organizations, but also international visits and exchanges, exploring how deaf identity was constructed. At the same time, Shaw demonstrates that "socialist deafness" was far from a monolithic concept: significant tensions and alternative understandings existed within the socialist bloc, going beyond what Soviet activists envisioned, or perhaps even desired (p. 46). One particularly valuable contribution of this chapter is its attention to the lived experiences and emotions of participants and activists involved in these transnational exchanges, the so-called "socialist deaf tourists", and their feelings (p. 50). The following chapter, *Work as a Form of Emancipation: The Emergence of Czechoslovak Defectology* by Marek Fapšo and Jan Randák, focuses on the emergence of Czechoslovak defectology and the figure of Miloš Sovák, the founder of this discipline in the post-war period. The authors argue that defectology in Czechoslovakia should not be understood merely as a Soviet export; they stress the need to examine the transfer of defectological concepts within local professional practices rather than as a "pre-programmed" transmission (p. 72).

They also highlight that defectology's position after the communist takeover was far from secure: during the 1950s, its leading proponents had to actively work to legitimize it in the eyes of party officials, even though it drew heavily on Marxist positions and the teachings of I. P. Pavlov. Precisely this link to Pavlovian doctrine, the conceptual and language framework it provided for talking about disability, helped defectology achieve a more stable footing. In the third chapter, *Disability Assessment under State Socialism*, Teodor Mladenov examines disability policy in the Soviet Union and its influence on socialist Bulgaria. He explores how the "Soviet disability blueprint" was translated and reshaped in this context. Furthermore, he analyzes disability policy under state socialism through the lens of "medical-productivism," aimed at creating "hyper-able" and "motivated" laborers (p. 95). Mladenov situates these attempts within a broader discussion of the transformation from industrial to post-industrial societies and considers the role of control and discipline in both neoliberal and state socialist regimes.

Frank Henschel's study, *The Formation of "Disability": Expert Discourses on Children's Sexuality, "Behavioural Defectivity", and "Bad Families" in Socialist Czechoslovakia (1950s–1970s)*, examines expert discourses on "defective children" in socialist Czechoslovakia from the 1950s to the 1970s. He focuses in particular on pedagogical and psychological knowledge concerning the "sexually deviant child." Henschel identifies an important shift in expert discourse: an increasing emphasis on the idea that "deviant" children were primarily the result of a "bad family environment." This reasoning stemmed from the observation that, despite the establishment of a new socialist society, social problems persisted; consequently, blame for "defective individuals" was attributed either to remnants of the "old society" or to an individual's failure to adapt to the new social order. Within the discourse on defective children, this argument broadened to encompass the entire family. Thus, the focus shifted from a structural to an individual level (pp. 135–136). Maria-Lena Faßig in her chapter, *Discourses of Prevention, Risk and Responsibility in the Women's Magazine Vlasta (1950s–1980s)*, makes a similar observation in her study of the popular women's magazine *Vlasta*, as she examines what was considered a threat to children's health. She traces a shift in prevention discourse: whereas in the 1950s the emphasis lay on combating infectious diseases and promoting vaccination, later discourse placed increasing stress on parental responsibility for children's health (p. 161). In addition, the later decades witnessed a renewed interest in genetics.

Kateřina Kolářová and Filip Herza, in their study *Engineering Socialist Integration in the Age of Normalisation: Roma and People with Disabilities as Objects of Care in Socialist Czechoslovakia*, examine the intersection of disability and ethnicity. By analyzing state policies toward the Roma population, they show that integration efforts were primarily framed in paternalistic terms. They also highlight a key contradiction in this approach: initiatives to involve Roma more fully in social life simultaneously served as strategies to silence or slow down the political emancipation of emerging Roma elites (p. 190). Moreover, the conceptualization of race and disability shifted over time; by the 1980s, it had taken on more conservative and determinist overtones. Pia Schmäser's contribution, "*We as parents must be helped.*" *State-Parent Interactions on Care Facilities for Children with "Mental Disabilities" in the GDR*, focuses on interactions between the state and parents regarding the placement of disabled children in care facilities in the GDR, particularly in extra-familial settings such as day-care centers and residential homes. Her analysis combines two perspectives: a top-down view, based on official state actors, infrastructures, and policies concerning people with disabilities; and a bottom-up approach, grounded in parental correspondence and written complaints, which examines how parents negotiated with state authorities. Schmäser draws on the concept of *Eigensinn* to trace how the dynamics of the state–parent relationship evolved in the GDR, especially during the Honecker era, when parental voices gained greater prominence. In line with Mary Fulbrook's thesis of the "participatory dictatorship," Schmäser argues that parents appropriated the rhetoric of late socialism in East Germany to make greater demands on the state concerning care for disabled children.

The final two contributions, by Martina Winkler and Natalia Pamula, explore shifting representations of disability under state socialism. Winkler, in her chapter *Disability and Childhood in Socialist Czechoslovakia*, focuses on children's literature and media, analyzing how narratives of childhood and disability were framed. This perspective allows her to address broader questions concerning constructions of normality and attitudes toward diversity in socialist societies. Similarly, Natalia Pamula's closing chapter, *Out of Place, Out of Time: Intellectual Disability in Late Socialist Polish Young Adult Literature*, examines representations of disability in young adult literature in late socialist Poland, with particular attention to portrayals of mentally disa-

bled children. The four novels Pamula analyzes are set in rural environments, which play a central role in shaping depictions of these children. The protagonists are depicted as living in poverty, rendered helpless and voiceless, while the rural setting itself emerges as a space of violence and deprivation (p. 297). The disabled characters are read as instances of “bare life”, lives marginalized by economic injustice, state neglect of rural areas, and social prejudices. The village itself mirrors this marginalization, positioned at the fringes of socialist modernity.

Overall, this edited volume addresses an important and understudied topic: the history of disability under state socialism, approached from a variety of perspectives. It examines the emergence of expert knowledge about people with disabilities, the formation and implementation of state policies, and the ways disability was represented in the media. A significant number of the contributions highlight a broader shift in how disability was conceptualized between the 1950s and the era of late socialism. While in the immediate post-war period disability was framed primarily through the emerging discipline of defectology, with a strong emphasis on labour as the main vehicle for social integration, the later socialist period increasingly foregrounded the role of the family environment alongside this productivist trope. Although disability might at first glance appear marginal to the broader history of socialism, this volume demonstrates, and this seems to me one of its key contributions, that disability provides an illuminating lens for examining major questions of modernization, identity formation, and the construction of norms in post-war societies, as well as the intertwined histories of care, control, and repression. Importantly, the individual chapters explore not only the utopian projects, plans, and visions of socialist disability policy, but also the limits, paradoxes, and internal contradictions inherent in these approaches. As the volume demonstrates, these tensions in turn provide a productive starting point for further historical research. Two possible avenues for further development come to mind. First, a stronger comparative engagement with Western Europe could help situate the socialist experience more fully within transnational histories of disability. Second, in addition to expert discourses or representations, closer attention to sources connected with the infrastructure of care, its administration, organization, and everyday functioning, could deepen our understanding of how socialist disability policies operated in practice.

BOOK REVIEW

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Inclusion, Exclusion, and the Post-War Welfare State¹

Abstract: *This review analyses the book *Marginalized Groups, Inequalities and the Post-War Welfare State* (eds. Monika Baár & Paul van Trigt). This book is an important contribution to the study of the welfare state, as it examines welfare systems from the perspective of those excluded from them, such as ethnic, gender, racial, and sexual minorities, as well as people with disabilities. Based on this perspective and by studying several Western European countries as well as international organizations, the book provides an interesting view of the consequences of the welfare state – who it includes and who it excludes. Although the book focuses mainly on Western Europe and the United States, this approach to studying the welfare state from the perspective of marginalized groups is significant and can be used as a framework for analysing other regions and for comparative studies.*

¹ The research is within the ERC Project "Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good". The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

Keywords: *Welfare state; marginalized groups; social exclusion; post-war Europe.*

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Marginalized Groups, Inequalities and the Post-War Welfare State (eds. Monika Baar & Paul van Trigt) is a significant contribution to welfare state studies and to the scholarship on social care more broadly. The volume represents a shift in the way welfare state, social assistance, and social protection systems are approached.

Traditionally, two dominant tendencies have characterized the study of welfare states. First, analyses have tended to adopt a nation-state framework, focusing on the development of national welfare systems and, at times, comparing them across countries. This approach has frequently involved the use of typologies such as those of Esping-Andersen, which categorize welfare systems into liberal, conservative, and social-democratic regimes (Esping-Andersen, 1990). Such an emphasis is understandable: from their origins – and especially in the post-World War II period, when social protection expanded significantly across Europe – welfare systems were indeed organized on a national basis, as the system was constructed to protect citizens in case of vulnerability (Introduction, pp. 1-3).

Second, welfare state research has long been centred on the citizen-worker nexus, examining the relationship between the contributing worker and the benefits they receive: what portion of their contributions is returned, and what kind of protection is provided in cases of unemployment, accidents, or old age. This contributor-centric approach has meant that scholarship has largely concentrated on the majority of citizens who actively paid into and benefited from these systems (Introduction, pp. 3-4).

This volume's primary focus is on migrants, disabled people, racial and sexual minorities, and other marginalized groups whose access to social protection in the post-war era was either excluded or very limited, even at the peak of welfare state expansion in Western Europe (Introduction, pp. 4-6; Ch. 2, pp. 29-48; Ch. 3, pp. 49-68; Ch. 9, pp. 155-

171). Through a series of chapters that examine both national case studies and the role of international organizations such as the UN, the ILO, and the European Communities (Ch. 1, pp. 9-28; Ch. 2, pp. 29-48; Ch. 4, pp. 69-80), the book reveals that while the post-war period indeed witnessed a significant expansion of welfare coverage – including industrial workers, artisans, small shopkeepers, and even agricultural producers – many groups remained outside these systems.

For example, in the chapter on Denmark, Heidi Vad Jønsson discusses how, in the immediate post-war period, migrant workers initially had the same labour rights as local workers. However, over time, these rights began to be restricted, conditioned on “the integration of workers into Danish society.” For example, language exams and proof of social integration were required, and welfare benefits were no longer regarded as unconditional rights but rather as privileges granted only to those workers who demonstrated successful integration into the host society (Ch. 9, pp. 155-171).

Similarly, Karim Fertikh, in the second chapter, which focuses on the 1957 European Convention on the Social Security of Migrant Workers, shows that all efforts to advance a platform guaranteeing equal rights for all migrant workers across Europe were consistently obstructed by national governments. They were unwilling to extend to foreign workers the same rights available to local workers, who, after all, also had the right to vote (Ch. 2, pp. 29-48).

In his study of the Social Affairs Commission of the early European Communities, Brian Shaev notes that while measures were adopted to guarantee equal rights for steel and coal workers – primarily local male industrial workers – similar European-level measures for migrant workers and women were not mentioned (Ch. 1, pp. 9-28).

A similar transformation occurred regarding disabled workers. As Gildas Brégain demonstrates in his chapter on the ILO, in the immediate post-war period there was an inclusive approach aimed at rehabilitating all disabled citizens. Later, however, this approach shifted to become market-oriented, assisting only those individuals who could be integrated into the labour market while neglecting those without the potential for such reintegration (Ch. 3, pp. 49-68). The key reason, as the contributors demonstrate, is that the very criteria used by state institutions to determine eligibility – citizenship, formal labour market participation, and normative assumptions about productivity – also acted as

barriers of exclusion (Ch. 6, pp. 101-117; Ch. 9, pp. 155-171). This dynamic of inclusion and exclusion constitutes one of the central analytical axes of the book.

Another important contribution of the volume is its emphasis on the agency of marginalized groups. These populations were not passive, nor merely the objects of exclusionary policies; rather, they were active in trying to shape welfare systems. Migrants' associations, disability rights activists, queer movements, and human rights advocates all fought to gain a voice in the formation of social protection policies (Ch. 7, pp. 119-135; Ch. 8, pp. 137-153). This perspective shifts the narrative from one of "state benevolence" to one of contested social rights.

Thus, Monika Baár writes that in the 1980s, disability activists intensified their efforts to have their rights recognized and to gain greater independence in their daily lives. However, this effort – and their discourse – was co-opted by the Thatcher government to justify welfare cuts (Ch. 7, pp. 119-135). In Belgium, according to Anaïs van Ertvelde, activists for the rights of persons with disabilities, while strongly advocating for the protection of welfare provisions, simultaneously began efforts to develop grassroots movements emphasizing autonomy and community living. Yet even in Belgium, this type of discourse was occasionally used to restrict the benefits available to persons with disabilities, with such restrictions justified on the basis of individual autonomy (Ch. 8, pp. 137-153).

The book also proposes a periodization of welfare state development in the second half of the twentieth century. The post-war moment (1940s–1950s) saw a significant expansion of citizenship-based rights and access to welfare as a response to the humanitarian catastrophe of the war, for example Italy and France temporarily implemented universal benefits due to the severe difficulties in the aftermath of the war. (Ch. 6, pp. 101-117). The 1970s–1980s marked the neoliberal turn, which curtailed previously broad entitlements, reframing social protection as a conditional benefit rather than a right, and emphasizing individual responsibility (Ch. 7, pp. 119-135; Ch. 4, pp. 69-80). The late 1980s and 1990s introduced a paradox: while the discourse of exclusion and human rights became more prominent, it was often appropriated by policymakers and neoliberal think tanks to justify welfare cuts, reducing expenditures on pensions, healthcare, and social assistance even as the language of rights proliferated. These cuts were often justified as increasing the autonomy of individual – by giving them more space to

decide for themselves – and improving the efficiency of the system. (Ch. 4, pp. 69-80; Ch. 8, pp. 137-153).

From this perspective, the general conclusion of the book is that, although many aspects of social protection and welfare – such as access to adequate healthcare – constitute basic human rights and are guaranteed by the universal principles of human rights, they remain tied to possession of a passport from a specific country and to contributions. This arrangement disadvantages broad social categories that lack these characteristics (Conclusion, pp. 173-189). For this reason, the authors call for a reconsideration of welfare systems through a more transnational approach, placing equality, justice, and respect for human dignity at the centre of social policies (Conclusion, pp. 186-189).

As noted above, this volume constitutes a significant contribution to welfare state historiography, as it places at the centre of analysis those who were excluded from, or had only limited access to, systems of social protection. Employing an interdisciplinary approach and moving across scales – from the state level to international organizations such as the ILO and the European Communities – the book offers an inter-scalar study of how both national bureaucracies and international structures ultimately failed to provide a truly international framework for social protection, whether at the European or global level. By challenging Esping-Andersen's typology of welfare regimes, the volume leads to an important conclusion: welfare regimes themselves produce exclusions and inequalities among citizens.

While the book focuses primarily on groups excluded and marginalized by welfare systems – migrants, disabled people, and racial and sexual minorities – these groups are mostly examined as separate categories. The analysis does not pay sufficient attention to intersectionality: whether there were shared mechanisms of exclusion affecting individuals who embodied multiple marginalized identities, and how such intersectionality shaped their experiences within welfare systems. Furthermore, when examining activism to strengthen social protection, the book could have explored more deeply whether there was collaboration or conflict between different marginalized groups in their struggles for inclusion (Williams, 1995).

Another point that could have been researched more broadly is the book's geographical focus. While it analyses post-war welfare systems in Western Europe and includes one chapter on the United States, it largely omits Central and Eastern Europe – regions that also underwent crucial economic and political transformations after the Second

World War, transformations that profoundly affected their welfare regimes (Inglot, 2008). This omission is particularly striking given that many of these countries officially espoused socialist ideologies, placing the working class – at least rhetorically – at the center of public discourse. Consequently, their social protection systems prioritized the industrial working class, often to the detriment of other, more marginalized groups (Koleva, 2023). A comparative study of “Western capitalist welfare regimes” and “Eastern socialist welfare regimes” would have offered valuable insights into commonalities and divergences in the treatment of marginalized populations.

Similarly, the volume could have extended its scope to the Global South, where many countries emerged from colonial rule in the post-war decades and began developing their economies (Dey Biswas, Sambo, & Pellissery, 2024). Many of the migrant workers excluded from Western European welfare systems originated from these former colonies. It would have been illuminating to examine the extent to which colonial legal frameworks influenced post-colonial welfare regimes, and how this legacy shaped the position of migrants within European welfare systems. Moreover, given that the Soviet Union and other socialist countries sought to exert influence in the Global South – and were themselves regarded as development models by several post-colonial states – the competition between East and West over social policy models warrants attention, particularly in relation to the industrial corporations from former colonial powers that remained active in these regions.

Beyond these remarks, the book’s core framework – studying welfare regimes not from the perspective of the contributing worker but from the vantage point of those excluded or only partially included – is of lasting scholarly significance. This approach has considerable potential for application beyond Western Europe, including in Eastern and Central Europe, as well as in the Global South. It also opens the way for comparative analyses of East and West, North and South, providing a broader and more nuanced understanding of how welfare regimes have historically shaped inclusion and exclusion. Thus, this edited volume is an important contribution to the study of welfare states and social protection, that lays a foundation for future research extending to other regions and dimensions.

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BOOK REVIEW

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Mapping the Field of Care¹

Abstract: *The text is a review of “Dimensions of Care: In-between Personal Experience, Social Regulations and Health Activism”, a collective volume introducing a variety of perspectives on caregiving in family and institutional contexts, related policies and regulations, on the one hand, and personal experiences, on the other. The value of this collective work lies in foregrounding and mapping out the vast, diverse and unexplored field of care. Moving beyond mono-dimensional biomedical approaches, the authors offer a wealth of conceptual and practical insights that will inspire future work.*

Keywords: *care; disability; medical ethics; social medicine; social policy; health activism.*

¹ The publication is within the ERC Project “Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good” (LEVIATHAN). The project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

Stavru, S., Karamelska, T. (eds.) (2021). Dimensions of Care: In-between the Personal Experience, Social Regulations and Health Activism. Sofia: Mediina Demokratsia Foundation, ISBN 978-619-90423-5-9, p. 423 p. [In Bulgarian].

OA: [https://www.challengingthelaw.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Izmereniya_na-grizhata.pdf](https://www.challengingthelaw.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Izmereniya_na_grizhata.pdf)

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Cover art by: Mina Dicheva

This book² does not provide a definition or conceptualization of care. Instead of theorizing care, the volume offers multiple perspectives on different types of care, mobilizing approaches from law and ethics, sociology, psychology and psychiatry, history and philosophy, social medicine, disability studies and social gerontology. From another angle, the chapters of the volume cover the entire life span, from birth to death and from family relations to interactions with institutions. The book is ‘populated’ by people in need of various forms of care (babies, disabled children, the mentally ill and the elderly) as well as by those providing care, whether families or institutions/professionals.

The first part of the volume comprises four chapters discussing care at home for disabled and terminally ill people. Galina Goncharova introduces the concept of ‘alternative social timing’ to explore the specific dynamics of care for disabled people and the potential for coping with the crises it entails for the caregivers, most often female family members: mothers, daughters, even granddaughters. Alexandra Traykova draws on two sophisticated insider perspectives – those of cultural theorist J. Stacey and sociologist A. Frank, who have reflected on their own personal experiences of cancer and the cultural narratives surrounding it. Both Goncharova and Traykova frame their cases in ethical terms, evoking the patients’ and caregivers’ ideas of the ‘good life’ and the metamorphoses brought about by their condition. While these authors focus on individuals and their (im)possible empowerment, the following two chapters offer a diametrically opposite perspective, addressing the legal and practical aspects of social policies related to care. Ivan G. Dechev, a legal expert at the Ombudsman Institution, discusses the reform in assistance care based on the Personal Assistance Act adopted in 2019. His analysis compares the opportunities and limitations of the National Programme ‘Assistants for People with Disabilities’, EU-funded projects operated by local authorities, and the provisions of the

² Ставру, С., Карамелска, Т. (съст.). (2021). *Измерения на грижата: между лично преживяване, социалните регулации и здравния активизъм*. София: Фондация „Медийна демокрация“.

Personal Assistance Act. The author concludes that the Personal Assistance Act is an important step toward better-quality and more accessible care. In the same vein, the following chapter, penned by Martin J. Ivanov and Radoslava Lalcheva, situates home care within Bulgaria's social services system, examining its integration with medical care and the opportunities for personalization and better accessibility. The chapter is based on statistical data of the types of home care, analysis of normative documents and, above all, the authors' own experience in the non-government sector, focused on social services and social entrepreneurship.

The second part of the volume comprises four chapters dealing with childcare and its gendered dimensions. It opens with two very pertinent historical chapters: Milena Angelova explores the medicalization of childhood in the context of anti-tuberculosis campaigns during the first half of the 20th century. She shows how the invention of the category of 'pretubercular children', who were taken away from their families to be educated in 'open-air schools', corresponded to a broader political and cultural agenda of social hygiene. The same period and social context is the focus of Kristina Popova's chapter on social surveys of working-class living conditions conducted by women social democrats in the 1930s. Popova places their activities within the broader framework of women's movements in early 20th-century Europe, highlighting both their solidarity in giving voice to deprived populations and the limitations imposed by eugenic views. Voice is at the core of the next chapter as well, which connects to Goncharova's piece on family care for children with disabilities. However, its author Lyuboslava Kostova focuses on the absence of fathers and their missing voice. She calls for breaking the silence, stressing the importance of including fathers' stories and voices as a prerequisite for social change. Finally, Monika Bogdanova advocates for the relevance of the psychoanalytic paradigm for baby care.

A group of three chapters on obesity and healthy lifestyle stems from a research project led by Sonya Karabeliova and Radina Stoyanova. Under their methodological guidance, a group of psychology students applied various analytical tools to investigate knowledge about obesity, attitudes towards overweight people, and motivations for a healthy lifestyle among 16-45-year-olds. Regardless of the specific correlations established, and despite the limited sample size which pre-

cludes generalization, this part introduces yet another important dimension, that of self-care. Thereby, it contributes to the mapping of the vast and diverse field of care.

Two chapters are dedicated to psychiatric care. Margarita Gabrovska argues that mental illness is less a medical problem than a social one, especially when viewed from the perspective of institutional care. The reason is that mental patients are not treated with a view to re-integration in society but as passive recipients of psychiatric care, which leads to the loss of autonomy and the fragmentation of personality. This is a social problem because of the lack of policies providing psychosocial support. As a specification of, and partly a counterpoint to, the negative aspects of care singled out by Gabrovska, the following chapter details all forms and institutions of psychiatric care in Bulgaria and outlines their organization and functioning. The authors, Vladimir Nakov, Hristo Hinkov and Stefani Nikolova, are affiliated with the National Centre for Mental Health and Analyses where the RECOVER-E project is being implemented. This international project aims to establish well-functioning community mental health teams, offering a possible remedy for practices and policies that fail to meet patients' needs.

The final part of the volume is dedicated to the last stage of the life course – old age and the care of the elderly. Dessislava Vankova's chapter outlines the potential of social medicine to provide principles and guidelines for the health and wellbeing of older people through integrative approaches to health and ageing, promoting active ageing and viewing it in relation to quality of life. The last two chapters focus on one of the most serious conditions of old age – dementia. Boryana Bundzhulova notes the radical differences between the life-worlds of dementia and 'normality', and develops a validation method informed by phenomenology and psychoanalysis, as a way to understand and support people with dementia. Teodora Karamelska takes another perspective, focusing on the psychosocial problems of caregivers. She aptly argues that dementia is also 'a family members 'disease', stressing the daily difficulties faced by relatives caring for the sick. She suggests ways for caregivers to mobilize biographical resources that could potentially result in a positive re-assessment of their experiences.

As a conclusion to this part, and to the volume, Karamelska's interview with Assoc. Prof. Ignat Petrov, psychiatrist and gerontologist, adds the precious personal perspective of a veteran of Bulgarian gerontology and an expert on dementia. His practical advice, captured in the title of the interview, is that the most important for patients is that their

nearest and dearest relate to them with warmth. This message captures very well the essence of the whole book, which combines serious in-depth research with empathy and compassion.

I conclude by recommending this book not only to researchers and students but also to caregivers and general readers seeking to understand care in its multiple modes and dimensions. The ambition of the volume to make visible and map out a broad, complex and diverse field has been successfully achieved. By arguing for the need to overcome mono-dimensional biomedical approaches, the authors offer a wealth of conceptual and practical insights that will no doubt inspire future work.

BOOK REVIEW**Violeta Kotseva, PhD****Associate Professor,****Department of “Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology”****Faculty of History, Sofia University “St. Kl. Ohridski” – Bulgaria****[vkcoceva@uni-sofia.bg], ORCID 0000-0001-9573-7926****Contribution to the History of Health Education in Bulgaria**

Abstract: *The review discusses the monograph Health Education in Bulgarian Society in the XIXth Century (until 1878) [Здравната просвета в българското общество през XIX век (до 1878 г.)] by Vladimir Terziev. The book traces the development of health education in Bulgaria in the second half of the 19th century. The author aims to analyze the modernization of the Bulgarian society through the prism of scientific medical knowledge and the process of its dissemination. In a broader perspective, the book highlights the clash between traditional and scientific medicine. The author’s ambition is to write a narrative in the spirit of social history with elements of interdisciplinarity. The analysis follows a historical approach with commentary on written sources.*

Keywords: *health education; medicine; social history.*

Terziev, V. (2024). Health Education in Bulgarian Society in the 19th Century (up to 1878). Sofia: Avanguard Prima, ISBN 9786192399658, p. 404 [in Bulgarian].

<https://academicabooks.bg/product/здравната-просвета-в-българското-общ>
Copyrights: © “Avanguard Prima” Press

Vladimir Terziev's book¹ presents, examines and analyzes health-educational initiatives in Bulgarian society in the period 1856-1878 and their role in establishing the norms of modern scientific medicine. In the context of the wider modernization of Bulgarian society during this period, the book's focus on the clash between tradition and modernity via an analysis of new norm of health and healing, is undeniably relevant. Given that for a long time the themes of hygiene and health culture have been marginal to our humanities, a detailed analysis of this aspect contributes to attempts at clarifying the history of health care. The lack of a comprehensive study on health education in view of the rise of modern (bio)medicine further underlines the timeliness of the chosen topic.

The book is based on Terziev's PhD thesis, defended at the Faculty of History at Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski". The author currently works within the established traditions of Bulgarian historical scholarship, relying on analysis and comparison of written sources and maintaining a positivist attitude toward facts and details.

Structured into an introduction, four chapters, a conclusion and a bibliography, the book spans 404 pages. The bibliography includes extensive archival material from the State Archive and its branches in Smolyan, Varna and Plovdiv, as well as those held at the Bulgarian Historical Archive. It draws on published archival collections, memoirs, early printed books, periodicals, scholarly research and online resources, demonstrating a very good command of the literature and digital sources on the subject.

The main aim of the study is to trace the emergence of modern health knowledge during the Revival period and the ways in which it spread (p. 6). Already on p. 11 the author frames the project as a study of everyday life, social relations and changes in perceptions through an analysis of the process involved in the replacement of traditional medical knowledge with modern knowledge. The author explores health education as a reflection of Revival period education and as part of the history of health care in the country. He rightly notes that health culture is a key marker of the transition of Bulgarian society to the Modern Age (p. 12).

The introduction outlines the study's chronological scope, methodology, and key sources. The main methodology focuses on the analysis of historical sources and data. Given the interdisciplinary nature of

¹ Терзиев, В. (2024). *Здравната просвета в българското общество през XIX век (до 1878 г.)*. София: Авангард прима.

the topic which combines three scientific fields – history, medicine and culture – a broader interdisciplinary approach might have provided a more solid basis for the conclusions drawn from the work, although in places the author ventures into the intermediate zone between history and cultural anthropology.

The first chapter deals with the main forms of health knowledge in 19th century Bulgaria. Terziev consistently addresses several focal points: folk/traditional medicine; modern medicine and the clash or co-existence between them, as well as the degree of scientific knowledge among Bulgarians of the time. Drawing mainly on historical data, the author engages with the notion of cultural dualism (after M. Georgiev), a term describing in this case the coexistence of two medical systems which are distinct both in terms of content and philosophy. The study remains mainly historical and this in some parts prevents the author from expanding his analysis. The rise of modern medicine is not a linear process of replacement and disappearance of some cultural forms at the expense of others. The coexistence of different medical systems is visible, even today. Every healing practice exists thanks to shared knowledge about the causes of diseases and their respective treatments. If there were no publicly shared trust in their efficacy, they would soon disappear. Even today, healers continue to enjoy significant popularity. A cultural analysis of the period would show that science-based medicine was familiar to only a handful of educated medics, while the vast majority of the population shared a radically different worldview whose needs were filled by traditional healers and their healing practices.

The second chapter examines the modernization of Bulgarian health culture during the Revival. The author Vladimir Terziev consistently discusses the context shaped by the reformist acts of the High Gate (Високата порта); the increased interest among Bulgarians in the medical profession and its gradual establishment as one of the prestigious professions among the emerging Bulgarian intelligentsia; and the influence of modern health knowledge on pharmaceuticals.

The third chapter is devoted to health education within the framework of Revival period education. The author pays special attention to hygiene as a form of disease prevention. It is a meaningful approach that most clearly shows that modern medicine was built on a radically different understanding of disease, requiring not only treatment but also prevention of disease that demanded a complete change of worldview and therefore lifestyle.

The fourth chapter analyzes the distribution of health-related printed publications (books, brochures, press) during the Revival period. The author offers a systematic look at the main titles published during the era, focusing on the role of the printed press and the main themes that health literature advocated during the period as part of the broader transformation of medical concepts.

Vladimir Terziev demonstrates thorough knowledge of the historical literature on the subject. He skillfully integrates sources into a coherent narrative while using them to analyze the process of modernization of Bulgarian society.

Throughout the book, Terziev traces the coexistence of traditional and scientific medicine, framed as a stark opposition – the former is unscripted, non-institutional, passed down within the family and family circle but accepted and shared by all, and the second is institutionalized through norms outlining the parameters of a healthy body and society. Throughout the text, the author walks in the safe and comfortable field of facts and written data. Yet, a cultural analysis would have given greater depth to the study. Replacing one concept of health and healing with another requires tracing broader societal processes of modernization. Strict reliance on historical methods and analysis in studying societal processes risks schematic or hasty conclusions. The use of data that go beyond the chronological scope of the study could also have illuminated the complexity and non-linear character of these developments. Also missing from the text is an exploration of the ‘consumers’ of modern health culture – who were they, were they mainly urban dwellers, or were there rural and uneducated populations among them? Answers to such questions would further clarify the impact of health education on Bulgarian society during the Revival period.

These observations, however, do not diminish the significance of the book. Terziev’s study makes an important contribution to the history of health care, particularly health education in the years following the Crimean War. With the vast amount of source material collected, the book provides a valuable foundation for further analysis and new analytical perspectives.

BOOK REVIEW

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The Age of “Tender Nails”: How Bulgarians Discovered Childhood in the 17th-19th Centuries¹

Abstract: *The book How Childhood Was Lived and Thought about by Bulgarians presents ideas on childhood in Bulgarian discourse of the 17th-19th centuries through an analysis of texts by the most prominent Enlightenment figures.*

Keywords: *childhood; Ottoman rule; 17th-19th centuries; Enlightenment.*

Danova. N. (2023). How Childhood Was Lived and Thought by Bulgarians (17th – 19th Centuries), Sofia: “Paradigma”, ISBN: 978-954-326-509-1, 690 p. [in Bulgarian].

<https://paradigma.bg/book/1531-kak-e-jivyana-i-kak-e-mislена-detska>
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¹ The research is within the ERC Project "Taming the European Leviathan: The Legacy of Post-War Medicine and the Common Good". The project has received funding from the European Research Council under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 854503).

The Balkan Enlightenment has not yet been studied through the lens of the history of childhood. In her book *How Childhood Was Lived and Thought by Bulgarians (17th – 19th Centuries)*,² Nadya Danova highlights the child as a central figure of the Balkan Enlightenment. Under the conditions of Ottoman rule at that time, Bulgarian society “discovered” childhood. It entered public discourse, and questions of upbringing and education became key themes in the writings of Enlightenment thinkers.

The topic of childhood during this period of Ottoman rule in the Balkans has been of interest to Nadya Danova for many years. The book is the result of her extensive research into both the history of childhood and the processes of Balkan and Bulgarian modernization. Yet her motivation is not purely academic. She is also driven by contemporary concerns, noting that many present-day attitudes toward children bear traces of earlier centuries. With this book, she seeks to raise awareness of these enduring legacies while also dismantling the romantic attitude and “elevated tone toward the past.”

For her research, Danova examines inscriptions in church books, manuscripts, calendars, school regulations, periodicals, and unpublished documents. She reinterprets numerous well-known texts “through the prism of the history of childhood.” Danova situates her work within a broader scholarly tradition, recalling that the history of childhood as a discipline began with Philippe Ariès’s seminal *Centuries of Childhood: A Social History of Family Life*. Ariès argued that in the medieval past, children were regarded much like other dependent groups in society. The rise of the nuclear family and the spread of schooling from the 14th – 15th centuries onward gradually established childhood as a distinct, protected phase of life. These changes created new emotional bonds but also introduced techniques of discipline and control. From this perspective, the history of childhood emerges as a branch of social history that has revitalized historical scholarship by bridging diverse fields: demography, medicine, linguistics, art history, women’s and gender history, and more. The debates sparked by Ariès’s book helped refine understandings of childhood and led to richer, more nuanced reconstructions of children’s lives in the past. For the first time in Bulgarian historical literature, Danova provides a detailed historiographic survey of this field, demonstrating that significant expertise has already accumulated in both Bulgaria and the wider Balkans.

² Данова, Н. (2023). *Как е живяна и как е мислена детската възраст от българите (XVII - XIX в.)*. София: Парадигма.

She also examines how European Enlightenment conceptions of childhood interacted with those of Balkan and Bulgarian writers – often emerging in a context of suspicion toward, yet gradual acceptance of, Western ideas. What unfolds is a dynamic network of exchanges that shaped new attitudes toward children, while modern norms spread into the Balkans unevenly and at a slow pace, yet always in dialogue with European models. For the author’s large-scale project, it was necessary to present the interrelationships between the European Enlightenment, the Greek, Serbian and Bulgarian processes of modernization. As one of the leading experts on cultural transfer during the Balkan Enlightenment, she maps the multitude of connections – translations, borrowings, adaptations. The result is a rich and coherent picture of children’s place in society, at the crossroads of Orthodox religious traditions, foreign educational influences (French, Italian, German, English, American), national aspirations, and everyday attitudes towards children. At the core of Nadya Danova’s book lies a detailed study of the Bulgarian case, which situates it within the broader framework of the European Enlightenment and its educational views on childhood. Bulgarian authors did not yet know how to characterize and distinguish childhood, often designating it as “tender nails.” This bodily metaphor was adopted from Byzantine literature and some modern Greek authors, and persisted into the first half of the 19th century. Gradually, however, the notion of childhood acquired greater depth and complexity. From the early 1800s, the powerful drive to adopt European models brought a constant influx of new attitudes toward children and their upbringing, though these were accompanied by deep anxieties. Many writers feared that European ideas might erode traditional values, provoke social disorder, or destabilize families. Danova demonstrates that such cultural transformations did not unfold linearly. Decades passed before the ideas of Erasmus of Rotterdam, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, Johann Pestalozzi, François Fénelon, Thomas Hobbes, Benjamin Franklin, and later Friedrich Froebel reached Bulgaria. Their works were often translated only in fragments, modified, or left unpublished for long periods. For example, Rousseau’s *Émile, or On Education* (1762) – a cornerstone of European Enlightenment thought – was translated into Greek by the Bulgarian Nikola Piccolo as early as 1811, but the manuscript remained unpublished. Although Balkan intellectuals knew and cited the work, it only appeared in print in Greek in 1880, in Serbian in 1872 (after circu-

lating as a manuscript from 1864), in Romanian in 1913, and in Bulgarian in 1906. Translations of Pestalozzi and other authors followed similarly delayed trajectories.

Tracing the evolution of the ideas on childhood, Danova analyzes texts of some twenty Bulgarian writers from the 18th and 19th centuries – figures who laid the foundations for modern attitudes toward children and schooling. By reconstructing their biographies and intellectual environments, Danova highlights the formative influence of their education, personal libraries, and cultural contacts. These individuals – priests, doctors, merchants, writers, and publishers – shared a deep commitment to questions of childhood and education. Among them were pioneering figures: Nikola Piccolo, translator of *Émile* (1811); Petar Beron, author of the first Bulgarian primer (1824); Neofit Rilski, compiler of the first Bulgarian grammar (1835); Ivan Bogorov, founder of the first Bulgarian newspaper (1846); Konstantin Fotinov, publisher of the first magazine (1844); Rashko Blaskov, editor of the first pedagogical periodical (1872); Petko Slaveykov, editor of the first children’s magazine (1871); Sava Dobroplodni, who published the first book on children’s health (1846); Hristo Danov, founder of the first Bulgarian publishing house (1857) and others. Their biographies show the crucial mediating role of Greek education and literature in transmitting Enlightenment ideas to the Balkans, bridging Western European thought and Balkan intellectual life. The analysis reveals the intersection of the different cultural influences that resulted in ambivalent views on childhood. Most Bulgarian Enlighteners perceived the child as marked by ‘original sin’, but also as a “white book” or “clean slate” in the Aristotle sense, transmitted through European Enlightenment translations. They shared penal practices and tirelessly recommended beating and other punishments as tools for education and morality, justifying them with biblical texts and presenting the rod as a plant “emerging from paradise.” At the same time, all these authors emphasized the importance of childhood as a period in a person’s life, the need for special care and activities for children, and expressed modern views on the role of the secular school over religious instruction. In the 19th century, the discourse on children expanded significantly, especially in periodicals. Issues such as upbringing, children’s health, vaccination, high mortality rates, the importance of children plays, and toys entered public debate. Alongside textbooks, children’s literature – translations, adaptations, and original texts – appeared. Yet, children continued to be treated pri-

marily as objects of influence rather than equal participants, and corporal punishment remained closely tied to notions of upbringing. Most Enlightenment-era Bulgarian authors, influenced by Fénelon, Condorcet, Pestalozzi, and others, recognized the importance of girls' education, but still confined women's roles to home and family. An exception was Lyuben Karavelov, the revolutionary writer and publicist, who argued that women and men share the same intellectual capacities and should receive equal education. He advocated raising boys and girls alike to be lively, intelligent, and enterprising – rather than subdued through punishment.

The history of childhood is usually seen in close relation to the history of women. Nadya Danova's book gives us the opportunity to read the 'birth' of childhood in Bulgarian society as a male project, part of the history of the male writers who shaped attitudes toward children in early Bulgarian modernity.

How Childhood Was Lived and Thought by Bulgarians (17th – 19th Centuries) reveals the value of a deep historical perspective on the study of the history of childhood. It contributes to awareness of both historical change and the continuity of the experience of childhood experience, as well as to public sensitivity and responsibility toward children. The book also shows how the history of childhood, as a scientific field, can not only offer comparative approaches beyond the divided terrain of national histories in the Balkans and Europe, but also show the close interconnections and exchanges of ideas and attitudes toward family, childhood and children.

BOOK REVIEW

Editors' note: Although *Japanese Psychotherapies: Silence and Body-Mind Interconnectedness in Morita, Naikan and Dohsa-hou* was published back in 2017, it remains a valuable contribution to the topic of medical pluralism and cross-cultural psychotherapy studies.

The book's quiet depth and nuanced insight resonate with the broader goals of this issue: to foreground diverse therapeutic traditions and plural approaches to healing. We are pleased to revisit this work, which connects Eastern and Western traditions through careful scholarship and embodied experience.

The book review featured here was originally published in Japanese by Rev. Mari Sengoku – a scholar, practitioner, and Jodo Shin Buddhist minister. To accompany the reflection on the book's significance this review provides, we share a mixed-media painting by the book's author, Velizara Chervenkova. The three Japanese cranes not only might evoke associations with the three therapies central to the book, but they can also serve as a visual metaphor for the gentle interweaving of movement, silence, and healing explored within its pages.

The heartfelt review is complemented by a brief commentary on the book's core subject by Osamu Imura, Professor Emeritus of Psychology at Osaka University (Japan).

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The Healing Power of *Ma* and the Mind-Body Connection in Japanese Psychotherapies – Focusing on Morita Therapy, Naikan Therapy and Dohsa-hou

Abstract: *This review commends Velizara Chervenkova's scholarly work for its thorough and nuanced exploration of three Japanese psychotherapies: Morita Therapy, Naikan Therapy and Dohsa-hou within their cultural and philosophical contexts. The book effectively elucidates the role of silence (ma) and mind-body interconnectedness as core therapeutic mechanisms, and demonstrates their applicability beyond Japanese populations through case studies and cross-cultural analysis. Posi-*

tioned as a valuable successor to earlier foundational texts, the work contributes significantly to the global understanding and dissemination of Japanese psychotherapies.

Keywords: Japanese psychotherapies; Morita Therapy; Naikan Therapy; Dohsa-hou; cross-cultural analysis.

Chervenkova, V. (2017). *Japanese Psychotherapies: Silence and Body-Mind Interconnectedness in Morita, Naikan and Dohsa-hou*. Singapore: Springer Nature, eBook ISBN 978-981-10-3126-7, XX & 275 p.

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This book is a scholarly English-language work written to introduce three psychotherapies developed in Japan – Morita Therapy, Naikan Therapy, and Dohsa-hou – to clinicians and clients outside of Japan. Its original English title is *Japanese Psychotherapies: Silence and Body-Mind Interconnectedness in Morita, Naikan and Dohsa-hou*. The author has studied clinical psychology, counseling, and Japanese in Bulgaria, and earned her PhD at Osaka University’s Graduate School of Human Sciences with a dissertation on this theme. She has also presented at the Japan Naikan Association’s academic conferences, and may already be familiar to many of the association’s members.

ences, and may already be familiar to many of the association’s members.

As the reviewer who wrote the preface for this book and has had the pleasure of a close exchange with the author, I am deeply impressed by this scholarly yet poetically and beautifully written analysis of Japanese-style psychotherapy. I feel this poetic expression reflects the author’s own character. As a Westerner deeply fascinated by Japanese psychotherapies, Velizara Chervenkova presents her sincere and humble approach to “seeing things as they are” (jp.: *arugamama*), while as an academician her wish is to accurately convey to readers deep insights, presented even before the book’s main body – in the introductory Chapters 1 and 2. Quoting prominent Japanese authors such as Lafcadio

Hearn, Tetsurō Watsuji, Hayao Kawai, and Bin Kimura, the book discusses how Japanese religion, climate, geography, and culture have shaped a spiritual sensibility distinct from that of the West. It explains how these aspects are embedded in the structure of Japanese psychotherapies.

Chapter 3 discusses the origins, methods, and benefits of each therapy – Morita, Naikan, and Dohsa-hou – in the order they developed. It also compares each of them with Western approaches: Morita Therapy with Metapsychiatry, Naikan with Freudian psychoanalysis, and Dohsa-hou with Body-Mind Psychotherapy. In addition, the book's central thesis focuses on two key characteristics of Japanese psychotherapies, which the author considers most significant.

The first of them is the cultural value of silence and the concept of *ma* – Japanese culture fosters a mindset that cherishes silence and *ma* (Jp.: interval, space; between, in-between). In the therapist-client therapeutic relationship, *ma* and quiet moments are sustained by mutual trust, and these elements serve as powerful healing forces in all three therapies. And second, there is the deep interconnection between mind and body. As mental transformation occurs, physical symptoms often improve as well. This reflects a profound mind-body correlation that can ultimately lead to personal growth.

Chapter 4 uses case studies and the author's own training experiences in both Japan and Bulgaria to demonstrate that the healing power of *ma* and the mind-body connection are not limited to Japanese individuals – they possess universality that transcends culture and ethnicity. An appendix at the end includes photographs and materials taken by the author during her visits to various training centers and clinics across Japan. From the first to the last page, the book is filled with thoughtful efforts to clearly convey the practical aspects of Japanese psychotherapies, showing the author's deep consideration for her readers. As someone who was slightly involved in the publication process of this book, I am truly fascinated how the author's many years of hard work have been distilled into this one volume.

In conclusion, it has been nearly 40 years since Dr. David K. Reynolds introduced Japanese psychotherapies to the world in his book *The Quiet Therapies: Japanese Pathways to Personal Growth* (1980). This new work by Velizara Chervenkova serves as a precious successor, reconnecting Naikan therapy with the world. It also compels Japanese readers to reflect on the essence of their own culture, which they

might be forgetting. I cannot help but be moved by this truly outstanding book.

* * *

Osamu Imura, PhD

Professor Emeritus of Psychology at Osaka University – Japan

Western psychotherapies are primarily aimed at helping clients deepen their self-understanding, and at supporting their self-growth and transformation by verbalizing their own experiences, while therapist accepts and empathize with them. On the other hand, the three psychotherapies born in Japan are characterized by placing importance on the client's experiences themselves and on enhancing self-healing power rather than verbalization. Another difference from Western psychotherapies is that they are often conducted in groups. These and other characteristics are explained in details in the book crafted by Velizara Chervenkova.

Interest in Eastern cultures and religions is increasing in the Western world, and experience-oriented techniques such as mindfulness seem to be spreading. However, I think that Japanese psychotherapies in particular have not yet been introduced much enough outside Japan and the Asian continent. I therefore sincerely hope that Velizara Chervenkova's contribution to the spread of the knowledge on Japanese psychotherapies would serve as a catalyst for the further fusion between Western and Eastern psychotherapy.

Silently, We Soar Aloft (watercolor and acrylic paint on canvas, 300x900 mm), by Velizara Chervenkova-Antonova

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Translator's note: This book review was originally published in Japanese in the Japan Naikan Association's official journal, *Naikan Research* (Vol. 24, № 1, 2018; pp.71-72). It was translated into English by Velizara Chervenkova-Antonova upon the author's due permission, along with the commentary provided by Prof. Osamu Imura.

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